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EGAS MONIZ SCHOOL OF HEALTH AND SCIENCE
EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND LAW

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ORAL

PRESENTATIONS

CRIME AND JUSTICE

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TITLE **What Works in Appeals for Information and Public Service Announcements?**

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ABSTRACT

Missing person investigations make up a vast proportion of a police district's workload. A common strategy is to release a missing person appeal to the public with the aim of someone coming forward with information that could aid in locating the missing person. However, previous research has shown that they are widely ineffective in their current format. In contrast, public service announcements (PSAs) have been more extensively researched. PSAs provide information with the aims of changing or preventing the adoption the undesirable behaviour, as opposed to an appeal which aims to receive rather than provide information. However, for both, their success relies on cognitive processes within their intended audience. The recipient must pay attention, engage with the material, and remember the content before creating a behavioural change. Therefore, this research takes the form of a systematic review, collating available research on approaches relevant disciplines have taken to create effective PSAs and appeals for information. The systematic review examined all existing literature on 'what works' in PSAs and appeals across multiple disciplines. It sought to answer the following question: what factors relating to the type of content of a PSA or appeal for information increases cognitive processes in the public? Studies were included if they compared the content of PSAs or appeals in applied settings and if the outcomes of the studies looked at their effects on cognitive processes (i.e., memory, attention, engagement, behavioural change). The findings focus on features that have been found to successfully increase cognitive processes in five disciplines. Examples of successful features include, but are not limited to, emotional valence, framing, and narrative style. Overall, the results provide an evidence base that can aid in informing what works within and across disciplines, with a primary focus on features transferrable to a missing persons context.

KEYWORDS **Public service announcements, appeals for information, cognition, missing person appeals**

TITLE **Solving Burglary and Robbery Incidents in the Netherlands:
A Nationwide Multilevel Analysis**

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ABSTRACT Background: Eck (1983) proposes that whether or not a crime is solved mainly depends on two things: the solvability of the crime based on its characteristics and the amount of effort by the police during the investigation of the crime. He hypothesizes an interaction effect between the solvability of the crime based on its characteristics and investigative effort. However, solvability studies thereafter have mainly looked at the influence of case characteristics on crime clearance. Only a few studies looked into the effect of investigative effort while accounting for case characteristics and even less studies hypothesized about and tested the interaction effect. Aim: The current (ongoing) study analyzes case outcomes of reported burglary and robbery incidents in the Netherlands from 2018 until 2022. Methodology: Because criminal investigations are generally done in police teams, our modeling strategy will account for the nested structure of the data, with cases nested in teams. We first test how much of the variation in case outcome can be contributed to investigative effort by the police, differences between police teams and case characteristics. We then test the hypothesis that the effect of investigative effort on case outcome is dependent on the case characteristics. Results: Preliminary findings will be presented at the conference.

KEYWORDS **Criminal investigation, solvability, investigative effort, crime clearance, burglary**

TITLE **The Role of Proneness to Guilt and Shame Among People in Custody in Promoting Restorative Justice Processes in Prison**

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ABSTRACT

Objective of the study: This research examined the role of guilt and shame proneness among people in custody in shaping attitudes toward restorative justice (RJ) and in predicting the effectiveness of RJ practices.

Methodology and Results: In study 1 (n = 110) all participants completed the following questionnaires: Demographic, shame and guilt-proneness, level of regret and remorse, and willingness to participate in RJ process. Results showed that proneness to guilt, but not to shame, was correlated with willingness to participate in RJ. Mediation modeling showed that guilt-proneness predicted willingness to participate in RJ via its strong correlation with regret and remorse. Study 2 (n = 133)

was carried out in two separate phases. In the first, participants completed a questionnaire that examined shame and guilt-proneness and demographic questions. In the second phase, which included the same participants, they were divided into two groups. The experimental group was shown a video in which a crime victim related her story. Approximately 1 hour later, the participants completed questionnaires identical to those used in Study 1, but without the part that examined the shame and guilt-proneness, which they had completed in the first phase. The control group did not watch the video and only completed questionnaires.

Results revealed that high guilt proneness predicted high willingness to participate in a further RJ process, whereas shame proneness moderated the effectiveness of RJ practice.

Conclusion: This study contributes to the literature both theoretically and practically by providing in-depth understanding of the role played by proneness to guilt and shame among people in custody participating in RJ. The study creates an interdisciplinary integration between the field of RJ and the psychology of emotions. On the practical level, the results can help practitioners and researchers develop interventions to promote the effectiveness of RJ in prison.

KEYWORDS **Restorative Justice, Prison, Guilt, Shame**

TITLE **Overview of the corruption phenomenon in Romania from the perspective of individuals convicted of bribery**

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to observe the typology of individuals convicted of bribery based on three criteria: the public or private sector in which they operate, the specific type of activity, the value and nature of the goods that were subject to bribery, and the number of bribery acts committed. We believe that, with a mindset focused upon creating criminal policies, we can identify information vital for criminal laws and policies. In order to achieve this objective we managed to identify the areas prone to being focus points of this type of criminal activity or as weak pressure points that could fail the honesty test of public or private officials. In order to achieve this result, we analysed final convictions pronounced by the superior courts in Romania (Courts of Appeal and High Court of Cassation and Justice) in the years 2022 - 2023. In total, 99 decisions were reviewed, resulting in convictions for 138 individuals for 151 bribery offenses. We expect to reveal through this research the type of pressure on each of the two sectors, private and public, the category of persons involved, the authorities, sectors and institutions that know particularly high pressure from criminal activity. The study is relevant, on the one hand, because it shows where the main efforts of judicial authorities should be concentrated, and evidently, where should efforts be sustained to combat the phenomenon even further. However, it also highlights areas where it is necessary to rethink how judicial authorities operate, particularly regarding the lack of visible results, for example, such as bribery in the private sector.

KEYWORDS **Bribery, Corruption phenomenon, Convicted individual**

TITLE **Intervening in power dynamics during mediation: when and how?**

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ABSTRACT

Mediation, as a method of dispute resolution, offers parties the opportunity to collaboratively and voluntarily address their conflicts under the guidance of a multi-partial mediator. The control mediation allows parties over the dispute resolution process has sparked discussions about the mediator's role in navigating power dynamics between parties during mediation. Despite this debate, empirical research on the topic remains sparse. This conference presentation unveils two studies that explore the perspectives of both mediators (Study 1) and parties (Study 2) regarding the 'when' and 'how' of mediator intervention in these power dynamics. Mediators' (n=12) and parties' (n=13) narratives on power in parties during mediation were explored using semi-structured in-depth interviews. Participants were involved in social, family, or civil and commercial mediation in Flanders or the Netherlands. Interviews took place between 2022 and 2024 and were analyzed using a grounded theory approach. First, results indicated a perceived need for mediator intervention for four power-related objectives: parties' (1) informed and (2) pure consensus, (3) movement towards agreement, and (4) the absence of a 'winning' or 'not-losing' approach. Next, the main power-related threatening factors to these objectives included parties' (1) skill and knowledge, (2) counsel, and (3) sense of powerlessness or guilt, as well as the co-party's (4) use of threats, intimidation, or hindering communication, (5) lack of commitment, and (6) lack of decision-making authority. Finally, we identified several interventions aimed at safeguarding the aforementioned objectives by addressing these threats, including threat-transcending interventions (e.g., contrasting the observed behavior with the objective) and interventions specific to each threat (e.g., exploring the co-party's substantive boundaries to address their lack of commitment). These findings highlight the need for a nuanced consideration of power in mediation and provide mediators with empirically grounded tools for when and how to intervene in power dynamics between parties during mediation.

KEYWORDS **Mediation, Alternative dispute resolution, Power, Interventions**

VIOLENCE MYTHS AND PERCEPTIONS

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | VIOLENCE MYTHS AND PERCEPTIONS

TITLE Does anybody believe in Rape Myths anymore? Examining the Prevalence and Correlates of Rape Myth Beliefs Among 3000 UK Adults

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Much prior research has examined the existence of rape mythology throughout the western world and scrutinised the societal groups most likely to endorse these falsehoods. Yet, researchers have typically recruited a small number of community participants or student samples, resulting in varied findings and a lack of consensus in the literature. The aim of this study was to therefore to examine the contemporary prevalence and correlates of rape mythology throughout the UK through surveying a large community sample of adults.

Methodology: 3149 UK adults aged 18 to 78 (M Age = 31.89) took part in a cross-sectional survey online that included two established attitudinal measurement tools; the Acceptance of Modern Myths about Sexual Aggression (AMMSA) Scale and the Pre-trial Juror Attitude Questionnaire (PJAQ), alongside socio-demographic questions (age, gender, ethnicity, education, parental status).

Findings: Whilst many rape myths appear to be in decline, several myths remain prevalent including those that infer women often falsely allege sexual violence and exaggerate the scale of the sexual violence problem. Results also reveal age, gender, ethnicity, and educational differences in rape myth beliefs with the greatest group differences found between men and women. Hierarchical regression analyses determined that four PJAQ legal attitude subscales (Racial Bias, Social Justice, System Confidence, Cynicism toward the Defence) were significant predictors of AMMSA scores. After controlling for sociodemographic variables, these PJAQ attitudes remained predictive of rape myth beliefs, alongside gender and ethnicity.

Practical Implications: These results provide new insights into the contemporary prevalence of individual and collective rape myth beliefs among the UK public. Findings therefore highlight the urgent need for targeted educational intervention programmes among certain groups whose attitudes are most problematic, especially given the civic duties they hold as prospective jurors.

KEYWORDS Rape myths, Prevalence, Power, Acceptance of Modern Myths about Sexual Aggression, Pre-trial Juror Attitudes Questionnaire

TITLE **An Introduction and validation to the Forced-to-Penetrate Myth Acceptance Scale (FTP-MAS): A new attitudinal tool for assessing myths that surround female perpetrated sexual**

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ABSTRACT

Purpose - The purpose of this study is to develop and validate a new measurement tool designed to capture endorsement of myths surrounding female perpetrated sexual violence against men, commonly referred to as 'forced-to-penetrate' cases.

Design/methodology/approach - Data were collected among a sample of 4152 UK adults aged 18 - 55+ (52% female). Dimensionality and construct validity of the Forced-to-Penetrate Myth Acceptance Scale (FTP-MAS) was investigated using traditional Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) techniques.

Findings - CFA results indicated that FTP-MAS scores are best captured by a three-factor model (1. Distorted Sex and Gender Roles; 2. Harm Minimisation; 3. Offence Denial). Excellent composite reliability and differential predictive validity were observed for all three subscales. Group differences were also tested among a number of co-variables including having previously served as a juror, with results indicating that former jurors scored significantly higher across all three sub-scales of the forced-to-penetrate myths.

Originality/value - The FTP-MAS constitutes the first measurement tool which allows for the assessment and evaluation of public attitudes towards female perpetrators of sexual violence who force men to penetrate without consent. As such, this tool enables researchers to better capture and understand the multi-faceted nature such myths and can be used as an outcome measure in research seeking to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions that aim to debunk endorsement of such falsehoods.

KEYWORDS

Forced to Penetrate, Female Perpetrated Sexual Assault, Rape Myths, Confirmatory Factor Analysis

TITLE**Politics, Personality and Problematic Victim Attitudes:
Examining the role of right-wing authoritarianism, sexism
and just world beliefs on public attitudes towards victims of
sexual exploitation.**

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ABSTRACT

The current study examined the relationship between political orientation, right-wing authoritarianism (RWA) and problematic beliefs about sex trafficking victims within US and UK populations. In the first study, participants (N = 444) responded to multiple questionnaires measuring demographic characteristics, sex trafficking attitudes, and right-wing authoritarianism. The results showed that individuals holding RWA beliefs are less understanding of sex trafficking victims' difficulties in leaving their situations, support paternalistic approaches supporting survivors and have less empathy towards victims. Mediation analyses indicated that the relationship between political orientation and problematic victim attitudes is partially mediated through right-wing authoritarianism. US participants also held more problematic attitudes towards ST victims than UK participants, despite reporting greater awareness about ST issues and expressing greater beliefs in their abilities to reduce sex trafficking. The second study used an experimental (vignette) to examine the mediating roles of sexism and just world beliefs behind the RWA-victim attitude relationship. Our presentation discusses the practical implications and recommendations of the project.

KEYWORDS Sex trafficking, Sexual exploitation, victim blaming

TITLE **Victims of rape and the quality of encounters with Swedish police: Quantitative research insights**

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on raped women's perceptions of their encounters with Swedish police, with a specific focus on quality of encounters, trust, questions asked during police interviews, and perceptions of justice. We constructed a web-based questionnaire, and participants were recruited through an advertisement distributed via Swedish support organizations, and through posters and information hand-outs distributed at gynecological emergency units across Sweden.

106 women, of which 74 (69.8%) had reported to police, participated. Results show that the participants viewed the general questions asked during police interviews negatively: 57% reported them as intrusive, 54% reported them to lack empathy, and 46% reported the questioning to demonstrate victim blaming. Where officers explained their line of questioning the perceived degree of intrusiveness and victim-blaming were both reported as lower, however, a majority of participants (57%) reported that no explanation was given. An index was created for quality of encounter with police, based on responses to three questions (min =1, max =5) on the perceived level of empathy, validation, and belief in participant's story. Index scores (M=3.03, SD =1.34) suggests that, overall, encounters with the police tended to be viewed as more positive than negative, although a substantial proportion of the sample still rated their encounters at the lower end of the index. Participants who reported a higher quality in police encounters also reported a higher trust in both police work and in the criminal justice system as well as a higher degree of received justice. However, more than half of the participants (51%) reported that they had not received any justice.

Findings demonstrate victims' need for information, for trauma-informed policing, and the importance of quality of encounters on victims' trust and perceived level of received justice - insights which might help inform policy and practice developments, both in Sweden and more generally.

KEYWORDS **Rape victims, Police, Justice, Questionnaire study**

TITLE Exploring Perceptions of Marital Rape Across South Asia, MENA, Western, and Eastern Europe

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ABSTRACT

Objective of the study: Marital rape (MR) is a pressing societal issue and public health concern that has received insufficient attention despite its prevalence across developed and developing nations (WHO, 2018). Thus, this study focuses on understudied regions such as South Asia (SA) and MENA. A cross-cultural study of these regions and Western and Eastern Europe has been conducted.

Methodology: Researchers created 9 standardized marital rape scenario vignettes (3x3) to study the impact of 'perpetrator justification' (no justification, deprivation, jealousy) and 'victim resistance' (passive, verbal, verbal & physical) on Rape-Supportive Attribution (Monson et al., 2000), Sex-Role Stereotypical Victim Blame Attributions (Monson et al., 2000), and Perceived Seriousness of Violence Measure (Yamawaki et al., 2009). Participants responded to an attention test after reading one vignette each. Ongoing online data collection will be completed by 30th April 2024. To date 1485 people from four studied regions have completed the survey.

Results obtained or expected: Preliminary analysis on data collected to date from three 3x3 Factorial ANOVAs indicates the significance of resistance level, with passive resistance associated with higher Rape Support and Victim Blaming. Cross-cultural variations were observed, with MENA participants showing significantly higher scores for Rape Support and Victim Blaming compared to other regions. Notably, individuals in Western and Eastern Europe perceive MR less severely than those in SA and MENA.

Conclusion: The context of rape scenarios play an important role in how the public and judicial system perceive marital rape. Analysis with a full dataset will increase the power of the study and shed light on the public's understanding of MR in different regions, enabling region-tailored interventions.

KEYWORDS Intimate partner sexual violence, domestic violence, underrepresented samples

PRISON CONTEXTS

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | PRISON CONTEXTS

TITLE Smart Prison – Digital Rehabilitation

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ABSTRACT

This presentation consists of studies published in 2022 and 2023. The studies were done in a new women's prison in Finland. The objective was to find out how the new prison concept named as "Smart Prison" can support rehabilitation and rights of prisoners. Smart prison concept states prison as a digital learning environment for a life without crime: every prisoner can use a personal cell device for various digital services supporting rehabilitative, educational, judicial, and psychosocial purposes. The first structured digital survey was submitted to both staff and prisoners one year after implementing the concept, and another one to prisoners 2.5 years after the implementation. The results obtained were promising. Prisoners used digital services daily and considered online contact to health care and close ones especially important. The covid-19 pandemic in 2020-2022 had its effect on the positive results, but the latter post-pandemic survey confirmed the results. In this survey prisoners were asked how well the concept could support their basic and human rights during incarceration. 60 % of respondents agreed that it helped them to take care of their rights during incarceration. The highest agreement was for rights regarding rehabilitation, studying, contact to close ones and staying informed about the outside world. As a conclusion, prison digitalisation is important for providing effective rehabilitation, services of the outside society, reintegration back to the society and even effect on recidivism. The next step is the use of AI for prisoner rehabilitation and management. We are expecting new results from pilots of Virtual Reality (VR) and other AI-based services for prisoners.

KEYWORDS prisoners, digitalisation, rehabilitation, human rights, artificial intelligence

TITLE Predictive validity of EssenCES for climate assessment in prisons and psychiatric detention facilities in Romania

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Objective

The main objective of the study is to validate the EssenCES prison climate assessment for prisons with semi open access, high security and for hospital prisons in Romania. We also intended to compare the results with other EU countries where prison climate was evaluated with EssenCES. The research collected data from four penitentiaries - two maximum security prisons (Arad and Craiova), two semi-open prisons (Timișoara and Satu Mare) and two psychiatric hospital penitentiaries (București-Dej and Mioveni). The sample 480 inmates and 120 staff members from the prisons and 87 inmates and 59 staff from prison hospitals.

Methodology

There were used the following measures EssenCES (Schalast, 2010), WES-10 (Friis, 1981), Institutional Aggression, Ward s level of security.

Results

Satisfactory values for the three dimensions were obtained in the internal consistency analysis, .84 for Inmate Cohesion, .73 for Safety and Security, .73 for Experienced Safety and Therapeutic Support .69. Each item loaded on its factor The 3-factor model is good according to the fit indicators (CFI and TLI above .95, RMSEA and SRMS = .05). Prison situation analysys shows that all items load on the factor where they should load (CFI and TLI above .90, respectively RMSEA and SRMS around .05, .06, 08). In the case of hospitals, however, due to a lower participation than expected the statistical analyses in this case are at the limit of significance and are discussed within the limits of the study.

Conclusions

In conclusion, statistical analysis confirmed the three-factor model proposed by Dr. N. Schalast for prison climate as a valid tool for climate analysis and feedback. This result is related to the literature that show the validity of EssenCES in different cultures (Tonkin et al, 2011) and its importance in appreciating the positive effects of therapeutic supportive climate and importance of remedial measures.

ABSTRACT

KEYWORDS

EssenCES, therapeutic hold, pathient's cohesion and mutual support, experienced safety, level of security

TITLE **The use of direct and indirect aggression among imprisoned women and men**

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ABSTRACT Introduction: This study examines the use of various forms of aggression among inmates. The aim of the study was to characterize the group of imprisoned men and women in terms of physical, verbal and indirect aggression. Additionally, the relationship between using and experiencing indirect aggression was analyzed and direct aggression, anger and hostility were tested as predictors of indirect aggression.
Method: Two versions of Indirect Aggression Scale (IAS-Aggressor, IAS-Target; Forrest S., et al, 2005) as well as Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire were used to examine selected psychological variables. The sample consisted of 38 imprisoned women and 40 imprisoned men.
Results: The results indicated more frequent use of physical and indirect aggression by imprisoned men and revealed positive relationship between experiencing and using indirect aggression both in the group of imprisoned women and men. There were no significant differences in the use of verbal aggression. Physical aggression and hostility predicted indirect aggression in examined penitentiary sample.
Conclusion: The results complement the current state of knowledge on aggression in the penitentiary environment. The surprising result proving that men use indirect aggression more frequently is inconsistent with the reports from the previous studies. Therefore, the conclusion is drawn that perhaps in this specific group, consisting of inmates, the use of indirect aggression is more typical of men than women. In order to verify the obtained results, it is worth carrying out similar analyzes in the future on a larger sample and with the inclusion of additional variables. Presented research suggests that indirect aggression among inmates can be a serious threat during incarceration. That is why early diagnosis and prevention of covert aggressive behaviors among inmates is needed.

KEYWORDS **Direct aggression, indirect aggression, sex differences, physical aggression, verbal aggression**

TITLE **Peer Mentoring and Identity Transformation: Supporting Women's Desistance from Crime**

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ABSTRACT

This study provides a qualitative exploration of identity transformation through peer mentoring within a specific criminal justice context. Focused on an operational women's prison in England and Wales, the research examines how peer mentoring influences the identity transformation of incarcerated women. Three key areas are scrutinised: the conceptualisation of peer mentoring by both inmates and staff, the impact of serving as a peer mentor on the identity of incarcerated women, and the broader implications of peer mentoring on prison governance and the continuity of the mentorship role. Taking a gendered approach, the study prioritises the viewpoints and experiences of female peer mentors. Utilising research interviews and focus groups conducted at HMP Holloway, the findings draw from interactions with peer mentors, mentees, prison officers, and project workers. Central to the study are the core principles underpinning peer mentoring for incarcerated women, including notions of sameness, authenticity, boundaries, and mutual aid. These principles are identified as fundamental to the effectiveness of peer mentoring in facilitating identity transformation in prison settings. The research highlights the practical and personal benefits accrued by peer mentors, including psychological impacts such as normalising the prison experience, fostering empowerment, and aiding in identity repair. However, it also acknowledges potential role conflicts and emotional challenges associated with peer mentoring. Furthermore, the study illuminates how peer mentoring serves not only as a support mechanism within prison walls but also as a tool for achieving broader correctional objectives, thereby showcasing its multifaceted nature. The study offers a nuanced analysis of identity transformation through peer mentoring. It advocates for the recognition and utilisation of the unique strengths and skills possessed by peer mentors, emphasising the role of peer mentoring in fostering identity repair and personal growth. The research calls for additional support and resources to bolster the effectiveness and sustainability of peer mentoring programmes in prison settings.

KEYWORDS **Peer mentoring, prison, women**

TITLE **Coping with prison demands: The role of internal and external resources for inmates' mental health**

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ABSTRACT Objective of the study: Previous research has underscored the detrimental impact of prison demands on inmates' mental health. However, it is conceivable that these effects could be weakened by inmates' internal and external resources. This study investigates whether 1) inmates' resilience as an internal resource and 2) experienced safety climate as an external resource can buffer against the negative repercussions of prison demands on inmates' mental health.

Methodology: In a cross-sectional survey study with N = 956 prison inmates the interplay between prison demands and inmates' resources was investigated. Moderation analyses were conducted to examine the influence of inmates' resilience as an internal resource and experienced safety climate as an external resource on the relationship between prison demands and inmates' experiences of depression, stress, and anxiety.

Results: Consistent with the existing literature, the findings revealed a positive relationship between prison demands and inmates' depression, stress, and anxiety. In line with the assumptions, inmates' resilience poses as an internal resource buffering the relationship between prison demands and inmates' mental health. Moreover, also the external resource safety climate can buffer the association of prison demands with inmates' anxiety, but not the association with depression and stress.

Conclusion: These results underscore the potential of both internal and external resources to support inmates in coping with the challenges posed by prison demands. Results underline the need for resilience-building measures in prisons and underscore the importance of fostering a positive safety climate. The study contributes to discussions on the dynamics between demands and resources within the prison system, thereby enhancing the comprehension of inmates' experiences and coping mechanisms.

KEYWORDS **prison demands, inmates' mental health, resilience, safety climate, resources**

COURTROOM PSYCHOLOGY

TITLE **Auditory Mirages in The Transcription of Indistinct Covert Recordings**

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ABSTRACT

Transcriptions of covert recordings are a major source of evidence in criminal trials. However, the poor quality of recordings often results in unintelligible speech. There is a widespread belief that poor quality covert recordings can be enhanced with appropriate audio filters, but such procedures may introduce distortions or even remove the audio content we aim to enhance. Additionally, transcription is often subject to contextual priming, a bias in speech decoding due to the effect of context and beliefs about the content of the recording. Here, we propose a new methodology for transcribing covert recordings of poor quality. This method was applied in a recent criminal court case and involves selecting the most relevant audio excerpts, asking several transcribers (who have no prior knowledge of the recording's content) to transcribe the content, and matching the transcriptions with linguistic indices (we used the Jaccard index) to determine the correlation among transcriptions. Transcriptions can then be merged to create a "most likely transcription." In our study, 50 transcribers provided transcriptions under all experimental conditions. They transcribed six audio excerpts: five containing potentially court-relevant content (but of poor audio quality) and one containing irrelevant content but of good quality, which served as a control to assess the transcribers' ability to decode speech. The overlap between the transcriptions of the various experimental excerpts ranged from a minimum of 34% to a maximum of 77%. The overlap for the control excerpt was 89%. The overlapping material was united to create a "most likely transcription," one of which included relevant information for the court, and above all, enabled the creation of a transcription whose quality was judged to be "Beyond Any Reasonable Doubt."

KEYWORDS **Cognitive Psychology and transcriptions, Covert recording transcription, Contextual priming in indistinct recordings**

TITLE **Is false memory research ready to be used in the courtroom?**

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ABSTRACT

In many judicial systems, courts sometimes seek expert witnesses to provide their insights regarding the memory performance of for example eyewitnesses. However, their reports might differ in the techniques they use to evaluate witness statements, the interpretation of findings, and the communication of the results. This study examined whether the literature on false memories is ready to be used in the courtroom. We used a new scoring system to assess the replicability, generalizability, and practical relevance of research in the area of false memories. In particular, eight topics were chosen, of which five are related to therapeutic techniques -EMDR, hypnosis, imagination inflation, imagery, and journaling- and three were related to individual differences -fantasy proneness, dissociation, and depression- and their relationship to false memories. We scored each article based on a variety of subcriteria to decide which research we would include in our review. Two reviewers searched through 3 databases - PubMed, PsychInfo, and Web of Science- using specific search terms for each subject. Subsequently, we assessed if the eligibility criteria were met based on the individual scoring scheme. Finally, in this review, we included studies from 2000 until 2024 that were in the English language. After the first screening, 344 papers were identified of which 214 were discarded after a duplication check (n = 137) and a full paper screening (n = 77). Therefore, the total number of papers included in this review was 180. The results showed that none of the eight topics met the replicability criteria. Subsequently, journaling/diary therapy lacked generalizability and only imagination inflation had practical relevance. To conclude, this review showed that most research on therapeutic techniques, individual differences, and their relationship to false memories lacks replicability and practical relevance. Hence, this puts into question whether expert witnesses can reliably use this literature in their testimonies in court.

KEYWORDS **False memory, replicability, generalizability, practical relevance**

TITLE **Tipsy testimonies: The effect of alcohol intoxication status, crime role, and juror characteristics on mock juror decision-making**

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ABSTRACT

Victims and witnesses are regularly intoxicated with alcohol during crimes and jurors must evaluate their intoxication-affected testimony when decision-making. Unfortunately, criminal justice systems often lack guidelines for determining how alcohol intoxication may impact a person's memory. Intoxication is instead framed as a common knowledge issue: jurors are assumed capable of making informed decisions about the complex relationship between alcohol and memory.

This study investigated the effect of the crime role of a testimony-giver (victim or witness), their intoxication level during the crime, and jurors' personal characteristics on mock juror decision-making. Participants (N = 181) read a trial transcript and completed an online survey assessing demographics, trial-related judgements, and expectations about and experiences with alcohol.

In general, greater victim/witness intoxication during the crime was associated with lower credibility ratings, higher cognitive impairment ratings, and fewer convictions. These results suggest participants better understood the dose-dependent effects of alcohol on memory compared to those in previous studies. We propose that improved dose-specific understanding was driven by simple communication of victim/witness intoxication using familiar lay metrics. Crime role did not impact dependent variables and juror characteristics exerted a limited influence: only alcohol-related work experience and the perceived gender of the victim/witness predicted a minority of outcome variables. Notably, alcohol expectancies did not influence jurors' decisions.

This study asserts the need for evidence-based jury education about alcohol and eyewitness memory to support informed decision-making. Educational strategies must include a strong focus on clear communication of intoxication information using recognisable everyday metrics.

KEYWORDS **Jury decision-making, alcohol, eyewitness memory, victim, witness**

TITLE **The Effect of Crime Type and Knowledge about Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) on the Judgement of Defendants with ASD**

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ABSTRACT

1. Objective of the study
Research found that defendants with ASD are judged more lenient than defendants for whom no diagnosis is mentioned. With this study, we test whether 1) knowledge about ASD is required to lead to more lenient judgements for people with ASD; and 2) the type of crime (crime: autism relevant vs. autism irrelevant) impacts on the judgement of autistic defendants.

2. Methodology
A 3 (defendant information: “ASD + Knowledge” vs. ASD vs. control) · 3 (type of crime: assault vs. stalking vs. burglary) between-within subjects design was used. Participants (N = 146) were randomly assigned an experimental group and presented with three fictional crime vignettes. Two groups (“ASD + Knowledge” and “ASD”) were told the defendant was autistic and received additional information about ASD in the “ASD + Knowledge” group.

3. Results obtained or expected
We found that for autism relevant crimes (assault and stalking), defendants with ASD received lower sentences than defendants without a (mentioned) diagnosis. For the autism irrelevant crime (burglary), autistic defendants were not judged more lenient than defendants without a (mentioned) diagnosis. Further analysis indicated that participants did indeed consider the link between ASD traits and the committed offense. Although there was a clear effect of crime type on the judgement of defendants with ASD, no difference was observed between the participants that did and did not receive information about ASD.

4. Conclusion
Knowing how different types of information can affect sentencing behaviour is crucial for training employees in the criminal justice system. Future research is needed exploring the relation between different types of information about ASD and sentencing decisions for autistic defendants.

KEYWORDS **Autism Spectrum Disorder, Sentencing Decisions, Type of Crime, Mock Jury**

POLICE WORK

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | POLICE WORK

TITLE **Police decision-making in the field: The case of major sports events policing**

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ABSTRACT Today's world is characterized by increasing complexity, risk, and uncertainty. Police officers play a social role that requires timely decisions, often made with scant information and a lot of doubts. Like the rest of us, the police decision-maker relies on mental tools, to be able to adapt to an ever-changing environment, making satisficing and ecologically rational decisions. The main goal of this study was to describe and understand how experienced police decision-makers from the Portuguese Public Security Police deal with uncertainty and make decisions in the context of major sports events policing. A total of 45 football matches (from the national and European competitions) were analysed using a naturalistic approach. Documents from the planning phases, operations orders, and sports policing reports, as well as field observation of police decision-makers and the application of the think-aloud protocol, were subject to a content analysis procedure. The results suggest that police officers' experience, information management, the use of heuristics, and mental simulation are central pillars in the decision-making process in major sports events policing.

KEYWORDS **Police decision-making, major sports events policing, naturalistic decision-making, uncertainty**

TITLE **How are identification parades constructed in the United Kingdom?: A survey of identification officers.**

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ABSTRACT

In the United Kingdom, identification parades (or ‘lineups’ as they are commonly referred to in the literature) are routinely administered to eyewitnesses of a crime. These parades must adhere to the codes of practice outlined in the Police and Criminal Evidence Act (PACE). However, these codes are quite vague in certain areas and leave room for the subjective interpretation of the officer constructing the identification parade. Alongside official guidance (e.g., PACE), academics have also provided recommendations for constructing parades based on findings from psychological research.

Despite best practice recommendations provided by both official bodies and academic researchers, what is currently unknown is whether current police practice aligns with these guidelines. Previous research shows that there is sometimes a disconnect between real police practice and recommended practice. To investigate this in relation to UK eyewitness identification procedures, we conducted a survey with identification officers in collaboration with the National VIPER Bureau to learn more about how identification parades are constructed in the UK.

As expected, our results showed that identification officers in the UK follow the guidance outlined in PACE as a baseline for their parade construction decisions. Beyond this, we highlight several key findings regarding areas which are open to the subjective decision-making of the individual officer. These areas include filler selection, similarity within a parade, and distinctive features. Using our findings, we provide recommendations for future research where there appear to be gaps in the guidance.

KEYWORDS **Police practice, identification parades, lineups**

TITLE **An exploration of the utility of virtual reality as a method of suicide negotiation training**

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ABSTRACT

Objectives

Crisis and suicide negotiation are currently primarily taught through role play. One limitation of this approach is the difficulty of simulating the often dangerous environments in which crisis negotiations take place. VR offers a possibility of complementing current training methods by allowing such immersive experiences. Here we report preliminary evaluation of a new VR environment simulating suicide negotiation on a rooftop.

Methodology

In two experiments student participants were first given basic training in crisis negotiation based on the behavioural influence stairway model. In study 1 (N = 47), the training varied with regard to whether it incorporated explicit example behaviours or not. In study 2 (N = 41), the training varied with regard to error handling strategies (error prevention or error management strategies).

In both studies, after training, participants were placed within the VR simulation. Participants chose between response options to the utterances of the suicidal virtual agent using a handheld controller. To test performance, responses either aligned with their training or not. We also measured their spatial and social presence quantitatively and (study 1) qualitatively.

Results

Performance was very high in both studies, reflecting the simplified interaction experience (i.e. selecting from limited options via controller). Immersion via social and spatial presence was good, and social presence was related to perceived empathy. Qualitative analysis indicated that realism was more dependent upon social than spatial presence, indicating a need to develop more realistic interactions with the virtual agent. Training impacted participant experiences of the interactions, but not performance.

Conclusions

Our initial findings indicate VR could be a viable method for crisis negotiation training, but there is a need to develop more complex scenarios and communication so that a more realistic experience of the intricacies of crisis negotiation can be captured.

KEYWORDS **Crisis Negotiation, Training, Behavioural Influence Stairway Model, Error Management, Virtual Reality**

TITLE **Warming up Cold Case Investigations: Cueing Old Memories
Using Temporal and Situational Mnemonics to Find New
Leads in Missing Person Investigations**

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ABSTRACT

Missing person investigations refer to cases where an individual has been reported missing and their location is unknown. Cold cases are those in which all investigative leads have been exhausted and a case remains unsolved. Currently, in the UK there are 13,000 long-term unsolved missing person investigations reported by National Crime Agency's Missing Persons Unit. Long-term missing person cases are especially difficult because as time progresses people's memory for potentially useful information regarding the missing person, such as names of people who might know something, declines. Further, it is likely that once promising investigative leads dissipate as it becomes more resource intensive to keep the investigation active. To address the challenge of long-term unsolved missing person investigations, we explored whether it is possible to uncover new investigative leads via the use of retrieval facilitation mnemonics. Participants were asked to think back to their early teenage years and produce a list of names of people they knew at that time but have not spoken to since. They were then asked to select the person they knew best from the list, imagine that they had gone missing at that time, and then provide a list of people that this person knew at the time of the (hypothetical) disappearance. The mnemonics used across two studies included temporal and situational mental reinstatement of context, category clustered recall, self-generated cues, and a social network task. Across both studies the memory-enhancing mnemonics were significantly more effective in facilitating recall in comparison to control conditions (no retrieval support). The implications of these findings for real-world long-term missing person investigations will be discussed, with reference to collaborative work underway with the charity, Locate International.

KEYWORDS **Cold Case, Missing Person, Investigation, Mnemonics**

TITLE **Crime Reporting and Citizen Satisfaction with the police: A Large-Scale Study among Reporting Citizens of Crime in the Netherlands**

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ABSTRACT

Fostering satisfactory police-citizens encounters holds utmost significance for the efficiency of the police, and the well-being of citizens and communities. Citizen satisfaction is derived from direct experiences with the police. Contact initiated by citizens themselves weigh more heavily on citizen satisfaction levels than contact initiated by police does as citizens generally expect more from voluntary contact. Therefore, to study citizen satisfaction with the police, it makes sense to look at citizen-initiated conversations. In particular, into crime reporting conversations as these represent the majority of citizen-initiated contact. We focus on crime reporting needs and expectations of witnesses and victims, and their satisfaction about the crime reporting experience. The current study extends the line of research by considering crime reporting channels. Online tools to report (e.g. internet forms, chatbots, and online platforms) are used more widely and could have impact on needs, expectations, and satisfaction levels. We capitalize a nationwide survey among crime reporting citizens in the Netherlands (n=25.000 approx.). Participants were asked questions regarding their experiences with crime reporting. Multilevel analyses will be conducted on quantitative data. We will provide a better understanding of citizens satisfaction with police after reporting crime. We will shed more light on which factors of the reporting process affect citizen satisfaction with the police. The emphasis will be on the following factors (1) reporting channels, (2) citizens' needs, (3) citizens' expectations, and (5) the impact of crime on citizens. Findings will offer valuable insights into strategies for enhancing crime reporting experiences, elevating citizen satisfaction levels, and fostering increased cooperation among citizens.

KEYWORDS

Citizen Satisfaction, Crime Reporting, Police-Citizen Contact, Needs and Expectations, Crime Report Channels

JUDICIAL DECISION

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | POLICE WORK

TITLE Jury on trial: Eyetracking as a tool to filter out biased jurors

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ABSTRACT

Jury decision making is a fundamental aspect of the criminal justice process. It is influenced by a mirage of factors and has two potential outcomes: finding the suspect guilty or judging them innocent. However, having biased jurors means that the decision outcomes could be compromised. Importantly, the use of peremptory challenges, which allow attorneys to strike potential jurors without giving a reason, can be used to exclude certain groups from juries, perpetuating power imbalances in the legal system while the inclusion of individuals with biases can result in the same end, thus resulting in a miscarriage of justice. Attempts to filter out biased jurors using psychometric tests are a common practice, however, they are not without limitations. Recently the application of eye-tracking and gaze direction methodology to reveal observers' overt attentional biases has become increasingly popular. In the present study, we proposed a novel data-driven methodology that directly tracks eye movements to identify biased jurors. A total of 106 participants watched a simulated crime showing one of the fictional offenders (white or black male) holding a weapon whilst their eye movement was being tracked. Following this, participants completed several questionnaires and a mock jury trial. The study demonstrates how eye-tracking can be used to identify between-group differences (e.g., biased/unbiased jurors) in the viewing of offence-related moving scenes (e.g., knife crime). For example, revealing that biased jurors show attentional biases to an accomplice to the crime belonging to a different race other than their own, thus reflecting prejudice and discrimination. These biased jurors will likely recommend guilty judgement and harsher sentences in a mock jury trial. This ability to empirically identify such critical behavioural sections which are viewed differently by biased and unbiased jurors has significant implications for jury decision making and reducing miscarriage of justice.

KEYWORDS

Jury decision making, Jury biases, Eyetracking, Guilty judgement, Group comparison

TITLE **Mock Juries' Understanding, Perceptions, and Use of Alibi Evidence During Deliberations**

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ABSTRACT

An alibi has the potential to be a defence responsible for acquitting or, as evidenced in cases of wrongful convictions, erroneously convicting a defendant of an offence. The study aimed to qualitatively explore mock juries' understanding, perceptions, and use of alibi evidence during deliberations in a simulated criminal trial context. Four six-person mock juries viewed video footage of a trial re-enactment, before taking part in mock deliberations, where the deliberative discussions were recorded. The data was analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2022), a six-step recursive process for exploring patterns across a dataset, employing quality procedures as per Braun and Clarke's (2022) recommendations to demonstrate methodological integrity. The findings demonstrated that mock juries were overwhelmingly sceptical of alibis and perceived it to be of weak credibility when supported by easily fabricated person evidence and in the absence of any physical corroboration. Participants expressed an idealistic expectation for consistency across all aspects of the defence, with any discrepancies being indicative of deception, yet some demonstrated a degree of understanding as to memory limitations in alibi generation. Lastly, mock jurors relied on non-evidential factors to assess the credibility of the alibi, employing personal experiences, stereotypes, and non-verbal behaviours to assess the veracity of the defence. Whilst the sample size poses difficulties in terms of the generalisability and transferability of the findings, several areas for further research were identified as a result. In turn, the study highlights the need for greater awareness and education as to the nuances of alibi evidence, to ensure a fair and equitable legal system that mitigates for potential miscarriages of justice.

KEYWORDS **Alibi, Jury Decision-Making, Qualitative**

TITLE **Understanding and minimising the impacts of rape myths in juror decision-making**

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ABSTRACT

The literature has extensively illustrated the influence of rape myths on victim evaluations and verdict decisions, with calls for jury education to be implemented to minimise their negative impact. However, the lack of an articulated theoretical model explaining how rape myth acceptance impacts juror decision-making has stunted the development of a focused educational intervention for jurors in cases of sexual violence.

This presentation will explore the findings from three empirical studies addressing these aims and examining the role and malleability of rape myths in juror decision-making. Specifically, the cross-sectional design of study 1 and experimental design of study 2 examined the fit and validity of the proposed theoretical model using advanced structural equation modelling techniques. Additionally, study 3 evaluated the effectiveness of the newly developed educational video in reducing the impact of rape myths on jurors' verdicts and victim evaluations.

In the first study, the proposed model showed good fit to the data, supporting the theory that rape myth factors influence credibility, responsibility and empathy judgements, which subsequently impact verdicts. In the second study, increased rape-myth-relevant information resulted in significantly fewer guilty verdicts, which may be attributed to significant differences in perceived victim credibility between the conditions. Finally, the results from the third study suggested that the intervention was successful in reducing the influence of rape myths on credibility judgements. We discuss the methodological limitations and the implications of these findings for future research and applications to the criminal justice system in the UK and beyond.

KEYWORDS

Juror decision-making, Victim evaluations, Rape myth acceptance, Rape trial, Jury education

TITLE **Moral Anger or Disgust First? Exploring the Primacy Effect in Victim and Perpetrator Foci**

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ABSTRACT

Within the field of moral psychology, there is an ongoing debate surrounding the intricate relationship between moral transgressions and specific moral emotions, notably disgust and anger. According to some scholars, situational and dispositional factors play a critical role in influencing how these ethical violations shape socio-moral responses (Hutcherson and Gross, 2011; Tybur et al., 2009).

This study aimed to test whether inducing participants' attention towards the agent or recipient of a moral violation would elicit different emotional responses. The participants were presented with a set of vignettes that described moral transgressions across five dimensions: harm, humiliation, injustice, abandonment, and betrayal. After each description, participants were instructed to quickly and accurately judge whether the emotional reactions of third parties depicted in different facial expressions (anger, disgust, fear, neutral, sadness, and joy) were consistent with what would be expected regarding the misconduct. Drawing upon Clifford et al. (2015), the vignettes were created to highlight either the victim's experience (e.g., a person being tripped on the street) or the perpetrator's experience (e.g., a person tripping another). The hypothesis was that emphasizing the perpetrator would stress their poor moral character and elicit distancing reactions typical of moral disgust (Giner-Sorolla and Chapman, 2017). Conversely, focusing on the victim was thought to emphasize the harmful act and the victim's resulting personal distress, aligning more closely with moral anger (Giner-Sorolla and Chapman, 2017). The results indicate that directing participants' attention to the victim resulted in quicker and more frequent selection of angry expressions compared to disgust. However, a preference for disgust was primarily evident in scenarios depicting moral transgressions in the perpetrator-focus condition, but not in the victim-focus condition, only when compared to neutral affect. The study highlights the importance of appraisal in dealing with moral transgressions.

KEYWORDS **Moral judgment, moral transgressions, anger and disgust, victim vs perpetrator, third-party morality**

TITLE **Silenced Survivors: A Systematic Review of the Barriers to Reporting, Investigating, Prosecuting, and Sentencing of Adult Female Rape and Sexual Assault**

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ABSTRACT

Rape and sexual assault of adult women are recognised as highly underreported crimes to law enforcement. The low rates of reporting can be attributed to barriers that women face in disclosing their sexual victimisation to the criminal justice system, as well as challenges within the system that hinder the progression of cases and the attainment of convictions once a formal report has been filed.

We conducted a systematic review to identify and synthesise the barriers to reporting, investigating, prosecuting, and sentencing cases of sexual assault and rape of adult women. The overarching themes across all barriers and specifically the reporting stage can be summarised under a lack of trust in the criminal justice system, internal reactions, rape myths and societal norms, and perpetrator characteristics. The attrition of reported cases throughout the criminal justice system was mirrored in the evidence base for each stage, with progressively fewer studies available from the reporting to the sentencing stage.

Our findings underscore the critical imperative for reform within the criminal justice system. Central to this reform is prioritising victim-survivors' needs, improving the transparency of the criminal justice system and its processes, and addressing attrition rates.

KEYWORDS **Sexual assault, rape, criminal justice system, barriers, adult women**

COURTROOM PSYCHOLOGY II

TITLE Navigating Virtual Justice: Understanding the Importance of First Impressions on Credibility in Remote Testimonies

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic led to increased use of video conferencing in court trials, enabling remote testimonies and fully virtual trials. While this approach offers benefits such as reduced travel expenses and lower costs, it also raises concerns about how video-mediated communication affects credibility assessments. For instance, technical factors like camera position can influence how a person is perceived (i.e. likeability, social power), which can also impact credibility assessments, thereby complicating testimony conditions compared to traditional court settings. Also, previous research indicates that eye contact is linked to positive first impressions. However, in video-mediated meetings, eye contact/gaze is ambiguous, particularly in group settings. Thus, if remote witnesses are consistently judged as more or less credible than those physically present, procedural fairness could be compromised.

This study (mixed factorial design, N = 285) examined the effects of eye gaze/eye contact (towards the camera vs. elsewhere) and camera position (high, low, side angle). Participants watched two video-recorded witness statements (order was varied). Multiple repeated measures ANOVAs revealed that the first witness generally made a slightly more positive first impression and was judged to be slightly more credible than the second witness, but these effects were small. There were no main effects of camera position or gaze direction on credibility, first impression, perceived social power, or perceived norm violation. However, significant three-way interactions (camera position, gaze direction, witness order) suggest that effects of camera angle and gaze may depend on the order in which a witness testifies. Furthermore, results partially support the hypothesis that camera angle impacts perceived social power (less power when filmed from a high angle), but this was only true for the first witness. Overall, first impression, social power and norm violation significantly predict credibility for both witnesses. Practical implications for maintaining fairness and accuracy in virtual legal proceedings are discussed.

KEYWORDS Remote testimonies, credibility, witnesses, procedural fairness, video-mediated communication

TITLE **Too Controversial for the Court? How Politically Sensitive Court Cases about Climate Change affect Public Trust in the Judge**

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ABSTRACT Climate crisis, pandemics, mass migration: when political solutions for these and other societal issues are not found, courts are asked to step in and find solutions instead. Conflict resolution in these politically sensitive cases requires public trust. However, the public's trust in courts could be threatened. Legal scholars have argued that it may diminish precisely due to politically sensitive judgments. After all, the judge is traditionally expected to stay away from the political realm. When people perceive the judge to illegitimately intrude in politics, they may thus feel it oversteps the boundaries of its traditional role. Moreover, newspaper articles often refer to these actions as 'activistic'. However, unclear is how citizens perceive politically sensitive cases and what effects this has on their levels of trust in judges, since most of the legal research done so far is doctrinal in nature.

Two online studies investigated whether public trust in judges is affected by court rulings in politically sensitive (climate) cases. In Study 1, we presented vignettes of four 'sensitive' (two climate cases and two covid cases) and two 'neutral' cases from Dutch courts to participants. In Study 2, participants were presented with pilot-tested imaginary newspaper articles about a district court case. Political sensitivity and judicial activism were experimentally manipulated. Both studies showed that climate cases were perceived as more politically sensitive than neutral cases. Higher perceived political sensitivity was related to higher perceived judicial activism and lower trust in judges. Furthermore, perceived judicial activism was strongly related to lower trust in judges in both studies. However, trust in judges was not lower in either of the experimental conditions, suggesting that judicial activism in climate litigation has the potential to undermine trust in judges when perceived repeatedly; but single exposures to judicial activism are not likely to influence trust in judges.

KEYWORDS **Climate Litigation, Public Trust, Political Sensitivity, Judicial Activism**

TITLE **The influence of race in the courtroom**

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ABSTRACT

Ministry of Justice figures in the UK (2020) have shown that individuals from some racial groups are more likely to be stopped and searched by the police, and to receive longer custodial sentences as compared to those from other groups. The racial background of defendants and eyewitnesses can also influence the way they are perceived in a courtroom (Frumkin & Stone, 2020) and more substantially, may affect whether they are ultimately found innocent or guilty.

The aim of the present study was to investigate the influence of defendant race (black or white) on perceptions of the defendant and courtroom decisions. Three applied psychological experiments using ambiguous crime vignettes measured how different modalities- facial image, voice and name- may alter defendant perceptions and guilt ratings. Participants were allocated to either a same or different race condition and gave ratings of the defendant on their perceived credibility, deception, prestige and reliability, and provided guilt decisions and proposed sentencing. Analyses compared perceptions and decisions across different modalities and different racial background of the defendants and participants. Results and conclusions are discussed in the UK criminal justice context.

KEYWORDS

Courtroom decisions, Courtroom perceptions, Race, Ethnicity, evidence modality

TITLE**From Bias to Verdict: Investigating the Influence of Racial Bias and Individual Characteristics on Mock Jury Deliberations and the Implementation of Bias Reduction Interventions**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Despite the extensive body of literature addressing racial biases, cognitive biases, and their impact on jury decision-making, gaps persist in our understanding of how these biases interact and influence each other. There is limited research exploring the interplay between biases, personality traits, and the efficacy of intervention or verdict decision strategies to counteract biases. This study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How do pre-existing biases manifest within mock jury discussions?
2. How do juror attitudes, characteristics, and biases impact on the effectiveness of intervention strategies?
3. Are intervention strategies effective in the long-term and what is their relationship to juror bias and personality?

Methodology: An online questionnaire is used to collect qualitative and quantitative data in a mixed methods design. Participants answer a set of questionnaires evaluating their personality type as defined by the HEXACO personality inventory, as well as potential biases due to racial bias, legal attitudes, political identity, and participant's internal and external motivation to respond without prejudice. Participants then answer a set of vignettes that detail a grievous bodily harm case committed by either a white or black offender. A randomised subset will also receive a bias reduction intervention and are then tested on another case vignette.

Expected Results: Provisional results will be presented. It is expected that there will be a racial bias present in the verdict decisions, mediated by the participants motivation to appear less prejudiced. It is also expected that the bias reduction strategy will be effective in reducing biased decision-making. Relationships between other biases and personality will be evaluated.

Conclusion: This study aims to develop our current understanding of bias in the courtroom and the methods in which we can ensure a fair and unbiased trial is reached.

KEYWORDS Bias, Intervention, Courtroom, Decision-Making

FACIAL RECOGNITION

TITLE **Capturing concealed recognition by eye movements: A comparison of the sequential and simultaneous CIT for detecting concealed recognition of faces and objects encountered during a mock crime scenario.**

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ABSTRACT Suspects sometimes lie about recognising someone or something related to a crime. To detect such concealed recognition, we tracked participants' eye movements while they denied recognition of newly familiar faces and objects in a Concealed Information Test (CIT). The aim of this research was to examine whether the sequential or simultaneous CIT format was superior for detecting concealed recognition of newly familiar faces and objects familiarised during a mock crime. Guilty participants took part in a mock crime scenario where they met two accomplices that helped them steal a ring from a bag in a designated room (N = 29). During the CIT, participants were presented with photographs of the faces and objects sequentially or simultaneously while recording their eye movements (e.g., dwell time). Concealed recognition was detected by longer dwell times to the mock crime related photos in the simultaneous CIT (Cohen's $d = 0.9$), but not during the sequential CIT. Detection was most reliable for the ring object that was central to the crime (Choen's $d = 1.4$), which was also rated as highly familiar and highly distinctive. To conclude, the simultaneous test outperformed the sequential test and better detection was positively correlated with quality of encoding. The current findings provides further evidence that the simultaneous eyetracking CIT outperforms the sequential CIT.

KEYWORDS **Face recognition, object recognition, eye movements, concealed information test, mock crime**

TITLE **Congruency Trumps Individual Differences in Masked Face Recognition under Limited Feature Visibility**

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ABSTRACT

Masked perpetrator recognition poses major challenges for law enforcement. To address this issue, researchers have explored approaches that emphasize increasing the degree of correspondence in the context between the compared faces, referred to as contextual congruence. Here we investigated whether congruency between the encoding and the retrieval conditions can improve masked face recognition under highly demanding settings, where visibility is limited to the eyes only with varying levels of memory load. Additionally, we explored whether the advantage of congruity remains consistent across individuals with distinct levels of face recognition abilities. In 3 experiments, participants completed a standard face recognition using congruent sets, where images during the encoding and retrieval phases were presented in similar ways (i.e., full-full and masked-partial), and incongruent sets, where images were presented with different methods (i.e., full-partial and masked-full). Participants also provided confidence ratings for each decision they made. We additionally explored the potential influence of varying levels of face recognition ability using the Cambridge Face Memory Test. The results consistently supported the hypothesis that contextual congruency improves face recognition ($\eta^2 = .48$). When encoding masked faces, participants were better at recognizing partial faces than full faces, with the recognition of masked perpetrators benefiting from limiting the facial features available on the face to be recognized. Congruent sets also led to better discriminability than incongruent sets ($d_{\text{congruent}} = 0.96$; $d_{\text{incongruent}} = 0.53$). Additionally, high-ability face recognizers maintain congruency advantage over low-ability recognizers. Finally, we found that the face processing capacity limits can shape the relationship between confidence and accuracy. These findings suggest that contextual congruency is associated with face processing memory load and individual differences in face memory. Hence, this work provides valuable insights for law enforcement agencies to improve the identification of masked perpetrators, thereby enhancing public safety.

KEYWORDS **Face recognition, Congruency effect, Individual differences, Memory load**

TITLE Do Low Expectations of Encounter Mitigate the Benefit of Within-Person Variability on Sightings of Target Persons?

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ABSTRACT

People are unlikely to make a sighting of a missing or wanted person in a simulated search task. Most people do not devote enough attention to searching for the person, because they think it is unlikely that they will encounter the person. Additionally, people perform poorly at recognizing unfamiliar faces, which contributes to people failing to notice a mock missing or wanted person in their midst. Researchers have found that showing searchers photographs of unfamiliar people that showcase the variability in the person's appearance enhances face recognition and sightings. However, no one has examined how people's expectations of encountering the mock missing or wanted person impact how helpful seeing the variability in their appearance is to making a sighting. We examined both variables in a computer-based and a real-life simulated search task because people likely have higher expectations of encountering the mock missing or wanted person in the lab-based task than the real-life task. Unexpectedly, in the lab-based task, participants who saw low variability images performed better than participants who saw high variability images. This may be because the low variability images more closely resembled the missing person's appearance on the task. In the field-based task, variability did not affect sightings, but expectations of encounter did. Searchers who were told that there was a high chance of encountering the person performed better than searchers who were told there was a low chance, even though participants had the same chance to encounter the person immediately after they were asked to search for her. Our research demonstrates some nuance to the effect of within-person variability on search performance and extends existing research demonstrating expectations affect search performance.

KEYWORDS

Prospective person memory, missing person searches, within-person variability, face recognition, expectations of encounter

TITLE **The impact of forensic delay: facilitating facial composite construction using an early recall retrieval technique**

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ABSTRACT

Memory for facial features deteriorates over time, reducing the ability to construct a visual likeness of the face. Here we investigate the impact of delay on face construction and assess a novel mitigation procedure. In Experiment 1, participants recalled an unfamiliar face during Cognitive Interview and constructed a feature composite of it over forensically-relevant delays. Correct composite naming decreased rapidly after constructors encountered a 3-4-hour post-encoding delay, remained constant at two days, and reached floor-level after 1 week. Experiments 2-4 introduced a practical retrieval procedure, 3-4 hours after encoding, whereby participants wrote a detailed description of the previously-presented face, inducing a testing effect. For feature, sketch, and holistic systems, participants created more identifiable composites with, rather than without, early recall. Addition of a character-based interview further improved feature and holistic composites. Findings suggest an advantage of early verbal recall for facial-composite construction, and for combining interviewing techniques.

KEYWORDS

Face memory, facial composite, testing effect, self-administered interview, retention interval

TITLE **Impact of altered face distinctiveness on eyewitness identification performance**

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ABSTRACT Eyewitnesses of crimes often make identification errors, leading to exculpation of guilty individuals and punishment of innocents. In prior research, participants performed more accurately on standard recognition memory tests (old/new recognition tests) if face stimuli were caricatured. However, it is not clear whether this effect is specific to standard recognition tests, or if it moreover extends to face matching and simultaneous lineups, test types resembling real-world eyewitness settings. We therefore tested whether altered distinctiveness of unfamiliar faces, reached through production of caricatures and anticaricatures, impacted recognition performance for different test types: showups, face matching, and simultaneous lineups. Across all test types, participants showed poorer recognition for anticaricatures, as expected. However, contrary to our hypothesis, participants performed more accurately when shown veridical than caricatured faces. Additionally, the detrimental effect of caricature was observed to increase at delay. Present findings suggest that encoding specificity may have a greater impact on recognition performance of unfamiliar faces, as compared to the caricature effect. Caricature may improve recognition when face distinctiveness is consistent between encoding and test. In the context of most forensic practices, where unfamiliar faces are encoded as veridical, caricature may lead to inaccurate recognition.

KEYWORDS **Eyewitness testimony, Forensic lineups, Face recognition**

INFORMATION AND INTELLIGENCE

TITLE **With Great Power: Relationship Progression, Disclosure, and Power Dynamics in the Informant-Source Handler Relationship**

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ABSTRACT

Source handlers strive to elicit insider information from human intelligence sources, often done over the span of months or even years. Yet, we currently know little about the lifecycle of the informant-source handler relationship, the processes involved, and how this affects information disclosure across time. Drawing on Knapp's (1978) Staircase Model, we propose that informant-source handler relationships progress through four stages of increasing closeness and disclosure: Initiating, Experimenting, Intensifying, and Integrating. We theorise that three processes drive stage progression: similarity, empathy, and trust. Handler/informant power dynamics are also expected to influence relationship progression and disclosure. We tested this in two experiments, using a 4-week online role-play paradigm, where (mock) handlers elicited information about fictitious criminal activity from (mock) sources. In Study 1 we found that, whilst relationship-building markers increased across time, moving through the stages (i.e. changing the nature of the relationship and communication) was even more important to increasing perceptions of similarity, empathy, and trust, beyond the influence of passing time. Study 2 built on these findings to consider the effects of Power: whether wider power disparities between handler and informant yield a slower relationship progression. Results will be discussed in light of potential relationship-building targets. In practice, this will help source handlers to tailor their approaches according to the most central aspects of relationship-building.

KEYWORDS **HUMINT, Information Elicitation, Power, Relationship-Building**

TITLE **Using Individuation to Enhance Collaborative Recall in Intelligence Investigations**

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ABSTRACT

Intelligence-gathering investigations can involve covert teams of security operatives working together to gather information and inform investigations (e.g., terrorism investigations). Despite the important security implications of such teams, little research has explored effective strategies to implement for collecting information from groups. Individuation is a theory-driven strategy whereby group members are assigned distinct but complimentary information-gathering roles to enhance recall performance. This experiment aims to investigate the role of individuation on collaborative and individual recall.

This experiment employed a 2 (Strategy: Individuated vs. Control [no strategy]) x 2 (Type of recall: Collaborative vs. Non-collaborative) between-subjects design. Participants (N = 213) worked together in triads as ‘undercover security operatives’ to inform a ‘terrorism investigation’. Around the laboratory were various pieces of information regarding the attack (e.g., suspect information, device/weapon information, location information), as well as redundant/irrelevant information. Half the triads were instructed to individuate by focussing on gathering information about either the suspects, devices, or locations. The other half of the triads (control groups) received baseline instructions to work together. All participants were then interviewed either collaboratively or individually about the information gathered. Interview transcripts were coded for (i) total information, (ii) correct information, and (iii) incorrect information recalled.

The results of this study will be discussed according to the pre-registered hypotheses. Whilst data analysis is ongoing, we expect that individuated participants will provide more accurate information during recall than control participants. We predict that participants who recall information collaboratively will provide more accurate information compared to those who recall non-collaboratively, and that this effect will be stronger for individuated participants.

By exploring the individuation strategy and recall approaches within the security context, the current research has potential implications for improving the efficiency and accuracy of security teams, to contribute to public safety and crime prevention efforts.

KEYWORDS **Memory, Individuation, Collaborative recall, Intelligence-gathering**

TITLE**Investigative interviewing in criminal, military disciplinary and intelligence all alike? The Interview Attitude and Interview Reaction questionnaire – cross-cultural applications**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: There is a dearth of (cross-culturally) validated research instruments for assessing investigative interviewing. One instrument is the Interviewers' attitude and Interview reaction questionnaire (IAIRQ) which has been validated with Swedish people convicted of murder or sexual offenses. However, little is known if the questionnaire and its two-factor structure is also cross-culturally applicable to different contexts, including military disciplinary investigations, to suspects and witnesses alike, to intelligence interviews and resistance to interrogation, and if the IAIRQ differentiates between dominant and humane interviewing styles in realistic "Resistance to Interrogation (Rtol)"-exercises. We are interested in potential qualitative and quantitative differences.

Methods: Following forth-and-back-translations and the thinking-aloud-technique with 10 soldiers, 350 military witnesses, 260 suspects and 143 military hostages in an Rtol-exercise filled in the IAIRQ. Standardized dominant and humane interviewing were ensured by training experienced interviewers and their supervision. (Multigroup) CFAs and MANOVAs analysed construct validity.

Results: In the Rtol condition a three-factorial model provides the best global (SRMR= .05) and local fit; three interviewing attitudes and reactions differentiated between the dominant and the humane interviewing condition ($F[8,136]=15.31$, $p<.001$, $\eta^2=.47$). For military witnesses and suspects, three-factorial model achieve better fit (RMSEA=.07, SRMR=.06) than two- or one-factorial models. Reliability for the scales is good to excellent (.77- Cronbach- α :.97), regardless of group.

Conclusions: The IAIRQ is a relevant instrument across different situations, but differences have to be taken into account in its applications. Potential reasons for differences and potential improvements are discussed.

Note: Data collection and analysis is still ongoing with a potential for changes.

KEYWORDS Military, investigative interviewing, assessment, validation

TITLE Exploring the Legal Accuracy of Police Interviewers' Explanations of the Police Caution

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ABSTRACT

Objectives of the study: In England and Wales a suspect must understand the police caution for evidence to be admissible in court. Research has shown that very few individuals fully understand the caution, particularly individuals with intellectual disabilities and cognitive deficits. Previous experimental research has shown that simplifying the caution increased comprehension for typically developed individuals but not for those with intellectual disabilities. In practice, there have been misconceptions found in interviewers' explanations of the caution, most notably attributing the caution as a loss of the right to silence. The objectives of the current study were to explore (i) the legal accuracy of interviewers' explanations in suspect interviews, and (ii) if any differences existed when interviewers simplified the caution for suspects identified as vulnerable and for suspects not identified as vulnerable.

Methodology: Legal accuracy criteria were developed using the National Crime Faculty guidelines (1996) and the Crown Court Compendium (2022). The criteria were applied to 179 police interview transcripts (n = 92 suspects identified as vulnerable, and n = 87 suspects not identified as vulnerable). The criteria contained 13 prongs (4 prongs for sentence one of the caution, 7 prongs for sentence two of the caution and 2 prongs for sentence three of the caution). Results: Interviewers gave a fully accurate explanation of the caution (all 13 prongs mentioned) in 3.2% (n=3) of interviews with suspects identified as vulnerable and in 9.2% (n=8) of interviews with suspects not identified as vulnerable. There were no differences when interviewers simplified the caution for suspects identified as vulnerable.

Conclusion: Overall, it was found that very few interviewers gave a fully accurate legal explanation. This presentation will discuss the importance of providing a legally accurate explanation of the caution to suspects during a police interview.

KEYWORDS Police Caution, Vulnerable Suspects, Investigative Interview

TITLE **Developing an interviewer training tool to train Strategic Use of Evidence using suspect avatars**

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ABSTRACT Detecting deception in suspects is a crucial aspect of interrogation, yet it remains a challenging task. One empirically established approach to overcoming this challenge is the Strategic Use of Evidence (SUE). By presenting evidence gradually, SUE amplifies the differences between guilty and innocent suspects during questioning to elicit signs of deception. To aid its implementation, we are developing Suspect Avatar Training, a tool combining interviews with avatars that mimic suspect behavior with training interventions. This training provides an immersive mock interview experience where the interviewer orally asks questions, and the avatars respond based on algorithms reproducing human suspect verbal patterns. To develop avatar algorithms, we will analyze verbal patterns from 240 mock suspects through an online experiment, expecting guilty (vs. innocent) suspects to show reluctance to reveal or admit details that potentially incriminate them resulting in inconsistencies between evidence and their statements as well as within their statements. Suspects' cover stories (alternative explanations that avoid self-incrimination regarding evidence) will also be categorized to find their characteristics. The mock suspects' verbal patterns will then be integrated into algorithms driving avatar responses. Development of effective training can facilitate accessibility to practitioners to use the latest interviewing skills. This research will present the early stage of development, discuss its limitations, and outline the future steps for expansion.

KEYWORDS **Strategic Use of Evidence (SUE), Suspect interviews, Avatars, Simulation training, Feedback**

INVESTIGATIVE PSYCHOLOGY

TITLE **The Professional Rapport Scale for Investigative Information-Gathering Contexts, Observer Version (PRS_O): A synthesising measure of rapport.**

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development and validation of the Professional Rapport Scale (PRS), a comprehensive instrument designed to assess rapport in information-gathering contexts. Using a systematic approach, the PRS was developed based on recommendations in scale development and validation, as well as current literature and theories on rapport. To evaluate the psychometric properties, construct, and concurrent validity of the PRS, 404 participants were recruited for an online survey. Participants were tasked with viewing three videos portraying dyadic professional interactions, each manipulated to represent varying levels of rapport. They were then prompted to rate the perceived degree of rapport across these interactions, along with assessments of related (e.g., active listening, empathy, trust, respect) and unrelated (e.g. Hostility) constructs. Through Confirmatory Factor Analysis, the 26-item PRS was analysed, revealing five distinct components of rapport: mutual connection, paying attention, building a relationship, being approachable, and being professional. The factorial structure of the PRS was confirmed and demonstrated excellent internal consistency. The PRS also successfully detected variation in rapport levels, suggesting good concurrent validity. The construct validity of the PRS was substantiated by its alignment with established measures of rapport and related constructs, while exhibiting no correlation with unrelated variables. Therefore, the findings affirm the PRS as a reliable and validated measure supported by its good construct, concurrent, and factorial validity. It is argued that the PRS components of rapport represent a "toolkit" encompassing essential interpersonal skills that interviewers can utilise to foster a mutual connection and cultivate rapport.

KEYWORDS

Rapport, measure development, investigative interviewing, eyewitness, suspect

TITLE What Works in Behavioural Recognition?

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ABSTRACT

Over the last few decades, a growing evidence base for investigative interviewing has promoted a shift in the landscape from an accusatorial, confession-seeking strategy to an ethical, information-gathering strategy (Méndez, 2021). A valuable asset in this strategy is the ability to acknowledge and interpret an interviewee's behaviour and adjust one's own behaviour to facilitate, rather than inhibit, the interaction. The aim is to recognise and try to resolve barriers to cooperation to promote meaningful information elicitation (Brimbal et al., 2019). A sensible first step in understanding this ability is to understand the cognitive processes behind behavioural recognition.

Purpose: To provide an evidence base informing researchers and practitioners about the factors that could influence our abilities to recognise the behaviour or emotion of another person reliably and accurately.

Methodology: A systematic review examined existing literature across multiple disciplines where interviewing takes place. It sought to answer the following questions: (i) can we accurately interpret the dynamic behaviour of others? (ii) and if so, what factors influence this accuracy? 17 keyword sets were separately combined with a core Boolean string: '(rat* OR interpret* OR perce* OR judg* OR recog* OR identif*) AND (accura*)'. Studies were included for review if they examined accurate judgements of a behaviour, feeling, or emotion. Other inclusion criteria included: participation in or review of a person-to-person dyadic interaction, with minimum prior knowledge of the person.

Results: Out of an initial yield of over 7000 articles, 55 were included. It was found that individual differences in the interviewer, interview parameters and strategies, and interviewee presentation were all important areas of consideration.

Conclusions: The review highlighted the need for further empirical research to be conducted in this area but suggests that behavioural recognition is a trainable skill and has informed an experimental study aimed at testing the findings.

KEYWORDS Investigative, Interaction, Behaviour, Recognition

TITLE **Timing of Evidence Disclosure and Suspect Response in Homicide Suspect Interviews: What are the effects of suspect veracity and culpability?**

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ABSTRACT

There is a wealth of experimental research exploring the timing of evidence disclosure in interviews with suspects. Much of this research investigates how the timing of evidence disclosure affects the accuracy of veracity judgements made by interviewers/observers. However, there is a lack of field research exploring when evidence is disclosed in interviews using field data. The current study examined the temporal point in which evidence was disclosed in homicide suspect interviews, and how the suspects responded in relation to the timing of the evidence disclosed. The truthfulness of the suspect (veracity), and whether or not the suspect was later found guilty or innocent (culpability) of the crime for which they were interviewed, were considered as factors in the analyses. Sixty homicide suspect interviews were examined, obtained from a UK Police force. The timing of evidence disclosure was categorised in relation to the interview quartile. Suspects' responses were analysed in relation to these timings using a specially developed analytical coding framework. Suspect responses included, i. no comment, ii. silent, iii. unclear response, iv. information provided, v. challenge, vi. inaudible, vii. non lexical, viii. legal advice sought, ix. suspect not given an opportunity to respond, and x. a lack of memory. For all suspects, evidence was disclosed gradually throughout the interview, though disclosures were made with a higher frequency in the latter quartiles of the interviews. These disclosures were primarily made in interviews with suspects deceptively denying culpability. For these suspects deceptively denying culpability, there was a high frequency of suspects both providing information and challenging the disclosures in these latter quartiles, possibly indicating the effects of the incremental value of the evidence disclosed.

KEYWORDS **Investigative Interviews, Evidence Disclosure Timing, Deception**

TITLE **Lying under pressure: Examining the impact of stress and veracity on verbal and nonverbal behavior in credibility judgments.**

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ABSTRACT In four experiments, we examined the influence of stress on perceived verbal and nonverbal behavior in both truthful and deceptive statements, and its subsequent impact on credibility judgments made by independent observers. We used the Maastricht Acute Stress Test to induce stress in senders, and we presented observers with videos (experiments 1 and 3) or transcripts (experiments 2 and 4) of these senders reporting honestly or deceptively. Results highlighted a significant impact of stress on observers' judgments of nonverbal behavior, while the actual veracity predominantly influenced credibility assessments. Plausibility and believability emerged as robust indicators of truthfulness, emphasizing the need to consider situational variables and challenging the overemphasis on nonverbal cues. The findings underscore the importance of prioritizing verbal content in professional lie detection practices.

KEYWORDS **Lie detection, stress, nonverbal cues, verbal cues**

TITLE **The efficacy of Denial of the Victim arguments within simulated coercive control suspect interviews on attributions of victim and suspect blame**

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ABSTRACT

Objectives

We previously showed that Denial of the Victim (DoV) arguments in suspect interviews for coercive control increased attribution of blame against victims, but not suspects. The effect of DoV was stronger when participants endorsed ambivalent sexist beliefs. In two experiments we replicate these findings while varying the control group and adding a second influence behaviour: Benevolence, arguing that the behaviour the suspect is accused of is out of character.

Methodology

In both experiments, participants read allegations of coercive control made against a suspect and then interview scripts where suspects responded to the allegations with DoV arguments.

Study 1 (N = 131) used a within-participants design where participants attributions of blame to the victim and suspect were measured before and after exposure to the interviews.

Study 2 (N = 170) used a “no interview” control where participants were not presented with an interview script. Study 2 also included a second influence behaviour, benevolence to capture that in actual interview suspects use combinations of influence behaviours when making arguments.

Results

Study 1 showed that attributions of blame against the suspect decreased after reading DoV interviews, while attributions of blame against the victim increased. Sexist beliefs increased the strength of these relationships.

Study 2 showed DoV only increased attributions of blame against the victim in combination with hostile sexism. Benevolence directly reduced attributions of blame toward the suspect.

Conclusions

Study 2 replicated our finding indicating DoV primarily impacts on perceptions of victims, not suspects, and especially in combination with hostile sexism. The more sensitive within-participants design of Study 1 suggests that there may be direct effects of DoV even without sexist biases. Study 2 also showed that different suspect behaviours may have complementary effects, indicating the necessity to understand both the unique and combinatory effects of multiple influence behaviours within interviews.

KEYWORDS

Denial of the Victim, Coercive Control, Suspect Interview, Social influence, Techniques of Neutralization

INVESTIGATIVE INTERVIEW

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | INVESTIGATIVE INTERVIEW

Using Behavioural Crime Linkage to Improve Memory Documentation with Survivors of Sexual Violence in Kenya - A Randomised Control Trial

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ABSTRACT

Globally, 1-in-3 women report experiencing gender-based violence in their lifetime. Yet, few report these instances to the police due to the stigma associated with the crime, as well as the culture of impunity surrounding sexual violence. Instead, survivors frequently report to community actors, such as the Wangu Kanja Foundation (WKF) in Kenya. But these organisations are not trained to document incidents of sexual violence. To date they document cases using a basic intake form that requests an incident description, as well as the time, date, and location of the offence. As such, the current randomised control trial (RCT) aimed to train members of the WKF on interviewing best-practice and equipped them with a comprehensive documentation tool using behavioural crime linkage. We hypothesised that the comprehensive tool would elicit more memory details in total from survivors of sexual violence, as well as more behaviourally relevant details that could aid in the investigation and apprehension of prolific sexual offenders. A three condition (baseline WKF intake form pre-RCT training, WKF intake form post-RCT training, comprehensive documentation form) RCT was conducted. We collected data from 365 adult survivors of sexual violence in Kenya. One way ANOVAs comparing both total details recalled and behaviourally relevant details recalled within the three documentation conditions found significant main effects ($F(2, 362) = 205.98, p < .001, \eta^2p = 0.532$; $F(2, 362) = 167.09, p < .001, \eta^2p = 0.480$, respectively). Whereby participants interviewed using the comprehensive form recalled more details in total and more behaviourally relevant details than participants in both standard WKF conditions. We concluded that community actors can document detailed accounts from survivors of sexual violence using a comprehensive documentation tool following interview training. These comprehensive accounts will be pivotal in increasing investigation potential and prosecution of prolific sexual offenders.

KEYWORDS

**Sexual Violence, Kenya, Interview Training, Memory Documentation,
Behavioural Crime Linkage**

TITLE **Understanding the Effectiveness of Motivational Interviewing with People Who Have Committed Crimes: A Systematic Review**

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ABSTRACT Correctional rehabilitation programs designed for offenders tend to be highly structured, directive and skills-oriented. However, an offender with low motivation to change is unlikely to benefit from such programs, in fact, these approaches are likely to increase resistance. In that sense, Motivational Interviewing (MI) is emerging as an important tool to address this resistance by avoiding confrontation and promoting opportunities to enhance participants' intrinsic motivation. Evidence suggests that intervention programs that incorporate MI are more effective in both preventing and reducing offending behaviour. Recognizing this evidence, advocating for the integration of MI is critical to enhance the effectiveness of interventions.

This present systematic review aimed to analyse the effectiveness of MI among people convicted of different types of offence and undergoing both custodial and non-custodial measures. Additionally, this review aimed to identify the specific characteristics and needs of these populations.

Research was conducted in four databases (i.e., PubMed, Science Direct, PsycInfo and Cochrane). Studies written in English, Portuguese and Spanish were included. According to the defined inclusion criteria, 14 articles were assessed and included in this review.

Studies have shown that Motivational Interviewing is effective in reducing both recidivism and dropout rates, and in reducing drug and alcohol abuse. MI has also been found to increase various variables such as motivation for change, treatment compliance, therapeutic alliance, empathy, and other pro-therapeutic behaviors.

KEYWORDS **Motivational Interviewing, Effectiveness, Forensic Context, Offenders**

TITLE **Eyewitness confidence in the interviewing context:
Understanding the impact of question type and order.**

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ABSTRACT

The relationship between confidence and accuracy and the reliability of eyewitness identifications has attracted a lot of attention. In contrast, relatively little is known about the relationship between eyewitness confidence and accuracy of recall memory in interview contexts. Here, we manipulated questioning approaches to investigate the impact of Free-Recall and Cued-Recall questions, whereby the latter were witness-compatible (questions concerning details reported in the preceding Free-Recall) or witness-incompatible questions. We also manipulated the order these questions were asked. A sample of 124 mock witness participants watched a crime-video and subsequently recalled the event to understand the impact of question type and order on confidence-accuracy calibration. Our results show that a Free-Recall invitation and compatible (compared to incompatible) questions promoted more stable confidence. Compatible questions yielded fewer errors, more accurate details, and promoted more reliable confidence-accuracy calibration and discrimination, especially when they preceded the incompatible questions. Implications are discussed.

KEYWORDS **Eyewitness confidence, calibration, interview question type**

TITLE **Getting information quickly: The Time Critical Questioning (TCQ) protocol for time-sensitive interviewing**

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ABSTRACT

Getting information quickly can be critical in numerous operational contexts when time is limited (e.g., terrorist attack, hostage escape). Accurate and targeted information is needed to (i) assess and neutralise immediate threats, (ii) inform critical decision-making and response, or (iii) expedite transmission of intelligence information. The Time-Critical Questioning (TCQ) protocol, which comprises the I-RELATE Instructions and effective subsequent questioning, positively impacts the information provided by interviewees under time-sensitive conditions. In brief, this framework focuses on aligning the roles, goals, and expectations of interviewer and interviewee to maximise the reporting of relevant, tactical, or otherwise actionable information. Following a proof-of-concept experiment (N = 111), participants completed an immersive scenario (N = 142) and were then interviewed for 10 minutes. Participants in TCQ interview-groups reported significantly more correct information of tactical value (cf. direct approach) at no cost to accuracy. Extending previous work, this presentation will additionally discuss the findings of two new experiments on the TCQ and a field exercise with law enforcement. Experiments 2 (N = 80) and 3 (N = 240) examined the remote administration of the TCQ (i.e., via telephone). In Experiment 2, participants took part in an online activity and reported priority information to a remotely-located interviewer using the TCQ protocol or a Direct Approach. Participants in the TCQ condition reported more information and rated greater rapport with the interviewer than participants in the Direct Approach condition. In Experiment 3, we examined the impact of a remote TCQ interview on a delayed account conducted two-days later (initial results will be presented). Application of the TCQ protocol in the context of a live counter-terrorism exercise will also be discussed. With focus on memory, we will propose the next directions in research, and explore how the protocol might be adapted for use in different operational contexts.

KEYWORDS **Time-sensitive interviews, interviewing, witnesses, information gathering, memory**

TITLE **Piloting a training of trainers to provide feedback on child interviews**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Research shows that investigative interviewers need continuous feedback on their interviews to keep their interviewing skills at the level required for interviewing children in cases of suspected child abuse. In practice, interviewers rarely get systematic feedback or chances to update their skills. The purpose of this presentation is to introduce a cost-effective training model for experienced child investigative interviewers. The aim of the training was to equip participants with the necessary skills to further train other professionals in their own unit, providing them with feedback on child interviews according to evidence-based standards.

Methodology: The training and the materials were developed in collaboration with senior researchers and practitioners in the field.

Results: The training consisted of pre-training tasks on an online learning platform and a two-day seminar scheduled to allow plenty of time for discussion. Pre-course tasks included coding and hypothesis formulation exercises, preparing a presentation based on recently published scientific research, and self-assessment of an interview conducted by the participant. During the seminar, the participants received feedback on all the pre-course tasks and presented the current research. The lectures covered hypothesis testing, latest guidelines on child interviewing and how to give feedback on child interviews. Providing feedback was also demonstrated in practice with a real case example. After the training, the participants received access to the learning platform as teachers. Feedback from the training was collected both via discussion immediately at the end of the pilot training and afterwards in written form. The overall feedback was positive and suggestions for developing the training were constructive and easy to implement.

Conclusion: Based on the received feedback, the training program appears to be a useful tool for investigative interviewers to increase opportunities to get feedback and update their skills. However, research on the effectiveness of the program is still needed.

KEYWORDS **Child abuse, investigative interviewer training, providing feedback on child forensic interviews, training of trainers**

EYEWITNESS I

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | EYEWITNESS I

TITLE How the offender is portrayed and later identified: Does gender matter?

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ABSTRACT

Objective

The aim of this study is to identify differences in how men and women describe faces and to assess if identification accuracy is somehow related to those descriptions.

Methodology

Two hundred and fifty-six under- and postgraduate participants were asked to focus on a man's or woman's photograph (the target) for 10 seconds. After a 5-minute distraction task, they were instructed to write down a detailed description of the target. Finally, they encountered either a Target Present Lineup or a Target Absent Lineup. Therefore, there were four experimental conditions: a) male target-present lineup; b) male target-absent lineup; c) female target-present lineup and; d) female target-absent lineup.

Results

As expected, both men and women performed equally in every condition, finding no differences between present or absent conditions nor between female and male lineups.

Regarding descriptions, women provided longer and richer portrayals than men: their descriptions were significantly longer and a greater variability of descriptors was found.

Overall, performance in the target-absent-lineup was independent of the description's characteristics (for every group). However, differences were found regarding the target-present-lineup performance: the more features described, the worse the performance for men, and the better for women.

Conclusions

Men and women describe offenders differently. Specifically, women tend to provide longer descriptions and a wider range of descriptors. However, their performance when encountering a lineup task is equal, no matter if the target is present in the lineup or not.

Furthermore, the number of features described might be somehow useful for explaining men's and women's accuracy only when the culprit is present in the lineup. From a practical point of view, several limitations arise when considering descriptions to infer identification accuracy.

KEYWORDS Descriptions, Eyewitness, Target-absent Lineup, Target-present lineup, Accuracy

TITLE **Virtual Reality Study of Weapon Focus Effect: Meta-cognition Affects Confidence**

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ABSTRACT

It has been claimed that when a witness expresses high confidence that their accuracy will be remarkably accurate (Wixted & Wells, 2017). We test the novel idea that high confidence accuracy will be affected by meta-cognitive beliefs. In particular, when witnesses have an accurate appraisal of how a variable affects memory, then confidence will track accuracy reasonably well, but when witnesses have inaccurate beliefs about how a variable affects accuracy, they may end up being overly confident.

We test this proposal in an experiment in which participants viewed a bar scene in virtual reality. Participants played the role of bar managers and made a joystick response whenever a 'bar rule' was violated. Two minutes into the virtual reality experience, a man came into the bar and started yelling and cursing in the direction of the camera. In one version, he held a gun in his hand. In the other condition, he held a beer bottle in his hand. Participants then answered questions about the scene including responding to a six person lineup that was either target present or target absent. Following their decision, participants made confidence judgements. Participants also answered a series of questions about their beliefs about how various factors affect eyewitness accuracy.

Approximately 1/3 of witnesses responded that the presence of a weapon should improve eyewitness identification accuracy. About 2/3 responded that the presence of a weapon should impair identification accuracy. In the high knowledge group, highly confident witnesses were correct in 95.24% of suspect identifications in the no weapon condition and 88.88% in the weapon condition. In the low knowledge condition, highly confident witnesses were 95.59% accurate in the no weapon condition and 85% accurate in the weapon condition.

Results indicate that poor viewing conditions impair the confidence accuracy relationship.

KEYWORDS **Eyewitness, confidence, weapon focus**

TITLE **Should multiple single suspect lineups be conducted, and if so, how?**

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ABSTRACT

Police officials often have more than one suspect for a particular crime. Guidelines emanating from criminal justice bodies and from researchers recommend against using multiple suspects in a lineup, but there is little empirical evidence that supports this position. We have discovered that police officials in South Africa often present lineups to eyewitnesses containing more than one suspect, which is in part an efficiency measure, given that corporeal lineups must be used in South Africa. In some preliminary work we have discovered that the way in which lineups containing multiple suspects is presented is important. When lineups contain more than one suspect, should witnesses be limited to a single choice, or should they be allowed to over-rule an earlier choice, for instance? We report results from five studies of simulated crimes (with $N > 2500$ in total), in which we compare witnesses who viewed a simulated crime, and a) made a decision after viewing two lineups, b) made a decision for each of the two lineups i.e., were allowed to change their earlier identification of the ostensible perpetrator, or c) were allowed to make only one decision from the two lineups. We also compared them to the performance of witnesses who viewed the same simulated crime, but were asked to make decisions from 10 or 14 person multiple suspect lineups. We used multinomial regression, and constructed confidence-conditioned CAC curves, finding a potential advantage for witnesses who viewed two single suspect lineups, but only made a decision after viewing both lineups. They outperformed witnesses in the other single-suspect conditions, as well as those in the multiple-suspect conditions. We discuss the implications of this for police practice, and we present some additional results from a Bayesian analysis which suggest that it may not be wise to preclude multiple-suspect lineups.

KEYWORDS **Eyewitness testimony, identification lineups, multiple-suspect lineups, single-suspect lineups**

TITLE Identification performance across the life span: Lineups and the reaction time-based Concealed Information Test

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ABSTRACT

In the investigation of crimes, police use lineups to identify offenders. However, cognitive and social factors can deteriorate eyewitness identification performance in children and older adults. A less direct test of recognition such as the Concealed Information Test could be beneficial for child and older adult witnesses. In a field experiment, we mapped identification performance in a large community sample (N = 1,239) across the lifespan (ages 6-79 years) for two different identification procedures: classic lineups and reaction time-based Concealed Information Test (RT-CIT). Visitors of a science museum or science fair witnessed a recorded mock theft and then took either a classic lineup, or the RT-CIT. In the RT-CIT, longer reaction times to the familiar people from the stimulus film than to foils are indicative of recognition or the so-called CIT effect. As expected, young adults (18-45 years) consistently outperformed younger age groups in lineup performance. The RT-CIT showed a moderate capacity to diagnose face recognition and absence of recognition in the target-absent condition. Importantly, age did not affect identification with the RT-CIT. Thus, lineup performance was more vulnerable to age effects than the RT-CIT. However, this did come with a considerably lower utility (i.e., exclusion rate of more than 40%). These findings suggest that the RT-CIT might be considered an alternative identification procedure for children, offering protection for innocent suspects.

KEYWORDS

Eyewitness identification, confidence-accuracy relationship, memory development, memory detection, social demands

TITLE **Investigating memory and metamemory processes for sexual violence using passive and immersive stimuli**

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ABSTRACT We investigated differences in memory recall and metamemory processes at interview when participants encode an implied sexual assault scenario in VR or video. We will also explore whether retrieval effort indicators (e.g., pausing, fillers such as “um”) predict recall accuracy. Previous research investigating memory for sexual violence has used mock-crime videos and hypothetical rape scenarios. However, passively observing or reading about a sexual violence may not elicit memory and metamemory processes that are akin to real life. Virtual reality (VR) may increase how much an experimental task realistically simulates the real-life situation, potentially allowing for more informed applications. 18 female participants encoded an implied sexual assault via video (n = 9) or VR (n = 9), then were interviewed immediately and 7-days later using a two-phased structured interview (free recall, cued-question phase). Interview transcripts were coded for accuracy and retrieval effort indicators in relation to correct and incorrect details.

Preliminary analysis indicates that accuracy doesn't vary between encoding condition. For both conditions, accuracy was significantly lower for the cued-question phase compared to the free recall. Based on previous research, we predict that retrieval effort indicators will be predictive of recall accuracy. This project has significant potential to achieve real-world impact by informing future methodologies used to measure memory and metamemory processes for sexual violence. Specifically, it will shed light on whether methods for investigating memory for sexual violence are better conducted using in an immersive (VR) versus passive (video) format. It will also add to existing research on the predictive value of retrieval effort indicators, and extend this research by exploring indicators in the context of sexual violence. Practically, developing a way in which retrieval effort indicators could be systematically defined and understood may be useful in identifying weak memories that may not benefit an investigation.

KEYWORDS **Sexual violence, Memory recall, Metamemory, Interviewing, Retrieval effort indicators**

FALSE MEMORY

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | FALSE MEMORY

TITLE Does forgetting lead to false memories? The impact of directed forgetting on spontaneous false memory formation in children and adults

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ABSTRACT

In some cases, eyewitnesses delay disclosing information to the police after traumatic events, potentially leading to forgotten details and memory errors, including false memories. This study investigated the impact of directed forgetting on false memories for complex visual scenes in adults and children (aged 9-10), as well as the relation between PTSD symptoms and memory processes. Using a modified directed forgetting paradigm and a modified Deese/Roediger-McDermott (DRM) false memory paradigm with complex visual scenes, we aimed to: i) replicate the directed forgetting effect, expecting adults to exhibit a higher effect than children, ii) examine differences in spontaneous false memories, hypothesizing more false memories in children with fewer false memories (developmental differences) in the forgetting condition and iii) investigate the association between PTSD symptoms and memory processes. A 2 (Age group: Children vs Adults) x 2 (Instructions: Forgetting vs Remembering) between-subjects design will be employed with approximately 160 participants. Participants will study complex visual scenes while receiving directed forgetting specific instructions and undertake memory tests as well as fill in PTSD symptoms scales. Data will be analyzed using ANOVA tests, correlations between memory and PTSD scores, and Signal Detection Theory variables. This study aims to bridge gaps in previous research by exploring the interplay between intentional forgetting and false memories for complex visual scenes for both children and adults. Findings will contribute to understanding forgetting, false memories, and their implications, with an extended application in cases of abuse or violence where delayed disclosures can have severe consequences.

KEYWORDS Directed forgetting, false memories, complex visual scenes, children, adults

TITLE **What's with the memory distrust? Presenting research on memory distrust in various false memory tasks**

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The aim of the presented research was to investigate the role of memory distrust in the formation of memory distortions in four well-established false memory paradigms: a misinformation task, the Gudjonsson interrogative suggestibility procedure (GSS), an imagination inflation task, and the Deese-Roediger-McDermott list (DRM).

Methodology

In total, more than 1,000 people participated in one of the four experiments in the mentioned paradigms. Memory distrust was measured by questionnaires and experimentally manipulated (with the exception of the DRM list experiment) using two tasks: creating a description of childhood events and remembering nouns, after which the participants received negative feedback on their memory functioning. We also verified (GSS and misinformation task) or manipulated awareness of discrepancies (imagination inflation task) between true and suggested informations.

Results obtained or expected

ABSTRACT Although memory distrust is indicated as the most common cause of succumbing to suggestibility (eg. Blank, 1998, Polczyk, 2017), the results of two experiments on suggestibility (i.e., the misinformation task and GSS) indicate a minor role for memory distrust in the formation of memory distortions, even for participants who were aware of discrepancies between the original information and that which were suggested to them. A further two experiments are underway. In the study of imagination inflation, we expect to observe the influence of memory distrust under certain condition that is in people who are aware of the discrepancies between their own memories and what they have imagined. In the DRM word list paradigm, on the other hand, we do not expect to observe a relationship between distrust of memory and false memories, because in this paradigm there is no room to see discrepancies between true information and suggested information.

Conclusion

Our studies can contribute to a better understanding of memory vulnerabilities to distortion, with can have potential implications for forensic psychology.

KEYWORDS **Memory distrust, memory distortion, suggestibility, DRM, imagination inflation**

TITLE **Unmasking Forgetting and False Memories: Insights from a Meta-Analysis**

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ABSTRACT

Witnesses of crime might be interviewed about their memories after long delays. Details of their experience might then be forgotten which raises the question whether this forgetting might negatively affect the validity of testimony leading to false memory. The current meta-analysis study aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between forgetting and false memories. Data on correlations between true and false memories from 12 studies were included in the final analysis, comprising a total of 15 experiments and 79 correlations. Pooled effect sizes revealed a weak positive association between true and false memories overall. However, within the realm of studies looking the effect of false denials on forgetting, a small to moderate positive association was found between true and false memory generation. Moreover, a higher correlation between true and false memories was found in memory of events versus interviews, irrespective of whether participants were in the false denial or control group. These findings shed light on the complex relationship between true and false memories after forgetting, suggesting that while true and false memories sometimes go hand in hand, they can also be independent of each other under different contextual conditions.

KEYWORDS **Forgetting, False Memory, Meta-Analysis**

TITLE **Is False Memory Implantation Blind?: Exploring the Impact of Culture on False Memory Implantation for Repeated versus Single Events**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of culture (Western vs. Eastern) and event frequency (single vs. repeated) on susceptibility to implanted false memories. The false memory blind implantation method was used to convince Indonesian (N = 69) and Western (N = 94) participants that they had a childhood physical fight that damaged their clothing. In a quasi-experimental 2 (Culture: Western, Indonesian) x 2 (Event Frequency: repeated, single) design, participants were randomly assigned to conditions where the event was described as occurring once or multiple times. Participants from Maastricht University and Universitas Indonesia reviewed childhood events, including the critical event. Belief and recollection ratings were measured using adapted scales (Scoboria et al., 2004). Data was collected online (Qualtrics) over two phases in one week. The hypothesis was that event frequency would not affect false memory formation. The Indonesian sample was expected to develop more false beliefs, the Western sample would develop more false memories. Overall, 25-31% of participants experienced a false belief, and 4-7% experienced a false memory. Chi-square tests revealed no significant effect of event frequency on false belief or false memory formation, both before and after an imagination instruction ($\chi^2(1) = 0.14, p = .712$, and $\chi^2(1) = 0.003, p = .954$ for false belief; $\chi^2(1) = 0.03, p = .873$ and $\chi^2(1) = 0.16, p = .688$ for false memory). Binary logistic regression models indicated that culture significantly affected false belief formation ($p = .007$ before and $p = .010$ after imagination instruction), with the Western sample showing the highest rate of false belief formation. The Indonesian sample had the highest rate of false memory formation ($p = .044$). This research, using new methodologies and a diverse sample, fills literature gaps and has implications for forensic psychology, legal proceedings, and therapy. It enhances the ecological validity of false memory research and improves memory-related practices

KEYWORDS **False memory, Blind implantation, Cross-cultural, False belief**

TITLE **Open Science and Study Quality in False Memory Research: Trends, Perceptions, and Implications**

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ABSTRACT

Since the replication crisis in psychology, a pivotal event that underscored the issues of reproducibility and credibility in psychological research, the scientific community has been increasingly embracing open science practices. These practices are aimed at bolstering the reliability, transparency, and accessibility of research. To evaluate this progress, our project embarked on a dual exploration: firstly, we evaluated how false memory research has integrated open science practices in response to these evolving norms, and secondly, we examined public perceptions of these practices within legal psychology.

In Study 1, we conducted a scoping review of the false memory research literature since 2015. Specifically, the review examined the type of study and the incorporation of open science practices for each published false memory report, including open access publishing, material, data and analysis script sharing, and preregistration status. We analyzed the adoption of open science practices over time and investigated their associations with academic recognition.

In Study 2, we conducted an experimental vignette study to gain insights into public perceptions of these practices. In the study, participants were presented with legal case vignettes paired with fictional research summaries (varied in study design and preregistration status) and asked to decide on the fictitious case, taking into account the accompanying research. Specifically, we were interested in whether lay individuals recognize the enhanced reliability of the evidence associated with specific approaches, and if this recognition leads to increased trust in the finding or use within the decision-making process.

In the presentation, the findings from both studies will be discussed, shedding light on the current state and impact of open science practices in psychology, specifically false memory research.

KEYWORDS **Open Science, False Memory, Transparency, Reproducibility**

CHILD EYEWITNESS

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | CHILD EYEWITNESS

TITLE Revision and evaluation of ViContact 2.0 – an interactive training system for learning how to interview children about sexual abuse suspicions

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ABSTRACT

ViContact 2.0 is a multi-method interactive training system designed to teach professionals how to conversations with children in cases of suspected sexual abuse. The system includes e-learning modules, an in-person seminar, practice conversations with virtual children in a virtual reality (VR) environment, automated feedback, and supervision of real cases from participants' professional practice. A previous version of the training system demonstrated improvements in interviewing skills, self-efficacy and obstructive attitudes in a randomized controlled study. We now present a revised version of the training system, including increased automation through e-Learning modules, a new module on how to document conversations and a supervision module for real cases. In the revised VR component, participants questions can now be categorized in full automation based on a machine learning classification algorithm, making the human operator needed for the former version obsolete. We present the results of a pre-post designed study comparing the effectiveness of the automated VR training (AVR) with the former human-operated VR training (HVR). The data collection is currently being completed. A targeted sample of 30 student participants will take part in a two-hour VR training (either AVR or HVR) in which they verbally interact with virtual children to find out what happened to them and receive automated, personalized feedback targeted to improve their interviewing skills. Performance changes in VR interviews pre and post training serve as main outcome measures. We expect no significant differences between AVR and HVR regarding pre-post changes in various behavioral performance measures (proportion of recommended questions, proportion of supportive utterances and degree of supportiveness in opening and closing phases), and in selfreport measures (self-efficacy and obstructive cognitive and emotional patterns). A similar performance of the automated compared to the human-operated version would justify the application of the revised ViContact training in practice.

KEYWORDS Child Sexual Abuse, Child Interviewing, Child Protection, Virtual Reality

TITLE **Enhancing Child Abuse Investigations: Comparing Hypothesis Formulation by Experts, Novices, and AI Models**

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ABSTRACT

The initial formulation of hypotheses is critical in guiding interviews towards unbiased information gathering. Despite the advancements in child investigative interviewing such as the development of structured interviewing protocols, there is currently a gap in the research literature on how the child's interviewer should formulate hypotheses when investigating suspected cases of child abuse. This study has two aims: First, to propose a way of developing and evaluating pre-interview hypotheses and assessing how they can be incorporated into the interview protocols through the formulation of questions aimed to explore them. Second, to compare the quality of Large Language Model (LLM)-generated hypotheses against those formulated by both novices and expert human investigators. Through an analysis of hypotheses formulated based on 8 case vignettes, we expect to show that while LLMs (specifically GPT-4 and Llama 2) can outperform untrained individuals in generating broad, theoretically grounded hypotheses, experts possess a superior ability to translate theoretical knowledge into practical, investigatively relevant hypotheses. We will also look at how hypotheses are translated into questions that can be used to collect information during the investigative interview. The study included a total of 3,722 hypotheses, formulated by five participant groups. The presentation will focus on the comprehensiveness of hypothesis sets created for each vignette, with each set comprising all the hypotheses crafted by a single participant to explain the suspicion of abuse. Our results showed that the comprehensiveness of hypothesis sets suggested by GPT-4 ($M = 2.194$, $SD = .046$) was significantly better than the others. In detail, Experts ($M = 1.934$, $SD = .079$) performed equally to Psychologists ($M = 1.733$, $SD = .046$) and Llama ($M = 1.881$, $SD = .046$), $p > .05$, which outperformed the Naïve humans ($M = 1.653$, $SD = .046$), $p < .005$, $95\%CI[.046, .410]$. We also performed a qualitative analysis of the themes present in the questions participants suggested for testing their hypotheses during the investigative interview. Nine themes emerged, and participant groups showed distinct approach to hypotheses testing, with Experts and Psychologists focusing their questions more on details of the abuse and relationship to the perpetrator, while Naïve individuals and LLMs suggested questions related to the child's mental state and behavior, and family dynamics. This study reveals LLMs' promising utility as cognitive support in the investigative process, demonstrating their capacity to outperform human experts in certain aspects of hypothesis formulation. It demonstrates the possibility of integrating the use of LLMs in the preparation phase of investigative interviews, potentially leading to a more objective and thorough exploration of child abuse allegations.

KEYWORDS **Investigative interview, child abuse, hypotheses, large language models**

TITLE Promoting honesty in children through mutual reciprocity

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ABSTRACT

Background: Research suggests that promising to tell the truth increases the likelihood that child witnesses will go on to tell the truth during investigative interviews. That said, promising to tell the truth could be considered akin to asking children to pledge an oath which is not permissible in courts in some countries. It therefore remains important to find an effective, evidence-based, honesty-promoting strategy for use during interviews with child witnesses that will be accepted across jurisdictions.

Method: Participants (N = 88), aged 7-12 years, first engaged in an interactive task with a confederate, they then witnessed the confederate steal money from a wallet and they were asked to keep this transgression a secret. All of the children were interviewed about what they had witnessed. At the beginning of the interviews, a third of the children were reminded of the importance of being honest during their interviews (control condition), one third were asked to promise to tell the truth (promise condition), and the final third were primed with reciprocity by engaging in an open conversation with the interviewer who disclosed information about themselves during the rapport-building phase. They were told that the interviewer would remain honest and they should be honest too (reciprocity condition). Whether or not children disclosed the transgression, and when they disclosed the transgression during their interviews, was recorded.

Results: The interview strategies did not influence children's truth- and lie-telling behaviour, but the type of questioning did. Children were significantly more likely to disclose the transgression in the direct questioning phase compared to the free narrative, regardless of the interview strategy.

Conclusion: Although children were more likely to tell the truth in the direct questioning phase, this is not recommended by best-practice guidelines. Therefore, it remains important to find alternative evidence-based interview strategies that promote honesty in children during the free narrative phase of the interview.

KEYWORDS Child witnesses, Promoting honesty, Investigative interviewing, Reciprocity

TITLE **Judicial Impact of the NICHD investigative interview protocol in Portuguese criminal cases**

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ABSTRACT

The NICHD protocol has been identified as the best example of applied science in children's investigative interviewing, recognition obtained through strong empirical grounded research (Lamb et al., 2018). For this reason, Peixoto, Ribeiro e Alberto (2013) choose to adapt to the Portuguese context the NICHD Interview Protocol, given its ecological validity which replicates the approach used by forensic interviewers in many countries and is consistent with best-practice guidelines advocated by research and practitioner groups. Peixoto and collaborators (2016) revealed that the Portuguese NICHD Investigative Interview Protocol version behaves similarly to other versions, particularly in terms of interviewer behavior and child responses. The NICHD Protocol also has demonstrated to have a strong influence in the case outcome (Pipe et al., 2013). The aim of our study was to verify the impact of the protocol in Portuguese judicial proceedings, particularly if the introduction of evidence-based practice for interviewing child witnesses produced changes in case outcome.

We identify case characteristics that predicted (i) whether criminal charges would be filed and prosecution sought, expecting that interview condition would have a significant effect on the likelihood of charges being filed, and (ii) whether convictions, acquittals, or dismissals of charges were more likely in the Protocol than the non-Protocol condition. The study presents data that demonstrates the importance of the use of the NICHD Investigative Interview Protocol on judicial decision making. Also shows that the use of a better methodology of interviewing children will increase evidence quality and judicial efficacy. The study is the first to test the impact of the Protocol in European type criminal proceedings.

KEYWORDS **Children, Investigative Interview, NICHD Protocol, Judicial Decision Making**

TITLE **Similar Rates of Denial in NICHD and Control Interviews with Alleged Child Abuse Victims in the Netherlands**

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ABSTRACT

In the current study, we examined 38 National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD) interview transcripts, and 30 control transcripts from interviews from an earlier study (Erens et al., 2022) conducted with alleged child victims of abuse at Dutch child protection services. We investigated whether denial and avoidance rates differed statistically significantly based on the interview protocol used. We detected 57 denial and 282 avoidance statements across the 68 interviews. No statistically significant differences emerged between 1) the proportion of denials using NICHD (42%, $n = 16/38$) and control interviews (30%, $n = 9/30$), and 2) the average number of denial statements between NICHD ($M = 0.84$) and control interviews ($M = 0.83$). Furthermore, denials (and avoidances) were not more or less likely to occur in response to certain types of questions, even though the majority of denials in our sample occurred in response to option-posing questions (60%, $n = 34/57$). Denials did occur statistically significantly less often within the first half of the individual interviews in NICHD than control interviews. Our findings call attention to difficulties child protection services face in investigative interviews with alleged child victims.

KEYWORDS

Child Abuse, NICHD interview, Child Investigative Interview, Denial, Child Abuse

VICTIMS

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | VICTIMS

TITLE “Signs of safety” and the “3 HOUSES” as useful tools for at-risk children and adolescents’ assessment and intervention

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ABSTRACT Working with children and young people at risk as well as with their families is a demanding challenge for professionals, both in the assessment and intervention phases. Victims of adverse childhood situations (maltreatment, abuse, neglect or separation/divorce from their parents) need support to integrate and adapt to change. It is important to facilitate the child's disclosure, in particular about what is going on in their world, and it is essential that the information collected is analysed with care, respect and rigor. Tools exist that aid in establishing a positive and trusting relationship, which is essential for partnering and collaborating with children, young people, and their families to build sustainable changes. The resources "signs of safety" and "3 HOUSES" were developed with the aim of ensuring that the voice of children and young people is more present in the work carried out by forensic psychologists. These tools enable professionals to collect insights into the child's viewpoint and also help them comprehend the reasons for the services' involvement with their family. This allows for a chance to be heard and to grasp the proceedings at each stage of the process. These resources, in use since 2005 in England, can be applied in diverse manners to meet the needs of the victim. Moreover, they should be tailored to the context and culture of the families that professionals are assisting. This communication will share potential adaptations in the application of these resources, along with information gathered from real cases, and its integration into intervention plans tailored to the needs of at-risk children and youth.

KEYWORDS at-risk children and adolescents, signs of safety, 3 Houses, assessment, intervention

TITLE **Mental health in non-consensual intimate image-sharing adult victims: The link with adverse and positive childhood experiences**

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ABSTRACT

Childhood experiences influence adult life at various levels. Several studies highlight the impact of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) and positive childhood experiences (PCEs) on mental health and experiences of victimization in adult life. The present study aims to analyze the relationship between ACEs, PCEs, anxiety, and depression; compare victims and non-victims of non-consensual intimate image-sharing regarding ACEs, PCEs, anxiety, and depression in adulthood; and verify the predictors of mental health. The sample comprised 931 Portuguese adults (654 female and 277 male) and 190 (20.4%) victims of non-consensual intimate image-sharing, with ages between 18 and 77. The participants responded online to the sociodemographic questionnaire, a non-consensual intimate image-sharing victimization checklist, the Childhood Adverse Experiences Questionnaire, the Benevolent Childhood Experiences Scale, and the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale. The Ethics Committee of Egas Moniz School of Health and Science approved the study, which followed the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. The results showed that ACEs are related to higher scores of anxiety and depression, and PCEs are related to lower scores of anxiety and depression. Victims of non-consensual intimate image-sharing showed more ACEs, anxiety, and depression and fewer PCEs. Furthermore, the explanatory model of anxiety using a multiple linear regression showed that non-consensual intimate image-sharing, sex, age, emotional neglect, and PCEs are significant predictors of anxiety symptoms in adulthood, explaining 24% of their variance. Non-consensual intimate image-sharing, age, emotional neglect, childhood exposure to domestic violence, and PCEs are significant predictors of depression, explaining 26% of their variance. This research shows that childhood experiences significantly shape adult life. Both adverse and positive experiences are linked with future victimization and affect mental health. Findings highlight the importance of further understanding the relationship between those variables, emphasizing the need for early intervention and support to mitigate the long-term effects of adversities.

KEYWORDS

Non-consensual intimate image-sharing, Adverse Childhood Experiences, Positive Childhood Experiences, Anxiety, Depression

TITLE **AI Tools in Combatting Online Child Sexual Exploitation and Abuse: Challenges and Opportunities**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Online child sexual exploitation and abuse (OCSEA) is considered one of the main threats children face and, in 2023, only the National Center for Missing and Exploited Children received more than 36.2 million of CyberTipline reports, representing a massive number of potential new victims and criminal investigations. Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology has been developed to support investigators and prevent this type of criminality. The objective of this study is to identify and analyse the current challenges and opportunities of applying AI to combat OCSEA from a psychological and criminological perspective.

Methodology: This study adopted an integrative literature review, involving a thorough search of peer-reviewed articles in B-On, PubMed, PsycInfo, Scopus and Google Scholar databases, grey literature sources and hand searching in order to understand the conceptual and empirical dimension of OCSEA and the integration of AI in preventing and combat this phenomenon. The search terms included were: "online child sexual exploitation and abuse" or "child sexual abuse" or "law enforcement" and "artificial intelligence" and "prevention", in English, Portuguese, Spanish and French.

Results: The findings of the study demonstrate the importance of developing and incorporating AI tools to prevent and combat OCSEA. Existing research confirmed the potential of AI in assisting law enforcement in investigating these cases and in preventing and reducing victimization. However, concerns arise regarding using AI, specially related to image models trained on child sexual abuse material and the potential volume of AI generated child sexual abuse material.

Conclusion: AI has enormous potential in combating OCSEA and in protecting victims. However, the development and implementation of these solutions encompass a series of challenges that must be addressed for a responsible and safer use of technology. Further research is needed to provide clarity in the development and implementation of this technology, particularly when applied to different forms of OCSEA.

KEYWORDS

Online child sexual exploitation and abuse (OCSEA), Artificial Intelligence, Child victimization, Victim protection, Crime prevention

TITLE “We don’t talk about that around here’: An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) of South Asian men’s experiences of sexual violence in the UK

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ABSTRACT

Background

Sexual violence against men is an understudied issue, particularly among ethnic minority groups. This study explored how South Asian cultural norms shape disclosure, help-seeking, and reporting to the police for male survivors in the UK.

Methods

Using interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA), semi-structured interviews were conducted with 11 South Asian male survivors of sexual violence currently living in the UK. Participants were recruited through specialist support organisations. Interviews explored participants' experiences of disclosure, cultural factors surrounding sexual violence, and barriers/facilitators to support and reporting. Data were analysed following IPA's idiographic approach to identify themes across participant accounts.

Results

Three key themes emerged centred on familial pressures, cultural taboos, and barriers to support/justice. Familial reputational pressures made survivors reluctant to disclose and they often received dismissive reactions. Cultural taboos about sex and mental health meant survivors felt unable to recognise their experiences and needs. Barriers to professional support and criminal justice services included stigma and lack of cultural understanding. Distrust of systems discouraged justice-seeking, with negative experiences for those reporting abuse.

Conclusions

Traditional South Asian values regarding family honour, gender norms, and stigma created obstacles to disclosure and help-seeking for male survivors. Culturally-tailored outreach and supports are needed to overcome taboos and empower South Asian male survivors to access appropriate care and report to the police. Findings emphasise the intersection of masculinity and culture in shaping experiences of sexual violence. Implications for services and the criminal justice systems are discussed.

KEYWORDS Sexual Violence, Ethnic Minorities, Reporting, Male victims

TITLE Psychological processes linking childhood maltreatment to later intimate partner violence victimization

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ABSTRACT

Objective. In the UK, more than half of adults with a history of childhood maltreatment (CM) experience intimate partner violence (IPV) later in life, but what makes this group particularly vulnerable to revictimization remains unclear. Here, we estimated the effect of CM on IPV beyond their common risk factors, and examined the psychological processes contributing to this effect.

Methodology. We used genetically informed causal inference methods to estimate the effect of CM on IPV in 12794 young adults from the UK Twins Early Development Study (TEDS). Additionally, together with a diverse lived-experience panel, we co-produced qualitative interviews involving 16 survivors of CM and IPV to investigate the psychological pathways linking these two experiences.

Results. The TEDS participants with a history of CM were 3 to 4 times more likely to experience IPV than their peers at age 21 and 26, respectively. CM exhibited a modest but significant effect on IPV in causal models accounting for their shared etiology ($\beta = 0.15-0.21$). The co-production work highlighted how possible psychological outcomes of CM, such as increased risk tolerance and threat avoidance, may shape partner selection and relationship dynamics. Planned qualitative interviews will further elucidate how such processes may lead to increased risk of IPV; results will be presented at the conference.

Conclusion. Our results highlight the unique contribution of CM to subsequent experiences of IPV, over and above their common risk factors. Moreover, they emphasize the role of psychological processes linked with CM in driving the association between these experiences, complementing IPV theories that focus primarily on the psychology of perpetrators. Overall, these findings underscore the need for psychological interventions aimed at supporting survivors of CM in developing safe intimate relationships.

KEYWORDS Childhood maltreatment, Intimate partner violence, Genetically informed design, Qualitative design, Lived experience

OFFENDERS

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | OFFENDERS

TITLE Knowledge about sex offender registration/notification policies and sexual offending behavior in a community sample of adolescents in the U.S.

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ABSTRACT

In the U.S., most states require adolescents who sexually offend to register their personal information with local law enforcement agencies. Their personal information also may be posted online to notify communities about the potential risk they pose. Because some common adolescent sexual behaviors are illegal (e.g., sexting, consensual sex with a similar-aged peer), many youth may be subjected to these juvenile registration and notification (JSORN) policies. This is concerning because the sanctions may subject youth and families to serious harm.

JSORN policies are based partially on the idea that risk of being sanctioned deters adolescents from offending in the first place. Our objective was to test this assumption. We administered an experimental survey to 338 U.S. adolescents. We investigated whether adolescents knew that certain sexual behaviors can result in registration and notification, as well as whether policy-aware youth were less likely than others to have engaged in those behaviors. We also tested whether adolescents' knowledge differed by graduated sanction type: criminalization; criminalization plus registration; or criminalization, registration, and notification. Finally, we explored whether a brief educational intervention could boost adolescents' policy knowledge.

Results showed that, without intervention, 27% of adolescents failed a quiz assessing knowledge that certain sexual behaviors could lead youth to experience legal sanctions. Policy knowledge did not differ across sanction types, and was unrelated to actual sexual offending, which 28% of our adolescents reported. Although the educational intervention was effective, our other findings suggest improving adolescents' knowledge about JSORN policy is not likely to curb offending. These findings cast doubt on the deterrent potential of U.S. JSORN policies while simultaneously demonstrating the number of youth at risk of being subjected to them. U.S. policymakers should look to other countries to identify more effective, less damaging policy alternatives.

KEYWORDS

adolescents, sex offender registration, community notification, deterrence, public policy

TITLE **Adverse childhood experiences, the use of illicit drugs, and mental health in sex offenders**

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ABSTRACT

Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) are events that occur before the age of eighteen and include situations of family dysfunction and/or victimization. ACEs are often related to depressive, anxiety, and stress symptoms, and their severity in adulthood is associated with the amount, frequency, and type of exposure to ACEs. Sex offenders have a higher prevalence of ACEs and a high consumption of illicit substances. The present study aims to analyze the relationship between ACEs, use of illicit drugs, stress, anxiety, and depression in sex offenders and compare a sample of rapists and child molesters in those variables. The sample consisted of 135 male adults, 48 (35.6%) rapists and 87 (64.4%) child molesters. The participants answered the following: a sociodemographic questionnaire, a checklist of illicit substance consumption, the Adverse Childhood Experiences assessment tool, and the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale assessment tool. The Ethics Committee of Egas Moniz School of Health and Science approved this study, and all the ethical and deontological aspects indicated in the Declaration of Helsinki were respected. The results showed that total ACEs were positively correlated with depression, anxiety, and stress. The use of illicit drugs was positively correlated with emotional abuse, sexual abuse, emotional neglect, substance abuse in the family, and total ACEs. Rapists had a higher consumption of illicit substances, more family mental illness or suicide, higher depression and stress symptoms, and fewer experiences of parental divorce when compared to child abusers. This study could enable the development of strategies to reduce the adverse impact of ACEs through specific intervention programs, awareness campaigns, or the development of intervention protocols that meet the needs of these individuals.

KEYWORDS **Sex offenders, Adverse Childhood Experiences, Illicit drugs, Mental health**

TITLE **Does The Setting Matters? Characterizing and Classifying Rural and Urban Arsonists**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Many fires are started intentionally, and the conditions of the setting of the fire (SF) can lead to different crime opportunities in rural or urban areas. Despite the different conditions and opportunities for committing crimes in rural and urban areas, studies have yet to focus on the SF. Rural arsonists tend to set fires in vegetated areas, while urban arsonists usually target dwellings and other properties. Although urban and rural arsonists share similar characteristics, some studies suggest that they differ in psychosocial and behavioral characteristics, such as age and motivation to start fires. Aim: This study analyzes the psychosocial, behavioral, and offending characteristics of rural and urban arsonists. It also aims to distinguish rural arsonists from their urban counterparts by classifying them into subgroups. Methodology: The criminal cases of 330 arsonists (n=221 in rural areas, n=103 in urban areas, and n=6 in both) were collected from the Directorate-General of Reintegration and Prison Services database. Descriptive statistics were conducted to characterize the sample and Latent Class Analysis was used to identify different subgroups within this population. Results: Although some similar characteristics are shared from both rural and urban arsonists(e.g., gender, behavior after the crime, ignition device used for setting the fire), the findings reveal the existence of three different groups: Rural Arsonists-Consumption Problems(n=141,43%), Rural Arsonists-Mental Health Problems(n=120, 36%) and Urban Arsonists-Revenge Against Family/Intimate Partners(n=69, 21%). When comparing both SF, individuals from the rural groups differed from the urban group in terms of age, criminal history, relationship to the victim, and motivation for setting the fire. Conclusion: Arsonists have different characteristics when considering the SF: in rural areas, criminal behavior patterns are influenced by psychological and social integration problems, while in urban settings, family relationship/intimate partner problems have a greater impact. These findings contribute to prevention and intervention strategies for this type of crime.

KEYWORDS

Deliberate firesetting, Arson, Rural Crime, Urban Crime, Latent Class Analysis

TITLE Exploring Disparities among Dark Web Child Sexual Abuse Material Users: Self-Reports of Offenders

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ABSTRACT

Objective of the study: This study aims to investigate potential differences between CSAM users who admit to being charged for a sexual offense and those who assert no such charges.

Methodology: Data was collected through a survey from anonymous offenders actively seeking child sexual abuse material (CSAM) or searching for help for their use of CSAM on the dark web. The survey explores their help-seeking behavior, motivations for CSAM use, sexual interest in children, CSAM victim demographics, pornography consumption, offline and online child sexual abuse, CSAM perpetration, recent sexually abusive behavior toward children (SCHiMRA-B), and adverse childhood experiences. The survey, available in twelve languages, remains open.

Results obtained: With 3782 respondents to date, preliminary findings show that 76% of the respondents identify themselves as male, 10% as female, and 5% as non-binary (8% preferred not to disclose gender). Slightly more than half of the participants (51%) fall within the 18-34 age range. One fifth of the male respondents reported being charged for sexual offence against a child and 27% against an adult. Notably, female participants reported charges slightly more often compared to their male counterparts: 21% charged of a crime against a child and 32% against an adult. The youngest respondents (18-24 years old) reported the highest frequency of charges. Variations in behaviors and beliefs were also identified between those charged and those without charges.

Conclusions: Preliminary results indicate significant differences in demographic profiles, behaviors, and beliefs between CSAM users reporting charges for sexual offenses and those who do not. The implications for preventive work and further research will be discussed.

KEYWORDS CSAM, dark web, Offender behaviour

TITLE **Of Lolitas and Jailbait – An Exploration of Incel Discourse surrounding Sex with Minors**

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ABSTRACT Incels (involuntary celibates) form an online subculture united in their frustration at being unable to engage in a sexual relationship with a woman. Recently, following several misogynistic, violent attacks, incels have been marked as a hate group. Most research focuses on their hatred and violent rhetoric aimed at women, and to a lesser extent, members of sexual and ethnic minorities. However, a subset of incels also appear to endorse and even encourage sex with underage, even prepubescent, girls. These incels explain such extreme views through evolutionary science, and they appear to emphasise concepts such as “purity” as it relates to girls and women. Little is known about the prevalence and nature of incels’ endorsement and encouragement of sex with minors on incel forums. However, given the rapid growth of these online communities, and the involvement of increasingly younger men and boys, it is vital that we understand how such ideas spread in these online spaces.

The aim of this study is to shed light on incels’ online discourse surrounding sex with minors. We use a database of 7 million+ comments made over the course of seven years on one of the largest incel forums. We compare incels who espouse views in favour of sex with minors, with those who oppose these views and those who are neutral on the subject. This comparison will occur on a variety of linguistic dimensions (positive and negative affect, hostility, anger, insecurity etc), using automated language processing. Further, we explore the trajectory of such comments, to determine whether newer members “catch” such views from older members. Finally, we perform a brief, qualitative analysis to further examine the nature of comments surrounding age and consent. This study is exploratory, but we expect to get a better understanding of the scope and nature of this issue.

KEYWORDS **incels, sexual abuse, linguistic analysis**

EYEWITNESS MEMORY

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | EYEWITNESS MEMORY

TITLE **The Nature of ROC Practices in Eyewitness Memory Research**

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ABSTRACT

Eyewitness memory research has reformed police practices and policy and is sometimes relied upon in legal proceedings. Due to the practical implications derived from this research, it is imperative to evaluate how practical recommendations are postulated. To assess the practical relevance of research, effect sizes and its interpretation play a pivotal role. In this study, we examined how the frequently used effect size Area Under the Curve (AUC) obtained via Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves are used and interpreted in eyewitness memory research. Via a systematic literature search, we identified 157 eyewitness memory related articles that conducted ROC curve analyses resulting in 1580 AUC values. Approximately 90% of the studies relied on statistical significance to interpret the AUC values. This practice can be problematic as the sample sizes in many studies were rather large which can lead to statistically significant effects that are trivial. Also, more than half of the studies did not report 95% CIs for their AUC values. Finally, power analyses were frequently not conducted and if they were they were, they were oftentimes not reproducible. To improve the practical inferences of eyewitness memory research, we highlight the need of establishing a smallest effect size of interest, focusing on 95% CIs, and conducting reproducible power analyses.

KEYWORDS

Eyewitness memory, Receiver Operating Curve characteristics, Effect sizes, Power analyses

TITLE **A cross-cultural and intra-cultural investigation of the misinformation effect in eyewitness memory reports**

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ABSTRACT

The culture in which individuals are socialised can play a role in shaping their eyewitness memory reports. Drawing on self-construal theory and using a mock witness paradigm, we examined cultural differences in the misinformation effect. A 2 (Cultural Group: Ghana, United Kingdom) x 2 (Misinformation Exposure: Control items, Experimental items) mixed design was used. Participants sampled from collectivistic (Ghana; n = 65) and individualistic (UK; n = 62) cultures were exposed to misleading post-event information (PEI). The between-subject factor was cultural group, and the within-subject factor was misinformation exposure. Participants provided a free recall account and then completed a recognition task that included misinformation items. Cultural difference in misinformation endorsement was not observed in free recall. However, participants from the collectivistic culture endorsed more misleading items in the recognition task than those from the individualistic culture. We also found that individual level cultural orientation within the respective cultures may play a role in the misinformation effect. Specifically, horizontal individualism was negatively associated with the acceptance of misleading post event information about central details for mock witnesses from the collectivistic cultural group. Horizontal collectivism was also negatively associated with the acceptance of misleading information about background/peripheral details, for mock witnesses from the individualistic cultural group. These findings provide preliminary insights into the role of culture in susceptibility to misleading PEI and further highlight the importance of eliminating leading or suggestive questioning from investigative interviewing practices.

KEYWORDS

Eyewitness memory, Misinformation effect, Cultural orientation, Investigative interviewing

TITLE **Emotional Witness Effect and Misinformation: Implications for Misidentification, Reliability, and Memory Accuracy in Forensic Contexts**

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ABSTRACT

The emotional state of a witness can impact how they are perceived within a forensic setting. If the emotions a witness portrays seem incongruent with their statement, they are perceived as deceptive, untrustworthy, or inaccurate. This study considers the dynamics of this effect on perceptions of reliability and honesty, and observer memory accuracy of the events described, with a focus on susceptibility to misinformation, as well as the subsequent (mis)identification of the suspect. Here, the role of misinformation within the recall stage is measured, offering new insight into cross-over effects with gender and emotional states. It is predicted that the emotional tone of a witness's video statement (neutral versus emotional) influences how observers perceive the statement and subsequently recall its details, as well as the influence of misinformation. The interaction of emotional expression and the gender of the witness is also considered. The analysis will emphasise expectation effects concerning emotions and gender, exploring the beneficial aspect of emotions enhancing accurate witness recall and identification, contrasted with the detrimental effects where emotional cues may divert attention from factual statements and susceptibility to misinformation. By investigating these effects, the results aim to contribute to our understanding of how emotions impact judgments in forensic settings.

KEYWORDS **emotions, eyewitness, misidentification, misinformation, gender**

TITLE Collaborative Interviewing of Eyewitnesses: A Field Study

**AUTHORS,
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ABSTRACT

When eyewitnesses talk to each other after witnessing a crime, they can contaminate each other's memory for the crime. However, collaborative interviewing of witnesses can, under certain conditions, be beneficial. Laboratory research has shown that collaborative interviewing can lead to new information and that witnesses often correct each other's mistakes. Although laboratory research has revealed benefits associated with collaborative interviewing, until now it has remained unclear how these findings translate to practice. Our aim was to examine whether these laboratory findings would generalise to real police interviews in the field. Witnesses of serious incidents (e.g., a police shooting) were interviewed individually and then collaboratively by real police investigators, resulting in 15 interviews of 1-2 hours each from five witness pairs (5534 details in total). All interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed. Interview transcripts were coded for type of detail, forensic relevance, verifiability, witness retrieval strategies and interviewing techniques. There was little overlap between the information reported in the individual and collaborative interview. On average, the Collaborative Eyewitness Interview resulted in 131 new details, more than half of which were considered highly relevant to the police investigation. Using qualitative examples, we demonstrate how content-focused retrieval strategies, such as acknowledgements, repetitions, restatements and elaborations, can elicit new and highly relevant details. Our results suggest that the Collaborative Eyewitness Interview could have considerable added value in practice, especially in cases where individual interviews have not provided sufficient investigative leads.

KEYWORDS collaboration, eyewitness memory, interviewing, error pruning, cross-cuing

TITLE **Psychological Assessments in Legal Contexts: A Survey of Indonesian Psychological Expert Witnesses**

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ABSTRACT

This study extended the work of Neal and Grisso's findings (2014) to the Indonesian context, examining how Indonesian psychologists work as expert witnesses in legal cases and conduct forensic evaluations. Investigating this issue was imperative due to Indonesia's unique legal processes and procedures, which may differ from the countries in which these studies have been done to date, and these differences may be important for understanding the quality of psychological evidence used in Indonesian legal settings. An online questionnaire was administered to members of the Indonesia Forensic Psychology Association (APSIFOR) with experience as expert witnesses in legal cases. We investigated the most common referral questions, the frequently used psychological assessments, the reasons behind using or not using them, and the sources of information relied on when evaluating legal cases, through two parts: recent experiences in conducting forensic psychological reports and general experiences as an expert witness. In general, Indonesian psychologists (N = 42) used psychological tools in assessing cases, and projective and graphic tests were the most commonly used tools, followed by personality and clinical inventories. Furthermore, the variety of tools used was rather small, with most evaluations employing the same set of tools regardless of the referral questions. Apart from using psychological tools, other sources of information that were most relied on when evaluating cases were examinee interviews, observations of the examinee, and interviews with the examinee's relatives. The primary reason they used certain psychological tools was to improve credibility, while the most common reasons they did not use any psychological tools were unjustified time constraints and the unavailability of suitable tools. While certain findings corroborated Neal and Grisso's study (2014), we also encountered contradictory results. We discuss the implications of this research for Indonesian psychological expert witnesses and suggest potential areas for future development to enhance their work.

KEYWORDS

Indonesia, expert witnesses, forensic evaluation, psychological assessment, forensic psychologist

INTIMATE PARTNER VIOLENCE

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | INTIMATE PARTNER VIOLENCE

TITLE Cyber Dating Abuse among Dutch and Italian Young Adults

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ABSTRACT

In recent decades, communication and information technologies have gradually become increasingly central in our lives. This is especially true for adolescents and young adults, particularly from the point of view of social relationships; while these technologies have undeniable advantages, they also pose specific challenges and risks. One major problem, for example, relates to enacting various forms of aggressive and violent behaviors through new technologies, which can circumvent spatial and temporal constraints. In the context of romantic relationships, this phenomenon is known as cyber dating violence or cyber dating abuse.

The present research aims to shed light on this phenomenon, considering both perpetration and victimization, through an online survey disseminated in Italy and the Netherlands. The survey includes validated questionnaires to investigate the association between perpetrating/being a victim of cyber dating abuse and several variables in samples of non-clinical young adults (18-35 years old; n=208). In more detail, the psychological variables included comprise: empathy, as measured by the Interpersonal Reactivity Index; narcissism, Machiavellianism, psychopathy and sadism, as measured by the Short Dark Tetrad; pathological traits of personality, as measured by the Personality Inventory for DSM-5 Brief Form; symptoms of anxiety and depression, as measured by the Generalized Anxiety Disorder-2 and Patient Health Questionnaire-2 respectively. The research’s purpose is to examine which personality traits are characteristic of cyber dating abuse perpetrators and which are characteristic of its victims. A cultural comparison of prevalence and characteristics in Italy and the Netherlands is also carried out. Hierarchical regressions indicated that younger participants, higher in antagonism, sadism and anxiety, and lower in perspective-taking were more likely to enact behaviors related to cyber dating abuse. For victimization, the only significant variables were higher sadism and narcissism. The most frequently reported motivation for both perpetration and victimization was jealousy. Practical implications and future directions are discussed.

KEYWORDS Cyber Dating Abuse, Violence, Dark Tetrad, Victims, Offenders

TITLE **Leaking: Offender behaviour in the run-up to fatal intimate partner violence as a basis for risk analyses**

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ABSTRACT With the ratification of the Istanbul Convention, there is an international consensus on the need for political action to prevent intimate partner violence. Part of the Convention is the obligation to carry out risk assessments and take preventive measures in cases of intimate partner violence. Standardised risk assessment tools based on risk factor analyses are often used for this purpose. More recent approaches also address behavioural aspects, such as the leaking behaviour of perpetrators, i.e. various forms of announcing and hinting at impending crimes, as a significant warning signal. In research on terrorism and amok, leaking has proven to be a regularly occurring and relevant early indicator of serious targeted violence. Our research is based on the analysis of 60 Public prosecutor's files on attempted and completed homicides in ex-partnerships or in the event of separation (Germany, 2012- 2020). With the aim of examining whether taking leaking behaviour into account can improve existing approaches to risk analysis, we focussed on the phenomenology of leaking in the run-up to a homicide as well as on indicators of the severity of leaking. Probabilities of occurrence and modalities are critically discussed and placed in a practical context.

KEYWORDS **Intimate Partner Homicide, Risk Assessment, Prevention**

TITLE Typology of Femicides

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ABSTRACT

Gender-based violence against women is a serious and widespread problem that affects millions of women worldwide. In the year 2022, 89,000 women and girls were murdered, the highest level in two decades. In contrast to the general decline in homicide rates, there has been a relative increase in the killing of women. This trend points to different correlations and influencing factors in homicides of men and women. While men are primarily victims of violent confrontations with other men in public spaces, women are more likely to be killed by men in their social neighbourhood.

This study addresses the observed gender-based violence discrepancy by analysing female homicides on a gender-based basis, using the concept of femicide. Femicides in Germany have so far only been examined in fragments, with existing studies concentrating on specific forms such as intimate partner femicides and so-called "honour killings." This study takes a comprehensive approach and analyses all registered female homicides in selected federal states in 2017. The aim is not only to determine the proportion of femicides in all homicides, but also to create a femicide typology using a latent class analysis. This typology is based on differences in the characteristics of the perpetrator, the pre-existing relationship between the perpetrator and the victim, the circumstances of the crime, and the motives established by the courts. The analysis currently comprises the evaluation of all criminal proceedings categorized as (attempted) homicide in the selected federal states in 2017. The results of this analysis form the basis for the development of a femicide typology, which will be presented at the conference.

KEYWORDS femicide, typology, latent class analysis

TITLE **Love and Accountability: Victim-blaming in Intimate Partner Violence**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of romantic narratives on perceptions of intimate partner violence (IPV). In the first experiment (n = 182), participants were presented with narratives depicting romantic and non-romantic motives for violence within romantic relationships, with a control condition where the motive was not included. They read short journalistic pieces portraying male offenders and female victims, then assessed the personal accountability of the offender and victim, as well as the criminal accountability measured by anticipated sentence length and perceived severity of punishment. Results revealed a tendency to assign greater accountability to the victim when the offender declared love as the motivation for the violence. Additionally, male participants considered the offender less accountable when the motive was romantic. Due to the lack of significant differences between romantic and non-romantic conditions in terms of criminal accountability, we conducted an additional experiment on legal professionals (n = 264), anticipating greater sensitivity to questions regarding sentencing. However, none of the results were significant, suggesting potential differences in perceptions of the role of romantic narratives in legitimizing IPV between laypeople and legal professionals. This underscores the importance of understanding how societal roles may influence attitudes towards IPV.

KEYWORDS **Intimate Partner Violence, Victim-Blaming, Legitimization of Violence**

TITLE “This is What Happened”: The Influence of Power on
Misinformation Acceptance after Co-witness Discussion
between Romantic Partners

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ABSTRACT Co-witness discussion commonly leads to the communication of misinformation and a subsequent contamination of eyewitness memory. The nature of the relationship between co-witnesses has been demonstrated to influence event recall following discussion, with the possibility of specific dynamics within these relationships skewing memory further. Power within a romantic relationship refers to the extent to which an individual can influence their partner’s feelings, thoughts or behaviours to achieve their own goals. The present study considered whether the existence of power dynamics influenced the amount of misinformation accepted between romantic partners following co-witness discussion of a distressing event. Members of a romantic couple were individually shown the same event, however remained unaware that their partner’s version of the event contained differing details to their own. Participants then engaged in co-witness discussion about the event with their partner – whereby non-matching information was shared – before separately completing an individual recall of the event. How power dynamics impacted an individual’s relationship wellbeing, and post-discussion psychological wellbeing was also measured. Results indicated that romantic partners who were higher in power tended to accept more misinformation, and maintained higher romantic relationship wellbeing. However, findings did not signify power as a predictor of post-discussion psychological wellbeing. This research replicates misinformation acceptance after co-witness discussion, and suggests that pre-existing relationship dynamics between co-witnesses can influence this process. Implications will be discussed.

KEYWORDS Co-Witness Discussion, Misinformation Acceptance, Romantic Relationships, Interpersonal Power, Psychological Wellbeing

DECEPTION AND LIES

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | DECEPTION AND LIES

TITLE **Using the Asymmetric Information Management (AIM) technique to detect deception**

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ABSTRACT

Detecting deception is difficult and as such experts have focused on creating new tools that proactively elicit differences between truth tellers and liars. This presentation offers an insightful overview of the innovative Asymmetric Information Management (AIM) technique, showcasing its utility for both practitioners and researchers. The AIM technique works by effectively encouraging truth tellers to expand upon their narratives, resulting in richer, more detailed accounts than they might otherwise offer. Conversely, these same instructions present a dilemma for deceptive individuals, often compelling them to strategically manage the information they disclose. The simplicity of implementing these instructions within interview settings makes AIM technique a versatile tool, with potential applications extending into diverse domains such as fraud detection. For optimal results, we advocate for the integration of AIM instructions with complementary interviewing tools, techniques, or methodologies, such as those designed to support memory recall. To date, three published studies have explored the effectiveness of AIM technique for enhancing lie-detection.

KEYWORDS **lie-detection, AIM technique, Investigative interviewing**

TITLE **The Face of Deception: How Your Mimicry Tells the True Story**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: There are contested claims that communication receivers mimic communication senders less when senders are deceptive compared to truthful. Our studies evaluate a novel computer-based measure of facial mimicry to determine its potential to inform the debate. By examining the facial reactions of individuals receiving deceptive and truthful messages, we test whether this innovative approach can offer fresh insights into the relationship between facial mimicry and deception.

Methodology: We used video stimuli featuring individuals telling deceptive and truthful narratives. In Study A 65 participants were shown high stakes videos about real-life child abduction police broadcasts and asked to assess the truthfulness of the people depicted. Study B, replicated Study A using lower stakes lies, but with higher quality video stimuli, improving confidence in the accuracy of the analyses. Study B also contrasted positively and negatively valenced lies. In both studies facial mimicry was measured using Affectiva Affdex within the iMotions platform.

Results and Expected Results: Contrary to hypotheses, Study A showed a small but significant effect whereby participants mimicked deceptive speakers more than truthful ones. In ongoing study B, our results will test if the unexpected results of study A replicate with higher quality stimuli.

Conclusion: The findings of study A raised questions about the validity of using mimicry as an indicator of deception, as we found only a small effect in the opposite direction to that hypothesised. In study B, with the introduction of higher-quality video stimuli, we can test if the effect replicates. Our findings also indicate a need to directly contrast human versus automated coding to determine if our unexpected findings are due to differing measures. Given the scarcity of studies focusing on the receiver's mimicry in deception detection, especially utilising advanced research techniques, further research is important to validate and expand upon these preliminary findings.

KEYWORDS

deception detection, facial mimicry, veracity judgements, automatic facial expression analysis

TITLE **Strategic Use of Evidence training with LLM-Avatars improves deception detection in subsequent mock-suspect interviews**

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ABSTRACT Strategic Use of Evidence (SUE) is a technique based on the counter-interrogation strategy differences of guilty and innocent suspects and has been shown to improve differentiation between these suspects. However, even though interviewers may have received theoretical training in good interview practices including SUE, they often do not apply this knowledge in actual interrogations. We aimed to investigate whether practice with Large Language Model (LLM) based avatars would improve the ability of naive participants to use SUE in interviews with mock-suspects. The study included 78 interviewers and 78 mock suspects. We utilized an LLM platform to create two guilty AI suspects with answer algorithms based on research describing suspect counter-interrogation strategies. Interviewers were divided into three groups: 1: Theoretical training in SUE + interview practice with AI suspects, 2: Theoretical training in SUE, and 3: Control group. The results showed that interviewer in the Theoretical+AI suspect interview group were more likely to use evidence-statement inconsistencies to judge the veracity of human mock suspects compared to those in the Control group. Furthermore, compared to interviewers from either the Control or Theoretical training group, those who received both Theoretical and AI suspect interview training demonstrated a higher likelihood of accurately judging the guilt or innocence of the human mock suspects. The findings suggest that naive interviewers can be trained to use the SUE technique with AI suspect avatars with the training effect transferring to later interviews with human suspects. Such avatars have a huge potential for use as a scalable approach to learning interview techniques.

KEYWORDS **Strategic Use of Evidence (SUE), Large Language Models (LLM), Artificial Intelligence, Avatars, Suspect interviews**

TITLE **From Anecdotes To Real-Life Examples: A Survey On Self-Deception**

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ABSTRACT Self-deception, a motivated process of maintaining false beliefs despite contrary evidence, is a phenomenon explored mainly through anecdotes and philosophical hypotheses, with scarce empirical data. This study's main aims were to examine the prevalence of self-deception in the general adult population (18 years and older) and to gather real-life examples illustrating instances of self-deception. Furthermore, we aimed to investigate the motivations that drive individuals to engage in self-deception, identify specific strategies and cognitive processes used to maintain false beliefs in the face of contradictory evidence and examine the various impacts and consequences of self-deception, both in the short-term and long-term. We gathered data from 239 adults (18+ years old) using a survey with open-ended and multiple-choice questions and the Paulhus Deception Scales (Paulhus, 1998). Findings revealed a high frequency of self-deception (91.32%), with a high awareness of existing contradictory information (70.8%) and often motivated by the desire for emotional well-being (21.18%) or increased confidence (18.23%). Strategies to maintain self-deception included ignoring (16.47%), not paying attention to (17.06%) and/or avoiding (14.71%) contradictory evidence. Participants reported various impacts, from immediate emotional discomfort to long-term consequences on self-esteem and relationships. The study discusses the interplay between theories and beliefs regarding self-deception and actual reported data. Moreover, understanding the dimensions and characteristics of self-deception can shed light on the complexities of this phenomenon and its implications in forensic and legal psychology.

KEYWORDS **self-deception, false beliefs, self-enhancement, denial**

TITLE **Is the Uncertain Self Good at Detecting Lies? The Influence of Personal Uncertainty on Deception Detection**

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ABSTRACT Five experiments (total number of judging participants = 1309, four different kinds of stimulus materials with a total of 464 messages, total number of judgments = 19,634) investigated the influence of personal uncertainty on the process of lie detection in social relationships. Building and extending on basic assumptions of uncertainty management models, we reasoned that uncertainty about themselves motivates people to evaluate the quality of their relationships. A crucial aspect of the quality of relationships with other people is the truthfulness with which they communicate verbally with you and anyone else. We proposed that if these assumptions are valid, reminding people of their personal uncertainties should lead them to use valid verbal cues in veracity judgments more. This enhanced usage of valid verbal cues should result in better accuracy in deception detection. An internal meta-analysis of the five experiments reveals only a small, not significant, overall effect of uncertainty salience on detection accuracy with larger effect sizes for experiments conducted in the laboratory than for those conducted online. Hence, if personal uncertainty plays a role in the process of deception detection, it seems to be subject to moderators such as methodological or motivational factors.

KEYWORDS **Deception detection, lie detection accuracy, veracity judgments**

CONFESSION AND DECEPTION

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | CONFESSION AND DECEPTION

TITLE What do Legal Experts Know About False Confessions?

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ABSTRACT

False confessions happen regularly in police interviews. To prevent and reverse wrongful convictions based on false confessions, it is important for legal experts to be aware of the existence of false confessions and the risk factors related to them. We therefore conducted a survey with defense attorneys, public prosecutors, and criminal judges (N = 191) to examine their knowledge about false confessions. All respondents believed that false confessions occur in police interviews. However, in contrast to research findings, only 75% of respondents assumed that false confessions can occur due to pressure in the police interview and around 25% indicated that minimization and maximization tactics would not increase the risk of false confessions. Respondents believed that mental illness, low intelligence, withdrawal symptoms, and leading questions would be the strongest contributors to false confessions. Overall, defense attorneys demonstrated higher levels of agreement with the presented evidence-based risk factors than public prosecutors and criminal judges. Around 60% of respondents indicated that suspect interviews should always be recorded in order to prevent false confessions. Overall, these findings suggest that legal experts underestimate the risk of confession-oriented tactics and the importance of protective factors which could hinder them to prevent innocent suspects from falsely confessing and act as safeguard against convictions based on false confessions.

KEYWORDS interrogation, confession, wrongful conviction, legal decision-making

TITLE **Honesty-Humility and Truth-Bias: An Advancement of Levine's Truth Default Theory**

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ABSTRACT

Within Truth Default Theory, Levine (2014) defines situational factors that influence people's veracity judgements. In consideration of the individual-difference hypothesis regarding individuals' veracity judgements, which posits that person effects play the largest role in whether a message will be judged as a lie or as truth, the present research investigates the influence of personality on veracity judgments. Specifically, the present research focuses on the Honesty-Humility trait, which emanates from the HEXACO model of personality. Given recent research revealed the Honesty-Humility trait to be positively correlated with trust, we hypothesized that people higher in Honesty-Humility will tend to evaluate their interaction partners as more often being honest rather than dishonest, thus displaying an increased truth bias. We conducted three online studies (Study 1: N = 485; Study 2: N = 613; Study 3: N = 375), in which we first assessed participants' Honesty-Humility scores using the relevant items from the HEXACO-PI-R, followed by asking them to judge several messages from various stimulus persons as either true or lied. Results of two studies revealed significant positive correlations between Honesty-Humility and people's truth bias (Study 1: $r = .10$, 95% CI = [0.01; 0.19]; Study 2: $r = .12$, 95% CI = [0.04; 0.19]), while one study revealed no significant correlation (Study 3: $r = -.06$, 95% CI = [-0.16; 0.04]). Notably, the latter study probably suffered from low power. To the best of our knowledge, this line of research presents the first empirical evidence demonstrating higher trustworthiness expectations for people higher in Honesty-Humility in the context of lie detection.

KEYWORDS **Honesty-Humility, truth bias, lie detection, truth default theory**

TITLE Uncovering Lies During Investigative Interviews: Analysis of Response Latencies and Error Rates to Unexpected Questions

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we aim to detect identity deception during investigative interviews by integrating the analysis of response latency and error rate with the unexpected questions technique.

Sixty participants were assigned to an honest (n = 30) or deceptive group (n = 30), with the latter instructed to memorize false biographical details of a fictitious identity. Both groups underwent a face-to-face investigative interview comprising a randomized sequence of control, expected, and unexpected open-ended questions regarding their identity. The honest group was required to answer truthfully, whereas the deceptive group was asked to respond using the pre-memorized fictitious identity. The responses were audio-recorded for detailed analysis.

Our findings indicate that deceptive participants exhibited longer latencies and higher error rates for expected (requiring deception) and unexpected questions (for which premeditated deception was not possible). Longer response latencies were also observed in deceptive participants when answering control questions (which required truthful answers). Moreover, a within-subject analysis highlighted that the unexpected questions significantly impaired individuals' performance compared to control and expected questions. Leveraging machine-learning algorithms, our approach achieved a classification accuracy of 98% in distinguishing deceptive and honest participants. Additionally, a classification analysis on single responses was conducted.

Our findings underscore the effectiveness of merging response latency metrics and error rates with unexpected questioning as a robust method for detecting identity deception in investigative interviews. This approach addresses a significant gap in the scientific literature by offering a method that allows for lie detection without the individual's awareness that the technique is focused on the credibility assessment. Moreover, it can be applied retrospectively to interviews that have been conducted, allowing for the exploitation of data that are routinely acquired. Lastly, it doesn't impact standard judicial or police procedures, as no ad hoc tests are administered, thus preserving the continuity of the investigative interview.

KEYWORDS Deception Detection, Investigative Interviews, Response Latencies, Errors, Unexpected Questions

TITLE The misinformation effect in single and repeated events

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ABSTRACT

The misinformation effect has been extensively studied using a paradigm in which participants experience an event, are exposed to misinformation, and subsequently recall the original event. In the field of memory for repeated events (sequences of similar experiences), researchers have examined suggestibility to misleading information using suggestive/biasing interview techniques, particularly with child samples. Using that methodology, a recent study indicated that adults endorsed more misleading suggestions of experienced than non-experienced details. In the present study, we examined suggestibility to experienced and non-experienced details using the classical misinformation paradigm in two preregistered experiments. In Experiment 1, 128 participants watched four videos depicting a group of individuals installing spying devices in different locations across the city. Following a filler task, participants watched a video of a confederate recalling the first (target) video. The narrative contained accurately repeated, control, and misleading experienced and non-experienced items. Experienced items were details from non-target instances; non-experienced details were semantically related alternatives. Following a second filler task, participants completed a free recall, cued recall, and a recognition task. Recognition analyses indicated higher accuracy for control than misled items, consistent with the misinformation effect. Contrary to previous research, we did not find any significant differences in the endorsement of experienced and non-experienced details. Participants were more accurate when they reported knowing or remembering the selected responses, and we found good confidence - accuracy relationship across all types of details, although stronger for accurately repeated and control than for misled details. Experiment 2 added a single-event condition (between-subjects), where participants watched one (target) video and subsequently watched three unrelated videos (data collection is nearing end). We will present analyses of free- and cued-recall reports to gain a better understanding of misinformation endorsement at tests that differently engage retrieval processes.

KEYWORDS Misinformation, Suggestibility, Repeated events

EYEWITNESS II

TITLE **The Analysis of Competing Hypotheses and Expert Witness Testimony: Counteracting Adversarial Allegiance in Witness Credibility Assessments**

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ABSTRACT

Cognitive biases, such as adversarial allegiance, can influence and negatively affect expert witness assessments. Flawed expert witness testimony has been identified as a significant contributor to wrongful convictions. Therefore, it is crucial for expert witnesses to implement effective debiasing strategies. The Analysis of Competing Hypotheses (ACH) appears, at least in theory, to be a promising debiasing method. However, there is a substantial lack of research regarding its validity and applicability in the context of expert witness testimony. The purpose of the present study was to examine potential benefits of the ACH method in expert witness assessments, specifically credibility assessments, while counteracting adversarial allegiance. To this end, psychology students and psychologists with prior knowledge in credibility assessments were invited to participate in an online study. Participants were presented with the summary of a criminal investigation regarding an alleged case of child sexual abuse and asked to assess the credibility of the alleged victim's statement. Half of the participants were instructed to apply the ACH method during their assessment while the other half was instructed to proceed as they usually would, thereby serving as a control group. In addition, the retaining party was varied: a third of participants was retained by the defense, another third by the accessory prosecution and the last third by the court, serving as an additional control group for retaining party. Data collection is currently still ongoing and will be finalized prior to the conference. It is predicted that participants will display adversarial allegiance if retained by the defense or accessory prosecution. Additionally, it is expected that only the ACH method will successfully counteract adversarial allegiance. The results as well as possible practical implications will be discussed.

KEYWORDS

expert witness testimony, credibility assessment, cognitive biases, debiasing strategies, Analysis of Competing Hypotheses (ACH)

TITLE **Examining the Impact of Witnesses' Personal Characteristics on Statement Validity Assessments (SVA) by Expert Witnesses: An Analysis of 521 Cases in Germany**

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ABSTRACT

In Germany, there is a decade-long tradition to consult psychological expert witnesses to judge the credibility of testimonies in criminal proceedings, mainly in sexual offense cases. German psychologists apply a procedure called Statement Validity Assessment (SVA), which is based on systematic testing of alternative hypotheses to the assumption that the statement is experience-based. The two main hypotheses to be tested are (1) the incriminating statement is based on fabrication, and (2) the incriminating statement is based on false memories. Within this framework, various factors, including personal variables such as age and cognitive abilities, play a crucial role in the overall assessment of individual cases. Despite the significance of these personal characteristics, there is a paucity of knowledge regarding their prevalence in SVA cases and their impact on expert decision-making.

We analyzed 521 SVA reports from 1988 to 2015 drawn from the archive of the Institute of Forensic Psychiatry at Charité Berlin. Based on this sample, we will describe the characteristics of the victim witnesses whose statements underwent SVA, with a specific focus on potential systematic differences in the outcomes of SVA reports. We will then present how characteristics of the victim witnesses were specifically integrated in the evaluation of the fabrication and false memory hypothesis, respectively. Our findings will contribute to a better understanding of the role of personal variables in SVA processes, providing insights into their implications for expert decision-making. Additionally, potentials and limitations of SVA will be discussed.

KEYWORDS

expert witnesses, statement validity assessment (SVA), CBCA, false memory, lie detection

TITLE **Many U.K. Legal Professionals Misunderstand How Memory Works and Believe in Repression**

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ABSTRACT

This exploratory, quantitative study examines misunderstanding about memory function especially for trauma, across three UK samples (N = 717): the lay public (n = 419), legal professionals (n = 150), and mental health professionals (n = 148). Delayed complaints of child abuse are prevalent in Western justice systems; they often rely upon uncorroborated memory testimony to prove guilt. U.K. legal professionals and lay jurors generally assess the reliability of such memory recall via common sense, yet decades of memory research show societal beliefs often conflict with science. Recent international research shows belief in repression remains strong, but lawyers' beliefs are unknown. In delayed complaint cases, belief in repression may potentiate injustice. Our primary study aim addressed this knowledge-gap. We collected unique survey data on U.K. judges', barristers' and solicitors' beliefs for traumatic repression and related notions. Our secondary aim was to similarly survey the U.K. public and mental health professionals and investigate the source of participants' memory beliefs. Participants were mainly self-selecting. Public participants were recruited via Prolific (<https://www.prolific.co/>). Legal and health participants responded to in-house advertisements. All participants completed a nine-item memory belief questionnaire (using Qualtrics software) with Likert-scale responses. Legal participants were also asked about delayed complaint cases. Statistical analysis (e.g. means, percentages and t-tests) used SPSS v27. Our findings reinforce concerns of a science - knowledge gap. Key results: repression was strongly endorsed by all groups (> 78%), as was dissociative amnesia (> 87%). Also, memory distortion may be poorly understood. Only 27% of lay participants and 49% of lawyers unreservedly "agreed" that false memories are "possible". Innate beliefs, professional and private reading were prominent sources of beliefs. Correcting memory misunderstanding and extending the contribution of memory science in the courtroom remains an important quest.

KEYWORDS **Memory beliefs, repression, dissociative amnesia, false memory**

TITLE**Are they really more suggestive? - A comparative analysis of EMDR and non-EMDR therapists regarding their views on traumatic memories and self-reported suggestive behavior in therapy practice**

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ABSTRACT

Recent works have pointed out the suggestive potential of EMDR therapy. They specifically stressed that EMDR therapists often endorse problematic beliefs on repressed memories, tend to discuss possibly repressed memories with their patients, and are instructed by EMDR manuals to operate with flawed memory metaphors (e.g., memory works as a video). However, studies including EMDR therapists as participants have only surveyed their beliefs and did not ask them about their behavior in therapy practice. Also, - to the presenter's best knowledge - no study has sampled therapists with and without EMDR qualifications to directly compare their survey answers. In this talk, I present a secondary analysis of a survey on memory recovery including N=258 licensed psychotherapists from Germany. The survey answers by n=51 therapists with an EMDR qualification were compared to those by n=207 therapists with no EMDR qualification. These comparisons yielded no statistically significant differences between the therapist groups regarding views on trauma and memory, how often therapists have assumed unremembered trauma behind symptoms of patients, how often they have attempted to recover assumed trauma memories, and how often they have recovered purported trauma memories based on assumptions. However, the difference regarding trauma assumptions behind patient symptoms was substantial on a descriptive level which may point at a possible lack of statistical power. The presentation concludes with a thorough discussion of potential reasons for these (non-)findings.

KEYWORDS false memory, psychotherapy, EMDR, suggestion, memory

TITLE **The Effects of Training on Confidence and Accuracy in Child-Eyewitnesses**

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ABSTRACT

Child-eyewitness evidence plays a crucial part in the criminal justice system. Children are prone to choose from lineups (Havard, 2012; Dunlevy & Cherryman, 2012), and overestimate their confidence (Brewer & Day, 2011; Destan & Roebbers, 2015). However, emerging work indicates reliability of child-eyewitness evidence can be improved (Winsor et al., 2021; Brewer, Keast, & Sauer, 2010). In the eyewitness literature, the extent to which training impacts child-eyewitness evidence remains largely unexplored. In the present study, we test the influence of training prior to lineup administration on the Confidence-Accuracy (CA) relationship and decision accuracy in child-eyewitnesses. Children (n = 53, data collection ongoing) viewed 12 target faces (6 white, 6 black; Dobolyi & Dodson, 2013). Following the encoding phase, children either received training or no training on the lineup task and confidence scale. Children then saw one lineup for each target face (either target-absent or target-present, randomly assigned to view lineups in one of two orders), made a lineup decision on each lineup, and provided confidence after each lineup decision via one of five scales (levels 1 to 4). Training significantly predicted overall accuracy, $B = 0.32$, $SE = 0.16$, $z = 1.99$, $p = .047$. For target-absent lineups, training significantly predicted rejection accuracy, $B = 0.47$, $SE = 0.18$, $z = 2.61$, $p = .009$. Preliminary CAC curves suggest an improved calibration pattern in the training condition compared to no training condition. This pattern is evident in younger ($M = 6.17$, $SD = 0.87$) and older children ($M = 8.75$, $SD = 0.83$), though ICIs suggest these differences are not significant. These results highlight the potential of pre-lineup training to improve lineup performance and calibration. Training increases decision accuracy and strengthens the CA-relationship in younger and older child-eyewitnesses.

KEYWORDS **Child Eyewitnesses, Confidence-Accuracy Relationship, Metacognition**

PERSPECTIVES ON SEXUAL VIOLENCE

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | PERSPECTIVES ON SEXUAL VIOLENCE

TITLE **Technology-Facilitated Sexual Violence (TFSV): Victimization and risk factors**

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ABSTRACT

Technological advancement has brought us closer, but it has also given rise to new forms of sexual violence. As a result, Technology-Facilitated Sexual Violence (TFSV) has emerged as a constant concern in modern society, requiring research efforts to understand its nuances, extent, and associated risk factors. This study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of TFSV in the Portuguese context, starting by exploring its different manifestations. Through quantitative analyses, we investigated the rate and victimization prevalence, victim characteristics, and the use of technology. An online questionnaire was completed (N = 500; 75.8% female) aged between 18 and 70 years (Mage = 31.31; SD = 13.26). The main results point to a high rate of victimization throughout life (72%) as well as in the last 12 months (70.8%). Although there are no significant differences between the sexes, in the case of sexual aggression / coercion, more females suffered the most severe type of TFSV. However, the gendering of TFSV emerges with specific behaviors. Females are more likely to be sexually harassed, while only women report being victims of non-consensual sexual experiences with someone they met online. On the other hand, men tend to report receiving offensive and / or degrading content related to their sexuality or gender identity. Additionally, younger people tend to report a higher rate of victimization. Regression analysis indicates that the model based solely on victim characteristics is more effective in predicting TFSV victimization, with younger and heterosexual victims being significant predictors. When we add technology use variables to this model, it remains significant, but with lower predictive capacity and without significant predictors among the technology use variables. This study suggests that the culture of harassment is deeply ingrained and finds an easy way to spread in the digital environment.

KEYWORDS **Technology-Facilitated Sexual Violence, Victimization, sexual violence**

TITLE **Verifiability in Sexual Assault Statements: True reports, False Allegations, and False Denials**

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ABSTRACT

Prior research showed that sexual assaults (SA) are frequently occurring in student population. SA experience is one of the most underreported traumas, and the extreme end of concealment is false denial. Between three and five percent of students opt to falsely deny being assaulted, due to the fear of interpersonal consequence a disclosure might bring. Similar percentage (2-6%) of SA reports were also shown to be false allegations. Thus, the aim of this study was to investigate whether true SA statements, false denials, and false allegations could be differentiated using the Verifiability Approach (VA). The rationale VA is that genuine statements differ in their quality than fabricated ones, containing higher number of details that could in principle be verified. Prior research showed that VA aids differentiation of genuine and fabricated trauma reports, and as SA is a traumatic experience VA might be of use in examination of SA narratives as well. Our participants were students (N = 163), mostly females (M age = 21.3, SD = 3.2), pre-screened for history of SA. Students with such history were randomly allocated to either the control condition (n = 29) or false denial group (n = 42), whereas students without SA history were in the false allegation condition (n = 95). After receiving the group instructions, students wrote a report about their SA experience. Students' SA reports were then examined using the VA, by focusing on the frequency of verifiable and non-verifiable details, proportion of verifiable details, and total word count. Based on prior VA research, we expected that both true reports and false denials will contain more verifiable information than false allegations, which should contain more non-verifiable details. Results, however, indicated no group effect on the number of verifiable and non-verifiable details, proportion of verifiable information, and narratives' length ($F_s(2, 182) < 1.23$, $ps > .29$, $\eta^2 < .03$). Before making any conclusion regarding the utility of VA in Sa context, further investigation is necessary.

KEYWORDS **Verifiability approach, Sexual assault reports, False denial**

TITLE Employability bias and sexual offending

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ABSTRACT

Enhancing employability is important for reducing reoffending rates, yet individuals with prior sexual offences encounter formidable obstacles in securing employment opportunities. As a result of this, navigating the timing of disclosure regarding past offences becomes crucial. This presentation examines the nuances of employability biases, drawing upon insights gleaned from two comprehensive empirical studies.

In the first study, our research was focused on whether potential employers exhibit a higher propensity to reject candidates post-DBS check upon discovering a prior sexual offense. To elucidate this, we tasked prospective employers with selecting the most suitable candidate based on comprehensive evaluations encompassing application forms, CVs, and interview notes. Subsequently, we provided them with a DBS check reflecting either no prior offense (control group) or a record of sexual misconduct (rape, sexual activity with a child, or possession of indecent images of children). Our findings revealed higher rejection rates for individuals with contact offenses such as rape (57%) and sexual activity with a child (80%) compared to those with convictions related to possession of indecent images of children (49%).

In the subsequent study, we explored the efficacy of self-disclosure during the written application stage in mitigating rejection rates. Our results indicate a notable reduction in rejection rates across all categories when a self-disclosure was provided—rape (self-disclosure 63% vs no disclosure 70%), sexual activity with a child (self-disclosure 52% vs no disclosure 84%), and possession of indecent images of children (self-disclosure 23% vs no disclosure 69%)—underscoring the significant impact of early disclosure in reducing rejection rates.

These findings provide invaluable insights into qualitative decision-making strategies, offering a nuanced understanding of the complex challenges confronting individuals with prior sexual offences as they strive to secure meaningful employment opportunities.

KEYWORDS Employability bias, sexual offending, decision making

TITLE **The ‘Rough sex gone wrong’ defence in alleged sexual homicide cases in the UK.**

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ABSTRACT This presentation discusses an issue of increasing concern in the UK - the so-called ‘rough sex defence’ (RSD) used in alleged homicide cases where death is claimed to have occurred accidentally during consensual ‘rough sex’ - with the aim of exploring international comparisons. The RSD is overwhelmingly deployed by men charged with killings of women, where the victim has no voice in proceedings, rather than in non-fatal offences such as rape. The normalisation in mainstream media of sado-masochism has been postulated to have created a climate in which juries may be more accepting of ‘rough sex gone wrong’ as a credible defence. Possible explanations for the rise in the RSD include a) socio-cultural factors, including gender inequality, media glorification of violence, objectification of women and girls, and growth in online pornography and, b) developmental influences on young males, including insecure attachments and early trauma (e.g., abuse and witnessing violence), exposure to violent pornography, blunted empathy / hostility towards women, and engagement in depersonalised sex associated with power and control. The campaigning work of the UK group ‘We Can’t Consent to This’ highlighted the rise in the RSD over the last 50 years. This helped inform the UK Domestic Abuse Act (2021). This Act sets out that a person is unable to consent to the infliction of harm for the purposes of sexual gratification that would result in injuries legally defined as actual bodily harm or higher and, by extension, to their own death. This session seeks discussion with delegates from different jurisdictions of information and issues, aimed to inform future research.

KEYWORDS **Rough sex defence, Violence against women, Domestic Abuse Act**

TITLE Escalation in the frequency of sexual offending

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ABSTRACT

Escalation research in rape and serious sexual offences is a parameter within trajectory research that examines whether an individual commits increasingly more serious crimes over time. Escalation in the frequency of sexual offending examines whether repeat sexual offenders will increase in offending as time between crimes decrease. Preliminary findings reveal that escalation is present in a small subset of prolific sexual offenders when type of offence and severity of offence is taken into consideration, however it remains unclear what escalation in frequency patterns are exhibited across this cohort of offenders. Using police data from three forces across England and Wales, 11,780 primary suspects with three or more crimes and 95,604 victims were analysed. Time between crimes were computed to analyse whether suspects of sexual crimes escalate, de-escalate or remain stable in their crime series. Further analysis was conducted to see whether escalation in frequency of sexual offending differed between types of sexual offenders: rapists, contact and mixed. (statistical analysis is still on going). Escalators vs non-escalators were compared across variables for differences; age of victim, ethnicity of suspect, total number of previous victims, total number of previous crimes and relationship between suspect and victim. Developing a clear picture of what escalation pathways look like in repeat sexual suspects has the potential to aid police in both investigative efforts and disruption of future offending.

KEYWORDS Sexual offending, Escalation, Frequency

RISK MANAGEMENT

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | RISK MANAGEMENT

TITLE **The Association Between Criminal Risk Assessment Outcomes Using START:AV and OASys and Misconduct Among Incarcerated Emerging Adults: A Prospective Study**

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ABSTRACT

Criminal risk assessment plays a central role in execution of custodial sentences (Shingler et al., 2018). It aims to target correctional treatment efforts (Scott et al., 2019). Criminal risk is assessed by application of instruments comprised of factors that are robust and significant predictors of future offending (Zara & Farrington, 2013). Various validated assessment tools exist, tailored to different offender groups, including juveniles and adults. However, it is not clear which instruments are more suitable for emerging adults (i.e., from 18 to 24 years old), which, according to Arnett (2002), can be defined as distinct developmental stage.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the significance of risk assessment instruments, used in Lithuanian prison service for adults and juveniles, in predicting misconduct among emerging adults serving custodial sentences.

The study involved 99 young adult males (M = 20.74, SD = 1.682, aged 18 to 23 years) serving custodial sentences in 4 out of 8 prisons in Lithuania. Criminal risk assessment utilized both the juvenile-oriented START:AV (Viljoen et al., 2014) and the adult-oriented OASys (Home Office, 2002) instruments. Furthermore, violent behaviour, non-violent offenses, substance use, and unauthorized absence were assessed over a three-month period subsequent to the risk evaluation.

The results indicated that within the incarcerated emerging adult sample, the START:AV showed significant predictive power for violent behaviour, whereas both the START:AV and the OASys effectively predicted substance use. However, neither risk assessment instrument demonstrated significance in predicting non-violent offenses or unauthorized absence among this group. Given that juvenile and adult risk assessment tools are grounded in distinct factors reflecting different aspects of individuals in transitional age, it's crucial to flexibly consider individual developmental process when selecting risk assessment instruments for predicting misconduct during incarceration. The study was granted by the Lithuanian Research Council No. S-PD-22-101

KEYWORDS **Emerging adults, Custodial sentence, Criminal risk assessment**

TITLE **Evaluating SASH and Stalking Risk Assessment – Implications for the Handling of Stalking Cases**

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ABSTRACT

Stalking affects millions globally each year, with police crime statistics indicating a significant number of reported cases. However, the actual figures, considering the dark field, are likely much higher, underscoring the profound suffering and impact on victims' lives. This underestimation leads to the severity of stalking cases being overlooked, with possible dramatic consequences for the victims. Standardized instruments can help improve the police's handling of stalking cases by enabling officers to better assess the risk and take appropriate measures for further action. One such instrument is the Screening Assessment for Stalking and Harassment (SASH; McEwan et al., 2017). This study examines the German version of the SASH for the first time in terms of reliability and validity. Five experts from a victim support center assessed the level of concern in 24 stalking cases using the SASH, while another evaluated them with the Stalking Risk Profile (SRP; MacKenzie et al., 2009). Moderate to good inter-rater reliability was observed for the level of concern, with item-level agreement varying from low to substantial. Assessments of concern by SASH strongly correlated with SRP risk levels. Furthermore, a Latent Class Analysis provided evidence for four underlying types of stalking. The findings are incorporated into existing knowledge regarding stalking's risk factors and dimensions, while also exploring the implications for SASH's practical implementation in Germany.

KEYWORDS **Stalking Risk Assessment, Screening Assessment for Stalking and Harassment (SASH), Stalking Risk Profiles (SRP), Latent Class Stalking Profiles**

TITLE Using structured professional judgement to inform animal-related risk assessments with legal consequences.

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ABSTRACT Objectives: Over the past thirty years the use of structured professional judgement (SPJ) systems of risk assessment (e.g., HCR-20 etc.) have become common practice for Forensic Psychologists in the prediction of violence risk. The SPJ format has been extended to support accurate decision making in other areas related to human behaviour (e.g., suicide and domestic violence etc.). However, an SPJ approach has not been used in areas related to the prediction of non-human aggression such as dog bite risk. Tests to identify dog bite risk in the course of criminal proceedings are often personal assessments, which are often subjective, with no agreed format. This project focuses on developing an evidence based SPJ tool for dog bite risk. As part of a larger project, the research team is developing a comprehensive SPJ tool for dog bite risk which can be used across different contexts, including in criminal proceedings. The current work relates to the development of a related triage screening to assist the Royal Society for the Prevention of Cruelty to Animals (RSPCA) in assessing risk while on animal welfare visits.

Aims and objectives: This project aims to develop an SPJ system to assist RSPCA welfare officers in making judgements of presenting risk and the need to refer to social services or police agencies as a result.

Methodology:

- 1) A prototypical 24-item Dog Bite Risk -24 SPJ tool was reviewed to identify useful triage items.
- 2) RSPCA policy, management and animal welfare experts undertook a workshop to clarify and validate the structure of the SPJ tool.

Results: An SPJ tool was created for use by the RSPCA to assist in ensuring that risk assessments and subsequent referrals to the police or social services for subsequent criminal proceedings are consistently made and evidence based.

KEYWORDS Risk, Risk Assessment, Dog Bites, SPJ

TITLE **Identity pathology, psychopathology, and risk of reoffending in emerging adulthood: an examination of relationships in Lithuanian custodial male sample**

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ABSTRACT

Adolescence and emerging adulthood are often characterized as a search for one's place in the world and a pursuit of a personal identity sometimes accompanied by difficulties of externalized or internalized nature. Psychopathological problems, especially externalized ones, have always been considered as one of the causes of offending and usually are included in risk assessment. However, in adolescence and emerging adulthood, an identity pathology can also be considered as a risk factor. Risk assessments are performed routinely in Lithuanian correctional institutions, but the question of whether the risk assessment instruments reflect the specific characteristics related to the psychopathology or identity pathology of convicts is open. In the paper, the relationships between two risk assessment instruments and different kinds of pathology are analysed.

The sample consisted of 99 male offenders serving a custodial sentence and aged 18 to 23 years. For risk assessment, The Short-Term Assessment of Risk and Treatability: Adolescent Version START: AV (Viljoen et al., 2014) and Offender Assessment System OASys (Home Office, 2002) were used. The expression of psychopathology was evaluated using The Adult Self Report ASR (Achenbach and Rescorla 2003). The identity pathology was evaluated using the Assessment of Identity Development in Adolescence AIDA (Goth et al., 2012).

The results showed statistically significant relationships between psychopathology, identity pathology and START: AV scores of risk of adverse outcomes, strengths and vulnerabilities, however very few and some contradictory relationships with OASys scores were observed. The results suggest that the START: AV ratings more sensitively reflect the problems of young offenders and this can serve for the selection of appropriate interventions. However other explanations of the results, namely specifics of the assessment tools and procedures, qualification of raters, and specifics of risks assessed are going to be overviewed.

KEYWORDS **criminal risk assessment, identity, psychopathology, emerging adulthood**

TITLE **Artificial Intelligence in Offender Management**

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ABSTRACT

This presentation describes the development of a new Artificial Intelligence - based programme for the new offender management system in Finnish prisons. RISE AI is an expert and recommender system that is intended to analyse offenders' risk factors and other background information to recommend rehabilitative targets, services, and units that best meet offenders' criminogenic needs. It is intended to be a tool for senior specialists responsible for the assessment, sentence planning and placement of offenders in prisons. The development is based on the psychological, criminological and offender management knowledge. The theoretical background is based on the Risk-Need-Responsivity (RNR) model in offender assessment. RISE AI uses the database of offender management system which consists of data from official documents, actuarial risk assessment instruments and expert interviews regarding offenders. RISE AI's intention is to look for the optimal set of activities for each individual offender in a faster and more compatible way than before. In the future we will compare sentence plans made with and without RISE AI to find out the benefits and risks of AI-based assessment. If the programme functions ideally, the benefits expected are: (1) offenders are directed to services and activities that better meet their risk level and criminogenic needs, (2) the compatibility of the offenders' needs and their rehabilitation and its impact on the risk of recidivism will improve, and (3) faster and more accurate sentence planning process will improve quality of sentence time and use of staff and logistical resources. The risks and ethical questions of AI-based solutions when assessing individuals in vulnerable position are also considered carefully. As a conclusion, it's to be expected that AI-based solutions help with the psychological and criminological analysis of offenders. The presentation is based on an unpublished study: "RISE AI: Reducing the Risk of Recidivism with AI.

KEYWORDS

prisoners, artificial intelligence, offender assessment, offender management, risk analysis

INTERVENTION PROGRAMS

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | INTERVENTION PROGRAMS

TITLE **Implementing prevention of child sexual abuse program targeted to potential offenders and mandatory reporting law: Preliminary findings of a study with Portuguese judges**

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ABSTRACT

Objective. According to a systematic review, the prevalence of sexual interest in minors ranged between 2% and 24% (Savoie et al., 2021). There are growing concerns from academia and non-academic (e.g., WHO) asking for a more preventable approach to target sexual offenders. In this context, Karolinska Institutet (Sweden) developed Prevent It, a CBT intervention delivered online, anonymously, targeting individuals worried about their sexual urges toward children. The program was culturally adapted to Portugal and is currently being implemented. Notwithstanding, in Portugal Article 242º (Penal Procedure Code), all public workers must report any criminal incident they know. Since many legal and ethical questions arise during this implementation, we are developing a study with Portuguese judges to explore their perceptions about the relevance of prevention programs devoted to (potential) sexual offenders and their understanding of the interplay between Article 242º and the implementation of those programs.

Methodology. This study relies on a qualitative design based on a vignette plus a semi-structured script. Based on a convenience sample, until now, four judges with professional experience in child abuse cases were individually interviewed. All are female (age range = 45-66 years old). The interviews were transcribed and are being analyzed using thematic analysis.

Results. Participants agreed that prevention programs are relevant and valuable, and it is essential to have evidence of their efficacy. This kind of program should be transferred from the justice context to other environments, such as education and health. Judges were consensual regarding the usefulness of Article 242º to prevent child abuse, even when involving completely unknown people, and that prevention programs should rely on an open relationship between the participant and the professional.

Conclusion. Preliminary findings revealed the need to discuss further deontological guidelines, considering judges' perceptions that mandatory reporting is beneficial under any circumstances.

KEYWORDS

Prevent It, judges' perceptions, child sexual abuse prevention, PRIORITY, offenders

TITLE **The Development and Evaluation of the Early Awareness Stalking Intervention**

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ABSTRACT

Despite the high prevalence of and damage caused by stalking, there are no validated interventions to address it. Early and targeted intervention is essential in managing risks, preventing stalking escalation and thus reducing recidivism. The current research is evaluating the Early Awareness Stalking Intervention (EASI); a new, cost and time efficient, targeted and evidence-informed intervention for those who engage in ex-intimate stalking. The EASI multi-agency partnership model identifies people charged with stalking in the West Midlands region of the UK. These individuals are referred to a forensic psychologist to undertake focussed Acceptance and Commitment Therapy via remote/online methods with victims offered bespoke support. The outcomes of the intervention are being evaluated using mixed methods consisting of quantitative and qualitative data. During Phases 1 and 2 of the evaluation, eighty-seven individuals charged with stalking (or related offences) completed the EASI. Relative to a comparison group (n=94) who did not undertake the intervention, those who completed the EASI demonstrated lower levels of re-offending. Furthermore, individuals who completed therapy showed significant improvements in their psychosocial functioning on several psychometric measures administered pre and post intervention. These early findings suggest the EASI is showing a positive impact in reducing re-offending and psychological factors associated with perpetration of ex-intimate stalking. The implications for effective multi-agency working in the management of stalking cases will be discussed.

KEYWORDS **Stalking, Perpetration, Intervention, Evaluation**

TITLE **SATNAV Compass: a comprehensive school-based programme of (individual morality) change**

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ABSTRACT This paper presents the process evaluation from several trials of the SATNAV Compass intervention programme. SATNAV Compass has a longitudinal and participatory-led research design and is under continual co-development with practitioner collaborators. The project is guided by Situational Action Theory and the well-evidenced link between antisocial morality and adolescent crime and problem behaviour. The programme targets individual-level moral development and has been delivered and evaluated in three UK schools to date (N=240; 120 in experimental group, 120 in control group). The programme group carry out evidence-led and interactive activities, discussions, debates, and dilemmas during weekly 60-minute sessions, delivered in small groups of 6-8 adolescents. Data indicates that programme participants are engaged, enthusiastic, and task-focused during programme sessions, and that they report positive outcomes (for example, in their relationships with others, decision-making, and wellbeing) in relation to their control group counterparts. Whilst this work is ongoing, we will conclude that this work has the potential to contribute to child development and improve school climates meaningfully and comprehensively. The goal is to encourage positive decision-making to give children opportunities to reach their full potential. We discuss the potential for SATNAV Compass to be administered in different youth settings including youth work charities, schools, and youth offending teams. In future, SAT NAV Compass will be delivered simultaneously alongside consideration of moral contexts; by thoroughly embedding prosocial moral values within the curricular and noncurricular aspects of the school (SATNAV Climate) as well as adaptations to the wider school context (SATNAV Global).

Study funding: The British Academy & Loughborough University.

KEYWORDS **Morality, Youth crime, Crime decision-making, School intervention, Situational Action Theory**

TITLE**Changes in interpersonal Problems, empathy and sexual violence risk after INSIGHT intervention: Preliminary results from a feasibility Study with individuals who sexually offended children**

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the feasibility and outcomes of an individual cognitive-behavioral program based on schema therapy. The aim was to reduce the risk of sexual violence and interpersonal problems, while increasing empathy in individuals who sexually offended children (ISOCs). The Inventory of Interpersonal Problems and the Basic Empathy Scale – Adapted were administered to a treatment group and a control group, and two researchers independently scored the Sexual Violence Risk -20 questionnaire. Subsequently, treatment effects were computed. Approximately 80% of eligible men were recruited. Regarding outcome measures, no significant differences were observed between groups at baseline. Perpetrators who attended treatment showed significant reductions in interpersonal problems, risk of sexual violence, and increases in empathy. These changes were confirmed at the 3-month follow-up. The delivery of the INSIGHT intervention within forensic treatment services was feasible, and the intervention shows promise in effecting significant changes in reducing interpersonal problems and the risk of sexual violence, while also increasing empathy.

KEYWORDS Child sexual abuse, Intervention, Feasibility Study

TITLE **Reducing stigmatizing attitudes towards non-offending pedophile rehabilitation: A humanizing narrative approach with explicit and implicit outcome measures.**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate implicit and explicit attitudes towards Offending Pedophiles (OP) and Non-Offending Pedophiles (NOP) in US participants while also assessing the effectiveness of a humanizing narrative intervention in reducing stigmatizing attitudes towards NOP. Additionally, the influence of gender, political standing, and history of child sexual abuse (CSA) on attitudes was examined. With a sample size of 76, participants completed an Implicit Association Test (IAT) and explicit attitude questionnaires regarding OP and NOP. Participants were then assigned to one of three experimental groups: a passive control group, an active control group, or a humanizing narrative intervention group. In the passive control group, participants completed four simple mathematical tasks unrelated to the study content. In the active control group, participants read the 2022 DSM-5-TR diagnostic criteria for pedophilic disorder. In the humanizing narrative group, participants watched an 8-minute YouTube video in which a non-offending pedophile described their personal experience and the stigma surrounding their condition. Attitude measures were repeated post-intervention, and background demographic information was collected. The study found that more liberal participants reported less punitive attitudes towards NOP and were more supportive of rehabilitation. CSA history significantly impacted attitudes towards NOP, with victims reporting more punitive attitudes, perceiving NOP as more dangerous, and being less supportive of rehabilitation. At both the explicit and implicit levels, significant reductions in stigmatizing attitudes were not observed in any of the experimental groups. These findings do not support our hypothesis that significant reductions in stigmatizing attitudes towards pedophiles would be found on both explicit and implicit levels in the humanizing narrative condition. This is inconsistent with existing literature, as the narrative humanization intervention has proven effective in reducing levels of stigmatization at the explicit level among European samples. Surprisingly, implicit attitudes did not correlate with explicit attitudes in liberal participants, suggesting a discrepancy between self-reported attitudes and implicit biases. The findings highlight the complexity of attitudes towards pedophiles, with political standing and CSA history influencing explicit attitudes. The unexpected misalignment between implicit and explicit attitudes among liberals implies that although liberals self-report having less stigmatized views of NOP, they implicitly have a negative bias towards NOP that does not match their self-reported explicit attitudes. As this is the first study to use the IAT as a measure of implicit attitudes towards NOP, these results should be further investigated. Although the intervention's impact was not as robust as expected, its effect on reducing perceptions of deviance warrants further exploration, suggesting potential avenues for longer or more targeted interventions. This study was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at NYU Shanghai.

KEYWORDS

implicit and explicit attitudes, non-offending pedophiles, Implicit Association Test (IAT), child sexual abuse (CSA), stigmatization

CULTURAL INVESTIGATION

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | CULTURAL INVESTIGATION

TITLE Interviewers, and Interpreters: Understanding the Key Factors that Benefit Culturally and Linguistically Diverse (CaLD) Sexual Assault Victim/Survivors in Investigative Interviews

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ABSTRACT Culturally and linguistically diverse (CaLD) victim/survivors of sexual assault face heightened vulnerability, especially when investigative interviews neglect to consider their diverse attitudes and behaviours stemming from cultural differences (Vredeveltdt, Given-Wilson & Memon, 2023). Our research aims to uncover crucial factors that contribute to culture-sensitive sexual assault investigative interviews.

The current study seeks to validate potential disparities in memory report quality and quantity between CaLD and non-CaLD interviewees. Additionally, we investigate the role of interpreters in potentially mitigating these effects. We recruited bilingual Mandarin speakers and native English speakers to engage in an implied sexual assault scenario in a virtual reality headset. One week later, they then went through a cognitive interview with a trained interviewer to report on the scenario. The bilingual Mandarin participants were randomly assigned to be interviewed in Mandarin (M-M), in English (M-E), and 4) or interviewed in English with the assistance of an interpreter (M-I-E). Native English speakers were all interviewed in English (E-E). Participants provided a free recall report of the incident, and their stress levels were measured pre- and post-scenario and pre- and post-interview. Interpreters' stress levels were measured. Participants were also asked to describe their impressions of the interview, the interviewer, and the interpreter (in conditions where there was an interpreter). Preliminary results will be presented and discussed. We hope our results will shed light on the nuances that demand attention for a more culturally sensitive and just approach to investigative interview practices in sexual assault cases.

KEYWORDS Forensic Psychology, Investigative Interview, Culture

TITLE **Arabic within culture investigative interviews: Arabic native speaking lay-observer truth and lie accuracy, confidence, and verbal cue selection.**

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ABSTRACT

Cross cultural differences in behavioral and verbal norms and expectations can undermine credibility, often triggering a lie bias. However, research in this domain is heavily North American and Western European centric, and so how individuals from non-western cultures infer veracity, the cues they attend to, and the decisions they make is not well understood. We report novel research investigating native Arabic speakers' truth and lie judgments having observed a matched native language investigative interview with a mock person of interest. 217 observers viewed a truthful or a deceptive video interview and were either directed to attend to detailedness of the interviewee's responses as a cue to veracity or given no cue direction. Irrespective of condition, a truth bias (66% accuracy) emerged, but observers were most accurate (79%) in the truth condition. However, accuracy dropped to just 23% when instructed to use the detailedness cue when judging deception. The truthful interviewee was rated as more plausible and more believable than the deceptive interviewee. Verbal veracity cues attended too were constant across conditions with 'corrections' emerging as the most important veracity cue. Our results are mixed in terms of deviating from the findings of others in some areas, while offering some constant findings. Despite limitations, this research raises a challenge for research and criminal investigation practice in forensic interview contexts worldwide whereby western centric psychological understanding may not be as robust for non-western within cultural interviews. Our paradigm, results and implications will be presented and discussed.

KEYWORDS

Arabic first language interviews, Deception, Lay observers, Verbal cues, Behaviour cues

TITLE **How Culture Influences Eyewitness Testimony at the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR)**

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ABSTRACT

In an ever more globalized world, it is becoming more common for witnesses and those gathering evidence to originate from different countries. Investigators and legal practitioners from Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich and Democratic (WEIRD) societies frequently report problems when questioning witnesses from different cultural backgrounds. We conducted an exploratory thematic analysis of 64 witness transcripts from 16 cases at the ICTR, analyzing the ways in which culture influences courtroom testimony. We present four main findings. First, witnesses from non-WEIRD countries were more likely to say 'I don't know' or 'I don't understand' when questioned by attorneys from non-WEIRD countries than when questioned by attorneys from WEIRD countries, indicating a possible mismatch in cross-cultural communication styles and expectations. Second, we found no differences in the types of questions asked by WEIRD and non-WEIRD attorneys, suggesting that the norms and rules of the court influenced the questioning style more than the attorney's demographic background. Third, regardless of culture, closed questions were the most prevalent type of question asked to witnesses, which may reflect the strict parameters placed on attorneys in international trials. Finally, systematic coding of the transcripts revealed only few occurrences of the type of cross-cultural mishaps often cited in the literature based on anecdotal examples. We conclude that cultural background influences how witnesses perceive and respond to questions at the ICTR. Thus, it is crucial to acknowledge and address the cultural dimensions of legal communication and interpretation. Nonetheless, we urge caution against overstating cross-cultural challenges in international criminal trials solely based on anecdotal evidence. The implications of our findings for witness testimony in current and future international tribunals and courts will be discussed.

KEYWORDS **Culture, Eyewitness, Testimony**

TITLE **Ethno-Religious Disparities in Social Norm Enforcement:
Insights from Combined Experimental and Survey
Approaches**

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ABSTRACT

Experimental research on the enforcement of social norms in everyday life has significantly increased in recent years. Studies examining the effects of ethno-religious diversity on the sanctioning of norm violations have provided empirical evidence of ethno-religious asymmetries in the enforcement of social norms: minorities are more frequently targeted for sanctions in daily life. Previous research lacks a comprehensive examination of the causes of this unequal sanctioning.

This study contributes to existing research by combining field-experimental and survey research to investigate the mechanisms behind the unequal sanctioning of norm-breaking women depending on their religious (non-)affiliation with Islam (implied through wearing a hijab). This group is often met with skepticism in liberal democracies, and frequently experiences rejection from the majority society.

We hypothesized that women with hijabs would be more frequently sanctioned compared to women without hijabs. Additionally, we assumed that authoritarian aggressions increase the likelihood of sanctioning overall, and Islamophobic attitudes amplify the likelihood of sanctioning among women with hijabs. To examine sanctioning behavior, nearly 350 passersby in public were confronted with a field experimental intervention, the norm violation of “littering” and subsequently surveyed about their attitudes and socio-demographic characteristics.

Contrary to our assumptions, our results do not show that wearing a hijab increases the likelihood of sanctioning. Also, no reinforcing influence of Islamophobic attitudes can be demonstrated. However, authoritarian aggressions do increase the likelihood of sanctioning overall. Potential mechanisms that could have led to the present results will be discussed.

KEYWORDS

**social norms, sanctioning, discrimination, authoritarian aggressions,
Islamophobia**

TITLE **Unmasking Deception: How do Consumers Determine the Veracity of Online User Reviews?**

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ABSTRACT

To influence consumers to buy products of lower quality, criminals produce fake online consumer reviews, which in health and safety related products can not only lead to financial and emotional but also physical harm. Understanding how people make judgements about review veracity presents an opportunity to examine how people make deception judgments in a naturalistic setting, when there are direct personal consequences for the decisions they make.

The objective of this research is to develop a grounded theory of how consumers determine the veracity of online user reviews, within the context of online shopping behavior, with a longer term objective to develop interventions to strengthen consumer resilience.

Study 1 comprised 25 interviews with Dutch and German consumers analyzed through grounded theory. In study 2, we used a think-aloud method where participants described their thought processes while they decided whether or not they would like to buy 7 different products.

Study 1 showed that deception judgments only occurred late in the review process, after usefulness, credibility, and trustworthiness were evaluated. Furthermore, when deception judgments are made, they encompassed a wide range of cues, including evaluation of the reviewer, seller and platform and corroboration with external information as well as the content of the review itself. We expect that the second study will refine our developed theory by addressing the key limitation of our first study, which is that it is based upon recollections of purchasing behavior rather than capturing live decision making processes.

Theoretically, our research demonstrates how deception decisions are embedded within wider decision-making contexts. Practically, our research indicates that deception training interventions will have to be multifaceted and would likely include increasing the perceived legitimacy of genuine products and sellers as well as facilitating recognition of reliable cues to deception for individual users.

KEYWORDS **Fake reviews, deception detection, consumer-perspective**

JUVENILE

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | JUVENILE

TITLE **Mindfulness and Self-Compassion with caregivers of young offenders: a parallel non-randomized control trial**

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ABSTRACT

Working with delinquent youth is described as a defiant work. In particular, professionals which work with youth placed in Youth Detention Centers (YDC) are daily faced with work and relational challenges, while experiencing high levels of stress and physical and emotional fatigue.

As such, taking care of the well-being of these professionals is of paramount importance, more so as they are fundamental in the rehabilitation of young offenders. Recent studies have explored the impact of contextual cognitive-behavioral interventions with caregivers, (e.g., parents of individuals with developmental disabilities, nurses, healthcare providers), namely those based on Mindfulness and Self-Compassion. The Mindfulness Self-Compassion Program (MSC) in particular, has been found effective in reducing caregivers' feelings of overwhelmed about their own suffering and/or the suffering of others.

This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of the adapted form of MSC (12 group sessions) to caregivers working in Portuguese YDC, through a parallel non-randomized clinical trial. It was recruited a sample of 61 caregivers from four out of six Portuguese YDC: 2 YDC constituted the treatment group, composed for 28 participants that received the adapted form MSC program and, the remaining 2 YDC constituted the control group, composed for 33 participants that did not receive any intervention during. Caregivers of both groups were assessed through self-report questionnaires in four different moments: pre-treatment, post-treatments, 3-moths follow-up and 6-months follow-up.

The impact of the adapted form of MSC will be explored on intrapersonal (e.g., self-compassion, mindfulness and compassion towards others) as also in work-related variables (i.e., burnout and satisfaction with work). It is expected that the intervention may result in improvements on the caregivers' general well-being as also in their perception about the provided care.

KEYWORDS

Juvenile Justice, Mindfulness and Self-Compassion, Caregivers, Clinical trial

TITLE **Supporting parents dealing with childhood behavior problems: A feasibility RCT in Portugal**

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ABSTRACT

Concerning numbers of childhood behavior problems have been reported worldwide. Portugal is following international trends, with increasing numbers of externalizing problems. Research has shown that childhood behavior problems, as well as parental practices, are one of the leading risk factors for future delinquent and criminal behavior. Thus, parenting interventions are considered one of the most effective early strategies to intervene with externalizing conducts and prevent criminal behavior. Thus, the dissemination of evidence-based parenting programs is of foremost importance. This double-blinded feasibility RCT aimed to implement a parenting intervention in Portugal and: a) test key feasibility parameters; b) assess fidelity and acceptability of the Portuguese version of the program, and c) explore the effectiveness of the program in childhood behavior problems and parental sense of competence. Participants were primary caregivers of a child between the ages of two and 11 years old that identify difficulties in managing their child's behavior. Families were randomly assigned to an intervention or a waitlist control arm. Parents in the intervention arm participated in the Being a Parent program (Portuguese version: Ser Pai & Ser Mãe), an eight-week group intervention. Results suggest that the Being a Parent program can be implemented in the Portuguese context and effectively reduce childhood behavior problems, as well as increase parental sense of competence. Inherent challenges and clinical implications are also discussed.

KEYWORDS

Parenting intervention, Childhood behavior problems, Crime prevention, Randomized controlled trial, Feasibility

TITLE **Perceptions of Youth Undergoing a Custodial Measure
Regarding Their Life Trajectories**

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ABSTRACT Given the increasing prevalence and public attention to juvenile delinquency, along with a growing body of research on the phenomenon, this study aims to explore participants' perception of their life trajectory, accessing information about risk factors, and specific needs that influence involvement in delinquent behaviors. The study involved 12 young individuals with a history of delinquency and were undergoing custodial measure. Through the collection and thematic analysis of their life stories, five central themes emerged: socio-familial context, school, peer group, institutionalization, and future individual projects. These themes depict the various experiences encountered by young people throughout their life trajectories. Through a comprehensive analysis of participants' narratives, it becomes evident that the contexts in which children and young people are situated play an important role in shaping their development and life trajectory, including involvement in delinquent behaviors. Consequently, effective prevention strategies for juvenile delinquency necessitate a systemic approach, encompassing timely and targeted public policies addressing various domains of these individuals' lives - personal, familial, and social - across different stages of their development.

KEYWORDS **adolescence, juvenile delinquency, life trajectories**

TITLE **Poly-victimization, Resilience, and Anxiety in Delinquent and Non-Delinquent Youth Sample: A Comparative Study**

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ABSTRACT

When compared to experiencing only one type of victimization, poly-victimization is linked to more negative consequences and is considered a stronger predictor of developing worse mental health outcomes. Given the prevalent reports of child victimization in Portugal and the potentially heightened impact of poly-victimization on young delinquents, this study aims to verify the link between poly-victimization, anxiety, and resilience; compare delinquent and non-delinquent adolescents concerning poly-victimization, anxiety, and resilience; and identify the predictors of anxiety. One hundred forty-three youths aged 12 to 17 ($M = 14.93$, $SD = 1.63$) participated in this study (97 were young delinquents, and 46 were non-delinquents). Participants completed a socio-demographic questionnaire, the Juvenile Victimization Questionnaire (JVQ), the Resilience Scale (RS), and the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAIC). Results show a relationship between JVQ, the RS, and the STAIC. Young delinquents reported experiencing more episodes of victimization during their childhood, leading to higher levels of anxiety and lower levels of resilience. Our research confirms that poly-victimization has a negative impact on resilience, reducing both social and personal resources. Additionally, results showed that poly-victimization increases the risk of impaired psychological development and heightened levels of anxiety. These findings underscore the importance of prioritizing mental well-being in poly-victimized adolescents, highlighting the need for effective prevention and intervention strategies to combat delinquency.

KEYWORDS **Poly-victimization, Juvenile Delinquency, Resilience, Anxiety**

TITLE **Mental health care needs among Swedish youths convicted for severe criminal offences**

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ABSTRACT

In Sweden, individuals aged 15 to 18 years who are convicted for severe criminal offences are typically sentenced to youth detention under the Secure Youth Care Act (LSU, SFS 1998:603), rather than imprisonment. Since the late 1990's, secure youth care has been administrated by The Swedish National Board of Institutional Care (SNBIC), at specialized secure youth homes. However, recently, the Swedish government suggested and decided that from year 2027 juvenile offenders will be sentenced to imprisonment, provided within the criminal justice system. This study aims to illuminate the mental health challenges encountered by juvenile offenders and the corresponding care interventions. These needs necessitate attention, regardless of where they serve their sentence.

This cross-sectional study examined needs of care and treatment related to mental health condition, among juvenile offenders within SNBIC convicted of severe criminal offences. Psychologists at SNBIC completed web-based questionnaires focusing on diagnosed mental disorders, clinical symptoms, and urgent mental health conditions among the youths.

Response rate was 59 percent, including boys only. Most were diagnosed with at least one mental disorder, and nearly half having comorbidities. The predominant disorders, whether diagnosed or presenting clinical symptoms, were AD/H/D (affecting half of the group) and substance use disorder (SUD) (observed in approximately a quarter). Additionally, conduct disorder and depression disorder were frequently identified. Notably, no suicide attempts or acute mental health crises necessitating immediate intervention in the past six months were reported.

This presentation will address the mental health conditions and comorbidity among Swedish juvenile offenders, highlighting that their conditions do not significantly differ from boys in compulsory care due to antisocial behaviors and psychosocial problems. The presentation will touch upon the high prevalence of mental health care needs among these boys and the challenges faced by those responsible for executing the care, regardless of the agency involved.

KEYWORDS **Poly-victimization, Juvenile Delinquency, Resilience, Anxiety**

MENTAL HEALTH

TITLE **Psychiatric comorbidity among women with substance abuse in compulsory care at the Swedish National Board of Institutional Care**

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ABSTRACT

In Sweden, people with severe substance abuse can be taken into compulsory care according to LVM-Act (SFS 1988:870). The National Board of Institutional Care (NBIC) is a Swedish government agency delivering individually tailored compulsory care, currently operating eleven institutions for adults with substance abuse; four are women only institutions. The focus of this presentation is on psychiatric care needs among women subjected to LVM-care within NBIC.

In a cross-sectional study design, psychologist working at NBIC were asked to fill out a web-based questionnaire focusing psychiatric diagnoses, psychiatric clinical symptoms, and acute psychiatric conditions among their clients. Information about 110 women within LVM-care were collected (80% of the total population). Results include that, apart from substance abuse disorder, AD/H/D was the most common psychiatric diagnosis, which close to half of participants had.

Two out of five was diagnosed with, or showed clinical symptoms of, anxiety disorder; more than one third was diagnosed with, or showed clinical symptoms of, depression; two out of five was diagnosed with, or showed clinical symptoms of, PTSD. On average, participants presented three different psychiatric diagnosis (SUD included), and one out of five of the participants presented four or more psychiatric diagnoses. Furthermore, almost one third of the participants had presented one or more acute psychiatric condition during the past six months - the most common being suicidal behavior and psychotic episode.

The presentation contributes to a deeper understanding of the specific needs of women with substance abuse and psychiatric comorbidity, for example, the prevalence of PTSD was significantly higher than previously noted among men. In the presentation, the high prevalence of psychiatric care needs among women with substance abuse in LVM-care will be discussed, as well as the challenges of NBIC offering adequate care and the importance of extended cooperation with psychiatric care facilities.

KEYWORDS

Compulsory care, Substance abuse, Psychiatric comorbidity, Psychiatric care needs

TITLE **A call from inside the house: We need to update DSM criteria for malingering**

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ABSTRACT Malingering is defined as intentional fabrication or exaggeration of symptoms or deficits motivated by external incentives. The base rate of malingering in medicolegal neuropsychological assessments is estimated between 8% to 30%, at a cost of \$20 billion USD to social services (Chafetz & Underhill, 2013). Despite the high stakes, the clinical characteristics of malingering are poorly defined. The Diagnostic and Statistics Manual-5-Text Revision (DSM-5-TR), lists the following factors (1) the evaluation occurs in a medicolegal context; (2) marked discrepancy between the claimed disability and objective evidence; (3) lack of compliance with evaluation and treatment regimen; and (4) presence of antisocial personality disorder (APD). However, converging lines of evidence suggest that most of these criteria have poor discriminant and predictive validity. Indeed, mounting evidence has suggested that 1) malingering also occurs in clinical context; 2) some individuals can successfully mimic the sequelae of the claimed disorder on clinical evaluation; 3) the majority of malingerers are nominally compliant with both assessment and prescribed treatment; 4) APD is orthogonal to malingering and provides little predictive value. Further, the relevance of external incentive status and the volitional nature of deficit exaggeration is increasingly scrutinized in conceptualizing malingering. Objective measures of symptom and performance validity are not referenced in DSM-5-TR, despite accumulating evidence for their utility in identifying malingered symptoms and deficits. We present a critical analysis of DSM-5-TR criteria for malingering with proposed updates to reflect the evolution of the knowledge base in the past half a century.

KEYWORDS **Malingering, DSM-5-TR, Performance Validity**

TITLE **Symptomatology explains criminality among people declaring a head trauma, with or without a diagnosis of traumatic brain injury: A web-based survey**

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ABSTRACT

Context: The impact of symptomatology and head trauma on aggressive behavior has been demonstrated. However, the degree of influence of symptomatology on forensic behaviors has not been studied among people declaring a head injury whether or not there has been a diagnosis of traumatic brain injury (TBI).

Objectives: Study the way post-concussion symptomatology influences the variety of crimes committed and the number of interactions with police officers among people who declared a head trauma followed or not by a diagnosis of TBI, and the general population.

Design and participants: 358 responders to an online survey were assigned to three independent groups according to their self-reports: (i) without head trauma (CTRLs), (ii) TBI without diagnosis (TBI_{nd}) and (iii) TBI followed by a diagnosis (TBI_d). Participants completed an adapted version of the Rivermead post-concussion symptom questionnaire and reported the variety of crimes (theft, assault, etc.), as well as the frequency of interactions with the police.

Results: Both TBI groups reported committing a greater variety of crimes than CTRLs, and TBI_d reported having committed a greater variety of crimes than TBI_{nd}, regardless of gender and level of education. Furthermore, symptomatology was predictive of the frequency of interactions with the police in both groups, although it was greater in TBI_d.

Provisional conclusions: Symptomatology seems to be a determining factor and a common denominator in the occurrence of forensic behaviors after head trauma, with or without a diagnosis of TBI. The results may reflect the role of post-concussion chemical and psychological changes on social behavior. The co-occurrence of a head injury and a more severe symptomatology increases the risk of criminal behaviors. This finding highlights the possible impact of a head injury on family and socio-professional reintegration, regardless of the individuals involved.

KEYWORDS

symptomatology, traumatic brain injury, police interaction, variety of crimes committed

TITLE **A new tool for the assessment of financial capability**

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ABSTRACT

Financial capability refers to the ability to handle money and understand financial activities, so that the person's needs are consistent with their own values and interests, and it lies on a continuum from a refined ability to understand and manage finances to a total inability typical of individuals with an advanced state of dementia and/or a severe mental illness. Hence it seems necessary to have a tool that, together with legal and medical evaluations, enables the clinician to assess a person's financial capacity in the best way. Cognitive disorders and dementia care center in-patients and psychiatric treatment facility in-patients administered a new self-report questionnaire about financial capacities, lasting 30 minutes, consisting of five basic areas (daily and common financial skills; comprehension of scheduled expenses and management of contingencies; knowledge of how to analyze insurance/financial/investment plans; knowledge of basic legal and financial concepts) and two optional areas on donations and testamentary capacity. Participants also administered cognitive and neuropsychological questionnaires, together with a projective instrument for the assessment of personality characteristics. Participants of both the cognitive disorders/dementia and psychiatric groups presented a marginal competency or no competency at all in the tasks related to the financial capability, linked to a more or less severe cognitive impairment, showing a good ability of the newly implemented questionnaire to evaluate the construct on which it was built. The new tool resulted therefore as more user-friendly, up-to-date and faster than the already existing ones, and preliminary results will be presented to support it.

KEYWORDS **financial capacity, cognitive impairment, dementia, psychiatric disorders**

MENTAL HEALTH IMPACTS ON PROFESSIONALS

TITLE “We create a cloak, a shell that protects us”: The consequences of police work on police officers

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ABSTRACT

All first-line responders, of which police officers are included, are characterised by systematic exposure to traumatic situations during their working routines. The manifest or latent violence they usually face may generate high levels of stress resulting in problems in the physical and psychological health of police officers, making them potential secondary victims. Some health problems assume different configurations and may be masked, preventing the police officers from asking for help. Additionally, there still is a culture of silence within police organizations because of the stigma associated with mental health issues. All this inhibits these professionals from being alert to some signs and isolated symptoms hindering an appropriate approach and increasing the risk for some serious health disruptions to install. So, long before specific clinical conditions can be identified police officers may present a set of diverse health indicators constituting valuable information for clinicians, psychologists, and even police managers and decision-makers to work with. The main goal of the study was to gain better knowledge about the impacts of police work on police officers' health. Using a qualitative approach, exploratory research was conducted. A semi-structured in-depth interview was conducted with 74 police officers from different police units of the Portuguese Public Security Police, after hierarchical authorisation. Participants were given an informed consent form, assured anonymity and confidentiality, and freely participated in the study. Results from the content analysis of the interviews (transcribed verbatim) show the will and need to talk about the difficulties and specific challenges faced while performing their job, the job sources of stress, a variety of psychological impacts, and the respective defence strategies they mobilise.

KEYWORDS

Police officers, Secondary victimization, Health consequences of police work, Police psychology, Exposure to traumatic events

TITLE **Psychological Well-being among Professionals who work with Domestic Violence Victims**

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ABSTRACT

Domestic violence (DV) significantly affects not only victims but also the professionals who supports them. These professionals are exposed to emotionally intense and traumatic stories, potentially leading to negative psychological effects. Objective: The presented study aimed to assess these professionals psychological well-being, coping strategies, and self-care. Methodology: The study adopted a cross-sectional design. 251 professionals who work with DV victims answered voluntarily to an online questionnaire with a set of questionnaires. Data was analyzed with IBM SPSS. Results: Results showed moderate levels of burnout and Compassion Fatigue (CF) among participants, along with moderate symptoms of depression and anxiety. Notably, high levels of Compassions Satisfaction (CS) were observed, suggesting a potential protective factor against the adverse effects of DV intervention. The analysis of predictors for psychopathological symptoms showed the significant influence of CF, avoidant coping, and self-care on professionals' mental health. Specifically, avoidant coping was associated with exacerbating negative mental health outcomes, while self-care practices showed promise in mitigating the impact of CF on depression and anxiety. These findings underscore the importance of addressing the emotional toll on DV professionals, promoting effective coping strategies, and encouraging self-care practices to support their mental health. Implementing comprehensive support systems for DV professionals is crucial for enhancing their resilience and well-being, thereby ensuring their continued ability to provide essential support to victims.

KEYWORDS **professionals, domestic violence victims, mental health**

TITLE **Protecting Police Officers and Their Families Online: Social Media Harms, Risk Mitigation and Support Needs for children**

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ABSTRACT

Increasingly police officers in public-facing roles are subject to online threats and harassment. While this is often framed as a way to 'redress police injustices' or as a democratising potential of 'watching back', it threatens individual officers' social standing and wellbeing outside of their professional role. Their family members are involved directly and immediately, either because they are also targeted or because they have to live with fears and accept restrictions to their online participation in order to safeguard their police family members. Yet, there remains scant research on the experiences of dependants, particularly children of police officers. This study focuses on teenage children of police officers by exploring their experiences with online harms, how they negotiate the use and access to social media with parents, safety measures taken, and potentially dangerous behaviours they might engage in. Semi-structured interviews with 36 teenage children aged 13-17 discovered that all participants have witnessed online hate and criticism aimed at police officers. Some teenagers were also subjected to bullying or humiliation outside of the internet such as by peers at school. As a result, most participants refrained from disclosing their parents' identity to others, worried about their parents' physical and online safety, and also worried about their own safety and likelihood of being bullied/harassed online. While teenagers were aware of the risks of the policing profession, they were active on various social media platforms. Although many of them declared to keep safe online, some teenagers used gaming apps and other instant messaging platforms to speak to and share personal information with random people. This study highlights the impact policing profession has on children and how they navigate through the digital space, and encourages open communication between parents and young people in safeguarding children online.

KEYWORDS

Children of police officers, social media, online safety, online restrictions, negative experiences

TITLE **Building resilience against secondary trauma in organisations working to support survivors of sexual and domestic violence**

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ABSTRACT

In the United Kingdom (UK) there is a vast violence against women and girls (VAWG) sector working tirelessly to support survivors of sexual and domestic violence. Most of the work force are women. A small body of international research has focused on those working with victims of domestic violence and sexual assault, but there is limited research from the UK. The aim of this research is to develop an understanding of the effects that working with survivors of trauma has on VAWG practitioners in the UK. The research aims to create an evidence base around two potential outcomes of working with survivors of trauma: secondary traumatic stress and post-traumatic growth. An anonymous online survey open to all adult practitioners (frontline workers, managers, and administrators) who work with survivors of sexual and domestic violence or other forms of VAWG in the UK has been completed by 100 participants to date. Preliminary findings will be presented focusing on understanding the effects that working with trauma has on VAWG practitioners identifying the personal and environmental/ organisational factors that contribute to developing secondary traumatic stress and post-traumatic growth among VAWG practitioners and exploring whether the measures in place to support those working with trauma lead to better outcomes. Developing a greater understanding of the effects of working with trauma on VAWG practitioners, including the specific challenges encountered by those from minoritised services, is crucial for sustaining effective support to survivors through trauma-informed and holistic services. The findings from this research will feed into the development of good practice measures for the VAWG sector and help mitigate any adverse effects.

KEYWORDS **Vicarious trauma, post-traumatic growth, sexual violence, domestic violence**

TITLE **Finding the unfindable, looking into the far future - limits of psychological science**

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ABSTRACT In my oral presentation I want to raise questions and start a discussion and maybe research into the topic. To my knowledge there is not much what psychologists can really do in assessing forensic or also family psychological cases.

The problem of face validity in personality tests, the restrictions of risk assessment instruments, and the absolute lack of really helpful scientific and evidence based instruments is big.

On the other side is the legal system and society who want to be safe of perpetrators and there are children that want to be saved from incapable parents.

I want to give an overview on what I know is there as regards instruments and what is needed dearly in my point of view.

KEYWORDS **diagnostic, risk assessment, best interests of children**

PERSONALITY DISORDERS

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | PERSONALITY DISORDERS

TITLE **Executive dysfunctions in emotional processing in psychopathy**

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ABSTRACT

Numerous reports indicate the role of both emotional and executive deficits in the mechanism explaining psychopathy. Some of them concern the limitations of correctly identifying the emotional expressions of others, which, as a result, cannot be used as signals for the regulation and control of behavior. The most common ideas concerning the etiology of psychopathy could be verified empirically, usually focusing on the selective analysis of limited recognition of emotional expressions or other aspects, such as executive control and other cognitive processes involved in the processing of emotional information. The aim of presented research was to determine whether executive dysfunctions are general deficit in psychopathy or rather specifically connected to emotional processing. Presented research project was carried out in a group of 108 noncriminal participants. The obtained results showed that subjects with a higher level of psychopathy revealed a reduced ability to recognize emotional expressions of distress and demonstrated smaller interference effect in the emotional Stroop task but performed correctly in the classic Stroop task. It suggests that deficiency in emotional processing, including executive control based on this type of signals, may be more important deficit in psychopathy than the general effect of executive dysfunction.

KEYWORDS **psychopathy, executive dysfunctions, behavior control, violence**

TITLE **Investigating the Relationship Between Dark Triad Personality Traits and Altruism**

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CONTACTS**

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ABSTRACT

It has been determined that individuals with narcissism, Machiavellianism and psychopathy, which are not included in the clinical dimension but are evaluated at the subclinical level and called Dark Triad personality traits in the literature, are associated with impulsivity, manipulation, behavioral aggression, etc. Altruism is defined as a moral attitude and view that adopts self-sacrifice for the good of others as a principle. The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between dark triad personality traits and altruism, which are risky in terms of crime and violent behavior.

In this study, Personal Information Form, Short Dark Triad Scale, Altruism Scale were used. The obtained data were analyzed by SPSS.

Of the 186 participants, 62.9% were female and 37.1% were male. According to the correlation analysis between the scales, there was a moderate positive relationship between Machiavellianism, Narcissism and Psychopathy and Selfishness subscales ($r: .305$; $r: .340$; $r: .450$), a weak positive relationship between Narcissism and Selflessness subscales ($r: .208$), and a weak negative relationship between Psychopathy and Selflessness subscales ($r: -.194$).

According to the results of our study, it was found that there is a positive relationship between psychopathy, narcissism and Machiavellianism, which are dark triad personality traits, and selfishness. In addition, it was observed that individuals with psychopathy traits had lower selflessness. In order to prevent criminal behavior, it is thought that similar studies should be conducted with large participants to understand the variables that increase the tendency towards psychopathy. In addition, considering the effect of environmental factors including family members such as violent punishments, inconsistent guidance, inconsistent authority structure, violence and neglect in the development of psychopathy, it was noteworthy that parental attitudes have an important place in raising altruistic individuals who are sensitive and have high social responsibility.

KEYWORDS **dark triad, dark triad personality traits, altruism**

TITLE **The impact of porn use and personality factors in judgement of sexual consent**

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Objectives: This study aimed to examine how individual differences in personality factors in the form of the Dark Triad (Machiavellianism, narcissism and psychopathy) and rape myth acceptance interact with the consumption and use of different types of pornography to impact on attitudes towards sexual consent.

Methodology: 164 Participants completed an online survey including the Short Dark Triad (Jones & Paulhus, 2014), Sexual Consent Scale (Humphreys, 2004), Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale (McMahon & Farmer, 2011), Pornography Usage Measure (Busby et al., 2020) and Pornography Usage Type (Hald, 2006) measures. In addition, participants were asked to make judgements about the appropriateness of the behaviour of individuals described in a vignette measure (based on Humphreys 2004) which depicted a sexual encounter where the individuals consented, acquiesced or were forced into sexual behaviour.

ABSTRACT Results: A number of the individual differences variables were inter-related with rape myth relating to all of Dark Triad types; Machiavellianism, narcissism and psychopathy as well as all subscales of the Sexual Consent Scale. The relationship between these individual difference factors and the use and type of pornography will be described in detail as well as analysing and comparing those groups who agree with and use, more extreme pornography. The types of pornography use are analysed to identify the patterns of pornography use and the extent to which there are differences between those individuals endorsing the use of extreme porn and those who do not use extreme porn. This is also examined in terms of how porn use relates to other factors including the acceptability of different behaviours in consenting, acquiescing and non-consenting (rape) scenarios. The results of these multiple comparisons will be presented with a view to better understanding the complex relationship between personality / attitudinal variables, pornography use and judgements of sexual consent.

KEYWORDS **Dark Triad, pornography type, rape myth, sexual consent**

TITLE **The truth behind the screen: Measuring the ability to identify lies on dating apps**

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ABSTRACT

Dating apps have gone from anecdotal use in the early 2000s to a veritable societal phenomenon in 2023. Today, they are an integral part of our daily lives, giving users access to a list of profiles selected to suit their needs. To maximize the number of matches, the use of lies in the presentation phase is a strategy that's frequently used. This study examined the ability to detect these lies. Participants had to judge whether actors (50% females and 50% males) were telling the truth (50%) or lying (50%) about their certain aspects of their life, such as professional activities, hobbies or personality traits. Because individual differences determining the ability to detect lies are poorly understood, this study also investigated the predictive power of self-monitoring, psychopathy, Machiavellianism, narcissism and empathy on the ability to discriminate lies from truth and on response tendencies. The results of this study will be presented and discussed at the EAPL 2024 congress.

KEYWORDS **Lie detection, Dating apps, psychopathy, empathy**

TITLE **Dark personalities and sexual machismo: Latent profiles and associations with acceptance of sexual violence**

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ABSTRACT

Individuals high in the Dark Tetrad traits (i.e., narcissism, psychopathy, Machiavellianism, sadism) are more likely to show high sexism and favorable attitudes toward sexual violence (particularly male sexual violence against women). However, little is known about whether these traits and sexism can be combined to form groups and whether favorable attitudes toward sexual violence differ among these groups. Therefore, this study explored how the Dark Tetrad traits and sexual machismo combine to form latent profiles and how the acceptance of sexual violence, including specific rape myths, vary across these profiles. A total of 252 adults between the ages of 18 and 70 ($M = 35.6$, $SD = 14.3$) completed the Short Dark Tetrad, the Sexual Machismo scale, and the Beliefs about Sexual Violence scale. Latent profile analysis yielded three profiles: malevolent and sexist profile members showed above average levels of Machiavellianism, high levels of all other Dark Tetrad traits (particularly psychopathy and sadism) and high levels of sexual machismo (2.8% of participants; 71.4% men), slightly malevolent and sexist profile members exhibited above average levels of all traits and sexual machismo (31.7% of participants; 20% men), and benevolent and non-sexist profile members scored low in all traits and in sexual machismo (65.5% of participants; 12.1% men). The malevolent and sexist group showed higher acceptance of sexual violence and most specific myths compared to the other profiles but showed similar levels of victim consent and false allegations to the slightly malevolent and sexist group. Furthermore, the slightly malevolent and sexist group exhibited higher acceptance of sexual violence and most specific myths compared to the benevolent and non-sexist group. These results indicate that favorable attitudes toward sexual violence differentiate individuals high and low in Dark Tetrad traits and sexual machismo.

KEYWORDS **Dark Tetrad, sexual machismo, acceptance of sexual violence, rape myths**

VICTIMS SUPPORT STRATEGIES

TITLE Reaching the under-reached groups: Effective Targeting in Domestic Abuse Service Provision in the UK using a mixed-methods approach

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ABSTRACT

Following a needs assessment in 2021 by the Derby and Derbyshire Domestic and Sexual Abuse (DSA) Partnership Board, a gap was identified in the provision of DA services to victims who within the categories: (a) Over 35 years of age, (b) Male, (c) Living with long-term physical and/or mental health ill-health or disabilities, (d) Carers, (e) LGBTQ+, (f) Protected characteristics of race and religion and, (g) No recourse to public funding. This study aimed to assess the barriers that prevent or dissuade access of these under-reached victims to DA services and recommend improvements for enhanced engagement with services. The study was carried out in a three-stage approach: (1) gathering quantitative data from service referral data and other archival data, (2) interviews with 11 social workers from DA services, and (3) interviews with 8 DA survivors. Chi-square analyses showed that most male clients were attended by the helpline rather than in-person services; whilst accommodation were most likely to work with individuals identifying as Black and Asian, or living with long term illness. Each set of qualitative data was analysed using Thematic Analysis. The lack of understanding of the under-reached groups' needs was identified as a key theme by Service Workers. Under this theme, challenges were mainly related, but not limited, to ethnicity, age, gender, and sexual orientation. While survivors identified personal barriers such as not recognising the abuse, lack of trust in the services, or not believing to be entitled to support as a barrier. Recommendations include increasing consistency between quantitative data reporting across services, offering training related to cultural competency and mental health, making DA services more visible, educating the wider public on DA, and supporting and engaging with 'by and for' services.

KEYWORDS

Domestic Violence, Protected characteristics, Support services, Barriers to access, Mixed methods

TITLE**Seeking to Drive Change Through the Incorporation of Lived Experience: An Example for Domestic Abuse**

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ABSTRACT

In this presentation we will discuss the innovative collaborative co-production approach that we have been taking to help inform and drive change in criminal justice and support systems to ensure that they better meet the needs of diverse domestic abuse victim groups.

SEEKERS (Sharing Experience, and Expertise and Knowledge for Effective Responses and Support) is a collaborative partnership between victim-survivors of domestic abuse, advocates, third sector parties and organisations, police and academics. The aim of the partnership is to provide co-learning and development opportunities which incorporate and utilise different forms of lived experience, alongside specialist insights and expertise, with the aim of better understanding issues and challenges associated with the criminal justice processing of domestic abuse cases, and how best to support victims as they navigate this process. The primary goal of the partnership and the activities undertaken is to try to ensure equitable access to justice for all victims/survivors of domestic abuse, including those from minoritized or excluded communities.

This work is helping pave the way in terms of reforming systems and driving change, by demonstrating how procedures, policies and practice can be enhanced through stakeholder involvement and the incorporation of lived experience from diverse perspectives.

KEYWORDS

Domestic Violence, Criminal Justice System, Lived Experience, Victim Voice

TITLE **Personality Profiles of Fathers and Mothers in High-Conflict Child Custody Cases**

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ABSTRACT

The evaluation of parents has gained increased significance as courts prioritize the best interests of the child. Therefore, in child custody cases, particularly those characterized by high levels of conflict, it is common for Portuguese courts to request psychological assessment of the parents, particularly regarding their personality traits. The present study aimed to identify the personality profiles of parents involved in high-conflict child custody cases and their associated characteristics. To achieve this, data from the 16PF-5 personality questionnaire were analyzed from archived cases of child custody or child protection (within the scope of child custody cases). The sample consisted of 120 parents, including 64 fathers and 56 mothers, aged between 24 and 62 years. The results indicated that 35.8% of the sample exhibited a tendency to manipulate their image. Two distinct profiles emerged for the fathers - extroverted manipulators and anxious non-manipulators - and three for mothers - self-controlled manipulators, introverted manipulators, and anxious non-manipulators. Analyses revealed that only one profile of each sex did not exhibit a tendency to manipulate their image. Additionally, high levels of anxiety were found among parents in child custody cases characterized by high conflict. The findings underscore the importance of using personality questionnaires capable of detecting image manipulation in child custody evaluations due to the propensity of these parents to manipulate their image.

KEYWORDS **Child custody, high-conflict, parents, personality**

TITLE Navigating Criminal Justice Systems and Processes as a Homicide-Bereaved Person: Insights From Lived Experiences

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ABSTRACT

This body of work explores homicide-bereaved persons' encounters with criminal justice agencies and experiences of criminal justice systems and processes. It also considers support provided, and the extent to which this was effective in meeting their needs, as well as support needs which were not met by current offerings.

The research was conducted in collaboration with the charity 'Support After Murder and Manslaughter' (SAMM). Their membership was surveyed via a questionnaire that was completed either as a paper-based version (N=157) or online (N=121). The final sample comprised 278 individuals who had been bereaved through murder or manslaughter, 233 of whom were female (84%) and 45 of whom were male (16%), with an average age of 60.96 years.

Court and trial processes were reported to be the hardest for those bereaved by homicide to navigate, being more challenging than coronary and investigative processes, which were seen to have fewer negative impacts for the individuals and their families. Different people found different forms of support more or less helpful at different stages post-bereavement. Generally, peer-support and support from family/friends were viewed as being more helpful than support from the police or other criminal justice agencies. The CPS was viewed as the least helpful source of support.

In summary; whilst navigating criminal justice systems and processes can be challenging at the best of times, this research illustrates that when bereaved through homicide these challenges are even more extensive, with a range of substantial and significant factors influencing overall experiences, the impacts of which are extensive and long-lasting.

Ways in which we can better support those bereaved through murder and manslaughter are discussed, as well as how criminal justice processes might be informed and shaped by voices from those with lived experience of homicide from a unique perspective.

KEYWORDS Homicide Bereavement, Criminal Justice System, Lived Experience

AI IMPACT ON PSYCHOLOGY & LAW

TITLE The Effectiveness of AI-Based Scam Alert Systems: An Experimental Study on Preventing Police Impersonation Scams

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effectiveness of an AI-based immediate risk alert system in preventing investigator impersonation scams, focusing on the impact of these alerts on the recipient's level of scam suspicion and anxiety during scam calls. A five-stage scam script based on real investigator impersonation scams was developed, including 'Case Introduction,' 'Crime Involvement Explanation,' 'Involvement Verification,' 'Financial Information Extraction,' and 'Punishment Threat.' Seventy participants were divided into an experimental group (30 participants) who received AI-generated alerts at the 'Case Introduction' and 'Financial Information Extraction' stages, and a control group (40 participants) who did not receive any alerts. The dependent variables measured were the 'Level of Scam Suspicion' and 'Level of Anxiety.'

Repeated Measures ANOVA analysis showed that the stages of the scam speech significantly influenced the level of scam suspicion ($F(4, 68) = 4.64, p = 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.026$). The experimental group that received AI alerts showed significantly higher levels of scam suspicion compared to the control group (mean difference = $-0.772, p = 0.024$). However, the AI alerts did not significantly affect the level of anxiety ($p = 0.574$).

This study indicates that AI-based alert systems can be effective in increasing the suspicion of scam calls, thereby aiding in scam prevention. From an academic perspective, this highlights new research opportunities in behavioral analysis and real-time alert systems using AI technology. Practically, the implementation of such AI systems can serve as a crucial tool in fraud prevention programs, enhancing user education and awareness, and ultimately reducing scam victimization. The integration of AI warning systems can strengthen the fraud response strategies of law enforcement and financial institutions.

KEYWORDS

AI Alert, Scam Prevention, Police Impersonation Scam, Suspicion Level, Anxiety Level

TITLE Do AI-generated images affect laypeople's perceptions of witnesses' statements?

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ABSTRACT The truthiness effect is a well-established phenomenon whereby claims that are accompanied by semantically-related, but otherwise non-probative photos are deemed to be more trustworthy than claims without photos. Truthiness causes problems in legal contexts, as it may bias perceptions of evidence. We conducted one of the first experimental investigations of the truthiness effect in a legal setting, using real statements and AI-generated images from the campaign Exhibit AI (<https://www.exhibitai.com.au/>). In our experiment, participants read two statements made by asylum seekers who documented the conditions they experienced when housed in Australian offshore detention centres. These statements were presented in a randomised order. One of the statements was presented with non-probative AI-generated images illustrating the asylum seeker's offshore detention experience, and the other statement was presented alone. Participants were told that the images were AI-generated. Which statement was accompanied by the AI-generated images and which one was not was counterbalanced. After reading each of the statements, participants were asked to rate the statement on several dimensions, such as their belief in the claims made, their emotion upon reading the statement, their belief in the guilt of the Australian Government, how strong they believed the evidence was, and the actions they would take in response to the statement (e.g., donating funds or sharing a campaign on social media). The findings regarding how the inclusion of the AI-generated images impacted perceptions of the witness statements will be discussed. We hypothesize that ratings of believability, guilt, and evidence strength will be higher, negative emotions would be stronger, and participants will be more likely to act, when the statement is accompanied by an AI-generated image compared to without. Our research will help to determine whether such generative AI images, if used as evidence in legal proceedings, may prejudice legal decision-makers.

KEYWORDS Truthiness, Witness testimony, Legal decision-making, Artificial intelligence, Evidence

TITLE **How visualizing criminal stereotypes can inform legal psychological research and practice**

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ABSTRACT

Past data-driven computational research (Funk, Walker, & Todorov, 2017, C&E) made use of computerized faces to identify the facial features that people rely on when they make criminal character inferences. Using a new methodology (Peterson et al., 2022, PNAS), the present work relied on AI-generated faces to identify people's criminal stereotypes. In addition to using photorealistic stimuli, this project studied the effects of gender and ethnicity on the stimuli level (target face: European/East Asian looking X male/female) as well as on the rater level (participants: British/Chinese X male/female).

Each of the 4800 participants (~n = 300 for each cell) provided 100 unique ratings about how criminal different neutral faces looked. Like in Funk et al. (2017) as well as Peterson et al. (2022), algorithms then identified the facial information that participants used to make this judgment. The resulting face models that visualize criminal stereotypes suggest little evidence for gender differences or effects of ethnicity. I will discuss how the derived criminal face models can be used in legal psychological research and practice.

KEYWORDS **stereotypes, face research, new methodology, social cognition**

TITLE Do AI-generated images affect laypeople's perceptions of witnesses' statements?

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the development and integration of a hybrid chatbot, referred to as ChatCharlie, for quickly gathering initial accounts from eyewitnesses. Based on the UK College of Policing guidance, ChatCharlie has the potential for the timely gathering of investigation relevant information in the absence of a police officer and offers one way to consolidate the memory trace towards robust event recall during a later in-depth interview. Here, we report research evaluating the efficacy and acceptability of ChatCharlie using the mock witness paradigm. Ninety participants were recruited and interviewed across two phases: (1) an initial account interview immediately after the event and (2) a follow-up in-person interview, including a free and cued recall, one week later. In the initial account phase, participants were randomly allocated to either an in-person interview, a ChatCharlie interview, or no initial account interview (control).

Overall, memory accuracy and the amount of correct information recalled in the follow-up interview one week later did not differ significantly, regardless of whether the initial account was collected in-person or via ChatCharlie. However, as expected, both conditions outperformed the Control. There was a non-significant difference for the number of errors, but participants in the in-person condition confabulated more during a later interview than those in the ChatCharlie and control conditions, with no difference between the latter.

Participant perceptions of chatbot usage were positive, revealing comfort and a willingness to engage with ChatCharlie for quickly providing eyewitness information. Participants in the ChatCharlie condition also demonstrated increased ease in admitting memory gaps during follow-up interviews. However, privacy and security emerged as potential concerns, thereby influencing platform preferences and information disclosure behaviours thus highlighting the importance of transparent communication regarding data usage and maintaining public trust. The study paradigm, our findings and implications will be presented and discussed.

KEYWORDS Chatbot, Initial Account, Investigative Interview, Eyewitness, Memory

TITLE **Comparing the performance of a Large Language Model (LLM; ChatGPT) and naive human interviewers in interviewing children about a witnessed mock-event**

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ABSTRACT

The present study compared the performance of a Large Language Model (LLM; ChatGPT) and human interviewers in interviewing children about a mock-event they witnessed. Children aged 6-8 (N = 78) were randomly assigned to the LLM (n = 40) or the human interviewer condition (n = 38). In the experiment, the children were asked to watch a video filmed by the researchers that depicted behavior including elements that could be misinterpreted as abusive in other contexts, and then answer questions posed by either an LLM (presented by a human researcher) or a human interviewer. Irrespective of condition, recommended (vs. not recommended) questions elicited more correct information. The LLM posed fewer questions overall, but a higher proportion of the questions recommended by the literature. There were no differences between the LLM and human interviewers in unique correct information elicited but questions posed by LLM (vs. humans) elicited more unique correct information per question. LLM (vs. humans) also elicited less false information overall, but there was no difference in false information elicited per question. The findings show that the LLM was competent in formulating questions that adhere to best practice guidelines while human interviewers asked more questions following up on the child responses in trying to find out what the children had witnessed. The results indicate LLMs could possibly be used to support child investigative interviewers. However, substantial further investigation is warranted to ascertain the utility of LLMs in more realistic investigative interview settings.

KEYWORDS **Artificial Intelligence, Large Language Model, Child Abuse, Interview**

BIAS EYEWITNESS FACTORS

ORAL PRESENTATIONS | BIAS EYEWITNESS FACTORS

TITLE **Serious Errors in Eyewitness Descriptions: The Effects of Distance, Lighting, and Disguise**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Eyewitness perpetrator descriptions are frequently marked by incompleteness and inaccuracies. However, surprisingly little research has focused on the repercussions of serious descriptive errors on the apprehension and conviction of either perpetrators or innocent suspects.

Objective: The objective of this study was to systematically evaluate serious descriptive errors by having participants estimate, using a standardised scale, the attributes of a mock perpetrator under varying encoding conditions. This approach quantified error rates, aiding in identifying errors that could mislead police investigations, potentially resulting in the wrongful arrest of innocent suspects.

Method: Participants (N = 1325) were sequentially presented with 4 (of 8 possible) live mock perpetrators for 20 seconds each. The mock perpetrators were presented in either optimal or suboptimal lighting, at a distance of 5, 12.5 or 20 meters, and whilst wearing either no disguise, sunglasses, a hood, or a hood and sunglasses. Directly after each viewing, the participants were asked to give descriptive estimates of the of the age, height, weight, gender, and the visual distance to the mock perpetrator. This was also followed by a line-up task. Results: Based on 4456 descriptive estimates by 1325 participants, initial findings show that greater distance and disguise, regardless of lighting conditions, led to higher chances of serious gender estimation errors. However, age, height, and weight estimation errors (± 5 units) were less influenced by distance and disguise, and in some cases, error rates decreased with increased distance.

Conclusion: This study highlights significant errors in eyewitness descriptions. However, defining "serious errors" is ambiguous. For example, errors in weight may not impact apprehension as much as errors in age or gender. Further research is crucial to establish consistent criteria across these dimensions.

KEYWORDS **Eyewitness, Descriptive Reports, Viewing Distance, Lighting, Disguise**

TITLE **Forgotten Benefits of Within-Witness Decision-times as an Assessment Variable**

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ABSTRACT We examine the role of decision times in sequential lineups for eyewitness identification. In particular, we employ a within-witness comparison method, which potentially controls for factors known to make decision times difficult to interpret. Our approach involves comparing decision times for positive identifications against the average rejection times for known-innocent foils within sequential lineups. Here we staged an unusual event, and, one week later, compared identification outcomes from live simultaneous with live and photo/video sequential lineups, using target-present and target-absent lineups (N = 150). Different from previous studies, decision times were inconspicuously measured for each lineup member. Using within-witness comparisons of choosers in sequential lineups, false choices took significantly longer than rejection times of previously shown foils. Additionally, we explored the relationship between decision confidence and response accuracy, introducing a continuous Confidence Characteristic Curve (CAC), finding that confidence and accuracy are monotonically positively related. We did not find an advantage for live sequential lineups over photo sequential lineups but choosing rates were significantly lower in sequential lineups.

KEYWORDS **eyewitness identification, sequential lineup, decision time, within-witness measures, confidence**

TITLE **The Influence of Interracial Contact on Gaze Behaviour: An Eye-Tracking Investigation**

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ABSTRACT

The cross-race effect—recognizing same-race faces better than cross-race faces—is a reliable contributor to eyewitness identification errors, which reflects differences in how people process faces (Lee & Penrod, 2022). Eye tracking indicates differences in gaze behaviour for same-race versus cross-race faces (e.g., Goldinger et al., 2009). However, most studies have compared two races (cf. Stelter et al., 2021), considered White versus Asian/Black faces, examined gaze only during face encoding (but cf. Anzures, 2022), and/or did not consider interracial contact (cf. Burgund, 2021).

We examined the gaze behaviour of White participants ($n = 38$) for different Target Race faces (Asian, Black, Hispanic, Multiracial, White) during encoding (8 female faces) and recognition (8 old, 8 new female faces) using an old/new recognition paradigm. We found a reliable CRE for discriminability of White ($d' = 0.28$) compared to Asian ($d' = 0.27$), Black ($d' = 0.21$), and Multiracial targets ($d' = 0.14$; $ps < .002$), but not for Hispanic targets ($d' = 0.06$, $p = .08$). Furthermore, we found reliable differences in gaze behaviour for same-race compared to cross-race faces, which were in line with the literature and our expectations. For instance, participants made longer and more fixations to same-races than cross-race faces, but this was only true for Hispanic and Multiracial faces during encoding and for Black and Multiracial faces during recognition ($ps < .03$). Furthermore, participants made longer and more fixations to the nose/mouth area of cross-race than same-race faces during both encoding and recognition ($ps < .01$). The presentation will discuss these results, the results for other gaze measures and the role of interracial contact. Our findings are relevant to understanding the mechanisms that cause the CRE under some but not all cross-race circumstances, which, in turn, can help the criminal justice system evaluate cross-race identifications.

KEYWORDS **cross-race effect, eye tracking, interracial contact, gaze patterns, own race bias**

TITLE **Lost in translation: The application of psychological insights on the reliability of witnesses in a legal context**

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ABSTRACT

Much psychological research has been done on the reliability of witnesses, but do these insights find their way to the courtroom and into judgements? This question is addressed in my recently finished legal PhD dissertation. One of my studies concerns eyewitness identification procedures, which is extensively researched by legal psychologists. Therefore, I first conducted an extensive analysis of the literature to describe the psychological insights. Secondly, I researched the Dutch legal framework. Specifically, I conducted desk research and studied legislative history, Supreme Court rulings, the case law of lower courts (approximately two hundred cases), and legal literature. . Thirdly, I compared the legal framework with the psychological insights. This analysis showed that the legal acknowledgement of the studied psychological insights is – to put it mildly – limited. Of course they are not legally binding, but lawyers, legal scholars and judges generally do recognize their existence and importance. These psychological insights are, however, ‘lost in translation’.

In my presentation, I will zoom in on this finding. More specifically, I want to address three issues. First, I want to present the loss. Therefore, I will present some of the identified differences between the psychological insights on eyewitness identification and the forementioned legal approach. Secondly, I will explain the loss. This part aims to provide more understanding and insight in the legal context, the reality of judicial decision making and – most importantly – the legal framework that dictates judicial reasoning. Thirdly, I will share my thoughts on how to minimize the loss and increase the gain. In other words: I will suggest how psychological insights can be incorporated in a more comprehensive and adequate matter in judicial reasoning. My research led me to the overall conclusion that a more risk-based approach clears the path for a reasoned assessment of relevant psychological insights.

KEYWORDS

witness reliability, assessment of evidence, criminal law, evidentiary value of witness statements, judicial reasoning

SYMPOSIA

PRESENTATIONS

**SYMPOSIUM | More Than Meets the
Eye: The Need to Include
Bidirectionally to a Deeper
Understanding Of Intimate Partner
Violence**

Chair(s): Andreia Machado¹, andreia.machado@ulusofona.pt

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TITLE **Who is the victim and who is the perpetrator? The influence of gender stereotypes on bidirectional intimate partner violence**

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ABSTRACT

Intimate partner violence poses significant social consequences for its victims. While numerous studies have highlighted the prevalence of one-sided violence, there is a growing body of research shedding light on the occurrence of bidirectional violence within intimate relationships. However, recognizing this phenomenon proves challenging due to entrenched gender stereotypes that typically depict women as victims and men as perpetrators. Therefore, it is imperative to delve deeper into this issue. This study endeavors to investigate bidirectional violence using three virtual reality scenarios, wherein participants were tasked with identifying the victim and perpetrator, gauging the severity of the violence, and determining the most suitable resolution. A total of one hundred and sixty-two undergraduate students were randomly assigned to view one of the three virtual reality scenarios and subsequently completed a questionnaire. The findings demonstrated that participants considered physical violence more severe than psychological violence, the proportion of violence "female-domination" more severe than "male-domination", judged more the women when initiating the conflict, and did not consider that there were differences in responsibility, seriousness, and severity of injuries in the proportion of violence "male-domination". These results underscore the need to deepen our understanding of this phenomenon, raise awareness, and develop more inclusive prevention and intervention strategies aimed at challenging prevailing gender stereotypes.

KEYWORDS **bidirectional, intimate partner violence, gender stereotypes**

TITLE Exploring the Impact of Mutual Violence on Intimate Relationship Satisfaction

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ABSTRACT

Recent literature suggests that intimate relationships are often characterized by bidirectional violence, wherein both partners perpetrate and endure acts of psychological, physical, sexual, or stalking violence, all of which have detrimental effects. One risk factor frequently cited for bidirectional violence is satisfaction with the intimate relationship—a multidimensional construct defined by the spouses' perception of the relationship through a cost-benefit assessment. This study aimed to explore the impact of bidirectional violence on satisfaction with intimate relationships within a community sample. A total of 767 participants completed an online survey comprising a sociodemographic questionnaire, the CTS-2 conflict scale, and the Kansas Marital Satisfaction Scale. The results revealed that bidirectional violence emerged as the most frequently reported form of violence in the past year, accounting for 50.4% of cases. However, contrary to expectations, this prevalence did not significantly impact satisfaction with intimate relationships, with both men and women reporting similar levels of satisfaction. Psychological violence was the most prevalent typology, affecting 43% of participants, yet it did not exert a significant effect on satisfaction levels. Furthermore, the utilization of negotiation strategies, consistent with previous findings, did not demonstrate a positive influence on satisfaction levels. The high prevalence of bidirectional violence underscores the necessity of better understanding this phenomenon. Additionally, the lack of discernible repercussions on satisfaction levels, despite the pervasive presence of violence, highlights the urgent need to investigate what appears to be a normalization of violence within intimate relationships. Considerations regarding implications and suggestions for future studies will be provided.

KEYWORDS Bidirectional, Intimate partner violence, Marital Satisfaction

TITLE **Do partners agree on their report on intimate partner violence? Insights from a community and a forensic sample**

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ABSTRACT

While widely used, concerns have been raised regarding the validity of the proxy method to assess intimate partner violence (IPV). This is particularly concerning when only victimization experiences are questioned, as it may bias the data on which policymakers, intervention programs, and clinicians base themselves when developing effective strategies to address IPV. Therefore, there is a pressing need to improve the understanding of interpartner agreement when assessing intimate partner violence (IPV) and explore the reliability of the proxy method in different settings.

Using the Conflict Tactic Scales Revised (CTS-2), this work aimed to do so using a community sample of 268 different-sex couples and a forensic sample of 62 different-sex couples involved in the Portuguese judicial system due to an IPV-related crime perpetrated by men. New indexes to evaluate interpartner agreement were introduced and the analyses encompassed various: percent agreement, Gwet's AC1, Tau-b, and Intraclass correlations (ICC), considering both men's and women's perpetration.

The results show that both men and women report victimization and perpetration experiences of different forms of IPV and that interpartner agreement is generally better on the occurrence of IPV than on its frequency in both samples. Interpartner agreement also tends to be higher in the community than in the forensic sample.

These findings emphasize the need for comprehensive IPV assessment practices that go beyond the proxy method and consider both partners' perspectives, particularly in court-related settings, but also to enhance the efficacy of interventions and public policies tackling IPV.

KEYWORDS **Intimate Partner Violence, Assessment, Interpartner agreement**

SYMPOSIUM | Understanding Sex Offending Behaviour

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TITLE **The consistency of distinctive behaviours exhibited during stranger rape offences**

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ABSTRACT

Behavioural crime linkage (BCL) is underpinned by two core assumptions; that an offender's behaviour is consistent enough across a crime series that it can be demonstrably recognised as a pattern, and that an offender's behaviours are distinctive enough other offenders that individual offender behavioural patterns can be identified (Bennell & Canter, 2002). Previous research involving interviewing crime analysts who conducted BCL highlighted the importance of distinctive behaviours in looking for links between offences, given the sheer volume of offences between which they are asked to consider links (for rape offences in the UK this may be as many as 30,000; Woodhams et al., 2019) noting that distinctive behaviour can help to focus their search for potentially linked offences (Davies et al., 2018). During this research, it was postulated by crime analysts that distinctive behaviours demonstrate more consistency across series than other types of offences, because those are the behaviours that are important to an offender (as opposed to more 'functional' aspects of an offence), and that, therefore, effort will be made to replicate them across their series (Davies et al., 2018). While there is some research which speaks to this assertion - for instance, variable consistency has been demonstrated using behaviours deemed to be linked to an offender's inner motivation (Woodhams, 2008) - this question has yet to be explicitly empirically tested. This study aimed to empirically test this premise, using data from the UK's Violent Crime Linkage Analysis System, used by the Serious Crime Analysis Section (SCAS) at the National Crime Agency. Analyses are ongoing and are being conducted to see whether distinctive behaviours are significantly more likely to be consistent than other, more common offences.

KEYWORDS **rape, sex offending, behaviour, consistency, distinctive**

TITLE**A cross-cultural comparison of adult sexual assault committed by strangers: Analyzing similarities and differences in demographics, approach, and assault characteristics between the UK and the US**

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ABSTRACT

Sexual assault is a global issue. Across the world specialized teams collect and analyze data on these crimes to advance national, regional, and local understandings of offender trends, to reform criminal justice responses to protect victims and hold offenders accountable, and to ultimately prevent future crimes. Various studies continue to identify macro, societal-level structures which contribute to these horrific individual-level criminal encounters. However, few compare how sexual assault varies cross-culturally. The objective of this study was to compare UK and US samples of sexual assault offenses to determine similarities and differences in various characteristics of these crimes. Via an international partnership between two specialized research teams, data from each country was analyzed to create comparable case samples and then build equivalent demographic, approach, and assault variables. These paired variables were then analyzed to determine how often certain characteristics were present in sexual assault offenses for both samples. Our results include several comparative descriptives which either aligned or were culturally distinct. We discuss how culturally specific macro-level forces are likely to explain identified differences. Finally, we discuss how cross-cultural collaboration highlighted several limitations to sexual assault data collection and distribution methodologies which render comparative analyses increasingly difficult to perform.

KEYWORDS rape, sexual assault, cross-cultural, international

TITLE **Factors influencing differential engagement with a multiple perpetrator rape: A mixed-methods investigation**

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ABSTRACT

Multiple perpetrator rape (MPR) is an international problem but the instances where not everybody in the group rapes the victim(s) have not been studied. This research investigated those MPRs and the factors influencing the behavioural decisions of those who engaged in non-penetrative sexual abuse. A mixed methods approach was used in three interconnected studies. First, the opinions of 10 expert-stakeholders were qualitatively gathered; the findings informed subsequent studies. Then, 439 UK community adults completed a quantitative survey about the MPR, themselves, and their actions. Lastly, 17 individuals were interviewed about their involvement in MPRs. Analyses involved deductive thematic analysis, frequencies, cluster analysis, and ordinal logistic regressions. The rapes took place in social contexts in inside locations. They involved homogeneous groups of two/three perpetrators (men and women) known to one another against two/three known victims. A three-level taxonomy of increased engagement was found, with highest engagement involving both positive (victim-helping) and negative (facilitatory) actions. Degree and type of participation, including mobility between indirect/ direct actions and positive/negative behaviours, depended on dynamic and interrelated individual-, group-, and environmental-level factors. Over 60% engaged in facilitatory actions (e.g. holding the victim) and non-penetrative sexual acts (e.g. masturbating). 20% passively watched the rape or alternated between engagement and passive presence. Less than 10% helped the victim. Passive and negative engagement were influenced by perceptions of consent, relationship with the victim and group, number of victims and locations, MPR's context and one's level of moral disengagement and MPR proclivity. Differences in the decision-making process of behaviours during and after the MPR were noted. Assessments of safety and self-preservation moderated bystander interventions, but increased fear and compassion for the victim was able to bypass prior considerations and prompt immediate, direct action. The work has theoretical, legal, and practical implications for policing and prevention.

KEYWORDS **multiple perpetrator rape, decision-making, mixed methods, perpetrators, sexual violence**

TITLE “Are we sure that he knew you don’t want to have sex?”:
Discursive constructions of the perpetrator in police
interviews with rape victim/survivors

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ABSTRACT

Recent reports and statistics suggest issues in the Criminal Justice System’s (CJS) treatment of rape victim/survivors who wish to pursue legal action (EVAW Coalition, 2019; Smith & Skinner, 2017; Home Office, 2022). Considerable attention has focused on the possible contributing factors for the high attrition and low prosecution rates for rape. This paper explores police rape stereotype use in interviews with rape complainants from a critical discourse perspective to critique the balance of power within an interview, and how this might impact attrition and prosecution decisions. Ten police interviews with rape complainants were analysed for rape stereotypes: perpetrator related stereotypes were consistent and widespread. These appeared in the form of the interviewer constructing the perpetrator as misunderstanding or the victim/survivor miscommunicating non-consent, or agentless and passive talk. A notable finding was the way constructions interacted with the spectrum of stranger to partner rapes. Constructions within stranger rape cases were often agentless passive talk, backgrounding the perpetrator and foregrounding complainant behaviour. Within acquaintance rape cases, misunderstanding constructions were more frequent, with the focus on visible signs of distress and ‘mixed signals’, with passive and agentless talk. Partner rapes centred on misunderstandings related to the complainant’s knowledge and understanding of consent, coercion vs force, verbal vs nonverbal nonconsent, and the interviewing officer’s ignorance, or lack of knowledge, of perpetrator coercion and other domestic abuse factors. These findings align with findings from Operation Bluestone Soteria (OSB, 2023), thus the recommendations are in alignment with those made by OSB’s Pillar One. They include a more suspect focused investigation, assisted by specialist teams; training with a cognitive framework to address and help interviewing officers understand the underlying mechanisms which perpetuate and drive rape stereotypes; and systems change approaches to the CJS as a whole.

KEYWORDS policing, rape, investigative interviewing, rape myths

SYMPOSIUM | Improving Police Practice

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TITLE Navigating the Individual Culture of Rape and Serious Sexual Offence (RASSO) Investigators: A qualitative analysis of their experiences and socialisation

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ABSTRACT

In England and Wales, two high profile convictions of serving police officers for both rape and murder, have raised serious questions relating to the culture and legitimacy of policing. These sparked the Baroness Casey Review that concluded the Metropolitan Police have widespread “institutional racism, misogyny and homophobia” (HMIC, 2023; pp.17); spotlighting attitudes resulting from the culture that have been commented about in all corners of the countries. These attitudes can produce negative consequences within RASSO investigations, with officers appearing cynical or suspicious leading to victims feeling that they aren’t believed, and some are re-traumatised by this experience. Research on culture more broadly suggests that an individual’s culture is made up of an interaction of both their experience and the collective cultures they are part of (Bendassolli, 2019; Valsiner, 2014). Therefore, to understand police culture, it is important to explore the individuals within police; their backgrounds, motivations and other collective cultures that impact them. There is currently limited research surrounding police culture of RASSO investigators from an individualistic perspective. By conducting reflexive thematic analysis on the data generated from semi-structured interviews with RASSO investigators, this research aims to explore (i) how investigators’ expectations compare to their experiences within policing and the RASSO investigation team, and (ii) how does individual culture interact with police culture.

Themes constructed are: Motivation when joining and remaining within policing, Learning Your Craft, Pressure to Cope, The Importance of Life Experience and Feeling Experienced.

This research will aid in creating a more subjective picture of the police culture of RASSO investigators, through understanding the experiences, socialisation, and culture of one specialised team.

KEYWORDS police culture, rape culture, criminal investigations

TITLE **Impact of Specialism in England and Wales: An Online Survey**

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ABSTRACT The study investigated current, former, and retired officers' opinions of specialism, and explored the interactions between wellbeing, organisational support, and perceived role competence in endorsing specialism developments in England and Wales. The study also focused on participants perspective on the development of specialism for sex offences. Survey questions were drawn from an exploratory review of the literature as well as policy documents and included validated scales relevant to the research objective, tailored to a policing context. A correlational research design has allowed for an in-depth investigation of interactions and casual relationships testing among a range of variables that could be related to a more (or less) successful implementation of specialism. Over 100 police officers completed the survey in full. Participants worked for both specialist and non-specialist units, with crime-specific expertise ranging from terrorism and organised crime to sexual offences. Greater perceived confidence and better overall wellbeing were correlated with higher specialism endorsement and higher force-specific satisfaction. Regardless of specialisms, participants indicated how the level of support received by their organisation is not always adequate or satisfactory. Differences between retired and active police officers were also explored. This study was the first of its kind to take a methodical quantitative approach to specialism in England and Wales and that delved into some of the personal, social, and contextual variables that positively affect it in a policing context. This is in line with evidence from international publications, highlighting positive effects of specialism on officers' efficacy, case handling and specialist skills retainment. We argue that evidence-based findings on the measured benefits of specialism should be considered by officers, forces and members of the criminal justice system when assessing the value of investing in specialism, specifically for underfunded crime types, like sex offences.

KEYWORDS **policing, police specialism, sex offences, officers' wellbeing, Evidence Based Policing**

TITLE **The process of developing a tool for identifying and managing risk in none convicted sex offence perpetrators**

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ABSTRACT

Identifying and managing sex offence perpetrator risk is crucial to policing. Previous research found low conviction rates for sex offence perpetrators, coupled with the use of alternative disruption methods like civil orders being under-utilised. The objective of this talk is to explain how we developed a professional decision-support tool that helps identify and manage risk in non-convicted serious sexual offence perpetrators. As part of the tool officers are signposted to potential disruption tactics, as a way in which they can manage risk. The tool was developed in collaboration with a police force in Wales (Dyfed Powys), the National Crime Agency (NCA) and two universities (namely Bournemouth University and the University of Suffolk). The project involved multiple strands, which encompassed the following components: 1) A literature review of risk assessment tools used in policing in England and Wales for interpersonal crimes (such as rape, sexual assault, domestic violence, and stalking), including evaluations of the tools' reliability and validity. 2) 13 interviews with officers (DIs, DSs, DCIs) in Dyfed Powys (between 40 minutes to 2 hours per interview). The interviews were transcribed verbatim and analysed using a content analysis. 3) Case reviews of 19 redacted adult RASSO cases from the force, half of which were NFAd, and the others submitted to the CPS for a charging decision. 4) A workshop to discuss the findings of the research and present the preliminary tool. This approach meant we were able to build a tool that was grounded in the scientific evidence base but also relevant and nuanced to the needs of officers, thus appropriate for the policing context. Ultimately, this work highlights the benefits of collaborative working between agencies, academics, and practitioners to develop well-rounded novel tools that tackle some of the biggest challenges we face in crime prevention.

KEYWORDS **Risk management, policing, sexual offences, disruption tactics**

TITLE **The Application of Behavioural Crime Linkage in Investigations: An Investigator's Perspective**

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ABSTRACT

Despite a vast number of empirical studies contributing to the theory of behavioural crime linkage (BCL), these studies largely focus on the theoretical and analytical aspects of BCL, with nearly all practical understanding of BCL taken from the perspective of the analyst. This study explores the application of BCL advice from the perspective of senior investigating officers (SIOs). SIOs were interviewed using case studies of serial sex offences where BCL was used to evaluate the practical application of BCL in real life investigations. Thematic analysis identified three main themes: how BCL is integrated in an investigation; officers' attitudes to BCL and facilitators and challenges to using BCL. Novel findings were observed in SIO's utility of BCL advice in providing a focal point in which to explore possible leads and to evaluate risk of the offender, informing investigative strategy. In addition, findings highlighted collaboration and information sharing between the investigative team and analysts as paramount to the efficiency and effectiveness of BCL advice in its application to the investigation. The study's findings offer insights for both practitioners and researchers into how BCL is utilised by SIOs, providing understandings on what works well, what is needed to work well, and where barriers lie from an investigative viewpoint. Understandings provided in this study pave the way for more studies to further explore how BCL is used as a tool by investigative teams and what more needs to be done to improve and increase its utility in practice.

KEYWORDS **Behavioural Crime Linkage, Crime Analysis, Sex offence investigations, Sex offence behaviours**

SYMPOSIUM | Wrongful Convictions **Across Europe**

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TITLE European Registry of Exonerations (EUREX)

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ABSTRACT

The goal of EUREX is to collect data on European cases of miscarriages of justice through an online registry (<https://www.registryofexonerations.eu/>) to inform academics, legal professionals, police practitioners, policy makers, and the public on the number, causes, and consequences of wrongful convictions in Europe. Since its launch in January 2024, EUREX has collected 123 exonerations across 17 European countries. In total, the individuals behind these cases spend 835 years incarcerated for a crime they did not commit with an average of about seven years in prison, mainly based on (attempted) murder or manslaughter and sexual offenses. The analysis of these cases identified five primary contributing factors for wrongful convictions. For example, false confessions contributed to the wrongful conviction in 34% of the cases and false accusations or perjury led to a wrongful conviction in 28% of the cases. Contributing factors also occurred in combination with each other. This presentation will offer an overview of the first findings derived from the EUREX dataset, shedding light on the complexities and trends observed across wrongful convictions in Europe. The following presentations in this symposium will present exoneration cases from Germany, Austria and Sweden. Through an open discussion, we aim to explore both commonalities and discrepancies among these cases with the audience.

KEYWORDS wrongful convictions, exonerations, false confessions, false accusations

TITLE The Peter Heidegger Case

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ABSTRACT

On July 6th 1993, Claudia Deubler, a 28-year-old taxi driver, was shot and killed near Salzburg, Austria. On July 8th, Peter Heidegger, a 19-year-old soldier with prior convictions (non-violent crimes), became the prime suspect after witnesses had placed him in the area. Additional testimonies also added weight to the suspicion: He had no alibi and did not return to his military post the morning after the murder. Furthermore, during a non-authorized search of Heidegger's room, the police discovered a flare gun, which they assumed may have been the murder weapon. However, the projectile that killed Deubler was actually never found.

Initially, Heidegger believed he was arrested and interrogated because of desertion. Only towards the end of the interrogation did detectives confront him with the murder, to which he maintained his innocence. The next day, after a night spent alone in police custody, Heidegger confessed to the murder after being interrogated repeatedly using minimization and maximization interrogation techniques. His confession did not align with any physical evidence, and he retracted it after 14 days. Nevertheless, Heidegger was convicted of murder and armed robbery in 1994, receiving a 20-year sentence. Shortly after the verdict, Daniel Neuwirth, a 16-year-old, claimed responsibility for the crime and also implicated his friend Tomi Schöndorfer. However, the police doubted Neuwirth's testimony due to his substance abuse and mental health issues and his testimony was ignored. Only after persistent efforts by Heidegger's legal team, the case was reopened in 2001. Neuwirth confessed again and also provided crucial perpetrator knowledge. Schöndorfer denied all allegations. Ultimately, Heidegger was exonerated in 2003 after eight years in prison, while Neuwirth and Schöndorfer were convicted in 2007. Witnesses and detectives were investigated for their false testimonies, tampering with evidence, and abuse of authority. All investigations were eventually closed.

KEYWORDS wrongful conviction, false confession, coerced confession, exoneration

TITLE **The Case of Manfred Genditzki**

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ABSTRACT

In 2008, pensioner Lieselotte Kortüm was found dead in her bathtub. After two bruises were discovered under her scalp during the autopsy, the public prosecutor's office assumed a violent crime and brought charges against the former janitor and the victim's caretaker Manfred Genditzki. The court ultimately convicted him of murder, assuming he had motive to cover up the fact that he had embezzled money from her. Later, when it became clear that there was no proof for this, the prosecutor changed the narrative to an escalated argument, which also couldn't be proven. Mr. Genditzki was convicted of murder and his sentence was "life imprisonment" on May 12, 2010.

But he didn't give up. Together with his lawyer Regina Rick, he fought against the verdict. And indeed, according to the latest technology, it contained two errors. A computer simulation proved that both the position of the body in the bathtub and the two bruises could easily be explained by a fall into the bathtub. Additionally, a thermodynamic expert on the temperature of the water in the bathtub narrowed down the time of death so that Manfred Genditzki could no longer be considered the perpetrator, because he had an alibi for that time.

Even this did not impress the Munich Regional Court. It considered the application for retrial to be inadmissible. In this procedural situation, the lawyer Rick turned to the Wrongful Conviction Project Germany, of which I am a board member and supported her in tactical and procedural issues. Ultimately, the Munich I Regional Court ordered a retrial. Manfred Genditzki was then released from custody due to lack of sufficient suspicion in August 2022. In his final trial in 2023 he was acquitted and will be compensated for his time in jail.

KEYWORDS **wrongful conviction, exoneration, innocence**

TITLE The Swedish Quick Case

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ABSTRACT

Thomas Quick - who was born as Sture Bergwall - confessed to over thirty murders between 1993 and 2000 and was convicted of eight of them over the course of six trials in Sweden.

After conviction of theft and aggravated robbery with a hostage in 1991 Quick was sent to psychiatric care. Under the influence of therapy and with almost unrestricted access to drugs, Quick started to suggest his involvement with unsolved murders. Between 1993 and 2000, he confessed to over thirty murders, which he claimed to have committed in Sweden, Norway and Finland. He was convicted of eight of them. All the cases relied solely on his confessions. There was no (forensic) evidence or witnesses in any of them.

All confessions occurred a long time (7-29 years) after the findings of body parts (six cases) or the disappearances (two cases). Moreover, they were well known from the media and Quick was not subjected to restrictions of any kind during his hospital stay: he was able to meet journalists, to read newspapers and have unsupervised leave (during which he consulted the newspaper archives of major libraries).

In this case, there is no documented or even claimed police pressure influencing Quick to confess. He was delivered with the therapy-induced confessions to the police. The current investigations were not broad and unbiased, the investigators and the prosecutor deviated on several occasions from the statutory principle of objectivity.

In 2001, the new chief physician at the hospital terminated all medication. Seven years later, a drug-free Quick withdrew all his confessions. The same year, Quick got an attorney who agreed to work on re-opening the cases. With new evidence and new circumstances— in addition to Quick 's withdrawal of the confessions—Quick was exonerated for each of the eight murders.

KEYWORDS false confession, exoneration, therapy-induced confession

SYMPOSIUM | The Shadow of Doubt: Unraveling the Impact of Wrongful

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TITLE **What do we know about wrongful convictions with prison sentences in Spain?**

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ABSTRACT

Goals: Wrongful convictions have been studied internationally for more than 100 years but have hardly been researched in Spain. This study aims to fill this gap.

Method: We analyzed available judgments from the Spanish Supreme Court that admitted a review appeal to reopen a closed case in which a convicted individual claimed to be innocent. We selected judgments from 1996 to 2022. Trained pairs of coders independently assessed 68% of judgments in several rounds based on an ad hoc drafted coding scheme. The remaining 32% were coded by a single trained person. Krippendorff's Alpha intercoder reliability coefficient was greater than .72 for all categories.

Results: Eighty-nine cases of people wrongly sentenced to deprivation of liberty were identified. Ninety-two percent of exonerees were male. The judgments did not specify the citizenship of 60% of the exonerees; among the remaining cases, only about one half were Spanish. In 36% of the judgments, no information was provided regarding whether the person had criminal records or not. For the remaining cases, 56% of exonerees had criminal records.

Most exonerees were convicted of minor crimes. The most frequent offenses were crimes against property (46%), crimes against public safety (19%) and assaults (17%). Furthermore, 85% of individuals had been convicted of less than 4.5 years of deprivation of liberty.

Professional misconduct explained, at least in part, 64% of wrongful convictions. The second most prevalent factor contributing to wrongful convictions was misapplication of forensic science (27%), followed by misidentifications (17%), false testimony (16%), false confessions (9%), and other causes (13%).

Conclusion: Knowledge about the types of cases and the main causes involved in wrongful convictions could help improve the justice system. The primary solution would be better training for professionals involved in criminal investigations and forensic experts who provide guidance in judicial decision-making.

KEYWORDS **Wrongful convictions, Miscarriage of justice, Judicial errors, Prison, Exonerations**

TITLE **Public perceptions about exonerees: A systematic literature review**

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ABSTRACT

With an increasing number of wrongful convictions being overturned, the number of exonerated persons reintegrating back into society after a (long) prison sentence is also more prominent. In the last decade research has increasingly focused on how exonerated persons experience this reintegration, the obstacles they may encounter and how they are perceived by the community when transitioning back into society. Multiple different reactions are possible: negative perceptions and reactions (e.g. stigmatization and discrimination) as well as positive ones (e.g. support, compensation). However, it is currently unknown which opinions are most prevalent among the public, whether these perceptions differ according to exoneree characteristics or characteristics of the wrongful conviction (e.g. conviction based on a false confession versus faulty eyewitness testimony) or whether differences between jurisdictions can be identified. The aim of this study is to provide a state-of-the-art overview of empirical literature on public perceptions about exonerated persons and identify which gaps remain in the literature. Using a systematic review approach, we searched multiple databases (Web of Science, PsycInfo, Criminal Justice Abstracts, ProQuest and Ebscohost Dissertations) and identified around 25 studies focusing on perceptions of exonerated persons. Results are currently being analyzed and will be presented at the conference.

KEYWORDS **exoneration, public perceptions, attitudes**

TITLE **Forgiven but not forgotten; the effect of gender and crime on perceptions of Australian exonerees.**

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ABSTRACT In 2003, Australian woman Kathleen Folbigg was convicted of killing her four children. 20 Years later she was released from prison and her conviction was quashed. It turned out that her children had most likely died of natural causes, and thus no crime had taken place. Data from the US shows one in three wrongfully convicted women were convicted of crimes that involved harming their children or those in their care. More than 70% of these convictions were based on crimes which never took place, such as mothers being accused of murdering children when their death was an accident or due to natural causes. Less is known about cases like this in Australia, however, some of the most prolific Australian miscarriages of justice involve women being wrongly accused of murdering their children. While exoneration appears to be the fairy tale ending, research shows that stigma and negative perceptions continue to affect exonerees way beyond their release. Our project investigated if factors such as gender and crime type impacted perceptions of exonerees in Australia. Results will be discussed.

KEYWORDS **perception, exoneration, gender**

TITLE Exonerees' reintegration priorities: A qualitative analysis

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ABSTRACT

The negative impact of incarceration on formerly incarcerated individuals is well documented; however, there is emerging evidence that incarceration may lead to even worse outcomes for those who were wrongfully convicted. Upon release, exonerees face numerous difficulties, yet are often not provided with any programming or services to assist them with their reintegration. We conducted qualitative interviews with exonerees (N = 14) examining their post-release experience with attention to their priorities upon release. Using a thematic analysis, we identified three themes: support, deinstitutionalization, and community acceptance. Exonerees emphasized the importance of receiving physical, emotional, and financial support upon release. They also discussed the negative psychological effects associated with their transition from the community to prison, and their unique difficulties adapting to the prison environment. Many exonerees described how the already negative effects associated with their wrongful conviction were exacerbated by a community filled with prejudice and discussed their desire for others to believe in their innocence, and the importance of raising public awareness about wrongful convictions. These findings are important for understanding, and raising awareness about, exoneree's post-release experience, as well as informing policy. Ultimately, it is imperative that post-release programming and services become available for this underserved population.

KEYWORDS**exoneration, qualitative research, post-release experience, psychological effects**

TITLE **Restoring a sense of justice for people affected by wrongful convictions**

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ABSTRACT

Consequences of wrongful convictions are manifold, but have been documented to a lesser extent than its causes. A wrongful conviction affects the person wrongfully convicted (as the victim of an unjust criminal justice intervention and outcome), their dependents and family members, as well as, in cases with an identifiable victim of an actual crime in which there was a wrongful conviction, a victim of a crime. Consequences for the wrongfully convicted person do not only include having a criminal record, which will constrain them before it can be expunged, and having been punished for something they did not do (including incarceration), but also mental harm such as uncertainty, anxiety and depression due to the injustice endured. Their family members are emotionally, socially and financially affected. Victims of a crime in which a wrongful conviction took place may experience setbacks in their healing process upon learning of the wrongful conviction. To complement the connections made with victimological theory by other scholars (e.g., Doyle, 2020; Westervelt and Cook, 2010; Cook, 2022; Jackson et al., 2023), further considerations on how people involved are affected by these injustices will be presented. This presentation will draw on a qualitative, inductive analysis of written and audiovisual accounts in which wrongfully convicted individuals as well as their relatives and, in some cases, victims of the crime in which the wrongful conviction took place, reflect on how they were affected. It will particularly focus on issues experienced during and following the criminal investigation and judicial proceedings, and on justice needs. Collectively, these observations will inform advancing support services and providing relief.

KEYWORDS

wrongful conviction, psychological consequences, restorative justice, victimology

SYMPOSIUM | Police Engagement With The Public in The Community and Online: Technology, Culture, identity and interpersonal relationships

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TITLE **Community and police interactions: Perceptions of terrorism threat**

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ABSTRACT

The majority of terrorism and counter-terrorism research is actor-focused, with attention given to the terrorist and the radicalisation pathway. Insufficient consideration is given to those who suffer most, community members, some of whom change their behaviours due to terrorism catastrophising. Conducted in conjunction with the police, the current study investigated catastrophising with the aim of reducing community member fears about being collateral targets in terrorist attacks. Using the terrorism catastrophising scale (measuring helplessness, rumination, and magnification) alongside measures of anxiety and ethnocentrism, this research sought to examine which members of the public are most likely to catastrophise, and change their behaviour due to perceived terrorism threat, to determine pathways to reduce fear and enhance quality of life. Data were collected from a demographically and geographically representative sample of 1000 members of the UK public. Preliminary analysis shows that certain members of the public are more likely to magnify the threat of terrorism than to feel helpless or ruminate about it and that ethnocentrism features in heightened magnification. More analyses are forthcoming. These early findings have provided support to police officers on their community-based work, for example the importance of integration of community members who hold diverse beliefs in potentially reducing catastrophising about perceptions of terrorism catastrophising.

KEYWORDS **terrorism catastrophising, ethnocentrism, community policing**

TITLE **The Influence of Procedural Justice and Maladaptive Police Behaviour on Citizen Compliance: A Body-Worn Camera Analysis**

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ABSTRACT This study analyses police-citizen interactions captured on body-worn camera (BWC) footage, focusing on procedural justice behaviour, maladaptive behaviour, and their impact on citizen compliance. Through systematic observation of 157 videos, distinctions between interactions involving arrested and non-arrested individuals were examined. Specifically, we focused on police displays of procedural justice behaviours—Participation, Fairness and Neutrality, Dignity and Respect, and Trustworthy Motives—and maladaptive behaviour. Chi-square tests revealed significant differences in displays of Participation and Maladaptive behaviour by the police toward those arrested and those not. Additionally, we investigated the influence of police behaviour on citizen compliance levels during interactions with arrested individuals. Employing mixed-effects ordinal logistic regressions, we found that while Dignity and Respect were initially negatively associated with verbal non-compliance, the introduction of maladaptive behaviour as a model predictor attenuated this effect. Maladaptive behaviour was significantly associated with increased levels of both physical and verbal non-compliance during arrests, while procedural justice behaviours had limited impact. These findings underscore the significance of addressing maladaptive behaviour in police training and highlight the intricate interplay between police behaviour and citizen compliance. The implications of the research are discussed within the context of enhancing law enforcement practices and fostering positive police-citizen relations.

KEYWORDS **Procedural justice, Body-worn camera, Citizen compliance, Police behaviour**

TITLE **Police whistleblowing: A systematic review of the likelihood (and the barriers and facilitators) of the willingness of police officers to report the misconduct of fellow officers**

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ABSTRACT Recent high-profile cases of police misconduct have revealed that fellow police officers were often aware of the misconduct, but remained silent against it, compromising public trust in law enforcement. Here, we systematically review 'police whistleblowing' literature to identify the barriers and facilitators to officers challenging a fellow officer's misconduct. Employing PRISMA guidelines, we systematically reviewed 118 relevant papers, extracting data and coding key variables including who the 'target' of the research was; whether reporting practices were studied, and whether practical solutions were offered. A reflexive thematic analysis was carried out to assess consensus amongst researchers within the literature. Five themes - 1) knowledge and rules, 2) consequences, 3) interpersonal relations, 4) responsibility, and 5) police culture and group relations - emerged as barriers and facilitators to whistleblowing. The review revealed relatively poorer representation of internal police reporting structures and a limited repertoire of practical solutions, with only 40 papers proposing strategies, predominantly centred on training and education. This review also highlights methodological limitations in existing research, with an overreliance on survey methods and a dominant focus on the characteristics of individuals over the structural constraints of reporting. We further note the positive impacts of whistleblowing on policing as an institution and the development of practical strategies to overcome officers' reluctance to report misconduct remain largely unexplored.

KEYWORDS **Police Whistleblowing, police misconduct, reporting barriers, Prereporting facilitators, systematic review**

TITLE **Are you talking to me? A qualitative study of Facebook use by two police forces**

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ABSTRACT Despite social media use by the police increasing in recent years, little qualitative attention has been paid to how online spaces such as Facebook might be important sites for Police Force identity. Such sites warrant research interest as they may play an important role in trust-building and community engagement between Police and the citizens they serve. This presentation qualitatively analyses two stories told (prior to the pandemic) on the official police Facebook sites of a rural and an urban police force. The research explores the collaborative ways in which stories were positioned and constructed collectively by multiple narrators (both formal police posts, and the commenting public). The research found that entitlement to tell particular stories was challenged by the community and raised important questions regarding the perceived ownership of experiences in the criminal justice system.

KEYWORDS **social media, police identity, community engagement**

TITLE Exploring citizen forensics: witnesses, websleuths, vigilantes and the need for multi-directional channels of online collaboration

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ABSTRACT

Ubiquitous and pervasive digital technologies, including social media, routinely record the lives of many citizens. Although location tracking, images and direct reporting can be extremely useful to the police, these tend to treat the public as a 'sensor', providing data that is requested or harvested by law enforcement. This level of public engagement can often be quite different to the way that many citizens want to engage with the police, which can be characterised as 'websleuthing' (members of the public attempting to solve crimes online, often through social media). We developed a model of Citizen Forensics incorporating these different types of police/public engagement and explored the benefits, such as building trust, and challenges, such as the need for specialised skills, in designing multi-directional channels of collaboration. We also explored what happens when the 'sensor' and 'websleuth' approaches collide, including issues such as 'how should the police question a witness who thinks they have already solved the crime on social media?'. Employing a scoping review of digital applications and experiments using the eyewitness identification paradigm, our results suggest that more needs to be done with regards to digital police/public engagement to support empowerment and inclusion and avoid privacy breaches and vigilantism. In addition, policing guidelines for obtaining evidence from witnesses should not treat exposure to passively received old (print, TV) media as the same thing as an active engagement with new (social, online) media.

KEYWORDS

social media, police engagement, community engagement, eyewitness identification, citizen forensics

SYMPOSIUM | New Strategies for Detecting Socially Desirable Responding Assessing the Credibility of Individuals' Reports

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TITLE **Comparing Human and GPT-4 Performance in Scoring
Genuine and Deceptive Memory Reports for Credibility
Assessments**

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ABSTRACT

One of the main areas of research in forensic psychology focuses on investigating human memory and developing methods to assess the credibility of testimonies for application in forensic practice. Typically, experts manually analyse verbal memory reports, assessing their reliability based on characteristics such as emotional valence, and the quantity and type of details provided. However, this evaluation has been criticized for being somewhat subjective, expensive, and time-consuming. The recent advent of Large Language Models (LLMs), i.e., neural networks trained on large corpora to predict the next word given a sequence of input words, has provided new opportunities for the automated analysis of textual data. LLMs (e.g., GPT-4) are indeed able to generate coherent and contextually relevant responses given a specific prompt and can be instructed to simulate human judgments. This study aims to strictly compare the performances of human scorers and GPT-4 in analysing authentic and fabricated memories. Three datasets were examined. The first consisted of 2000 statements collected from Italian participants performing the Autobiographical Memory Task and the Sentence Completion for Events from the Past Test and was analysed for emotional valence and memory specificity. The second included 62 narratives about past holidays (32 genuine and 30 deceptive) transcribed from videotaped interviews. Human scorers and GPT-4 were instructed to extrapolate details along with the Reality Monitoring framework and Verifiability Approach. This analysis was then replicated on a subset of the Hippocorpus dataset, which includes 1000 English-written statements about genuine and deceptive memories from significant past experiences. Results concerning the inter-rater agreement between humans and GPT-4 scoring will be presented and discussed, highlighting potential and limitations of incorporating LLMs into psychological research for a more objective, reproducible, and automated analysis of memory reports.

KEYWORDS **Large language models, Automatic scoring, Deception**

TITLE **Descriptive Patterns of the MMPI-2-RF validity scales in a Large Database (n > 20,000) of Pre-employment police evaluations**

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ABSTRACT

The MMPI-2-RF is a widely used and valid clinical assessment measure for the evaluation of law enforcement. This presentation provides a large (n = 24,649) comparison group of law enforcement officers taking the Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory-2-Restructured Form (MMPI-2-RF) while undergoing pre-employment evaluations in the United States. In this study, we will focus on descriptive patterns observed across the validity scales, highlighting frequencies of elevations and patterns observed across the under-reporting scales. In prior work, L-r and K-r have shown distinct patterns of influence on under-reporting patterns, and latent models evaluating types of under-reporting are needed given the frequency of this fake-good response style within these evaluations. Thus, we will also explore patterns of various types of virtuous victim profiles. We provide frequency and descriptives for each of the over-reporting scales across the non-content (TRIN-r/VRIN-r), content-based (F-r, Fp-r, Fs, FBS-r, RBS, and SOS), and under-reporting (L-r/K-r) scales, replicating prior similar large database analyses. We will also provide exploratory results highlighting the distinct groups observed in under-reporting based on prior research including via latent profile analysis. Partial results related to the descriptive features of VRIN-r and TRIN-r are presented while complete analyses across scales will be presented. Both were highly skewed (2.86 [VRIN-r] and 3.93 [TRIN-r]) as expected with means and standard deviations of 37.12 (6.57) and 51.49 (4.09) for VRIN-r and TRIN-r respectively. TRIN-r had notably higher kurtosis in its distribution (23.88 [SE=.03]) than observed on VRIN-r (10.66[SE=.016]). In 73.2% and 84.9% of respondents produced no instances of incorrectly coded word pairs on VRIN-r and TRIN-r. From these results, both those presented and those which will be, clinicians will be more readily able to interpret the MMPI-2-RF base rate patterns with an additional large sample for comparison.

KEYWORDS **MMPI, Personality Assessment, Police, Validity Scales**

TITLE **Beyond Self-Report Assessment: Evaluating Socially Desirable Responding at an Implicit Level**

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ABSTRACT

A key assumption of self-report questionnaires, the most widely used in the field of psychological assessment, is that respondents accurately report relevant information and engage in providing honest answers. Nevertheless, in some evaluation contexts, such as in cases of child custody, weapon eligibility and personnel selection, it is clear that the person being evaluated may benefit from presenting themselves, voluntarily or involuntarily, in a favourable light. The tendency to provide overly positive self-descriptions is known as socially desirable responding (SDR) and is one of the most pervasive sources of bias in the field of psychological assessment, having enormous social and economic costs, especially in high-stakes evaluative contexts. Nevertheless, despite its impact, the research is quite scarce, and the tools for evaluating it are mainly self-reports, both standalone questionnaires and validity scales embedded in personality questionnaires. Nonetheless, such measures have been questioned for several reasons, including length, outdated formulation, low reliability, and high transparency. Meanwhile, research has shown how certain behavioural indicators, including response time, appear to be very useful in detecting socially desirable response style. The present study, using a simulation design, aimed to assess whether a novel variant of the Implicit Association Test (IAT), the SDR-IAT, may be useful and could be used as an indicator to distinguish between honest individuals and those who try to distort their responses. Participants were recruited and randomly assigned to two experimental groups: in the first group, participants completed a personality questionnaire in a honest manner, and then performed the SDR-IAT; participants of the second group completed a personality questionnaire with the instruction of responding in a SD manner, and then completed the SDR-IAT. Findings in this exploratory study may provide new insights regarding the effectiveness of new methods in assessing SDR, especially useful in high stakes contexts.

KEYWORDS

Socially Desirable Responding, Implicit Association Test, Psychological Assessment

TITLE Dark Tetrad and Faking Behaviour

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ABSTRACT

Personality traits, specifically Narcissism, Psychopathy, Machiavellianism, and Sadism, operationalized as Dark Tetrad (Paulhus, 2015), have been shown to relate to one's proneness to deceptive behaviour (Forsyth et al., 2021). Yet, it is unclear whether that tendency also reflects in one's presentation of health (i.e., faking behaviour). In this study, we investigated a relationship between the four personality domains (narcissism, machiavellianism, psychopathy, and sadism) with propensity to engage in deceiving presentation of health, in a better (i.e., faking good) and worse way (i.e., faking bad). Our student participants were administered measures of Dark Tetrad, as well as of symptom overreporting (Inventory of Problems-29; Giromini & Viglione, 2017) and underreporting (Supernormality Scale; Cima et al., 2003), and were asked about their history of faking behaviour and about their propensity and confidence to engage in such deception in different situations. We anticipate that scores on machiavellianism will be in the strongest association with frequency and success of faking behaviour, regardless of its quality (bad or good).

KEYWORDS Dark Tetrad, Faking Good, Faking Bad, Deception

SYMPOSIUM | Navigating Complexity: Perspectives on Interviewing and Decision Making in Asylum Cases

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TITLE **Challenges in asylum cases with unaccompanied minor asylum seekers in the Netherlands**

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ABSTRACT

Unaccompanied minor asylum seekers are minors below 18 from outside the European Union who arrive in the Netherlands alone, with other minors or with unfamiliar adults. Within the immigration authorities specially trained officials interview these minors and make decisions in their cases. During this process several challenges are encountered. On the one hand this concerns the interview and how to stimulate the minor to tell his story as complete and accurate as possible. On the other hand, this concerns the decision-making process and how to investigate alternative scenarios. In this presentation I will give a brief overview of the empirical knowledge on interviewing of minors and decision making (predominantly regarding criminal cases) and apply that knowledge to the practice of interviewing and decision-making in asylum cases with unaccompanied minors in the Netherlands. I will share observations from training sessions with specialist officials about the unique challenges they encounter.

KEYWORDS

Asylum, Unaccompanied minors, Investigative interviewing, Decision-making, Training

TITLE Experiences with Finnish Asylum Interviews from the
Perspective of Asylum Officials, Interpreters and Asylum
Seekers

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ABSTRACT Despite previous research on investigative interviewing in the asylum context, few studies have examined how the interview participants (interviewer, interpreter and asylum seeker) perceive the interview. Here we explored experiences of asylum interviews from all three perspectives. Additionally, we explored how well interviewers' and interpreters' views and attitudes align with empirical evidence regarding best-practice interviewing. A total of 62 interviewers, 63 interpreters and 55 asylum seekers answered an online questionnaire with open and closed questions about preparation, rapport building, question strategies and overall experiences. We found that the interviewers' and interpreters' views generally aligned with evidence-based guidelines for interviewing (e.g., use of open questions and rapport building). While 96.5% of the interviewers preferred open questions, 39.5% of the interpreters preferred closed questions over open questions. Half of the asylum seekers reported that the questions were almost always or often difficult to understand, and 64.0% were asked the same questions repeatedly. Three fourths of the asylum seekers reported that it felt uncomfortable to open up and talk about their experiences, and 43.0% were unsatisfied with how their account was translated. Interpreters reported that the use of closed questions presents a risk to interview quality that should be mitigated through training to guarantee the rights of asylum seekers. Overall, the current findings help us address weaknesses in interview quality (i.e., asylum seekers misunderstanding) to facilitate valid asylum evaluations.

KEYWORDS Asylum interviews, Investigative Interviewing, Interpretation, Rapport-building, Question style

TITLE Emotional Memories Across Culture

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ABSTRACT Asylum seekers often come from cultural backgrounds distinct from those of the immigration officials who interview and assess them. Yet the impact of culture on asylum seekers' statements has received limited attention. The focus of this study is on the intersection of memory and culture in the context of the asylum determination process. In a pre-registered experiment (N = 168), we examined cultural differences in mock asylum statements, comparing West African participants to a matched Western European control group. Participants were questioned twice about an emotional life event. Their statements were audio-recorded and transcribed. We will code the transcripts for quantitative characteristics such as the number of words and the number of details, and qualitative characteristics such as the content, emotionality, specificity, and self/other focus of the memory reports. We will also code for consistency within a statement, such as the number of omissions, commissions, repetitions and contradictions. Based on existing literature, we predict that the statements of West Africans will be less detailed, less emotional, less specific and more focused on social themes compared to the statements of the Western European control group. In addition, we hypothesize that the reports of the West Africans will be less consistent than the reports of the Western Europeans, because people from collectivistic cultures tend to focus less on presenting a coherent story than people from individualistic cultures do. Statements that are less detailed, less specific, less emotionally elaborate and less consistent may be deemed noncredible, simply because they do not meet asylum officials' expectations of what a genuine statement looks like. Further exploration of and more insight into cultural variations in memory and reporting, specifically about emotional life events, will facilitate the development of culturally nuanced credibility assessment tools.

KEYWORDS Culture, Memory, Asylum seekers, Credibility Assessment

TITLE **The influence of asylum seekers' preparation for their interview on the grounds for asylum on credibility assessment**

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ABSTRACT The criterion-based content analysis (CBCA) is the only credibility assessment technique recognized by Swiss jurisprudence. Although it is employed in interviews on the grounds for asylum in Switzerland, some criteria may not be able to discriminate credible from non-credible accounts in asylum interviews. Asylum seekers who present truthful grounds for asylum have high motivation (i.e. necessity to obtain protection) to prove their refugee status and additionally may receive information about the content of the interviews from their peers and legal representatives. They will likely use this information to prepare ready-made answers to appear more credible. Consequently, their ready-made answers might resemble those of a person presenting a fabricated narrative, which may reduce several criteria's diagnosticity. However, little research has investigated asylum seekers' preparation and its' effect on credibility assessment. We will therefore discuss possible issues related to asylum seekers' preparation for their interview on the grounds for asylum and the use of the CBCA in the asylum context through two study outlines. The first study investigates the extent of asylum seekers' preparation by themselves and by their legal representatives. For this, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with asylum seekers (about whether and how they prepare, e.g., with the help of peers) and an online survey will be carried out with legal representatives to explore the information they provide (i.e. concrete examples of interview questions). The second study examines the ability of the CBCA criteria to discriminate credible from non-credible statements in the asylum context. The CBCA will be applied to transcripts of Turkish asylum seekers suspected of having links to the Gülen movement, the only group of asylum seekers who consistently provide extensive means of proof to support their allegations. We predict that the general credibility score will not distinguish credible from non-credible statements.

KEYWORDS **Asylum interviews, Credibility assessment, Criterion-based content analysis**

TITLE **Digital evidence in asylum procedures: Biases in decision-making**

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ABSTRACT

Digitalization increasingly affects the governance of asylum and humanitarian protection in Europe. Thus far attention for how digital evidence is used in asylum decision-making, and what are the possible risks connected to this, is limited. Better access to information is said to have the potential to improve decision-making and access to protection, for instance by reducing arbitrariness in decision-making. But there are also potential biases that are particular to open-source information (OSINT) and other digital evidence. For example, decision-makers may systematically overestimate the objectivity and probative value of digital evidence. In an experiment among caseworkers of immigration authorities, we assessed how such biases may play out in asylum decision-making. Each participant was asked to read two fictitious case vignettes about respectively the credibility of a story about rocket attacks and the involvement in atrocity crimes. In each case evidence was given that seemed to contradict the timeline in the applicant's statements. We manipulated whether that evidence was digital evidence, collected in open-source research or through data carrier extraction, or witness evidence. Content and probative value of the evidence was similar for both versions. For each of the two cases participants were randomly assigned to one of the evidence conditions. Presentation order of the cases was randomized to control for order effects. Participants were asked to rate the credibility of the applicant's statements and the objectivity and strength of the evidence. Additionally, we asked participants to rate the objectiveness of different types of evidence that may be useful in asylum assessments. Preliminary results will be presented.

KEYWORDS **Asylum, Credibility, Decision-making, Digital evidence, Bias**

SYMPOSIUM | Increasing Inclusivity: Redefining the concept of vulnerability in criminal justice

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TITLE

Identifying and addressing Assessing vulnerability in young unaccompanied minors seeking asylum

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ABSTRACT

This presentation highlights the intersectional vulnerability of unaccompanied asylum-seeking minors.

Asylum seeking minors who are separated from adult carers are required to apply for humanitarian protection independently and must navigate complex legal and social structures to meet their needs. They are recognised as a vulnerable group, but what does 'vulnerability' mean in this context?

A review of published literature in the areas of early separation from caregivers, developmental considerations (e.g. memory, cognitive ability, relationships), exposure to traumatic events and culture.

Drawing these factors together recommendations based on current knowledge on how to best support unaccompanied asylum-seeking minors during interview are discussed.

KEYWORDS

Vulnerability, asylum, child and adolescent

TITLE **Reconceptualising Vulnerability in Police Custody:
embedding the evidence-base in law and imagining
alternative futures**

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ABSTRACT

Vulnerability in police custody is currently understood narrowly, by reference to mental ill-health and mental disorder, with some – but minimal – consideration for circumstantial factors. This definition has been influenced, but not entirely led, by the evidence-base emanating from legal psychology. This paper will offer a critical appraisal of the law vis-à-vis the legal psychology literature. It will do so by synthesising the core findings via an extensive literature review of the legal psychology evidence-base and, within this framework, an analysis of the law, including its substance and shortcomings. It is anticipated that legal protections enshrined in law will be found inadequate when aiming to protect the suspect, the case, and the process. A reconceptualisation of vulnerability is proposed and the paper will offer possible futures for pre-trial proceedings and the broader criminal justice process.

KEYWORDS **Vulnerability, suspects, pre-trial proceedings, police custody**

TITLE **Court and tribunal proceedings involving autistic adults:
Autistic community and justice system professionals'
perspectives**

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ABSTRACT There is little empirical research on autistic individuals' experience of participating and giving evidence in court and tribunal proceedings in the Justice System. Even less is known about the impact and effectiveness of 'Special Measures' - provisions aimed at enabling vulnerable people to give evidence in court and tribunal proceedings. Using qualitative surveys and semi-structured interviews, we examined the perspectives of autistic community members and justice system professionals regarding court and tribunal proceedings involving autistic adults. We recruited a total of 117 participants: (i) 70 autistic adults who participated in court and/or tribunal proceedings; (ii) 12 family members, friends, and/or carers who supported an autistic person through these processes and (iii) 35 justice system professionals who have worked with autistic people in these settings. Analysis of qualitative survey and interview data was conducted using reflexive thematic analysis. Our emerging findings indicate that many autistic people experience profound challenges when participating in court and/or tribunal proceedings. Such proceedings were often described as highly emotionally demanding for autistic people, prior to, during, and after court and tribunal hearings. The experience of participating in and giving evidence in these settings was frequently described as overwhelming; intersecting sensory sensitivity, social-cognition, and communication factors. Participants (across groups) who had experience with Special Measures and other adaptations broadly believed these to be beneficial for autistic people. However, the application of such adaptations was impacted by a range of factors, from autism disclosure to practical implementation. Based upon our emerging findings, many autistic people will require individually tailored support and adaptations prior to, during, and after court and tribunal proceedings. Given that participating in court and tribunal proceedings present often profound emotional, social-cognitive, communication and sensory challenges, many autistic people will be at clear risk of disadvantage when such support is absent.

KEYWORDS **Autism, Justice System, Evidence, Qualitative, Experience**

TITLE **The narrative coherence of autistic children's accounts of an experienced event in response to different interviewer prompts: A longitudinal study**

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ABSTRACT This study explored the narrative coherence of the accounts of an experienced event produced by autistic and typically developing (TD) children (ages 6-15 years) after delays of two weeks and two months. The sample comprised 27 autistic children and 32 TD peers, who were interviewed about the event using the Revised National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD) Investigative Interview Protocol. The study focused on assessing the narrative coherence of children's reports, emphasizing key story grammar elements and temporal features in their narratives. Results revealed that, over time, both autistic and TD children showed a decrease in narrative coherence, although this decrease was more pronounced in certain respects for autistic children. Despite this, autistic children, particularly those who were cognitively and verbally able, demonstrated the ability to convey their experiences coherently, with performances comparable to those of their TD peers. Interviewer prompts differentially influenced the narrative coherence of autistic and non-autistic children's accounts. This research showed that, when questioned appropriately, cognitively and verbally able autistic children can effectively communicate their personal experiences, even after significant delays.

KEYWORDS **autism, narrative coherence, delay, NICHD**

TITLE **Interviewing youth when investigating human trafficking:
Recent developments and calls for future research**

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ABSTRACT

Trafficking in human beings includes a range of different crimes such as for instance labour exploitation, sexual slavery, and exploitation in criminal activities. While there is considerable research and available best practice recommendations for interviewing young victims of abuse, much less research has focused on youth involved in human trafficking. This presentation will provide an overview of recent developments of interviewing young victims, witnesses, and suspects within the context of investigations of human trafficking. In 2024, a handbook on interviewing children in trafficking investigations is to be published, compiling the current knowledge on child interviews adapted to the circumstances of trafficking. Studies have found that children who are heard as victims of trafficking may be reluctant to describe their experiences and there are also concerns that some children who are forced or manipulated to engage in criminal activities by older perpetrators are perceived as offenders, rather than victims, by the criminal justice system. A particular group of concern is child victims of online sexual abuse, who may be faced as responsible for their victimisation by adults and who may experience the criminal justice process as severely retraumatising. An adaptation of the NICHD-R has been suggested for investigative interviews in this context.

KEYWORDS

children and youth in trafficking, child victims of trafficking, child investigative interviewing, child suspect interviewing, investigative interviews in online sexual abuse cases

SYMPOSIUM | Shaping Testimony: The Influence of Psychological and Situational Factors in Investigative Interviewing

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TITLE **Highwitness Testimony: Eyewitness Memory Performance in Cannabis Users when using the Sketch Cognitive Interview**

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ABSTRACT

Previous research indicates that cannabis intoxication may lead to the formation of false memories in eyewitnesses, affecting the validity of their testimony in legal settings. However, thus far no evidence-based interviewing method has been utilized in this context. In this quasi-experimental online study we used a modified version of the PEACE Cognitive Interview with cannabis-using and non-using eyewitnesses, and examined how the timing of intoxication affects memory recall. We tested four groups (total N = 132): regular users intoxicated at both encoding and retrieval (High1), users intoxicated only at retrieval (High2), sober users (Sober), and sober non-users (Control). During an online video call, participants watched a mock crime video, were interviewed with the Sketch Cognitive Interview (Sketch-CI) and completed a target-absent lineup task. The results showed no significant group differences in memory performance, assessed by the number of correct and incorrect details and confabulations, as well as accuracy and completeness. This suggests a beneficial effect of the Sketch-CI in the context of interviewing cannabis-using eyewitnesses. However, higher subjective feeling of intoxication was associated with decreased memory performance, implicating that the individual sensitivity to cannabis effects might determine the level of impairment. Future research is advised to replicate the present findings in a more controlled laboratory setting with an additional control interview condition.

KEYWORDS

cannabis, eyewitness memory, cognitive Interview, intoxication, substance use

TITLE **Enhancing Eyewitness Recall: The Cognitive Interview for Road Traffic Accidents**

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ABSTRACT Previous studies have proven that Cognitive Interview (CI) is an effective method to obtain detailed information details from traffic accident victims' personal experience in Indonesia. The current study aimed to extend this result by examining the accuracy of information obtained through an experimental design, with two recall times (immediate versus one-week delay). Additionally, we assessed whether the CI method could protect against the negative effects of suggestive questions. An experiment was conducted among young car drivers and motorcyclists in Indonesia who had never experienced an accident before (N = 173). Following the viewing of a video depicting a traffic accident, participants were randomly assigned to undergo either a CI or a Standard Interview (SI). Half of the participants were interviewed immediately after viewing the video, while the other half were interviewed one week later. Subsequently, during the final phase of the interview, participants were presented with suggestive questions to examine whether the CI would protect against accepting these suggestions. The result showed that the CI method consistently reported more correct details, particularly the event-related, central, and peripheral details compared to the SI method. Furthermore, participants reported more false details when interviewed after a 1-week delay than immediately. We did not find evidence that the CI could lead to an increase in accuracy nor immunized against the effects of suggestion. This experiment provides additional empirical support for the efficacy of the CI in the context of traffic accidents, particularly in Indonesia.

KEYWORDS **Cognitive Interview, standard interview, traffic accident, time delay, suggestion**

TITLE **Similar Rates of Denial in NICHD and Control Interviews with Alleged Child Abuse Victims in the Netherlands**

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ABSTRACT

In the current study, we examined 38 National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD) interview transcripts, and 30 control transcripts from interviews from an earlier study (Erens et al., 2022) conducted with alleged child victims of abuse at Dutch child protection services. We investigated whether denial and avoidance rates differed statistically significantly based on the interview protocol used. We detected 57 denial and 282 avoidance statements across the 68 interviews. No statistically significant differences emerged between 1) the proportion of denials using NICHD (42%, $n = 16 / 38$) and control interviews (30%, $n = 9 / 30$), and 2) the average number of denial statements between NICHD ($M = 0.84$) and control interviews ($M = 0.83$). Furthermore, denials (and avoidances) were not more or less likely to occur in response to certain types of questions, even though the majority of denials in our sample occurred in response to option-posing questions (60%, $n = 34 / 57$). Denials did occur statistically significantly less often within the first half of the individual interviews in NICHD than control interviews. Our findings call attention to difficulties child protection services face in investigative interviews with alleged child victims.

KEYWORDS

Child Protection, NICHD Interview, Child Abuse, Denial, Investigative Interview

TITLE **Facilitating disclosure: The impact of perceived trustworthiness and rapport on information sharing in remote interviews**

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ABSTRACT Information elicitation attempts increasingly take place remotely and interviewers who build rapport with their interviewees, whether online or offline, tend to elicit more information. While the role of rapport-building in investigative interviewing has been studied extensively, research has only begun to examine the role of trust in information gathering. Recent findings suggest that demonstrating trustworthiness increases information yield in face-to-face interviews. However, this effect has not been systematically compared with a control group, nor has it been replicated. Using a 2 (Trustworthiness: trustworthy vs untrustworthy) x 2 (Rapport-building: present vs absent) between-subject design, we investigated whether interviewer trustworthiness and rapport-building affect the amount of information disclosed in a simulated vetting interview via phone. First, participants (N=178) were asked to imagine that their friend 'John' is applying to be a police officer. Participants were then given information about John's life covering topics such as family, employment, drug use, and addiction history. Using different behavioural indicators in a novel trustworthiness paradigm, the interviewer was manipulated to be perceived as untrustworthy or trustworthy. After completing a manipulation check, participants were interviewed via Zoom (audio only to mimic a phone call), during which interviewers either built or did not build rapport. Lastly, participants were asked to rate perceived level of rapport, tendency to trust, reporting strategies, and attitudes about police legitimacy. It was predicted that interviewees provide the most sensitive information when interviewed by a trustworthy interviewer who builds rapport. Results will be informative for investigative practitioners tasked with eliciting information remotely.

KEYWORDS **trustworthiness, trust, rapport, information gathering, interviewing**

TITLE**The impact of individual characteristics and dyadic personality interactions between the suspect and the interviewer on rapport and investigative interviewing performance: A mock interview study**

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ABSTRACT

While the previous research evidence has demonstrated that individual characteristics can be beneficial for investigative interviewing performance, the role of dyadic personality interactions between the interviewer and the suspect remains unexplored within this context. Previous research has suggested that personality congruence could have significant implications on establishing rapport, since individuals who have similar levels of certain characteristics will tend to communicate in ways that are congruent, thus allowing them to find common ground and effectively establish rapport. Since this has been seldom examined in the interviewing context, the aim of the current study was to address this gap in knowledge. 57 policing students, who have previously received PEACE training, conducted 20-minute investigative interviews with three different mock-suspects as a part of their official undergraduate module assessment. All suspects and interviewers filled out the same pre-interview measures, consisting of HEXACO and Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQue). After the interview was completed, both suspect and the interviewer were asked to fill out questionnaires assessing the perceived similarity with the person they interacted with. Performance was rated by the module lead who administered the training using the PEACE criteria. While the analysis is still in progress, the preliminary findings suggest that the interactions between the suspect and the interviewer's individual characteristics on rapport building and overall performance are complex. Further analysis is pending to examine the effects of perceived and actual similarity in personality characteristics between the interviewer and the suspect. The findings of this study will have significant implications on the recruitment and training procedures surrounding investigative training, as well as important theoretical contributions.

KEYWORDS

investigative interviewing, rapport, individual characteristics, dyadic interactions

SYMPOSIUM | Expert in the Courtroom: From data to case work

Chair(s): Henry Otgaar¹, henry.otgaar@maastrichtuniversity.nl

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TITLE **Memories of sexual abuse in the distant past: Subtypes of (recovered) memories and the number of verifiable details**

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ABSTRACT Academic research has shown that truth tellers include more verifiable details in their report than liars (Nahari et al., 2014; Nisin et al., 2022). Would allegations of sexual abuse based on real experiences also contain more verifiable details than false allegations based on, for example, imagination? In case of a report of sexual abuse, a false allegation is not necessarily due to lying, but can be the result of confusing an internal generated (imagined) experience for an event that truly happened. In general, memories based on true events also contain more details than memories based on imagined events (Johnson & Raye, 1981; Kohnken et al., 1995; Johnson et al., 1988). Based on the works of Geraerts and colleagues (2007) and McNally and Geraerts (2009), it has been suggested that memories of sexual abuse, when recovered through an intentional search process such as psychotherapy, are more likely being false memories compared to memories that spontaneously resurface or continuous memories. Furthermore, case descriptions of recovered memories that exhibit some level of corroboration tend to involve spontaneous recovery (Schooler et al., 1997a; Schooler et al., 1997b). As a result, our investigation aims to determine whether memory reports of sexual abuse, retrieved after an active search process, exhibit a lower presence of verifiable details in comparison to memory reports of spontaneous recovered memories or continuous memories.

Police files of sexual abuse cases are used to classify the statement of the victim in one of 3 memory types: continuous memories, spontaneous recovered memories or recovered memories after an active search process. Independent raters score the independent variable (type of memory) and the dependent variable (verifiable details). The study focus is on the difference in verifiable details between these three between-subjects conditions. Results are expected June 2024.

KEYWORDS **memories, sexual abuse, verifiable details**

TITLE **Wrongful convictions in Belgium: State of affairs and need for progress**

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ABSTRACT Clementina Lyssens was convicted of poisoning her husband. The conviction was based on forensic evidence implicating the presence of arsenic, a deadly poison, in both the victim's biological samples and the coffee mug from which he allegedly drank before falling ill. Despite Clementina's assertions of innocence, the weight of this evidence was insurmountable. She was sentenced to decades of forced labor. However, revelations of fraudulent practices within the forensic analysis, brought to light years later by an assistant of the original toxicologist, ultimately led to Clementine's exoneration. This exoneration case is notable as it is the sole instance in Belgium's legal history and it is almost 100 years old. The European Registry of Exonerations (with cases from 1981 and onwards) reports exonerations in 17 European countries, but none originate from Belgium. Does this mean that Belgium's criminal justice system has been flawless since Clementina? Likely not... This presentation evaluates factors that potentially contribute to the conspicuous absence of exoneration cases in Belgium. We reflect upon the procedure for revision, awareness and education regarding wrongful convictions, and attitudes among legal professionals. This state of affairs is followed by an overview of current (extra-legal) initiatives in Belgium related to wrongful convictions. Lastly, we propose ideas aimed at elevating the prominence of the topic within the Belgian legal landscape.

KEYWORDS **wrongful convictions, benefit of the doubt, Belgium**

TITLE Examining legal professionals' beliefs about dissociative amnesia

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ABSTRACT

The DSM 5 (APA, 2013) describes dissociative amnesia as an inability to recall important autobiographical information, usually of distressing or traumatic nature, which would typically be retained in memory. Nonetheless, the concept of dissociative amnesia, also referred to as "repressed memory," remains contentious, producing significant debate across academic, clinical, and legal spheres. Despite these debates, beliefs regarding dissociative amnesia persist strongly within contemporary society, particularly among clinical professionals (Patihis et al., 2014) and the general population (Mangiulli et al., 2021).

The current work delves into the personal perspectives and beliefs held by judges, prosecutors, and lawyers in Belgium concerning dissociative amnesia. Through an online survey involving 78 Belgian legal professionals, we observed that half of the respondents had encountered cases involving dissociative amnesia at least once in their careers (50.0%; n = 39), with a notable increase since 2011. Furthermore, the majority of participants expressed agreement with notions seen as scientifically dubious, such as the belief that "Memory is capable of unconsciously blocking memories of traumatic events" (84.3%; n = 43) and "Memories of traumatic events, such as abuse, can remain inaccessible for many years waiting to be retrieved" (72.6%; n = 37). These findings shed light on the pervasive presence of pseudoscientific beliefs and convictions regarding dissociative amnesia, even among legal professionals. Such beliefs can yield significant ramifications. That is, the use of such a controversial term in legal proceedings may prompt individuals with a trauma history to perceive their memories as abnormal, potentially resulting in memory reports that deviates from reality (e.g., recovered memories of sexual abuse), thus contributing to miscarriages of justice (Otgaar et al., 2019).

KEYWORDS Dissociative amnesia, Trauma, Memory beliefs

TITLE **Through the lens of legal professionals: Examining the
Smallest Effect Size of Interest for eyewitness memory
research**

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ABSTRACT

Legal psychologists sometimes provide expert witness testimony about eyewitness memory in court. In their testimony, they regularly rely on scientific findings that decision-makers likely assume are practically relevant. However, it is not yet known which effect sizes are large enough to be deemed practically relevant for the courtroom, also known as the smallest effect size of interest. One way to determine the smallest effect size of interest is to engage stakeholders. In two studies, we recruited 97 legal professionals (e.g., defense lawyers, prosecution lawyers, judges) from the Netherlands and Belgium and examined what they consider the smallest effect size of interest to be for eyewitness memory research. The legal professionals in both studies were presented with hypothetical scenarios about an unarmed robbery wherein an eyewitness made different types of memory errors (e.g., misremembering a black gun). Then, legal professionals were asked how many of such memory errors they would allow before taking any legal actions (e.g., “In your opinion, how many of these errors in an eyewitness account would generally lead you to challenge the admissibility of the witness?”). The majority of legal professionals viewed 1-3 memory errors as practically relevant for legal decisions, but this depended on the type of memory error and detail. A nontrivial amount of participants indicated that they would never undertake legal actions after a witness made memory errors. Although these studies provide possible SESOs for eyewitness memory research, we urge that discussions on the SESOI for eyewitness memory research are continued.

KEYWORDS **Smallest effect size of interest, Eyewitness memory, consensus method**

TITLE **How do legal psychologists evaluate the validity of testimony? The importance of the order of evidence**

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ABSTRACT Legal practitioners sometimes ask psychologists to evaluate the validity of statements of victims, witnesses, and suspects. For their assessment, psychologists often have access to different pieces of evidence (e.g., a video recording of the interview, the suspect's statements). The order of examining evidence can affect decision-making. We surveyed 52 legal psychologists about the order in which they would examine the evidence in a statement validity assessment in a specific case. The legal psychologists were instructed that they had to provide expert witness testimony on the validity of the statement of an alleged child victim. The case file included the following documents: a verbatim transcript of the child interview at the police station, an audiovisual recording of the child interview at the police station, and a written statement of the suspect. The experts indicated the order in which they would consider these documents and explained the rationale behind their choice. There was no uniform approach among legal psychologists. About one third of respondents would first examine the audiovisual recording, then the verbatim transcript and finally the suspect's statement. In contrast, about one third would first look at the verbatim transcript, then at the recording and last at the suspect's statement. Our study suggests that legal psychologists lack sufficient knowledge on the importance of the order of evidence, and points to the lack of best practices and standards on the optimal order for examining evidence.

KEYWORDS **Cognitive bias, Expert witness, Linear Sequential Unmasking**

TITLE **Interviewing and interrogation: A review of practice and research from WWII to the present day**

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ABSTRACT Since World War II, interviewing to elicit information during police interviews/interrogations has changed and evolved to ensure scientifically-proven best practice continues. However, although there are international normative legal frameworks that prohibit torture and the ill-treatment of people who are detained, such practices have not been eradicated during questioning by various state agents. In addition, despite decades of empirical and field research to develop effective and ethical interviewing techniques based on psychological science, the global uptake of such approaches has been slow, largely due to scarce resources and, arguably, the absence of effective knowledge exchange between academic researchers and practitioners. This blitz talk will highlight the key, scientifically-proven, interview models that have been developed since WWII and will provide attendees the opportunity to download our new open-access anthology..

KEYWORDS

SYMPOSIUM | Understanding and Addressing Child Sexual Abuse: A forensic look at both sides of the coin

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TITLE **Child Sexual Abuse (CSA) offending patterns heterogeneity: challenges for prevention and intervention**

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ABSTRACT

The complexity of the behaviours that define sexual aggression has led to the need to map these behaviours, as this form of aggression can be perpetrated in person/internet, against adults, or against children and adolescents in a family or extra-family context. The use of these typologies guides the work of professionals who intervene in the various contexts of sexual aggression, analysing the complexity of this criminal phenomenon and identifying groups of individuals based on psychological, family and social characteristics, as well as risk factors for violence associated with criminal behaviour. Typologies can thus guide the definition of intervention plans and the study of recidivism. In the case of child sexual abuse, the complexity of the phenomenon includes motivation and the context in which sexual aggression occurs. This communication presents and compares two typologies of sexual offenders: one that characterises the patterns of criminal behaviour in the sexual abuse of children and adolescents in a sample of 232 offline offenders, made up of four criminal profiles (1. Intrafamilial Criminal Profile - Inadequate; 2. Intrafamilial Criminal Profile - Aggressive; 3. Extrafamilial Criminal Profile - Regressive; 4. Extrafamilial Criminal Profile - Seduction), which distinguishes between sex offenders from an intrafamilial context and those from an extrafamilial context (Soeiro, 2009, 2024); and another, based on a sample of 30 online sex offenders, which identifies three different patterns of criminal behaviour (1. Exploratory; 2. Sexual fantasies/paraphilias; 3. Mixed) (Soeiro & Guerra; 2015, 2024). The results point to the existence of heterogeneous characteristics associated with offline and online sexual abuse, indicating the relevance of variables such as the context of aggression, the severity of forms of sexual aggression and motivations. This multifactorial and typological approach to studying and understanding this reality makes it possible to guide the assessment and treatment of sexual offenders.

KEYWORDS

child sexual abuse, typologies and offending patterns, offline and online sexual abuse

TITLE **Interviewing males who perpetrated sex offenses: Key dimensions**

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ABSTRACT

Child sexual abuse is a significant public health problem with several negative consequences for the victims, their families, and society. The literature indicates elevated levels of underreported sexual offenses, attributed in part to the scarcity of tangible evidence and the lack of testimonies from both victims and perpetrators to substantiate occurrences. This underscores the imperative of conducting forensic assessments where interviews with the perpetrators are pivotal to providing a deeper understanding of the crime. However, research on the topic of interviewing perpetrators of sex offenses is still understudied, with most of the work focusing on developing theories underlying confessions. Thus, a literature review was conducted in order to identify the best practices for planning and conducting forensic interviews with sex offenses perpetrators. Results revealed that five dimensions should be considered when planning for and conducting forensic interviews with perpetrators of sex offenses. These dimensions include: i) introduction and establishing rapport; ii) introducing the topic; iii) eliciting narrative detail; iv) clarification/specific questions; and v) closure. These dimensions are also key elements of the investigative interview. They should be considered to obtain complete, accurate, and reliable information to help the investigation, allow for a better understanding of the case, but also inform the judicial decision-making process. The results of this review provide important guidelines for those who conduct interviews with perpetrators of sex offenses, both in the context of psychological assessment and in the context of criminal investigations.

KEYWORDS **child sexual abuse, forensic interview, perpetrators**

TITLE **Tackling Online Sexual Crimes: Guidelines for Forensic Evaluation**

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ABSTRACT

With the advancement of technology and the widespread availability of Internet access, there has been an alarming increase in sexual crimes against children and youths, particularly in the realms of child pornography and online abuse. This surge has consequently led to a notable rise in legal actions and the number of individuals accused of these crimes. In this oral presentation, we aim to offer guidelines for conducting forensic evaluations of individuals implicated in online sexual offenses against minors. We begin by defining the concept of forensic assessment, underscoring its significance and application within the legal framework, especially in the evaluation of sexual offenders. We then delve into the intricacies of assessing perpetrators who utilize the Internet to commit sexual crimes, addressing the unique challenges and specific guidelines necessary for a thorough evaluation. In discussing the assessment framework, we highlight a holistic approach that includes an in-depth review of history and a critical examination of evidence. This approach considers factors such as the risk of recidivism, motivations, behaviors, and the online impact on victims, alongside the use of validated psychological assessments and information sources. Finally, we propose recommendations for clear forensic reporting, focusing on the effective communication of findings. Through this oral presentation, we aim to shed light on the complexities of forensic assessment in cases of online sexual crimes, contributing to a deeper understanding of virtual crime phenomena and the challenges faced by forensic experts.

KEYWORDS

forensic evaluation, online sexual crimes, child pornography, risk assessment

TITLE **The Effectiveness of Forensic Interview Techniques in Child Sexual Abuse Cases: A Systematic Review**

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ABSTRACT

Child sexual abuse is widely recognized as a global public health problem. The child's testimony is essential to the case outcome, particularly due to the frequent absence of physical or biological evidence. Consequently, the child forensic interview, used to collect the child's testimony, plays a decisive role in criminal investigations. A previous scoping review, developed by these authors, identified, and described judicial procedures for collecting testimony from child sexual abuse victims, employing an evidence-based approach and a structured methodology. Thirty different forensic interview procedures were found. However, the effectiveness of each procedure in collecting child sexual abuse testimony was not assessed. The main aim of the systematic review is to analyze the effectiveness of procedures used to collect child sexual abuse testimony. The systematic review followed PRISMA guidelines and was registered on PROSPERO. Studies were identified through manual reference checking and in four electronic databases: PsycARTICLES, PubMed, SCOPUS, and Web of Science. In total, 95 studies were identified according to the defined eligibility criteria (e.g., empirical studies identifying an effectiveness measure of judicial procedures to collect child sexual abuse victims' testimony). Some of the included studies exclusively analyze a single procedure, while others compare two or three procedures. The outcome measures must be related to interviewers (e.g., the frequency of utterances of each type) and/or children (e.g., the disclosure of sexual abuse; the number of details provided). This review is intended to inform about the most effective and reliable interview procedure and, consequently, contribute to the development of policies and best judicial practices. In order to achieve child-friendly justice, evidence-based recommendations are provided to enhance the quality and consistency of interviews in investigative settings.

KEYWORDS **child sexual abuse, forensic interview, systematic review, testimony**

TITLE **Forensic Psychological Assessment in Child Sexual Abuse Cases: A Scoping Review**

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ABSTRACT

Child sexual abuse (CSA) is a public health concern, with consequences not only for the victims but also for their families and the community. A common definition characterizes CSA as the involvement of a person under the age of 18 years in sexual activity for which he or she is developmentally unprepared and unable to give consent. CSA can therefore be conceptualized as a traumatic experience because of the behaviors and dynamics involved, but also because it occurs at a developmental level of vulnerability, which can negatively affect several areas of the child's functioning. In CSA cases, in addition to the forensic interview to gather testimony, a forensic psychological assessment of the child is often required by the courts, focusing particularly on assessing the credibility of the child's testimony, as well as the potential psychological impact of the abusive situation. These assessments require specialized technical and scientific knowledge on the part of the forensic professionals who carry out these evaluations. However, inappropriate practices are still sometimes used. This can have serious legal implications and lead to secondary victimization of the child. Thus, this scoping review aims to map and synthesize the literature on forensic psychological assessment procedures and instruments, with a focus on the assessment of the credibility of testimony and the assessment of psychological impact. Following the PRISMA-ScR guidelines, the studies were identified through manual reference checking and in four electronic databases (PsycArticles, PubMed, SCOPUS, and Web of Science) and selected according to the predefined eligibility criteria (e.g. empirical studies with children/adolescent victims of CSA). A characterisation of forensic psychological assessment will be presented, including the procedures and instruments most commonly used, the contexts in which they take place, and the professionals involved. The review aims to identify and map the existing knowledge to inform future practice.

KEYWORDS **child sexual abuse, forensic psychological assessment, credibility, psychological impact**

SYMPOSIUM | How Are Parents and Legal Professionals Coping with Psychological Distress Related to Post-Separation Conflict?

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TITLE **How are domains of interparental conflict related to mothers' and fathers' post-separation psychological distress: a longitudinal and bidirectional perspective.**

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ABSTRACT

Using longitudinal data from 1551 parents from Quebec (Canada) separated for less than 2 years and with at least one child under 14 years old, this study used multigroup structural equation model analyses to explore the nature and direction of the association between four domains of interparental conflict (frequency/intensity, covert, overt, children's implication) and parents' psychological distress measured at 3 different measurement points at 2-years intervals each. In addition to these direct associations, indirect associations through various emotional and relational variables known to be associated with post-separation conflict (such as parents' struggles to reach post-separation custody arrangements, parents' level of satisfaction with custody, parents' level of adjustment to separation) were also explored. Results suggest that distinct conflict domains are directly and indirectly associated to psychological distress over time for mothers and fathers. More precisely, fathers seem to be more likely than mothers to be affected in the long term by overt conflict. Moreover, mothers' emotional and relational experience appears to be more significantly associated with psychological distress than interparental conflict. Indirect and bidirectional associations between conflict and psychological distress will be discussed for both parents. Findings from this study allow to better understand how mothers and fathers are impacted by distinct post-separation conflict domains and make it possible to develop interventions tailored to their specific needs. This study also underscores how important it is for professionals to address the psychological distress of parents experiencing post-separation conflict. Clinical implications will be discussed.

KEYWORDS

interparental conflict, psychological distress, parents' adjustment, parental separation

TITLE **A Cross-Perspectives of Parenting Plan Evaluation in Family Matters: Judges', Lawyers', and Evaluators' points of view of the service.**

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ABSTRACT

When faced with high-conflict families that present a variety of complex issues, judges and lawyers can call on the services of an evaluator to facilitate judicial decision-making and highlight the best interests of the child. Appreciated by judges to deal with the parents in a more optimal manner and by lawyers to reach agreements, the use made of parenting plan evaluations and the expectations placed on the evaluators can pose significant challenges to the evaluators themselves and to the legal professionals who use this service (judges and lawyers). Yet, few studies have explored the experience of all these actors in relation to parenting plan evaluations, and their perspectives have not, to our knowledge, been the subject of an analysis enabling them to be linked or contrasted. Based on qualitative interviews, the author proposes to present the viewpoints of 8 judges, 11 lawyers and 9 evaluators (4 psychologists and 5 social workers) working in Quebec (Canada) on their respective expectations and challenges on the use of parenting plan evaluations, and the consequences for families who participate to the evaluation process, which has not been sufficiently studied. The results highlight barriers to the proper use of parenting plan evaluations and reflect a mismatch between the role and expectations of lawyers, judges, and evaluators. Viewpoints of these actors will make it possible to identify the issues specific to everyone in order to suggest areas for improvement regarding the use of parenting plan evaluations and its benefits.

KEYWORDS **Parenting Plan Evaluation, Psychology, Law, Conflict Resolution**

TITLE **Parents' Point of View on Parenting Plan Evaluation: A Deflated Lifebuoy**

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ABSTRACT

Most separating parents manage to establish a cooperative coparenting relationship, at the time of separation or in the years that follow. Multiple psychosocial and legal services are available to help parents who have difficulty achieving this on their own. As a result, very few parents turn to the court to settle various family issues after separation. Those who do, however, tend to experience high levels of conflicts, to present personal characteristics that explain the chronicity of the conflict, and to make more frequent use of psycho-legal services, particularly parenting plan evaluation. It has been established that legal professionals view parenting plan evaluations positively, and that judges tend to follow the evaluator's recommendations. However, very few studies have attempted to understand the point of view of parents who have benefited from a parenting plan evaluation. Using transcripts of semi-structured interviews conducted with a sample of 24 separated parents from the province of Quebec (Canada), this study aims to understand the subjective experience of parents who have gone through a parenting plan evaluation process. The results show that the majority of parents had a bad experience at some point during the evaluation, and were disturbed by the process. Furthermore, they all complained of a lack of psychosocial or legal follow-up after the evaluation to help them implement the recommendations made by the evaluator or the judge's order. This study fills a gap in the scientific literature and offers relevant information needed to improve the psycho-legal services offered to families and, more specifically, the parenting plan evaluation process. The results sound the alarm about this service and offer possible solutions for making changes to improve the experience of parents.

KEYWORDS

Psychology, Parental Separation, High-conflict families, Parenting plan evaluation, Family Law

TITLE **Communication of results following parenting plan evaluations: common pitfalls and writing strategies to avoid them.**

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ABSTRACT

Communication of results and recommendations by psychologists to parents and legal actors following a parenting plan evaluation is crucial in this often contentious process. Despite the significance of these evaluations in determining best interests of children or parenting time arrangements, scant research has been conducted on the importance of this step for the understanding and acceptance of evaluators' recommendations. Studying how evaluators communicate results and recommendations may focus on the perspectives of families involved in parenting plan evaluations or those of evaluators (psychologists, social workers) and frontline legal professionals. Another research avenue is to examine how results of parenting plan evaluations are conveyed in evaluation reports from the point of view of the evaluators who write those reports and the families who receive them. These reports are a crucial communication channel between families, evaluators, and legal actors and often serve as the basis for court-ordered interventions. A focus group with four psychologists, one social worker, and three lawyers was convened to discuss their views on the best practices in result communication. Preliminary data from this focus group were compared with interviews with 24 separated parents who underwent parenting plan evaluations. Results highlight the importance of report writing practices that emphasize a communication style reflecting the diverse and often conflicting voices within the report, of adopting an embodied and affective tone in the report to acknowledge families' emotional strain and distress, and call attention to reflexivity and transparency in the discussion and presentation of results and recommendations. These writing practices are discussed within a performative writing framework which has recently been used to conceptualize forensic report writing. Though further discussion is needed, the communication strategies identified underscore the need to develop sensitive writing practices to enhance the understanding of evaluators' recommendations and avoid causing additional stress to children and families.

KEYWORDS

Psychology, Family law, Parenting plan evaluation, Communication of results, Forensic report writing

BLITZ

PRESENTATIONS

NEW PROCEDURES & LEGAL CONTEXTS

BLITZ PRESENTATIONS | NEW PROCEDURES & LEGAL CONTEXTS

TITLE **The first magnetoencephalography (MEG)-based concealed information test**

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ABSTRACT The Concealed Information Test (CIT) is a well-established method for detecting concealed information. For several decades, researchers have extensively investigated the CIT using various behavioral and physiological measures. Among these measures, the P3 event-related potential (ERP) stands out as particularly valid. While numerous CIT studies have focused on ERPs using EEG (electroencephalography), recent technological advances now enable the examination of the CIT paradigm using magnetoencephalography (MEG). MEG offers several advantages over EEG, notably its superior capability to pinpoint the location of underlying brain activity.

The present study is a conceptual replication of Klein Selle et al. (2021), utilizing MEG instead of EEG. Participants will be initially tasked with providing various personal details before undergoing the CIT. Within the CIT, we will compare two motivational conditions: a classical conceal condition and a novel reveal condition. In both conditions, participants are expected to orient towards the significant personal information, while only in the conceal condition are they expected to inhibit their responses. Consequently, this study will also allow us to investigate the theoretical mechanisms - orientation versus inhibition - underlying the ERP responses extracted from the MEG. Preliminary findings, as well as theoretical and applied implications, will be discussed.

KEYWORDS **Concealed Information Test, Magnetoencephalography (MEG), Event-related potentials (ERPs), Orientation, Inhibition**

TITLE **Reasons for Late Disclosure of Sexual Minority Status in the Asylum Adjudication Process**

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ABSTRACT

Although the Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees does not explicitly refer to sexual orientation as a reason for persecution, it is now widely accepted that persecuted sexual minorities qualify for asylum. Assessing the credibility of such claims to determine whether asylum-seekers meet the criteria for refugee status is a complex task for asylum officials. It is not uncommon that asylum seekers that belong to a sexual minority delay disclosing their sexual orientation, and such late disclosures might be met with scepticism from asylum officials. Here we explored the reasons for late disclosure of sexual orientation in 53 asylum applications. The most common reasons for late disclosures were not knowing that sexual minority was a ground for asylum (45%), not wanting other people to know about sexual minority status (36%), and not feeling comfortable talking about the topic (30%). Worryingly, in 13% of cases, the applicant had tried to disclose in earlier interviews, but had not been given an opportunity to do so; and in 12% of cases, the applicant experienced that the previous interview(s) had prevented them from disclosing. Although there was no association between the reason given and whether the applicant was granted asylum, the number of reasons were positively associated with being granted asylum. We discuss how even well-motivated late disclosures might negatively affect the asylum process.

KEYWORDS **Asylum Adjudication, Interviewing, Decision-making**

TITLE **A New Paradigm to Analyze Confirmation Bias in Legal Practice**

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ABSTRACT Psychological biases are believed to be the intrinsic nature of human beings. Confirmation bias, one of the most well-studied psychological biases, was frequently observed and reported in legal practice (O'Brien, 2009; Rassin, 2018). However, more recent research reported failures in finding confirmation bias in legal decision-making process (Maegherman et al., 2020; Maegherman et al., 2021; Arbiyah et al., 2023). With a closer look into the previous experiment design, we believe that latent flaws in the design of previous laboratory studies that reported the existence of confirmation bias might lead to a misunderstanding of the concept and thus an inaccurate measurement of confirmation bias.

Therefore, we are proposing a novel paradigm to study confirmation bias in legal practice. In contrast to traditional vignette studies in this field, in which participants who stick to their choice are categorized as bias and those who change their selection are recorded as unbiased, we will include an extra group of participants receiving randomized material to represent a bias-neutral control group. Confirmation bias will be quantified based on the difference in-group performance instead of how many participants change their selections. A more accurate measurement of confirmation bias in legal practice could contribute to new debiasing techniques, benefiting legal decision-making process.

This project aims at examining the potential causes of conflicting findings in the study of confirmation bias in legal practice. This blitz talk will present a novel paradigm to analyze confirmation bias and develop debiasing techniques.

KEYWORDS **Cognitive Biases, Confirmation Bias, Debias, Legal Psychology, Legal Decision-making**

TITLE Decoding Recanted Confessions: A Three-Viewpoint Study

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ABSTRACT

The phenomenon of recanted confessions, where individuals retract their previous admissions of guilt, poses intriguing challenges within the legal landscape. Existing research has predominantly focused on this phenomenon within the context of false confessions, exploring various factors that may influence the assessment of their veracity. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that not all recanted confessions are necessarily false; there are instances where individuals retract true statements. Hence the current (ongoing) study examines the phenomenon of a recanted confession considering both true and false admissions.

As a first step in this field of research, three perspectives are explored: lay people, judges, and lawyers, each using a different method. The perspective of lay people is examined with an experiment which tests general evaluations of confessions and the impact of recanting a statement on this evaluation. Secondly, experiences from criminal defense lawyers regarding recanted confessions are examined with semi-structured interviews. These interviews focus on circumstances in which lawyer's might advise their clients to recant a confession and how this might influence the defense strategies. Finally, the way judges deal with recanted confessions is explored by evaluating Dutch jurisprudence. Since the current research is still ongoing only the obtained preliminary results will be shared. By meticulously examining these perspectives, this study aims to enrich comprehension of this phenomenon, ultimately contributing to improved legal practices and the preservation of the criminal justice system's integrity.

KEYWORDS recanted confessions, lawyers, judges

TITLE **Impact of Juvenile Risk Assessment Information and Race on Judges' and Probation Officers' Decisions about Confinement**

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ABSTRACT

Many American youth are confined in out-of-home settings every year based on decisions made by judges and probation officers. Three hundred and twelve judges, court officers, and probation staff participated in an online vignette-based study aimed to better understand practitioners' interpretations and use of juvenile risk assessment tools in their confinement decision making. Results revealed that participants' estimates of the youth's likelihood to recidivate significantly differed with risk level, $F(3, 296) = 71.72, p < .001$. Participants estimated higher recidivism probabilities for White than Black youth across risk levels, $F(1, 298) = 4.17, p = 0.042$. Moderated mediation analyses demonstrated that practitioners' estimations of recidivism likelihood significantly mediated the relationship between the youth's randomly assigned risk level and the decision to revoke probation and confine the youth. While youth's race did not significantly moderate the mediation model, $b = -0.49, 95\% \text{ CIb} [-1.74, 0.47], \text{ SEb} = 0.55, p = 0.47, R^2 = 0.002$, the strength of the indirect effects was significantly affected by the youth's race (White, $b = 3.98, 95\% \text{ CIb} [1.69, 6.92], \text{ SE} = 1.32$, and Black, $b = 3.50, 95\% \text{ CIb} [1.54, 5.80], \text{ SE} = 1.11$) youth. This study suggests that legal decision makers appeared to apply categorical risk assessment data to their confinement decisions with little consistency from person to person, likely impacted by their idiosyncratic interpretations of risk category and by the race of the youth. Risk communication and confinement decision-making implications for legal practitioners and legally involved youth will be discussed.

KEYWORDS **risk assessment, juveniles, race, judges, probation officers**

TITLE **Liberals have Negative Implicit Bias towards Non-Offending Pedophiles**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate implicit and explicit attitudes towards Offending Pedophiles (OP) and Non-Offending Pedophiles (NOP) in US participants, while also assessing the effectiveness of a humanizing narrative intervention in reducing stigmatizing attitudes towards NOP. Additionally, the influence of gender, political standing, and history of child sexual abuse (CSA) on attitudes was examined. Seventy-six participants completed an Implicit Association Test (IAT) and explicit attitude questionnaires regarding OP and NOP. Participants were then assigned to different intervention groups, including a humanizing narrative intervention, passive control, or active control. Attitude measures were repeated post-intervention, and background demographic information was collected. The study found that more liberal participants reported less punitive attitudes towards NOP and were more supportive of rehabilitation. CSA history significantly impacted attitudes towards NOP, with victims reporting more punitive attitudes, perceiving NOP as more dangerous, and being less supportive of rehabilitation. The humanizing narrative intervention had limited effectiveness but resulted in NOP being perceived as less deviant. Surprisingly, implicit attitudes did not correlate with explicit attitudes in liberal participants, suggesting a discrepancy between self-reported attitudes and implicit biases. The findings highlight the complexity of attitudes towards pedophiles, with political standing and CSA history influencing explicit attitudes. The unexpected misalignment between implicit and explicit attitudes among liberals implies that although liberals self-report to have less stigmatized views of NOP, they implicitly have a negative bias towards NOP that does not match up with their self-reported explicit attitudes. As this is the first study to use the IAT as a measure of implicit attitudes towards NOP these results should be further investigated. Although the intervention's impact was not as robust as expected, its effect on reducing perceptions of deviance warrants further exploration, suggesting potential avenues for longer or more targeted interventions.

KEYWORDS **Pedophilic Disorder, Stigma, Implicit Association Test (IAT), Non-Offending Pedophile, Child Sexual Abuse (CSA)**

TITLE **The Impact of Physical Attractiveness, Gender of Defendants and Type of Crime on Sentencing Decisions**

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ABSTRACT

1. Objective

Researching the effect of physical attractiveness on sentencing decisions shows heterogeneous results: attractive defendants are said to receive either more lenient or harsher treatment than unattractive defendants. One explanation given for these contradictions is that the role of attractiveness on sentencing decisions differs depending on whether attractiveness is relevant to the crime. Specifically, across three studies we replicate and extend the classic Sigall and Ostrove study that showed attractive defendants receive more lenient treatment when they commit an attractiveness-unrelated crime (burglary) and harsher treatment when they commit an attractiveness-related crime (swindle). Further, we add the gender of the defendant as an additional dependent variable to determine its effect on sentencing decisions.

2. Methodology

A 2 (Attractiveness: attractive vs. unattractive) x 2 (Type of Crime: burglary vs. swindle) x 2 (Gender: female vs. male) factorial between-subject design was used in all three studies. Participants (N = 429) were randomly assigned to one of the eight conditions. After participants were presented with a picture of a defendant and a fictional case vignette describing the crime committed, they were asked to assign a sentence length to the case.

3. Results

The original findings by Sigall and Ostrove did not replicate. Across three studies, our results showed no significant differences in sentence lengths for neither attractiveness or gender of the defendant, or type of crime.

4. Conclusion

Our findings indicate that attractiveness and gender did not impact on judicial decisions, regardless of whether attractiveness was relevant to the crime or not. In conclusion extra-legal factors did not seem to bias the sentencing decision of participants as had been previously suggested.

KEYWORDS **Physical attractiveness, Gender, Sentencing Decisions, Type of Crime**

INVESTIGATIVE PSYCHOLOGY

TITLE **The impact of authority on the suggestibility and response style of suspects during police questioning**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Individual suspect characteristics can negatively affect the accuracy of their statements provided to the police. One such characteristic is a suspect's suggestibility. Individuals with high levels of suggestibility accept externally provided information (suggestions). Although it is generally accepted that suggestibility plays a role during police questioning, there is little academic knowledge as to its precise effect. Against this background, the aim of the study was to gain a further understanding of a suspect's suggestibility during police questioning. More specifically, it was explored to what extent suggestibility might be mediated by the authority (or lack thereof) of the person questioning the suspect and thus obtaining the suspect's statement.

Methodology: We conducted a pilot experiment to test the impact of authority and suggestive questioning on individuals' suggestibility. A 2 (authority vs. no authority) x 2 (suggestive questions vs. neutral open ended questions) between subjects design was used. Undergraduate criminology students served as participants. The Gudjonsson Suggestibility Scale (GSS) was administered, either by a peer (a fellow student, who is assumed to have no authority over the participant) or by a professor (teaching a course to the participating students). An amended version of the GSS - in which the suggestive questions were reformulated to neutral open ended questions - was administered to the other two groups of participants. Results will be analyzed using SPSS.

Expected results: It is expected that individuals who were questioned by a person without authority and using open ended neutral questions will show the lowest suggestibility scores. Individuals who were questioned by a person with authority and using suggestive questions are expected to show the highest suggestibility scores.

Conclusion: Both the authority of the person questioning a suspect as suggestibility can have a crucial impact on the accuracy of statements provided during police questioning.

KEYWORDS **Police questioning, Suspect, Suggestibility, Authority, Suggestive questions**

TITLE **Cognitions and emotions regarding child sexual abuse –
Implications for designing forensic interview training for
students of police law enforcement service**

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ABSTRACT Cognitions and emotions about child sexual abuse (CSA) have been shown to influence the attitudes of professionals when dealing with suspicions of CSA and when conducting forensic interviews with children who may be affected. The aim of this study is to identify possible differences in the cognitions and emotions associated with CSA among students of police law enforcement service. On this basis, recommendations for the design of their interview training will be derived.

The validated questionnaire "Cognitions and Emotions about Child Sexual Abuse (CE-CSA)" was completed by a sample of N = 210 students of police law enforcement service. The questionnaire consists of three scales: "justice system distrust", "naive confidence" and "emotional reactivity". The findings show that different independent variables (e.g. age, gender, affectedness) lead to different values on the three scales. This provides indications for the differentiated design of interview training to meet individual needs.

KEYWORDS **Child sexual abuse, Forensic interview training, police law enforcement service**

TITLE Cognitions and emotions regarding child sexual abuse –
Implications for designing training and interview training for
school staff

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ABSTRACT Cognitions and emotions about child sexual abuse (CSA) have been shown to influence the attitudes of professionals when dealing with suspicions of CSA and when conducting initial interviews with children who may be affected. The aim of this study is to identify possible differences in the cognitions and emotions associated with CSA among different groups of school staff (teachers, principals and school social workers). On this basis, recommendations for the design of their training will be derived.

The validated questionnaire "Cognitions and Emotions about Child Sexual Abuse (CE-CSA)" was completed by a sample of N = 287 members of school staff. The questionnaire consists of three scales: "Justice system distrust", "naive confidence" and "emotional reactivity".

The results show significant group differences. The three different scales of the questionnaire also show different values for gender and other independent variables. The findings highlight the need for different types of in-service training for school staff to meet individual needs.

KEYWORDS Child sexual abuse, Initial conversation, Interview training, school staff

TITLE **Breaking new ground with the use-the-best heuristic to facilitate deception detection**

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CONTACTS

ABSTRACT

Decades of research have shown that people are poor at detecting deception. Understandably, people struggle with integrating the many putative cues to deception into an accurate veracity judgement.

Heuristics simplify difficult decisions by ignoring most of the information and relying instead only on the most diagnostic cues.

We reported on 9 studies in which people evaluated honest and deceptive statements (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41562-023-01556-2>).

Participants performed at the chance level when they made intuitive judgements, free to use any possible cue. But when instructed to rely only on the best available cue (detailedness), they were consistently able to discriminate lies from truths. The simplicity and accuracy of the use-the-best heuristic provides a promising new avenue for deception research. Breaking new ground, we conducted studies to apply the heuristics in new situations (e.g., presidential lies) and will present the results at EAPL.

KEYWORDS **Deception, Heuristics, Credibility Assessment, Honesty, Details**

TITLE **The effect of priming about false positive and false negative decisions on the perceived credibility in child sexual abuse cases**

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ABSTRACT

Previous studies showed that media coverages about CSA (child sexual abuse) cases Döring & Walter, 2020), victim framing (Flusberg et al., 2022) and priming (Furlong, 2020) might affect the perceived credibility of the victims. In the present study, we primed the participants with 3 different informative texts about the potential biased judicial decisions; false positive, false negative and unbiased informative text in CSA cases before asking them to make a decision about the perceived credibility toward victim of child sexual abuse in a hypothetical scenario and examined the effect of priming on the perceived credibility of children.

The participants read a hypothetical child sexual abuse vignette in which a 10-year-old female child is disclosing a sexual abuse victimization to the participant. The child states her 40-year-old uncle inappropriately touched to her private parts in the kitchen of his home, yesterday. With the aim of investigating the effect of false negative/false positive decisions priming on the perceived credibility toward victims, the researchers wrote 3 different informative texts based on academic writings and scientific information (Cinsel Şiddetle Mücadele Derneği, 2021; Dağlı & İnanıcı, 2010).

The participants were 244 university students. They rated the credibility of the child victim in the vignette by using Child Sexual Abuse (CSA) Attributions Questionnaire (Davies & Roger, 2009), followed by Childhood Sexual Abuse Myths Scale (Koçtürk & Kızıldağ, 2018) which is used as a covariate in the present study.

The results showed that there are no main effects of priming type on perceived credibility while female participants scored higher on perceived credibility compared to male participants. Belief in child sexual abuse myths showed significant negative correlation with the perceived credibility. The practical implications of the result in forensic context will be discussed further.

KEYWORDS

child sexual abuse, perceived credibility, false positives, false negatives, priming

TITLE **A systematic review of trainable personal characteristics in Investigative Interviews.**

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, substantial effort has been dedicated into evaluating and developing training programs in investigative interviews of both children and adults. The use of new technologies such as serious gaming, virtual reality, and AI (e.g., Krause et al., 2024, Li et al., 2024, Haginoya et al., 2023) as well as the evaluation of effective course structures and instructional design (e.g., Cederborg et al., 2021, Zekiroski et al., 2024) have been the main aim of recent developments (Akca, Lariviere, Eastwood, 2021)

More work is needed in understanding the impact of new technologies, course structure, and instructional designs on investigative interviews, however, an area that has been neglected in recent years is how personal characteristic can influence training in investigative interviewing.

Personal characteristics can encompass aptitudes and competencies (Akca, & Eastwood, 2021). Aptitudes, can be defined as having a potential to learn or compute a task (Snow, 1992). Aptitudes can be seen as a more stable concept, making them less prone to modification through short-term interventions, and mostly used as a mere passive measure of interviewer's ability or suitability. Competencies, on the other hand, can be defined as abilities that can be developed through education or training (Akca, & Eastwood, 2021), making them of interest for training programs.

The aim of this study is to conduct a systematic literature review of the current knowledge around the impact of personal characteristics in investigative interviews, with the aim of selecting trainable competences.

A preliminary scoping review showed that some personal characteristics are related to interview performance, however, to the best of my knowledge, no one has looked into variables that can potentially be trained. The results of this study can increase awareness around trainable variables that can influence the outcome of training programs.

KEYWORDS

Investigative Interviews, Training, Individual Differences, Personal Characteristics, Learning

TITLE **The Effect of Volition and Memory Distrust on Eyewitness Suggestibility**

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ABSTRACT It is well established in the literature that eyewitness memory is vulnerable to post-event misinformation. Research has been concerned with understanding the factors that may exacerbate or diminish this effect. The current study explored the influence of volition (i.e., the ability to choose to engage with or avoid post-event information) and memory distrust on individual suggestibility. Participants provided subjective ratings of their memory performance by completing the Memory Distrust Scale ((Nash et al., 2022) before viewing a mock crime video. Subsequently, two-thirds of the participants were asked to express their preference regarding engaging with another witness' testimony. Regardless of their choice, all participants listened to the testimony. Those who preferred to listen to the testimony comprised the volition group, those who would have preferred not to listen comprised the non-volition group and those who were not asked formed the control group. Contrary to our expectations, the results showed that memory distrust did not predict participants' preference to engage with post-event information. Furthermore, neither volition nor memory distrust had an effect on misinformation acceptance. Implications of the results will be presented.

KEYWORDS **Volition, Memory Distrust, Suggestibility**

TITLE Protection against eyewitness memory conformity effect

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ABSTRACT

The memory conformity effect occurs when a witness observes a given incident (e.g. a crime), then talks about it with other witnesses and as a result of such discussion their memories are distorted. For instance, it can happen that a witness, despite seeing a thief wearing a black cap, testifies that the cap was red as this was the information heard from a co-witness. Therefore, this phenomenon may contribute to unreliable testimonies, which remain the leading cause of incorrect court decisions. Consequently, the major objective of the presented research was to test three methods of reducing memory conformity.

240 participants were examined in pairs. To test the memory conformity the MORI technique was used. It allows a pair of participants to sit beside each other, look at the same screen, and not be aware that the other person is watching a different version of the same event. The course of event in both versions was identical except for eight details. In the subsequent stages, the participants discussed half of the dissimilar details thus introduced the mutual misinformation, and then completed the individual test to compare the correctness of answers to the questions about the discussed details (related to misinformation) against the correctness of answers to the questions about the non-discussed details. In the experimental conditions, the individual test was preceded by one of three methods of reducing memory conformity: (1) extended warning against misinformation; (2) training about memory fallibility or (3) a technique that involves demonstrating to participants that their memory is sometimes fallible (inoculation).

It was confirmed that implementation of an extended warning against misinformation eliminated the memory conformity effect, while the application of training about memory fallibility and inoculation led to a reduction (but not complete elimination) of the studied phenomenon.

KEYWORDS memory conformity, co-witness discussion, eyewitness memory

VICTIMS & OFFENDERS

TITLE **The Interplay of Chronic Alcohol Misuse and Facial Recognition Abilities**

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ABSTRACT

Eyewitness testimony and identifications are often a driving force in police investigations. However, it is very common for eyewitnesses and perpetrators of a crime to be under the influence of alcohol. Minimal research has examined the complexity of cognitive impairment as a result of long-term alcohol misuse on facial recognition and eyewitness testimony. Using a 2 (Alcohol Misuse: Alcohol, Control) x 2 (Race: Same, Different) x 2 (Lineup: Target Present, Target Absent) mixed design, we will investigate the effect of alcohol misuse on facial recognition and whether duration of alcohol misuse moderates this effect. Participants will be shown a series of faces during an encoding phase; the test phase will consist of twelve lineups, some with previously encoded faces and others with all new stimuli (Dobolyi & Dodson, 2013). Participants will complete surveys assessing covariates between the two memory phases. Anticipated results will expand on prior research that has shown a main effect of alcohol misuse on lineup accuracy, where lower accuracy for facial recognition is displayed by those who have misused alcohol. Furthermore, we expect that years of alcohol misuse will negatively predict lineup accuracy. Pending results, the present study will inform on the growing body of research that long-term alcohol misuse should be considered when evaluating the credibility of an eyewitness. Data collection will begin soon and conclude in March 2024.

KEYWORDS **Eyewitness Identification, Facial Recognition, Chronic Alcohol Misuse**

TITLE **The Profile of a Child Sexual Offender: Understanding those who sexually offend against children to inform early interventions**

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ABSTRACT For my PhD, I am interested in furthering knowledge and understanding of sexual offenders, with a specific focus on those who offend against children. I will use a mixed methods approach with specific focus on four key areas; sexual fantasies, sexual deviance, cognitive distortions and understanding of consent. The literature has shown that these four key areas are part of the aetiology for sexual offending behaviour and sexual recidivism. The talk will focus primarily on the theory and methodology behind my second study; investigating the differences in cognitive distortion and understanding of consent between 3 main populations; the general public, incarcerated sexual offenders and, non-offending paedophiles.

KEYWORDS **Child sexual offending, Cognitive distortions, Consent, Sexual offending, Non-offending paedophiles**

TITLE **Gendering Narcissism: Different Roots and Different Routes to Intimate Partner Violence**

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ABSTRACT

Despite concerning figures which estimates that 2.9 million males have been a victim of domestic violence since the age of 16 in the UK, surprisingly little is known about the antecedents of violence in females. Narcissism – a personality trait characterised by a lack of empathy, entitlement, and grandiose fantasies – has traditionally been linked to male expressions of violence. However, accruing evidence finds differences in the expressions of narcissism in males (grandiosity) and females (vulnerability), suggesting that the pathways to offending in narcissism may be gendered but have yet to be tested. In this study, we investigated the mediating role of grandiose and vulnerable narcissism in the association between childhood exposure to maltreatment and later partner violence perpetration in adulthood, and the moderating role of gender in these associations. Participants (N = 328) completed scales of grandiose and vulnerable narcissism, perceived parenting styles, and physical/sexual and psychological abuse perpetration. Results indicated that retrospective reports of having mothers who were caring was negatively related to grandiose narcissism for males and vulnerable narcissism for females. Father overprotectiveness was positively related to grandiose narcissism in males. Self-reported vulnerable narcissism was related to greater perpetration of physical/sexual and psychological IPV in females, whereas grandiose narcissism was associated with greater perpetration of psychological IPV in males. For females, but not males, mother care was associated with reduced psychological IPV via lower vulnerable narcissism levels. These findings inform gendered risk markers of narcissism and perpetration of violence for intervention. Legal implications concern the need to review domestic violence legislations and implement gender-neutrality in its definitions, and further inform law enforcement and other public agencies to tackle domestic violence as a human issue and not a gendered phenomenon.

KEYWORDS

Female offenders, Female narcissism, domestic violence, Legislation, Policy

TITLE **What types of rapes are reported to the police? Situational and spatiotemporal factors**

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ABSTRACT

Rape is an underreported crime affecting large populations worldwide. Recognizing obstacles to reporting is pivotal in order to work towards removing them. However, previous results on the factors that could be associated with rape reporting are conflicting. In the present study, we investigated whether situational factors, including victim-perpetrator relationship, and spatiotemporal factors, were associated with rape victims' police reporting in a sample consisting of clients from a Finnish sexual assault referral center. We expected elements of aggravated rape, rapes with characteristics of "real rapes" according to rape myths, and the presence of factors increasing the evidential power (e.g., external evidence), to increase the reporting likelihood. We conducted a cross-sectional survey study and analyzed the experiences of 185 victims. No specific situational characteristics were significantly associated with reporting. However, we found a higher reporting likelihood among victims who had experienced physical violence and/or use of weapons or had been injured if the perpetrator was a stranger compared to a non-stranger. Also, we found that the environment in which the rape took place might influence reporting. The variation we observed in the rape cases suggests that there is no typical rape. The present study is one of few to investigate these factors in Europe and the first in Finland. As we examined a sample of victims who had sought help at a sexual assault referral center, our results are not necessarily generalizable for rape victims outside of this context. Therefore, future research should aim to investigate victims outside the support network.

KEYWORDS

rape, police reporting, situational factors, spatiotemporal factors, sexual assault referral center

TITLE **Simulated Investigative Interviews with Adult Witness Avatars – The Transfer Effect in Real-Life Mock Interviews**

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ABSTRACT Previous studies have noted that investigative interviews with adult victims and witnesses are often of low quality. Research also suggests that interviewing skills improve when the interviewers are given feedback on their performance. We have created a web-based software Adult Witness Avatars (AWA) to simulate investigative interviews with adult victims and witnesses which would help train them question types that will allow the witnesses to recall more accurate accounts. We examined whether avatar interviews coupled with feedback (vs. no feedback) would result in improvements in interview quality of real-life mock witnesses. Half of the 58 participants received process feedback after each of four simulated interviews. The avatars revealed pre-defined memories and made errors as a function of algorithms formulated based on previous empirical research on the response behavior of adult witnesses in experimental studies. Results show that receiving feedback after the simulated interviews increased the proportion of recommended questions (i.e. free recall and open questions) in real-life mock interviews compared to not receiving feedback (67% vs 49%, respectively). Future steps and implications for this type of software in training investigative interviewing skills will be discussed.

KEYWORDS **interviewer training, adult witnesses, serious gaming, feedback, transfer effect**

TITLE**The impact of the form of carrying out procedural activities and the course of criminal proceedings on the risk of secondary victimization among minor victims - preliminary conclusions from file resear**

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the speech is to present the preliminary results of file research conducted as part of a scientific project conducted from July 2023 to July 2024 entitled "The impact of the form of carrying out procedural activities and the course of criminal proceedings on the risk of secondary victimization among minor victims - file research" (MINIUM 7). The aim of the research is to assess the risk of secondary victimization among children who participated as victims in criminal proceedings, both at the preparatory and court stages. The study covered a large area of Poland, where a total of approximately 200 legally concluded criminal cases were examined, in which minors were the victims of the crime. The study covered only cases concerning selected sexual offenses (crimes of rape and other forms of sexual abuse). The research is carried out using an original tool in the form of a questionnaire, which contains a diagram according to which I analyze the files of the investigated cases in the same way. The questions concern, among others: the minor's contact with judicial staff and experts, the participation of the child's representative or attorney in the proceedings, the interrogation activities (number of interrogations, place, conditions and course of activities), the number of activities undertaken with the participation of the child and the persons conducting them. The obtained research results will, on the one hand, allow us to assess whether, in practice, proceedings involving minor victims are friendly to them and whether they may cause the risk of secondary victimization. On the other hand, the study will allow for the formulation of possible de lege lata and de lege ferenda conclusions regarding the provisions that regulate procedural activities affecting the situation of minor victims.

KEYWORDS

Secondary victimization, minor victim, procedural acts, criminal proceedings, file research

TITLE **A trauma informed approach to the sentencing of offenders with mental health difficulties**

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ABSTRACT

This paper, will address, research at the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland and experience as a Defence Barrister and legal teams in the Criminal Courts. A recent report by that Irish Penal Reform Trust (PIPS, 2022) indicated that all incarcerated women in Ireland has experienced trauma, and similar findings were recently presented by McAnallan and McGinnis (2021) . Experiencing trauma has both short- and long-term implications, including an increased risk of those who experienced trauma to engage with risky and violent behavior (Center for Substance Abuse Treatment, 2014) , and thus at increased risk to engage with the justice system. Therefore, it would be wise to assume that most, if not all, of the justice-involved populations have experienced trauma and should be treated accordingly. The paper, will discuss a trauma informed approach, study which takes into account the effects of childhood trauma, on criminal offending with the assistance of forensic psychological assessments, conducted on individuals with criminal charges before the Courts. New evidence, in a study conducted over two years, before the Courts, In a sample size of 100 defendants, almost 93% of defendants, were victims of childhood trauma. In the study, we adopted a trauma informed approach. The focus of this approach acknowledged the depth and extend of traumatic experiences, among our sample of defendants. The defendant participants in the study were asked a series of questions, in relation to their experiences of childhood trauma, and whether childhood trauma was linked to mental health issues in adulthood, and patterns of offending, a collaborative approach with psychology was adopted to address the impact of childhood trauma and patterns of offending. In the cohort, identified as being victims of childhood trauma, we adopted a collaborative approach, between the defence team, and psychologists. As a defence team, necessary Court applications, were made, seeking to instruct Psychological assessments, Court Reports, and Court attendances. The results of the study, demonstrated childhood trauma, impacting on brain development, and their behaviour in profound ways. This in turn was demonstrated to lead often to impulsive behaviour, emotional deregulation, challenges and difficulties controlling emotions, that contributes to involvement in the criminal justice system. The approach taken enabled the Court to tailor appropriate sentences, that benefited the offender, the community, and the victim, and assisted in a restorative justice approach at the sentence hearing. Such an approach, enables the Court to rely on the recommendations of Psychologists, and probation, to engage in a structured sentence approach, that takes into account the impact of childhood trauma on mental health and patterns of offending. The results will be discussed in two case study examples of two defendants, who experienced a completed reduction in offending, through engaging in a structured rehabilitation, that factored into account, the person being seen as a valued citizen in the community as part of their rehabilitation. The overall results of the study demonstrated, a reduction in incarceration, reduced offending and rehabilitation and restorative justice elements.

KEYWORDS

Trauma Informed approaches to sentencing, Forensic psychology and law, Judicial intervention of psychology and law, sentencing options, psychological interventions

POSTER

PRESENTATIONS

VICTIMS

POSTER PRESENTATIONS | VICTIMS

TITLE **Anxiety And Attachment in Adulthood: A Comparative Study Between Victims And Non-Victims Of Bullying**

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ABSTRACT Anxiety plays a significant role in attachment in adulthood, influencing how adults interact with others. Insecure attachment style and anxiety disorder are strongly linked. This study aims to analyze the relationship between anxiety and attachment in adulthood, compare victims and non-victims of bullying regarding anxiety and attachment, and analyze the predictors of anxiety. Participants answered a sociodemographic questionnaire, the Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale, and the Adult Attachment Scale. The sample was collected online and consisted of 86 (39 victims of bullying and 47 non-victims of bullying) participants, with 66 females and 20 males aged between 18 and 62 ($M = 33.01$, $SD = 15.419$). The results showed that anxiety symptoms are positively correlated with difficulty in trusting others and anxious attachment in adults. Victims of bullying have higher scores of anxiety, a greater anxious attachment, and difficulty trusting others. Furthermore, the explanatory model of anxiety using a multiple linear regression showed that difficulty in trusting others, anxious attachment in adults, and sex are significant predictors of anxiety symptoms in adulthood, explaining 28% of their variance. This study highlights the importance of considering attachment in the process of understanding anxiety. Identifying predictors like trust difficulties and anxious attachment can be important to developing effective interventions to reduce anxious symptomatology. Furthermore, reducing bullying victimizations can also be crucial to reducing attachment problems and anxiety in adulthood.

KEYWORDS **Attachment, Anxiety, Bullying, Adulthood**

TITLE **A Rainbow School Programme: Empowering LGBTQ+ Inclusion Through Skills Promotion with Educative Agents**

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ABSTRACT

School environments play a crucial role in inclusion and promotion of success for young people. However, young people who identify with different sexual orientations are constantly at risk of victimization and discrimination at school, at home, and in their communities, resulting in negative academic outcomes and mental health issues, with risks to physical and psychological integrity. Although most episodes of discrimination are carried out by peers, educational agents can also discriminate against LGBTQ students, explicitly and implicitly, through derogatory comments about sexuality and gender expression, contributing to a growing trend of homophobia, biphobia, and transphobia in the school context. In this sense, improving school environments for LGBTQ students should be well outlined by implementing resources that allow for the development of skills, perceptions, beliefs, and attitudes regarding the LGBTQ population. The present study aims to develop and test the effectiveness of a group psychological intervention program, together with EA, to promote school inclusion as a victimization prevention strategy. Adopting a longitudinal design with a quasi-experimental setup, the study will conduct pre- and post-intervention assessments using a protocol that integrates quantitative measurement instruments and semi-structured interviews. The anticipated follow-up, scheduled 6-8 months after program implementation, will provide insights into the stability of the results over time. It is expected that participants will be able to understand the behaviors, vulnerabilities, fears and weaknesses of LGBTQIA+ students, minimizing the risk of victimization in this population on school context, promoting a higher level of literacy in school inclusion of LGBTQIA+ students.

KEYWORDS **Intervention program, Educational Agents, LGBT, Students, victimization**

TITLE Cyber-Violence In Dating Relationships

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ABSTRACT

Background/Aim: In recent years there has been a high level of concern about the use of new technologies and Internet among young people, providing different ways of establishing social relationships, as well as new violence ways. In this sense, cyber-violence in adolescent dating has emerged, a phenomenon that is very widespread nowadays and which has an impact on all levels of people involved. New technologies constitute new tools for harassing, stalking and pressuring current or former partners, with as yet unknown risk factors for victimization. Interest in the study of online violence in adolescent couples has been increasing, however, it is convenient to examine the research methodology that underpins the obtained violence so far. Within this framework, the present study aims to analyse cyberaggression behaviours in dating relationships, as well as any variables that may be involved. Method: A systematic review of the scientific literature has been carried out, analysing 18 articles focusing on this topic. Results: The results showed that cyber-violence in courtship is a social and public health problem that has negative consequences for the involved adolescents, with a high prevalence of victimization by the partner or ex-partner. Additionally, the findings highlight the disparity of results obtained from previous research, referring, above all, to the prevalence of perpetration and victimization (cybercontrol and cyberaggression), frequency, gender differences in these behaviours, as well as the presence of sexist beliefs, romantic jealousy and other manifestations of violence. Discussion: Bearing in mind the limitations of our study, findings are discussed and new lines of research are proposed to examine the variables associated with violence in dating relationships in adolescence and young adulthood, with the aim of promoting action plans to foster healthy and prosocial relationships.

KEYWORDS Adolescents, Victimization, Cyber-control, Cyber-agression

TITLE **Unveiling Dark Traits: Sexting And Online Grooming Among Young Adults**

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ABSTRACT

Young adults frequently engage in Online Sexual Activities (OSA) via Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to maintain intimate relationships and explore their sexuality. OSA encompasses activities such as sexting and online grooming, and the prevalence of these behaviors has surged with the widespread adoption of ICT in interpersonal communication. While the link between personality traits and OSA is well-established, scant attention has been given to the association. The main objective of this study is to characterize the prevalence of sexting and online grooming among young Portuguese adults and examine their potential association with personality traits. Conducted as an exploratory cross-sectional study with a quantitative approach, the sample of the present study included 329 young adult Portuguese individuals, 81.8% female, aged between 18 and 25 years ($M = 20.83$, $SD = 1.992$). 255 (94.8%) of the women admitted to engaging in at least one act of sexting, and 227 (84.4%) of the women reported involving in at least one act of online grooming. 47 (85.5%) of the men admitted to engaging in at least one act of sexting, and 47 (85.5%) of the men reported involving in at least one act of online grooming. Findings reveal a positive correlation between sexting and online grooming. Higher levels of Machiavellianism and narcissism are significant and positively correlated with sexting experience and online grooming experience. Likewise, high levels of psychopathy are correlated with the experience of sexting and online grooming. This study aimed to contribute valuable insights into the prevalence of sexting and online grooming among young adults in Portugal, informing preventive and intervention strategies addressing internet-related risks. Additionally, it is hoped that this research will encourage further investigations into these phenomena within the Portuguese context.

KEYWORDS **sexting, online grooming, Dark Triad**

TITLE **Consistency In Decision Making About State Compensation for Violent Crime Victimization**

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ABSTRACT Every day, decision makers at the Dutch Violent Offences Compensation Fund (VOCF) review and make decisions on applications regarding injuries stemming from violent crimes. They decide whether or not the fund can offer an applicant a compensation and recognition for being a victim. These decisions are based on an evaluation framework in which the decision makers have a discretionary power. The discretion gives room for customization, and thus differences among cases. This is a positive aspect because this way the decision can fit a specific case. However, it can also induce unwanted variability. Meaning, factors that should not influence the decision, do influence the decision. Previous research in several fields has shown that factors that are irrelevant to the evaluation do significantly influence the decision, and that way induce unwanted variability. By researching their decision making process, we aim to investigate whether this is similar at the Dutch VOCF. With this research we intent to contribute to the equalization of the chances on compensation and recognition for victims of violent crimes. We will use several research methods. In this poster presentation we will show results of a registration data research and a brief preview of the results of a vignette study. The analysis of VOCF registration data will focus on percentages of adjudication and denial of applications, per decision makers over a period of several years. In the vignette study, VOCF decision makers decided on the exact same cases without being able to consult each other. The analysis will consist of measuring variability more deeply, and exploring which factors can play a role in this. In line with previous findings in other (legal) fields, we hypothesize that the results of our research will show unwanted variability between decision makers. Additionally, we hope to find some explanations for this variability.

KEYWORDS **variability, state compensation, inter-raterconsistency, (legal) decision making**

TITLE **The Family Centrality and Depression in Victims And Non-Victims Of Interparental Violence**

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ABSTRACT

Family atmosphere in childhood contributes to emotional bonds and values, favoring family members' physical and psychological well-being. In contrast, interparental violence can negatively impact the well-being of children. A hostile family atmosphere can increase the presence of depressive symptoms. The present study aims to analyze the relationship between the centrality of the family atmosphere and depressive symptoms, comparing victims and non-victims of interparental violence. We also intend to analyze the impact of family atmosphere on depression. The sample comprises 240 Portuguese adult participants (57 victims of interparental violence and 183 non-victims) who completed a survey using a sociodemographic questionnaire, the Centeredness Scale, and the Depression Scale. There is a statistically significant negative correlation between family centrality and depressive symptoms. Individuals who had not experienced interparental violence in childhood had higher values of family centrality compared to those who were victims of interparental violence, and victims of interparental violence in childhood had higher scores of depressive symptoms. Furthermore, the explanatory model of depression using a multiple linear regression showed that the family atmosphere is a significant predictor of depression symptoms in adulthood, explaining 21% of their variance. The findings underscore the importance of family atmosphere in shaping individuals' emotional well-being. Harmony in the family environment promotes emotional bonds and psychological health among family members. Conversely, exposure to interparental violence can precipitate depressive symptoms, emphasizing the importance of addressing family dynamics in therapeutic interventions. Psychologic intervention should emphasize family-focused interventions to bolster supportive family environments and mitigate the adverse effects of childhood adversity on long-term psychological well-being.

KEYWORDS **Interparental violence, Family atmosphere, Depression symptoms, Well-being**

TITLE **Tell me why. Perceptions of the reasons for intimate partner violence.**

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the perceived causes of intimate partner violence (IPV). IPV is sometimes legitimized, which is revealed, for example, in the downplaying of violent acts, the perception of violence as an acceptable form of conflict resolution, or victim-blaming. Reasons for legitimization are seen in various factors, both individual and social or cultural. These factors are reflected in narratives about IPV that link it with romantic themes. They appear in the public space regarding journalistic pieces, legal materials, or cultural texts. Therefore, the study focuses on the perception of IPV acts, the descriptions of which are presented in the form of press materials. The respondents read three newspaper articles, among which the key one presented a description of an act of violence between former partners: a male perpetrator and a female victim. The subject of the experimental manipulation was the motive behind the act of violence indicated in the narrative, i.e., romantic vs. non-romantic vs. no information on motive. Subjects who read the description devoid of information on the motive of the violence (n = 62) were asked to speculate on the reasons for the described man's behavior toward the woman. The answers given were analyzed in terms of the categories of reasons indicated underlying the violent act presented. A competent judge unfamiliar with the aim of the study identified the main causes categories indicated by the subjects and then these categories were compared with those distinguished by the researchers. The main threads were: mental disorders of the offender, frustration and problem with emotion regulation of the offender, sociocultural context (nurture, patriarchy, social roles), response to a woman's behavior (jealousy, provocation, disappointment, presumed betrayal). The aforementioned causes are discussed in terms of the presence of IPV legitimization indicators, primarily the lowering of the perpetrator's accountability and victim-blaming.

KEYWORDS

intimate partner violence, legitimization of intimate partner violence, victim-blaming

TITLE Exploring Strategies and Dimensions of Programs
Addressing Online Grooming Among Children and
Adolescents: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

Online child sexual abuse is widespread in contemporary society, owing in part to the growing technological expertise among both children and adults. While significant focus has been placed on intervening with perpetrators, it's imperative to also contemplate measures aimed at protecting children from potential abusers. Therefore, this review aimed to explore the various prevention programmes, interventions and methods designed to combat online grooming, specifically targeting adolescents. By focusing on prevention, intervention and mitigation strategies, the research seeks to systematise approaches to protecting children from these online threats. Databases in SCOPUS ELSEVIER®, ESBCO®, PubMed®, SAGE PUBLISHING® and WEB OF SCIENCE - CORE COLLECTION® were systematically searched for studies published. Studies providing different prevention methods for online child sexual abuse were selected. A total sample of n = 937 and a descriptive approach was used for this study. While the interventions seemed to improve knowledge retainment of online safety, there was no significant change for risky online behaviour. These findings provide specific suggestions for future interventions, particularly those focusing on risky online behaviours.

KEYWORDS online grooming, programs intervention, prevention, child, adolescents

Exploring Strategies and Dimensions of Programs

TITLE Addressing Online Grooming Among Children and Adolescents: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

The full scale invasion of Russia in Ukraine, which began in 2022, has been marked by various war crimes, including instances of sexual violence against Ukrainian civilians perpetrated by Russian troops. Although the Prosecutor's Office of Ukraine had documented 155 cases by January 2023, the full scope of these atrocities remains uncertain due to the ongoing war.

This study aims to investigate how the Ukrainian general population views the victims of sexual violence during the war. We will collect data on socio-demographic variables. To measure attitudes towards rape victims, we will use translated versions of An Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale (McMahon & Farmer, 2011), Attitude towards Rape Victims Scale (Ward, 1988), Rape-Perpetrator Empathy Scale and the Rape-Victim Empathy Scale (REMV; Smith & Frieze, 2003). Specifically for this research new scale called Attitude towards Rape Victims During War was created. The aim of the new scale is to measure publicity, victim blaming, assessing the work of the government and international organizations, society and its influence, personal support for victims, general acknowledgement about sexual violence during war.

Data will be gathered using an online survey, consisting of the above-mentioned measuring instruments as well as some additional questions regarding socio-demographic variables. The target group is Ukrainians over 18 living inside Ukraine. The link will be connected to the REDCap questionnaire containing the informed consent. The aim is to recruit 500 Ukrainian participants all over the world.

The survey will be conducted online, using such platforms as Facebook, Instagram, and other social media channels, with assistance from bloggers. Additionally, the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv will collaborate in distributing the survey. Moreover, to encourage participation, a lottery system has been established. The research budget is 500€. The list of charitable organisations that will take part in the lottery: Ukrainian Association in Finland and Ukrainian Yhdistys Pietarsaassa ry.

KEYWORDS online grooming, programs intervention, prevention, child, adolescents

TITLE **In Their Voices: Perceptions Of Individuals Who Sexually Offended Children About Insight Program**

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ABSTRACT The current literature predominantly focuses on outcome measures when evaluating the efficacy of psychological interventions for individuals who sexually offended children (ISOCs). However, a solely quantitative approach limits the depth of understanding regarding individual experiences and the nuanced processes involved in therapeutic transformations. To address this gap, semi-structured interviews were conducted with nine ISOCs who had completed a newly implemented structured and manualized individual program based on schema theory in Portugal. Employing content analysis, this study explored the participants' perceptions of the treatment. The analysis revealed 141 units related to the process of change and 719 units concerning perceptions of the impact and effectiveness of the program itself. The process of change category encompassed three subcategories: feelings, knowledge, and motivations. Additionally, the impact and evaluation of the program were represented by two subcategories: impact and program evaluation. Overall, participants reported positive outcomes associated with the Insight Program, underscoring the importance of addressing early maladaptive schemas to enhance intervention efficacy. Furthermore, participants identified the therapists' characteristics as critical factors in preventing dropout and facilitating knowledge acquisition. The implications of these findings are discussed in terms of potential enhancements to the program and broader implications for psychological interventions targeting perpetrators of child sexual abuse.

KEYWORDS **sex offending treatment, qualitative research, perpetrators' perceptions, schema therapy, INSIGHT Program**

TITLE Exploring Forgiveness Therapy with Jewish Theological Insights Among Addicts

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ABSTRACT

The intertwining of religions with cultures will continue to hold significant sway, demanding thoughtful integration into therapeutic approaches. Judaism, revered as one of the oldest faiths, will encompass a wealth of theoretical and practical wisdom applicable to mental health interventions. This study will delve into the efficacy of forgiveness therapy infused with Jewish theological perspectives, drawing from Enright's social scientific forgiveness therapy model. By delving into Jewish scriptures and interpretations, we will illuminate the transformative principles associated with forgiveness. The effectiveness of this therapeutic approach will be exemplified through its implementation within the "Returno" therapeutic community for addicts in Israel, operating within the Jewish framework. Quantitative research findings will be presented, showcasing how individuals undergoing forgiveness therapy within this context will report enhancements in psychological well-being.

KEYWORDS Worgiveness, Well-being, Addicts

TITLE **Type Of Offense Effects Attitudes Towards Restorative Justice**

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ABSTRACT

Objective of the study

Restorative justice (RJ) is an approach to justice in which the responses to a crime is primarily oriented towards repairing individual, relational, and social harm. A restorative justice program aims to get offenders to take responsibility for their actions, to understand the harm they have caused, to give them an opportunity to redeem themselves and to discourage them from causing further harm. This study examined, for the first time, the relationship between type of offense and public attitudes towards RJ, as well as the psychological mechanisms that explain this relationship. Specifically, we examined a model of three offense types (sexual, violent and property offenses) and their differential effects on such attitudes, including whether this relationship is mediated by belief in malleability, fear of crime, and perceived seriousness of the offense.

Methodology

Participants (N=608) read a definition of one offense and completed a short survey regarding malleability beliefs, fear of crime, perceived seriousness of the offense and their attitudes toward RJ.

Results Obtained and Conclusion

The findings indicate differences between offense types in malleability beliefs and attitudes towards RJ, so that for both variables the sex offense type was the lowest followed by the violent offense and finally the property offense type. Additionally, the findings indicate an indirect effect of offense type on attitudes toward RJ through malleability beliefs, and not through fear or perceived seriousness.

KEYWORDS **Restorative Justice, Offense Type, Public Attitudes, Prisons**

TITLE **Adverse And Benevolent Childhood Experiences and Anxiety
In Adulthood: A Comparative Study Between Victims And
Non-Victims Of Sexual Abuse**

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ABSTRACT

Childhood adverse experiences (ACEs) are traumatic experiences during the child's development, such as sexual abuse (SA). SA can lead to severe consequences (e.g., shame, anxiety) with adverse outcomes throughout life. On the other hand, the presence of benevolent childhood experiences (BCEs) (e.g., interpersonal support and positive self-perception) can mitigate the negative repercussions of ACE, increasing mental health in adulthood. The present study aims to analyze the relationship between SA and other ACEs and compare victims and non-victims of SA regarding ACEs, BCEs, and anxiety in adulthood. The sample comprised 168 Portuguese adults of both sexes, 30 (17.9%) victims of SA, with ages between 19 and 76. Participants answered online a sociodemographic questionnaire, a victimization checklist, the Childhood Adverse Experiences Questionnaire, the Benevolent Childhood Experiences Scale, and the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Egas Moniz School of Health and Science and followed the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. The results showed that SA is positively correlated with physical abuse, physical negligence, family dysfunction, and total ACEs. Participants who experienced SA reported more physical abuse, emotional and physical negligence, as well as more types of ACEs than non-victims of SA. Victims of SA also reported fewer positive experiences in childhood and more symptoms of anxiety. These findings demonstrate an association between several types of victimization, also showing that victims of SA show more anxiety symptoms than non-victims, possibly due to a tendency to have less BCEs. This study emphasizes the need to develop awareness-raising campaigns and prevention programs in SA that highlight the importance of experiencing more BCEs. This can be accomplished through family support, reducing victimization and lowering anxiety, and enhancing the quality of life in adulthood.

KEYWORDS

Sexual Abuse, Adverse Childhood Experiences, Benevolent Childhood Experiences, Anxiety

TITLE **Stalking Victimization in Adulthood: The Link With Adverse Childhood Experiences, Anxiety, And Stress**

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ABSTRACT Childhood is one of the most structuring stages throughout the life cycle and is influenced by several experiences, particularly adverse ones. Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) are potentially traumatic events with adverse outcomes on the individual's health, well-being, and quality of life. Experiencing these events can impact an individual's development at several levels, making them more vulnerable to being victimized by different crimes in adulthood, such as stalking. Since stalking is an unpredictable threat, it can lead victims to become hypervigilant and chronically fearful, increasing their levels of anxiety and stress, and deteriorating their psychological and social functioning. This study aimed to analyze the link between ACEs, anxiety, and stress and the differences between victims and non-victims of stalking regarding ACEs, anxiety, and stress. The sample comprised 218 participants (171 women and 47 men, 40 stalking victims) aged 18 to 76 ($M=34.74$, $SD=14.164$). The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Egas Moniz School of Health and Science and followed the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. Participants answered the sociodemographic questionnaire, the victimization checklist of stalking, the Adverse Childhood Experiences Questionnaire, and the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale. The results showed that ACEs are related to higher scores of stress and anxiety. Furthermore, victims of stalking were more likely to experience emotional abuse, sexual abuse, emotional neglect, physical neglect, family dysfunction, and other childhood adversity and to show high levels of anxiety and stress. This study promotes a better understanding of the link between ACEs, stalking victimization, and increasing levels of anxiety and stress. It can also be an important result to develop better intervention programs to mitigate the effects of ACEs, prevent stalking victimization in adulthood, reduce the victim's symptoms, and promote better well-being when stalking victimization has already occurred.

KEYWORDS **adverse childhood experiences, stalking, adulthood, stress, anxiety**

TITLE **The Impact of Interparental Violence On Affective Lability**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Interparental violence (IV) is the verbal, physical, and emotional aggression between parents, which will influence physical and psychological behavior toward the child or adolescent. IV affects different levels of the child's development (e.g., emotional and psychological) and can have long-lasting consequences for psychological adjustment in adult life. Being exposed to violence as an adverse experience as a child can result in deficient regulation of emotions or affective lability (AL). AL is the frequency, intensity, and speed of variation in the various emotional states, causing inappropriate reactions to the stimulus that triggered emotions, and is an important indicator of socioemotional development. Objectives: This study aimed to compare victims and non-victims of interparental violence in terms of AL and to analyze the impact of IV on AL. Method: This study used a sample of 191 participants aged between 18 and 75 ($M = 38.74$, $SD = 14.87$). An online protocol was disseminated, and participants answered a sociodemographic questionnaire and the Affective Lability Scale (ALS-18). The study was approved by the Ethics Committee and followed all the ethical principles. Results: The results showed that there are differences between victims and non-victims of IV regarding AL. Victims of IV have higher scores of AL on the total scale, and in the subscales of anxiety/depression and aggression. The results of the multiple linear regression indicate that age and experience of interparental violence are significant predictors of AL (age and IV impact AL). Conclusions: This study provides a better understanding of the impact that interparental violence has on the AL of the victims. Our results can help develop future intervention programs with children exposed to interparental violence, breaking the violence cycle and diminishing the development of AL.

KEYWORDS **Affective lability, Interparental violence, Impact, Victims, anxiety**

TITLE (Cyber)Stalking in Court Cases In Portugal: Victims,
(Cyber)Stalkers, Dynamics And Criminal Proceedings

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ABSTRACT Introduction: Stalking is considered a type of interpersonal violence defined as a pattern of persistent harassing behavior, with a prevalence of 20.7% in Portugal. With technology, the typical behaviors of stalking have spread to the digital environment (cyberstalking). Victimization by (cyber)stalking is associated with a decrease on general well-being, professional and economic losses, and clinical symptoms. These behaviors are described in law no. 83/2015, August 5, article 154-A of the Portuguese Penal Code, as a crime of "Stalking". This study was carried out in order to characterize the victims and (cyber)stalkers, frequent dynamics and the process of dealing with the crime. Method: This exploratory study, with a convenience sample and using a mixed methodology, was based on a documentary analysis of 182 first and second instance court decisions in Portugal. Three main themes of analysis were considered: (1) characteristics of the victim and the (cyber)stalker, (2) dynamics of (cyber)stalking, (3) characteristics of the processing of the crime of "Stalking". Parametric tests are currently being carried out to identify possible correlations between the variables under study. Results: The most common characteristics of the (cyber)stalker were male (88.8%), portuguese (87.8%), single (64.9%), with an average age of 45.27 and a criminal record (42.3%). The most frequent victim-(cyber)stalker relationship is that of ex-partners (41.8%), perpetrating stalking and cyberstalking behaviors simultaneously (37.6%). In 67.65% of cases, the accused was convicted, with a suspended prison sentence (44.65%) and an average of 3.48 related crimes. Personal testimony (99.21%) was the most used type of evidence and forensic psychological expertise (0.81%) the least frequent. Discussion and conclusions: This paper presents the preliminary results of the study. The discussion and conclusion will be presented, highlighting the implications of the study for the justice system.

KEYWORDS Stalking, Cyberstalking, Court judgments, Stalking dynamics, Portugal

OFFENDERS

POSTER PRESENTATIONS | OFFENDERS

TITLE **Positive and adverse childhood experiences and alexithymia in inmates and the general population**

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ABSTRACT

Individuals with alexithymia have difficulty identifying and describing their own emotions or the emotions of others, and childhood experiences can play an important role in the development of alexithymia. This research intends to analyze the relationship between adverse childhood experiences (ACEs), positive childhood experiences (PCEs), and alexithymia; compare a sample of inmates with a sample of the general population regarding ACEs, PCEs, and alexithymia; and verify if ACEs and PCEs impact alexithymia. The sample comprised 710 participants (560 from the general population and 150 inmates) aged between 18 and 73 ($M = 33.70$, $SD = 13.72$). The participants responded to the sociodemographic questionnaire, the Childhood Adverse Experiences Questionnaire, the Benevolent Childhood Experiences Scale, and the Toronto Alexithymia Scale. The Ethics Committee of Egas Moniz School of Health and Science approved the study, which followed the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. The results showed that alexithymia is positively correlated to ACEs emotional abuse, physical abuse, emotional neglect, family substance abuse, and family mental illness or suicide. However, alexithymia negatively correlates with PCEs. The group comparison showed higher scores in inmates in all ACEs, in externally oriented thinking and total alexithymia, and contrarily, revealed fewer scores of PCEs. Moreover, the explanatory model of alexithymia using a multiple linear regression showed that emotional neglect, PCEs, and age are significant predictors of alexithymia. This study emphasizes the impact of childhood experiences on alexithymia. Understanding this dynamic is important in designing interventions to address emotional difficulties, specifically in inmates. By recognizing the significance of adverse and positive childhood experiences, interventions can be developed to decrease the risk factors and strengthen the protective factors of emotional development.

KEYWORDS **Alexithymia, Inmates, General population, PCEs, ACEs**

TITLE **Intimate Partner Homicide: with and without a previous history of violence**

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ABSTRACT This study analyzes the impact of previous history of intimate partner violence through the comparison of cases with and without reports of previous violence. It is focused on a Portuguese sample (n=75) of female and male homicide offenders, being the majority of the analyzed cases perpetrated by men (84%) and presenting a previous history of intimate partner violence (72%). The most reported type of violence was psychological (91%), although there was evidence of co-occurrence of different violence types in the majority of cases. Ten of all cases (19%) evidenced violence only after the breakup of the intimate relationship. The majority of the homicide victims (54%) sought help. The results showed that perpetrators with a history of violence were unemployed, with criminal records involving crimes against persons, with substance abuse, and with a history of previous victim separations. In homicide, they choose a non-fire weapon and the crime took place during an argument. Perpetrators without a history of violence were older, and retired, with current relationships with the victim, pointing out the victims, health problems as a motivation, and using a firearm for the crime following. These results help to identify factors that could play a relevant role in lethality prevention strategies.

KEYWORDS intimate partner homicide, history of violence, post breakup

TITLE Intimate Partner Homicide: The Women Who Kill

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ABSTRACT

Background: Intimate partner homicide (IPH) is known as a lethal violence and the most extreme form of intimate partner violence (IPV). Recently, this phenomenon has acquired some attention in the scientific community. However, it should be studied further, especially in the context of female homicide offenders. Objectives: Analyze the risk factors for IPH, homicidal behavior and the criminal dynamics of female offenders. Method: 23 cases of IPH that occurred in Portugal, committed by women in heterosexual intimate relationships, between 2010 and 2021, were analyzed. The case analysis was conducted using a grid developed with the main risk factors. Results: The female offenders were aged between 20 and 65, and the majority were Portuguese and Caucasian. The most prevalent risk factor for IPH was a history of IPV (91.3%). In this context, the primary offender was the victim of IPH (52.2%). Bidirectional violence was present in 34.8% of the cases. There was also an absence of suicide after IPH. Most of the victims were under the influence of substances (63.6%) at the time of the crime. Conclusion: This scientific research allowed the characterization of the offender and the crime, as well as the clarification of common factors between male and female offenders in the context of intimate relationships. Despite the limited global and national expression, IPH has specific characteristics, regarding female offenders and the crime, which require specific responses in terms of prevention and intervention.

KEYWORDS Intimate Partner Homicide, Risk Factors, Intimate Partner Violence

TITLE **Social determinants of psychological well-being and life goals in deviant teenagers**

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ABSTRACT

We looked at factors shaping psychological well-being and social mobility of young people from deviant backgrounds. We were especially interested in how a set of social factors (group membership – EXITS, identification with the institution – collective self-esteem, and personal social support from peers and corrective educators) affect young people's psychological well-being in selected dimensions of the Ryff scale (personal growth, purpose in life, self-acceptance) and their aspirations for social mobility.

Responses from young people in correctional institutions (16–18-year-olds) in different institutional statuses (pre-trial detention, serving a sentence in a correctional institution, having special need education) were analysed. We were interested in how young people in a disadvantaged situation shape their vision of the future, their life goals, their resources based on positive emotions, resilience, coping with negative life events, their socio-emotional adaptation and peer support, their group memberships. In our study, we collected data in all 4 correctional institutions in Budapest and Central-Hungary Region (Nmale=85, Nfemale=44) by face-to-face interview.

The selected target variables were correlated with our predictor variables in multiple regression models. We were interested in the impact of psychological factors of peer support (group membership, institutional identification, perceived personal support) in addition to basic demographic factors (gender, institutional status, family background). We hope that our research will contribute to the exploration of the personal and peer conditions for their social integration and future success.

KEYWORDS **well-being, life goals, social reintegration, social support, correctional institutions**

TITLE Liberals have Negative Implicit Bias towards Non-Offending Pedophiles

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate implicit and explicit attitudes towards Offending Pedophiles (OP) and Non-Offending Pedophiles (NOP) in US participants, while also assessing the effectiveness of a humanizing narrative intervention in reducing stigmatizing attitudes towards NOP. Additionally, the influence of gender, political standing, and history of child sexual abuse (CSA) on attitudes was examined. Seventy-six participants completed an Implicit Association Test (IAT) and explicit attitude questionnaires regarding OP and NOP. Participants were then assigned to different intervention groups, including a humanizing narrative intervention, passive control, or active control. Attitude measures were repeated post-intervention, and background demographic information was collected. The study found that more liberal participants reported less punitive attitudes towards NOP and were more supportive of rehabilitation. CSA history significantly impacted attitudes towards NOP, with victims reporting more punitive attitudes, perceiving NOP as more dangerous, and being less supportive of rehabilitation. The humanizing narrative intervention had limited effectiveness but resulted in NOP being perceived as less deviant. Surprisingly, implicit attitudes did not correlate with explicit attitudes in liberal participants, suggesting a discrepancy between self-reported attitudes and implicit biases. The findings highlight the complexity of attitudes towards pedophiles, with political standing and CSA history influencing explicit attitudes. The unexpected misalignment between implicit and explicit attitudes among liberals implies that although liberals self-report to have less stigmatized views of NOP, they implicitly have a negative bias towards NOP that does not match up with their self-reported explicit attitudes. As this is the first study to use the IAT as a measure of implicit attitudes towards NOP these results should be further investigated. Although the intervention's impact was not as robust as expected, its effect on reducing perceptions of deviance warrants further exploration, suggesting potential avenues for longer or more targeted interventions.

KEYWORDS Pedophilic Disorder, Stigma, Implicit Association Test (IAT), Non-Offending Pedophile, Child Sexual Abuse (CSA)

TITLE **Beyond Recidivism: A Scoping Review Exploring Comprehensive Criteria for Successful Reintegration After Prison Release**

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ABSTRACT

Numerous studies have focused on recidivism as a key measure of successful community reintegration, yet a comprehensive analysis of reintegration criteria and associated risk factors is lacking in the literature. This gap hinders the development of targeted treatment plans within prison settings aimed at promoting the social reintegration of detained persons prior to release. Furthermore, it obstructs the criminal justice system's ability to consider pertinent indicators when making sentencing decisions.

The present study aims to identify and delineate additional criteria for successful social reintegration subsequent to incarceration. The review will encompass studies employing the PECO strategy (Population, Exposure, Comparison, Outcome). All peer-reviewed, cross-sectional, and longitudinal studies in English involving male and female participants over the age of 18 who have been incarcerated in various prisons will be considered. The included studies should address social reintegration criteria after prison release and variables associated to these criteria. Studies that represent grey literature, commentaries, reviews, conference papers, or academic works will be excluded. There will be no geographical, cultural, racial, or sexual restrictions on the included studies. Studies involving participants incarcerated in juvenile institutions, psychiatric hospitals, and community institutions will be excluded. The research will be conducted across multiple databases (Scopus (3,425 articles), EBSCO (50 articles), Web of Science (59 articles), b-on (3,188 articles) and pubmed (1,038 articles)). Two reviewers will independently assess and extract data, with a third serving as a consultant for conflicts.

The outcomes of this scoping review will offer comprehensive insights into the current state of the literature concerning the criteria for successful social reintegration after prison, including risk and protective factors. These findings will ultimately enable the formulation of guidelines for correctional policies, thereby fostering the rehabilitation of individuals within the prison system.

KEYWORDS **Detained persons, Prison, Reintegration, Scoping review**

TITLE **Guilty or Not Guilty by Reason of Insanity? A Comparative Study**

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ABSTRACT

Background. Some murders are committed under the influence of a psychotic state resulting from a mental disorder, mainly schizophrenia. According to the law, people with mental disorders do not have criminal responsibility. They are defined as not guilty by reason of insanity (NGRI) and therefore cannot be punished. This study aims to explore the differences between two groups of murderers: individuals who committed murder and were found NGRI and individuals who committed murder and were found responsible and guilty. The comparison is made by examining sociodemographic, psychiatric, criminological and forensic factors.

Methods. This study, conducted in Israel, analyzes the differences between 72 individuals who committed murder and were found NGRI and 56 individuals who committed murder and were found responsible for their actions and fit to stand trial (guilty).

Results. The findings show that NGRI participants were more likely to be from central areas, to be Jewish (rather than Arab), to be diagnosed with schizophrenia and have a background of hospitalizations before committing the murder, to have remained at the murder scene and/or called for help, and to be less likely to have committed the murder with a partner.

Conclusions. The findings add to the existing knowledge base about murder by reason of insanity and the differences between NGRI and criminal murderers. The characteristics of the NGRI group found here can help to identify risk groups and to develop and implement prevention programs for people with mental disorders who are at risk of violent behavior.

KEYWORDS **murder, insanity, schizophrenia**

TITLE Exploring the relation between reaction time-based concealed information detection and secondary psychopathic traits

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ABSTRACT

The reaction-time (RT) based concealed information test (CIT) presents various probe (familiar) items amidst irrelevant (unfamiliar) items. The task required "unfamiliar" response to probes may induce a response conflict. Resolving this conflict, by inhibiting the automatic "familiar" response, takes time and slows probe RTs - a phenomenon known as the RT-CIT effect. Notably, there is evidence to suggest that secondary psychopathy is characterized by disinhibition and impulsivity. Accordingly, in this pre-registered study (n = 86, student sample), we hypothesized that higher levels of secondary psychopathic traits would be associated with a larger RT-CIT effect. Contrary to our initial expectations, we observed no significant correlation between secondary psychopathy and the RT-CIT effect. Our Bayesian analysis also strongly supported the null hypothesis (BF₀₁ = 6.98). This result is reassuring as it cautiously suggests that secondary psychopathic tendencies do not compromise RT-CIT validity, even if they do not improve it.

KEYWORDS

Concealed Information Test (CIT), Psychopathy, Impulsivity, Reaction Time (RT), Response Conflict

FORENSIC AND PSYCHOLOGY ASSESSMENT

POSTER PRESENTATIONS | FORENSIC AND PSYCHOLOGY ASSESSMENT

TITLE Forensic psychological expertise in the Republic of Moldova

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ABSTRACT

In the Republic of Moldova, the forensic psychological expertise doesn't have the definition in the national, procedural criminal and civil legislation, being a narrower concept, a part of the general notion of forensic expertise which is defined and regulated by a series of legislative acts. We consider that the forensic psychological evaluation can bring some valuable responses of psychological matter regarding different aspects of criminal behavior. Taking into consideration the transitional period of development of the country, the legal field is still rigid and it is in changing process to adjust to present reality, to socio-economic, as well as, legal circumstances influenced by a series of factors. That is why we consider important to discuss with specialists of legal field regarding the psychological assessment in legal matters, focusing on the forensic psychological expertise. We organized some focus-groups on the given topic, at the end of which they filled in an opinion poll that included questions related to the lawyers' knowledge of forensic psychological expertise, the frequency of requesting the services of an expert-psychologist, as well as the types of civil/criminal cases that needed psychological evaluations, the possibilities of ordering a forensic psychological expertise, the consolidation of psychological expertise in the Republic of Moldova. In this study, 46 specialists of legal field have participated, namely the law enforcement officers aged between 28-54, with working experience 6-32 years in legal field, 75% of participant being men and 25% - women respectively. In this work, we present the results of the opinion poll that include as well personal reflections regarding the position and development of the forensic psychological expertise. The given study has revealed the „position” of the forensic psychological expertise, and emphasized the difficulties that the procedure face at the moment.

KEYWORDS forensic psychological expertise, the Republic of Moldova, law enforcement officers

TITLE **Exploring Authenticity in relation to Dark Traits: The Agentic & Communal Authenticity Inventory (ACAI) in a Competitive Gaming Scenario**

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ABSTRACT

Authenticity, the alignment between internal values and external expression, is vital in social interactions and is often perceived as an innate inclination towards genuine self-presentation. However, traditional perspectives often ignore the darker aspects of authenticity (e.g., psychopathy, Machiavellianism), where priorities reflect self-interested (agentic) goals above group interests (communal) and situational factors can trigger or conceal self-expression.

Recent theoretical efforts aim to incorporate these darker aspects into a more balanced understanding of authenticity, acknowledging the diversity of human experiences (Bulbuc & Visu-Petra, 2024). Expanding upon existing literature on authenticity, our research introduces a novel authenticity measure inspired by traditional frameworks (Kernis & Goldman, 2006) while accounting for the subjective experiences of individuals with dark traits, termed the Agentic & Communal Authenticity Inventory (ACAI).

We examine the ACAI's predictive validity for actual behaviours in a competitive gaming scenario (drawing inspiration from The Dictator's Game and The Joys of Destruction Game) by assessing self-reported agentic and communal tendencies in hypothetical scenarios.

Using a within-participant experimental design with power imbalance as a manipulated factor, our ongoing study investigates whether artificial status within a game environment elicits more robust responses based on individuals' dispositions compared to the salience of competitive group dynamics.

Specifically, we propose that individuals with high dark traits exhibit agentic behaviours across all conditions, with a particular increase in agentic behaviours in the high-power condition. Conversely, individuals with low dark traits are anticipated to exhibit sensitivity to social context, displaying heightened communal behaviours in low-power scenarios and increased agentic behaviours in high-power contexts, compared to demonstrating communal behaviour in the control condition.

This study aims to shed light on authenticity in emergent and adult populations with dark traits, offering potential insights for developmental approaches in younger populations where antisocial traits may be more challenging to diagnose.

KEYWORDS

Authenticity Inventory, Agentic tendencies, Communal tendencies, Dark Personality, Gaming Task

TITLE **Validating the Revised Screening Scale for Pedophilic Interests (SSPI-2) in a Portuguese Sample of Male Offenders**

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ABSTRACT

Accurately assessing pedophilic sexual interests is imperative for effective treatment and management of individuals who have perpetrated sexual offenses against children. This study aimed to validate the Revised Screening Scale for Pedophilic Interests (SSPI-2) within a sample of 170 male offenders convicted of such crimes in Portugal, with 104 in community settings and 66 incarcerated. Results demonstrated strong convergent validity of the SSPI-2, as evidenced by significant positive correlations with indicators such as the "sexual deviance" item of SVR-20, prior convictions for sexual offenses against children, and multiple child victims. Moreover, the SSPI-2 exhibited robust divergent validity, showing no significant correlations with self-reported psychopathy measures or associations with sexual offenses against adults or non-sexual crimes. These findings establish the SSPI-2 as a reliable tool for assessing pedophilic sexual interests, offering valuable insights for treatment and management strategies in the Portuguese context.

KEYWORDS

Pedophilic sexual interests, Atypical sexual interests, Sexual offenses against children, Assessment, Validation

TITLE **From exposure to parenting by lying in childhood to psychosocial maladjustment as adults**

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ABSTRACT

Parenting by lying is defined as a phenomenon where lying is used as a form of parenting to influence the behavior or feelings of children. Recent studies have found that parenting by lying may have negative psychosocial outcomes, but some results are inconsistent. The main objective of the present study was to analyze whether parenting by lying is associated with the development of antisocial lying to parents in young adulthood and other negative outcomes. The present work is based on an integrative literature review using the PRISMA protocol. This form of review includes studies with different methodologies in order to analyze the knowledge from previous research on parenting by lying. The searches were conducted in two electronic databases: Web of Science and Scopus. Journal articles published in English, Spanish, or Portuguese were selected and exhaustively analyzed. According to several studies conducted in different cultures and populations, parenting by lying seems to be extremely common. Analyzed studies found a positive association between parenting by lying and lying to parents as adults. Moreover, the frequency of parenting by lying was associated with more externalizing problems, internalizing problems, and psychopathy traits. It seems that lying to parents has mediating effect in the relationship between childhood experience of parenting by lying and current psychosocial maladjustment, while parent-child attachment has a protective mediational effect. In general, lying damages trust in relationships, and parental honesty may therefore be beneficial for preserving the quality of the parent-child relationship. Encouraging parents to praise honesty may better the communication in the parent-child relationship, as well as explicitly teach their children that antisocial lie telling is wrong.

KEYWORDS **parenting by lying, lying to parents, externalizing problems, internalizing problems, instrumental lies**

TITLE Exploring the role of Extreme Overvalued beliefs in Lone Actor Violence: Consensus on Terminology and Conceptualisation among Forensic Experts

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ABSTRACT

My PhD explores fixation driven by extreme overvalued beliefs (EOB) as a risk factor for lone-actor grievance-fuelled violence. EOB is a novel concept in clinical and forensic evaluations and describes an emotionally heavy and ego-syntonic fixation shared within a person's subculture. The fixation becomes increasingly overbearing, emotional, and absolute over time and is believed to grow rampant within online subcommunities (e.g., Incels) and conspiracy theories (e.g., QAnon) which have previously driven the will or perceived obligation of individual actors to commit acts of grievance-fuelled violence. EOBs often resemble delusions or obsessions in content and behaviour, but distinguishing between them is essential for reliable threat assessment, as the aetiology, cognitive components, and psychopathology can differ significantly. While the risk stemming from EOB is believed to be escalating, no reliable forensic or clinical tools have been developed, partly due to a lack of consistency and clarity in terminology. The current definition of EOB in a forensic context differs substantially from the definition of overvalued ideas (as seen in many mental disorders) presented in the DSM-5, where they are described as ideas not shared or accepted by a person's subculture (p. 826). While the concepts are closely related, the sharing of beliefs is a vital component of overvalued beliefs in threat assessment (Rahman & Meloy; McHugh; Wernicke), which introduces a significant discrepancy and debate regarding a mutually used and agreed-upon understanding in a clinical and forensic context. This is important to resolve, especially considering the legal implications of delusions and other severe mental illnesses in criminal cases. To address this limitation and lay the groundwork for future research, we are conducting a Delphi study and semi-structured interviews to reach a consensus among forensic experts regarding EOB's conceptualisation as a cognitive-affective driver of fixation.

KEYWORDS

Extreme overvalued beliefs, Overvalued ideas, Lone-actor grievance-fuelled violence, Fixation, Delusions

FORENSIC RISK ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT

POSTER PRESENTATIONS | FORENSIC RISK ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT

TITLE **Risk factors of suicides committed by children and adolescents**

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ABSTRACT

The aim of research was to prepare a psychological characteristic of young people (children and adolescents) who committed suicide, and determine some psychological factors which had a significant impact on their decision. Examination encompassed a group of 25 cases in which Institute of Forensic Research prepared a psychological reports for the court regarding the motives of suicide. The minimum age of examined at the moment of the suicide was 11, maximum 18 years old.

In each case court files were analyzed. We also conducted psychological interviews with persons from the environment of the deceased (parents, friends, teachers, etc.) and analyzed various works of victim (diary, farewell letter).

When preparing an expert opinion we took into account such aspects, as: live story of the person (especially last time before death), psychological disturbances, addictions and their influence on a person, emotional sphere (self-esteem, aggression), life activity (plans, value system), family situation, social relations and circumstances of death.

Detailed analysis showed that majority of examined grew up in full families, without manifestations of pronounced pathology and they potentially had good conditions for development but their psychological needs were not satisfied. They didn't receive sufficient support from parents and it was one of the main motivation of suicides. Another motivation were: experiencing peers violence (also cyberbullying), school problems or heartbreak. As for personality traits, young suicides showed more intense features of emotional and social immaturity than their peers.

As a police statistics shows, suicides among young people are growing as social problem and their victims are younger and younger children. For these reason such analysis may be important for experts reconstructing the psychological profile of suicide, because they broaden the knowledge about the causes of this phenomenon. It allows for more accurate statements about the motives of young people taking their own lives.

KEYWORDS **suicide, forensic diagnosis, risk factors of suicide**

TITLE **Couples therapy in cases of situational intimate partner violence: Translation and cultural adaptation of an intervention program for couples**

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ABSTRACT Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) is recognized as pervasive public health problem. IPV has been conceptualized from a dichotomous perspective - in which men are the perpetrators and women the victims. Recently, different typologies of violence have emerged, emphasizing the dyad and demonstrating other patterns than unidirectional ones. However, research, practices, and public policies have been dominated by a dichotomous perspective and little attention has been given to the dyads and the relationship dynamics involved in IPV. Besides, there is a greater understanding that interventions would be more beneficial if they incorporate a broader understanding of the IPV and target both partners. Couples' therapy seems to be an effective way to address the dysfunctional relationship dynamics providing an alternative model to deal with situational IPV. An example of an effective couples' treatment program in reducing IPV is the Domestic Violence Focused Conjoint Treatment (DVFCT).

In Portugal, national practices are still shaped by the prevailing one-side approach and no response exists for couples who stay together after/during IPV. This project aims to translate and culturally adapt the DVFCT - a manualized intervention program based on solution-focused brief therapy. The program aims to reduce all forms of violence; enhance positive affect between partners; and assist partners in taking responsibility for their own behavior. The adaptation will comprise different phases: (a) information gathering, (b) preliminary adaptation design, (c) preliminary adaptation tests, and (d) adaptation refinement. Throughout all phases, it is important to gain insight from local providers and clients to make adaptations based on the needs of the community. We expect to have a valuable and reliable intervention program tailored to Portuguese couples who experience situational IPV.

KEYWORDS **intimate partner violence, situational violence, couples' intervention, Domestic Violence Focused Conjoint Treatment**

TITLE **Indices of prediction for reoffending among a U.S. high school sample using the Big Four**

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ABSTRACT

Accurately identifying who will and will not reoffend in the future is essential for justice officials, policymakers, and researchers. When assessing the predictive validity of risk assessments, the area under the receiver operating characteristics curve (AUC) is the most common metric. Singh (2013) noted many additional validity indices, including sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, number needed to detain, number safely discharged, diagnostic odds ratio, and the logistic odds ratio. Yet, these indices are rarely examined in the risk assessment literature. Objective: This analysis aims to demonstrate the breadth and depth of knowledge gained when examining multiple predictive validity indices. Methodology: The data are from a longitudinal sample of high school students (Mage = 14.42, SD = .54) from the United States (n=2,619). Participants completed a self-report survey to assess delinquency and various risk factors for such behavior. At wave 1, previous offending behavior, personality, antisocial cognitions/attitudes, and perceived peer delinquency were assessed. These constructs captured the Big Four risk factors (Bonta & Andrews, 2015) and were collapsed into a composite measure of risk. Those scoring in the highest two-thirds of risk were predicted to offend at wave 2. The dependent variable was offending, measured at wave 2. Results: AUC = .77, sensitivity = .79, specificity = .60, positive predictive value = .98, negative predictive value = .60, number needed to detain = 1.02, number safely discharged = 1.51, diagnostic odds ratio = 5.66. Conclusions: These results indicate how different predictive validity risk indicators provide unique information. Moving forward, researchers and practitioners should rely on multiple validity indices and how they might be most appropriately and effectively used collectively to identify the best approach to predicting risk for reoffending, depending on the circumstances.

KEYWORDS **risk assessment, big four, validity indices**

TITLE **Assessment of social maladjustment of juvenile in the light of changes in law in Poland in JULY 2022**

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CONTACTS**

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the research project was to develop a model of psychological assessment in juvenile cases corresponding to contemporary psychological knowledge and amended regulations regarding proceedings in cases of demoralization and juvenile delinquency.

The provisions of the Act of June 9, 2022 on the support and social resocialization of minors apply in the scope of: proceedings in cases of demoralization and proceedings in cases of criminal acts. The Act does not clearly explain the definition and criteria for recognizing demoralization of varying degrees. The legal act itself does not set a boundary between demoralized people, those at risk of demoralization, and those for whom the said threat does not occur.

As part of the project, research was carried out with 117 psychology experts who assessed the importance of individual manifestations of demoralization (using a 5-point scale).

Of the 47 factors indicated, according to the respondents, the most important factors are:

regular mistreatment of the weaker, mobbing, bullying (4.86); animal abuse (4.81); regular use of intoxicants (4.77); practicing fornication, prostitution (4.76); burglary (4.70); arson (4.68).

The least important factors are: listening to inappropriate music (1.62); improper eating habits (1.60); participation in demonstrations e.g. regarding women's rights, equality marches, etc. (1.48); negative attitude towards faith and religion (1.44).

The result of the study was the development of an interview questionnaire taking into account various causes and manifestations of social maladjustment in juvenile, as well as risk and protective factors. Complete diagnosis can only be based on a deeper analysis of the mechanisms guiding a person's behaviour. Though it is time-consuming and can be conducted only by specialists, it includes a far greater number of evaluation criteria and analyses many more variables. Diagnoses of social maladjustment cannot be confined to the behavioural level, that is, to a description of the signs that indicate abnormality. To identify all of the relevant conditions influencing the appearance and consolidation of dysfunctional behaviours in juveniles it is vitally important to take account of a broad psychological and etiological diagnosis. This will mean a case study composed of partial diagnoses of different elements of the lives of juveniles that, in the final stage of inquiry, are synthesized to describe their psychological life situations.

KEYWORDS **juvenile, social maladjustment, risk and protective factors**

TITLE **The role of personal and environmental resources in preventing demoralization among juveniles**

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ABSTRACT

The aim of research was to create a list of factors which may be helpful in assessing the severity of demoralization in minors (according to the Polish law, a minor is a person between 10 and 17 years of age, which manifests various symptoms of maladjustment, such as: school problems, truancy, home escapes, aggression, contact with demoralized youth, etc.). Special attention was given to isolation and describe a group of protective factors constituting a kind of potential to protect a young person from increasing demoralization. This approach refers to the concept of resilience, which is most frequently defined as positive adaptation despite adversity. We also seek to understand how particular protective factors interact with risk factors and with other protective factors to support relative resistance in the case of examined minors.

During the research a special Questionnaire was used. It was created in the Institute of Forensic Research and containing a number of questions helpful in pointing out why a particular minor avoided demoralization and intensification of maladjustment and some of them improve their functioning?

Examinations encompassed a group of 115 young people which manifested various symptoms of maladjustment and demoralization. They were psychologically tested as a minor in connection with their court process. During the examinations a group of factors that can protect a person from increasing demoralization has been identified. They include variables related to personality traits of examined and factors related to their social environment (e.g.: positive and stable self-esteem, styles of coping with stress, social support, affiliation to different organizations like scouting or charity groups, etc.).

These studies may have a significant importance in the process of social rehabilitation of minors in the context of individual selection of resocialization methods and accurate assessment of the risk of increasing demoralization.

KEYWORDS **maladjustment, protective factors, minor**

TITLE **Cue-Induced Inhibitory Control in Forensic Patients with Alcohol Use Disorder: A Link to Criminal Recidivism Risk Assessed by Factor 2 Psychopathy**

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ABSTRACT

Cue reactivity is known to predict future relapse in substance use disorders (SUDs). Concurrently, substance use plays a crucial role in criminal recidivism following forensic treatment. Therefore, cue reactivity may be linked to criminal reoffending or even serve as a risk marker for its occurrence.

The present study sought to explore how exposure to alcohol cues in a Go/NoGo paradigm related to Factor 2 (Lifestyle/Antisocial) scores on the Psychopathy Checklist (PCL) in forensic patients diagnosed with alcohol use disorder (AUD). PCL-Factor 2, established as a robust predictor of criminal recidivism, served as a proxy for estimating the reoffending risk.

Data were collected from a sample of patients sentenced to addiction treatment in a high-security forensic hospital under section 64 of the German Criminal Code, which is applied when an unlawful act occurred in a state of intoxication or as a result of a SUD.

In the analyzed cohort of N=55 currently abstinent male patients (age: M=34.30 years), n=25 were diagnosed with AUD and n=30 had other SUDs. Patients completed two Go/NoGo Tasks featuring visual alcohol cues ("craving condition") or neutral stimuli ("control condition") on separate days in randomized order. Inhibitory control was determined using adjusted d-prime scores. Psychopathy assessments using the Psychopathy Checklist: Screening Version (PCL:SV) were obtained from hospital records.

Results showed that lower inhibitory control in the craving condition strongly related to higher PCL-Factor 2 scores in patients with AUD ($\beta=-.75$, $p=.003$). No associations were found for inhibitory control in the control condition, and performance in neither condition related to PCL-Factor 2 scores in those diagnosed with other SUDs.

These findings have implications for risk assessment, suggesting cue-induced inhibitory control may function as a valuable marker for reoffending probability. Future research should further explore substance-specific cue reactivity and its correlation with actual recidivism rates.

KEYWORDS

Cue reactivity, Response inhibition, Psychopathy, Lifestyle/Antisocial Factor, Recidivism Risk

TITLE **Technical Advisor to the Public Prosecutor's Office: The Involvement of the Technical Advisory Office (GAT) and the Forensic Psychology Office (GPF) as an active intervener**

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ABSTRACT

Co-witness discussion commonly leads to the communication of misinformation and a subsequent contamination of eyewitness memory. The nature of the relationship between co-witnesses has been demonstrated to influence event recall following discussion, with the possibility of specific dynamics within these relationships skewing memory further. Power within a romantic relationship refers to the extent to which an individual can influence their partner's feelings, thoughts or behaviours to achieve their own goals. The present study considered whether the existence of power dynamics influenced the amount of misinformation accepted between romantic partners following co-witness discussion of a distressing event. Members of a romantic couple were individually shown the same event, however remained unaware that their partner's version of the event contained differing details to their own. Participants then engaged in co-witness discussion about the event with their partner - whereby non-matching information was shared - before separately completing an individual recall of the event. How power dynamics impacted an individual's relationship wellbeing, and post-discussion psychological wellbeing was also measured. Results indicated that romantic partners who were higher in power tended to accept more misinformation, and maintained higher romantic relationship wellbeing. However, findings did not signify power as a predictor of post-discussion psychological wellbeing. This research replicates misinformation acceptance after co-witness discussion, and suggests that pre-existing relationship dynamics between co-witnesses can influence this process. Implications will be discussed.

KEYWORDS **Technical Advisory Offices, Forensic Psychology, Justice System.**

INVESTIGATIVE PSYCHOLOGY

POSTER PRESENTATIONS | INVESTIGATIVE PSYCHOLOGY

TITLE **Evolving Role of Public Safety Personnel in Climate Migration Management**

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ABSTRACT

Public safety personnel (PSP) are increasingly facing the complex challenge of managing climate migration, which has become a significant issue in the 21st century. Their role extends beyond traditional law enforcement duties to include providing crucial support and assistance to individuals affected by climate-induced displacement. As the first responders to emergencies, PSP often serve as the initial point of contact for those experiencing the traumatic effects of climate migration. These individuals may be deeply distressed by the upheaval of their lives and communities, requiring compassionate and empathetic assistance from PSP during moments of crisis.

However, PSP themselves are not immune to the mental health impacts of their duties. They face heightened levels of stress and trauma due to the increased frequency and severity of emergencies associated with their role. This can affect their ability to effectively carry out their duties and ensure public safety. The relationship between PSP and migrants affected by climate change is complex and multifaceted. In their home countries, migrants may have experienced social and political upheaval due to environmental degradation, shaping their perceptions of law enforcement. In host countries, PSP must navigate cultural differences and sensitivities while upholding security and order.

To address these challenges, PSP might undergo training to develop intercultural competencies and increase their awareness of mental health issues. By doing so, they can better serve the diverse needs of communities affected by climate migration and foster mutual understanding. PSP could contribute to building more resilient and inclusive communities in the face of environmental challenges.

This poster will present current knowledge on PSP's role in managing climate migration and supporting affected individuals, and discuss future research avenues. As PSP responsibilities go beyond law enforcement to address mental health concerns, understanding these dynamics is crucial for effective support and intervention.

KEYWORDS **Public safety personnel, Climate Migration Management, mental health**

TITLE 'Keep Your Eyes Closed and Ears Open': Can Eye-Closure Improve Voice Recognition Accuracy?

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ABSTRACT

Purpose. In several applied contexts, the voice may serve as the primary cue to identify suspects of a crime. However, identifying someone from their voice is prone to errors. Here, we examined the cognitive-load hypothesis and suggested that eye-closure could be extended to voice identification tasks to improve performance. Additionally, we explored how visual distraction during the encoding phase may impact subsequent voice recognition performance.

Method. Participants (n = 124) were randomly allocated to receive either an eye-closure instruction or no instruction during a voice identification line-up. Alongside the eye-closure conditions, participants received visual distractions or no distractions during the encoding of the target voice.

Results. Eye-closure had no benefit on performance accuracy. Additionally, visual distractions did not significantly affect subsequent voice recognition accuracy. Interestingly, eye-closure did affect participants confidence levels, although the direction of this influence, whether it increased or decreased confidence, varied depending on whether distractions were present.

Conclusions. These results question the utility of eye-closure during voice identification line-ups. Instead, effective attentional management and contextual factors might offer an explanation for some of our findings. However, further investigation is needed to substantiate these preliminary insights.

KEYWORDS Earwitness, Memory, Retrieval

TITLE Analyzing the questions asked in interviews with queer asylum-seekers

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ABSTRACT Asylum applications from SOGI minorities have increased in recent years and are expected to continue rising. It is crucial that the asylum interview is conducted in a way that supports legitimate decision-making and enables fair and accurate assessments of refugee status. Asking appropriate questions is one of the few tools at the interviewer's disposal to elicit detailed and accurate responses. Until now, questions asked in asylum interviews have only been sparsely studied. Worryingly, no prior study has investigated questions asked from SOGI applicants. In the current study, we analyzed question style, question type and question content in real-life interviews conducted with SOGI applicants. The sample consisted of 129 official asylum cases determined by Finnish state authorities 2014–2019. In accordance with best practice, interviewers mainly used the information-gathering style. However, only one-tenth of all questions were recommended open questions, whereas four-fifths were closed questions. More than half of the questions aimed at assessing credibility of SOGI status, less than one-third were about fear of persecution, and one-seventh were about other reasons for seeking asylum. To assess the credibility of SOGI claims, officials predominantly asked about the applicant's history of same-sex relationships, feelings about their sexuality and development of sexual identity. To improve current interviewing praxis asylum officials could ask more open questions, avoid accusatory questions altogether and focus more on establishing fear of persecution. Future research should examine how asylum seekers experience and interpret questions concerning SOGI status, to assess which questions elicit most relevant information.

KEYWORDS asylum-seeker, queer, asylum interview, investigative interviewing

TITLE **Efficacy and Longevity of Simulated Child Sexual Abuse Interview Training among Students and Child Protection Service Workers**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: allegations of child sexual abuse often present procedural challenges, primarily stemming from a lack of supporting evidence. In these instances, the child interview emerges as a pivotal element in the investigation, underscoring its significant importance. It is strongly recommended that interviewers adhere to best practices to facilitate the child in providing pertinent details related to the case. Employing open-ended questions is advised to reduce the risk of introducing suggestive influences and contaminating the child's narrative. Despite these recommendations, research indicates a tendency among professionals to deviate from best practices, resorting to leading and confirming questions.

Methodology: here, our objective was to conduct simulated interview training with avatars among CPS workers (N = 31) and subsequently compare their performance and learning pace with that of a student group (N = 34). Half of the participants in both groups received feedback during the training process. After the initial training, the participants returned to a second training session 3 months later.

Results: First, we found that CPS workers did not outperform the students in terms of asking more recommended questions during the first training session. Second, those who received feedback significantly improved in terms of asking a higher proportion of recommended questions and maintained this training effect after 3 months.

Conclusion: Avatar Training was equally effective in increasing the use of recommended questions in both groups and that training effects are maintained long term. Even experienced forensic interviewers may need training to achieve and maintain better interview quality.

KEYWORDS **Child Sexual Abuse, Investigative Interview Training, Serious Gaming**

TITLE Interviewers' and Interpreters' Experience of Official Finnish Asylum Interviews

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Recent psychological research has highlighted shortcomings and challenges in asylum interview and decision-making procedures. Nonetheless, few previous studies have examined how the interview participants perceive the interviews. The aim of the current study was to investigate how interviewers and interpreters experience asylum interviews and how their views and attitudes align with empirical evidence regarding investigative interviewing.

Methodology: Finnish asylum interviewers (n = 62) and interpreters (n = 63) completed an online survey consisting of rating scale, multiple-choice and open-ended questions. The main topics of the survey were interview preparation, interview dynamics, interview content, interpretation, and general views. The data was mainly analyzed descriptively by exploring the frequencies and distributions of the responses. Differences between the interviewers and interpreters were analyzed with a series of Mann-Whitney U-tests.

Results: Both groups reported views that were generally in line with evidence-based guidelines for investigative interviewing. However, compared to the interviewers, the interpreters' views on interviewing techniques were less aligned with best practice guidelines, with interpreters preferring closed questions over open and free recall questions. Both the interviewers and the interpreters agreed that it is important to prepare for interviews and to build rapport, however, several respondents also described various practical challenges related to these topics. Concerns regarding the quality of the interpretation were also reported by both groups. Most respondents reported that they found their work meaningful, but emotionally draining and challenging.

Conclusions: Due to the geographically restricted sample and low completion rate among the interpreters, more research is needed for broader conclusions to be drawn. Nevertheless, it is likely that some of the reported challenges and concerns also occur in other European countries adhering to the same EU standards and principles. The findings of the current study may be useful to improve the quality of asylum interviews, primarily in Finland.

KEYWORDS

asylum interview, interviewers, interpreters, investigative interviewing, survey

TITLE **The effect of response modality on witness statements when using the self-administered interview**

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ABSTRACT

The Self-Administered Interview (SAI[®]) elicits comprehensive initial statements from witnesses and can enhance subsequent statements. However, the SAI[®] requires a written response that may have disadvantages compared to a spoken account. This study tested the effect of SAI[®]'s response modality and its subsequent impact on a delayed retrieval attempt. After watching a mock crime, participants completed a Spoken-SAI[®], Typed-SAI[®] or no-SAI[®]. Four days later, participants read a news report with misleading post-event information (PEI) and, after another 3 days, completed a free recall and a recognition test. The Spoken-SAI[®] required less time to be completed than the Typed-SAI[®] but elicited accounts with a comparable amount of correct information and accuracy. Providing an initial account using the SAI[®] (vs. no-SAI[®]) produced more detailed accounts 1 week later regardless of response modality but did not reduce the susceptibility to misleading PEI. Regardless of response modality, most of the correct information recalled in the first retrieval attempt was also recalled in the second retrieval attempt, suggesting that a substantial number of correct units of information were preserved over the 1-week retention interval. Further, 21% of the units of information recalled in the second retrieval attempt were new correct units of information, suggesting that a formal police interview is important to obtain new information that was not captured in the initial self-report. This provides valuable insight for improving the SAI[®] and its applicability.

KEYWORDS **eyewitness testimony, post-event information, response modality, self-administered interview, witness statement**

TITLE **Assessing (un)biasedness in military disciplinary investigations for suspects and witnesses – One scale or two scales?**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Different biases are reported to challenge the ideal of truth-seeking in investigations. In our research, perceived bias plays a central role for military patients attributing their mental health condition to the investigative interview. Due to a lack of self-report measures for interviewees, our objective is to develop and validate (a) self-report measure(s) for military suspects and witnesses, to assess potential qualitative and quantitative differences and provide (a) short versions.

Method: Parallel versions for military suspects and witnesses were developed based on the MIIPS and qualitative research, containing 24- 25 items. These were completed by 319 witnesses and 232 suspects. Factor structure and correlations with affect, affective commitment and organizational justice, were analysed.

Results: Principle component analysis with varimax rotation yielded four factors explaining 64% of the variance for the suspect's self-report measure: (un)biasedness, neglecting evidence, suspect's image and shared history) and five factors explaining 61% for the witness (confirmation bias, truth-seeking, witness' image, relationship with witness/accusation type, exoneration tendency). Based on stepwise regression, (a) a four-item scale for suspects explaining 75% of the variance, and (b) an eight-item two-factorial scale for witnesses explaining 55% of the variance emerged.

Both versions are significantly correlated with procedural, relational and informational organizational justice ($r_s = -.52$, $r_w1 = -.40$, $p_s < .001$, $r_s = -.24$, $r_w1 = .09$, $p_s < .001$), negative affect ($r_s = .28$, $r_w1 = .34$, $r_w2 = .22$, $p_s < .001$), and commitment with the supervisor ($r_s = -.29$, $r_w1 = -.24$, $r_w2 = -.18$, $p_s < .001$).

Conclusion: It is recommended to use the two scales separately. Different degrees of complexity are reflected in the interviewer's relationship towards the suspect, the witness and the question at stake. Higher correlations with proximal criteria and lower correlations with distal criteria support criterion validity.

Note: Ongoing data collection and analysis might result in potential changes.

KEYWORDS **Investigative interviewing, military, suspects, witnesses, measuring bias**

TITLE **The Role of the Victims Information and Assistance Office as a Technical Advisor to the Public Prosecutor's Office**

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ABSTRACT

The Victims Information and Assistance Office (GIAV) was established in 2011 through a partnership between Egas Moniz School of Health and Science and the Lisbon Regional Department for Criminal Investigation and Prosecution (DIAP), working in articulation with the Public Prosecutor's Office in the context of crimes of Domestic Violence and maltreatment towards children, adults and the elderly. Since 2020, the office has been an integral part of the Specialized and Integrated Section on Domestic Violence (SEIVD) of the Lisbon Public Prosecutor's Office. GIAV has as main goals: Assistance to victims identified by the justice system; intervention in critical incidents; victims support during court and procedural proceedings (e.g., preparation and accompaniment of victims in Future Memory Statements – DMF; trials and victim inquiries); technical and scientific advisory services to Judicial Magistrates, Public Prosecutors, and other judicial actors (e.g., risk assessment of violence; proceedings with suspects defendants); training and scientific research on topics addressed by the offices. Since 2011, 340 violence risk assessments have been carried out: 294 in the context of intimate partner violence, 34 of maltreatment and negligence towards children, 10 of maltreatment and negligence towards the elderly, one case of human trafficking and another of mental illness screening. Furthermore, 1040 accompaniments of victims in DMF have been made, as well as 109 accompaniments in inquiries and 65 in trials, 257 telephone communications, 159 attendances, 91 referrals to competent institutions, 84 crisis interventions, 16 technical opinions and 68 diligences with juvenile defendants. Lastly, GIAV was also responsible for 24 training actions for Prosecutors and Technicians and eight seminars. The purpose of this poster is to demonstrate the work developed by GIAV and the office's role as a technical advisor to the Lisbon Prosecutor's Office, specifically about Domestic Violence.

KEYWORDS **Victim, Support, Prosecutor's Office, Technical Advice, Forensic Psychology**

CRIMINAL INVESTIGATION

POSTER PRESENTATIONS | CRIMINAL INVESTIGATION

TITLE **The influence of social anxiety among eyewitnesses in accurately recalling details in online vs. face-to-face interviewing**

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the quantity of information collected in eyewitness interviews (online vs. face-to-face) and how psychological phenomena such as social anxiety affect the way we disclose information. Anxiety in this study focuses on trait anxiety (i.e., anxiety in general), which was assessed prior to the experiment, and state anxiety (i.e., anxiety at a specific moment), measured three times throughout the experiment. Investigative interviewing among eyewitnesses is crucial during the criminal investigation process and helps determining the outcome of a case. Previous research found that the testimony medium affected the number of details collected from eyewitness testimonies. Additionally, reporting to a representative of authority (e.g., a police officer) face-to-face could be a socially laden activity that exacerbate state anxiety, especially among individuals with high trait anxiety. These individuals may have a more difficult time crafting narratives offline than they do online. Yet, little is known about how utilising a chatbot may alter the number of details acquired among them. This is what our research will focus on. Participants in the experiment completed a survey about trait anxiety before being invited to play a game. Thereafter, they were asked to complete a survey about state anxiety before being informed that a wallet was stolen during the game and that they needed to testify. They were randomly assigned to one of the interview conditions. The survey about state anxiety had to be completed again before the interview began. After the interview, participants had to complete this survey for the last time. The findings will shed light on how anxiety might be considered when conducting eyewitness interviews. They will underline the need of tailoring interviews to eyewitnesses in order to maximise information collection. Lastly, theoretical implications and practical advice for eyewitness interview techniques are examined.

KEYWORDS **Investigative interviewing, Anxiety, Eyewitness, Interviewing medium**

TITLE **Improving Earwitness Testimonies: Source and Destination Memory**

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ABSTRACT When it comes to the understanding of a conversation, knowing who said what (source memory) and to whom something has been said (destination memory) is crucial. In the context of earwitness testimony, it is therefore important that witnesses are able to correctly associate a particular statement with its source or recipient. Building on previous work, we sought to enhance these association performances. In an initial online study (n=127), we assessed the effects of three different focus tasks (Emotional Self/Speaker focus, Cognitive Self/Speaker focus, Speaker focus only) on performance in an association task linking a statement from a previously viewed scene to its source or recipient. We developed a questionnaire for this task. No significant differences were observed. We replicated this study in a face-to-face setting (n=59), again finding no significant differences between the experimental groups. Contrary to the previous findings obtained in the context of intentional encoding (Johnson et al., 1996), the results of this study suggest that the Self/Speaker focus task does not enhance source and destination memory performance in the context of incidental conversation encoding.

KEYWORDS **Source Memory, Destination Memory, Earwitness Testimony, Self/Speaker focus**

TITLE **Child sexual abuse myth acceptance of teacher students, police students and students of social work in Germany**

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ABSTRACT

Myths or misconceptions surrounding child sexual abuse (CSA) perpetuate stereotypes and false beliefs regarding the phenomenon. The endorsement of CSA myths has been demonstrated to influence the attitudes of professionals in their handling of suspected CSA cases and in initiating conversations with potentially affected children. This study seeks to evaluate whether students training for crucial roles in child protection, such as those studying in law enforcement, social work, or teaching professions, require additional education concerning CSA and CSA myths. To accomplish this, the validated "Child Sexual Abuse Myth Scale - German Version" (CSAMS-G) was administered to a total of n=697 German students enrolled in the aforementioned disciplines. Findings indicate generally low levels of myth acceptance, with only a few myths demonstrating higher levels of endorsement. The majority of these myths are associated with a subscale assessing acceptance of myths pertaining to handling suspicions and disclosures of CSA by children. Notably, the myth with the highest acceptance is that specific behavioral patterns always manifest when a child is victimized. Adding on to that, the participants showed a high acceptance of the myth that victimized children cannot talk about their victimization experiences. Participants showed rather high acceptance for myths regarding the social contexts in which they suspect CSA to occur more often. Additional findings will be elaborated upon in the poster.

KEYWORDS **child sexual abuse, myths, professional education**

JUROR-DECISION MAKING

POSTER PRESENTATIONS | JUROR-DECISION MAKING

TITLE **She Liked It™: Investigating The impact of attributional predictors on mock juror guilty verdict rates in cases of murder when defendants invoke the ‘rough sex’ defence**

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ABSTRACT

Objective. Defendants who use the ‘rough sex’ defence claim the victim consented to the acts that led to their death, resulting in 45% of cases experiencing lighter charges (i.e. manslaughter), sentencing or no prosecution. This research investigated mock juror decision-making through responsibility attributions and guilty verdicts within homicide cases employing the ‘rough sex’ defence.

Methodology. Two correlational studies explored the relationship between potential attitudinal predictors and verdicts through a vignette paradigm.

Study 1, the participants read a singular vignette, provided feedback concerning the dependent variables of verdict and responsibility attributions, then completed psychometric scales. Seven self-report scales measuring ambivalent sexist beliefs, rape and domestic violence myth acceptance, social dominance orientation, and gender norms and behaviours were completed. Acceptance rates were determined from verdict and victim/defendant responsibility scores. Adult participants (71.15% female, mean age = 46.50) from 56 countries contributed to Study 1 (N = 624) and Study 2 (N = 1,200). This mock juror design allowed for identification of the strongest predictive beliefs.

Study two explored attitudinal subscales of female stereotypical images/activities and dependence/deference, male self-reliance, the importance of sex, and dominance, domestic violence myths of victim character blame and minimisation, hostile and benevolent sexism, and she asked for it, he didn’t mean to, it wasn’t rape and she lied subscales.

Results. In order of highest to lowest effect sizes, ambivalent sexism, rape myth acceptance, domestic violence myth acceptance, and male role norms negatively predicted guilty verdict rates. Significant ambivalent sexism scale effects were found. Almost 47% of participants delivered a ‘not guilty’ verdict within the first study, study two is currently undergoing data collection and results will be analysed before the conference.

Conclusion. The researchers hope this inspires future research to utilise a mock jury paradigm as the results may have been a vignette-specific effect.

KEYWORDS

rough sex defence, rape myths, ambivalent sexism, gender norms, responsibility

TITLE **The influence of victim intoxication and inconsistent testimony on mock juror decision-making**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Victim alcohol intoxication is prevalent in criminal cases, impacting perceptions of witness credibility. This study examines how mock jurors evaluate victims in terms of intoxication and testimonial inconsistency.

Aims: 1) Investigate how victim intoxication influences verdicts, perceived defendant culpability, and perceived victim effectiveness. 2) Examine the impact of testimonial inconsistency on juror evaluations. 3) Explore any interaction effects between intoxication and inconsistency.

Methods: A mock juror study with 239 participants evaluated a crime scenario involving victim intoxication (intoxicated vs. sober) and testimonial consistency (consistent vs. inconsistent). Participants delivered verdicts, rated defendant culpability and victim effectiveness, and reported drinking habits (AUDIT-C) and beliefs about alcohol consumption.

Results: Victim intoxication did not significantly affect verdicts, perceived culpability, or victim effectiveness. However, jurors rated victims with inconsistent testimonies as less effective. Interestingly, drinking habits (AUDIT-C) did not influence verdict decisions, but jurors who believed alcohol intoxication is an irresponsible behaviour rated intoxicated victims as less effective.

Discussion: These findings challenge the assumption that intoxication automatically reduces juror trust, suggesting caution regarding instructions on witness reliability. However, inconsistent testimonies, regardless of intoxication, appear to negatively impact juror perceptions. Future research should explore the influence of intoxication on specific crime types and delve into why jurors view inconsistent victims less favourably. Additionally, examining juror characteristics could provide further insights.

KEYWORDS **alcohol, victim, jury, testimony**

TITLE **The Role of Gender and Pre-Trial Attitudes on Juror Decision-Making in Domestic Sex Trafficking Cases in the United States and the United Kingdom**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Little research has been conducted on juror decision-making in sex trafficking cases. Two of the authors conducted a prior investigation of the role of defendant gender on juror decision-making with a jury-eligible U.S. sample. The results indicated that the male defendant was more likely to be found guilty. However, the majority of verdicts were guilty. A follow up study was designed to build on the nascent understanding of the role of extra-legal factors in juror decision-making in sex trafficking cases.

Study Aim: This study examined whether country of residence (U.S. or U.K), sex trafficking attitudes, complainant gender, juror gender and right-wing authoritarianism (RWA) influenced juror decision making within a sex trafficking case.

Methodology: Jury-eligible participants from the United States and the United Kingdom participated in an online juror experiment in which an independent group design was used to manipulate the complainant's gender. Participants completed the Juror Decision Scale (JDS), the Sex Trafficking Attitudes Scale (STAS) and the Right Wing Authoritarianism (RWA) scale.

Findings: Sex trafficking attitudes predicted the believability of both the defendant and complainant. Greater negative beliefs about victims predicted greater defendant believability and lower complainant believability. U.S. jurors reported greater believability of both the complainant and defendant, and RWA was associated with greater defendant believability. However, none of the other factors, including complainant and juror gender, predicted participants' verdicts.

Conclusion: The findings suggest juror verdicts in sex trafficking cases may be less influenced by extra-legal factors, although further research is needed, especially with a more ambiguous case.

KEYWORDS **Sex-Trafficking, Jury Decision-Making, Gender**

LEGAL DECISION MAKING

POSTER PRESENTATIONS | LEGAL DECISION MAKING

TITLE **Texas Attorneys Recognize Problematic Eyewitness Procedures, but Plea Away Anyway**

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ABSTRACT

Prosecutors play an important gatekeeping role in preventing wrongful convictions. However, documented cases of wrongful convictions involving eyewitness misidentifications suggest prosecutors lack an understanding of unreliable identification procedures sometimes employed by police. In 2011, Texas passed reforms to improve the reliability of identification procedures. Since this time, judges have still admitted identifications obtained by police using improper procedures, leaving the prosecutor as the last line of defense to prevent a potential wrongful conviction. How they employ discretion is likely influenced by their knowledge of evidence-based best practices in identification procedures. The current study examined eyewitness knowledge among practicing prosecutors and defense attorneys in Texas. Given that 94% of convictions result from pleas, and a growing number of wrongful convictions stem from false guilty pleas, I also tested whether plea-bargaining decisions depended on identification procedures. A total of 196 attorneys reviewed a hypothetical case where the sole evidence was an eyewitness identification. The use of reliable identification procedures, specifically double-blind lineup administration and unbiased lineup instructions, varied. Results indicated that attorneys were knowledgeable regarding 13 eyewitness procedures, but less so on six procedures such as instructing the eyewitness to guess if they are unsure during an interview (a poor practice) and collecting inculpatory evidence before placing a suspect in a lineup (a good practice). Prosecutors were no more knowledgeable than defense attorneys. Reliable identification procedures did not influence plea bargain decisions. Instead, regardless of identification procedures, prosecutors viewed the defendant as more likely to be guilty and they were more likely to offer a plea deal than were defense attorneys to recommend one. These results suggest eyewitness knowledge may not be sufficient to affect plea bargaining decisions, underscoring the need for better education in the legal community.

KEYWORDS **eyewitness evidence, attorney decision making, plea bargain**

TITLE **Inside the judge's mind: influences on decision-making**

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ABSTRACT

Although legal psychology has an extensive history of studying legal decision-making, the perspective of judges has been the focus of very few studies. Their insight on how they reach their decision and potential influences they experience has not yet been thoroughly researched. The objective of the current exploratory study was to gain insights that could form the basis for further research. In this study, we focused on judges practicing criminal law. Respondents were found by sending judges an open invitation to participate in our study and by using network sampling. Using semi-structured interviews, we interviewed 22 judges. Given the exploratory nature of our study, broad themes were covered. These included possible influences on judicial decision-making and the ways diversity and inclusivity of the judicial organization could be connected to judicial decision-making. A thematic analysis was done on the interview transcripts, using ATLAS.ti.

The identified themes included various influences on decision-making, such as the attitude of the defendant and their lawyer at trial. Judges described self-reflection and collegial consultation as ways they dealt with possible influences on their decision-making. Differences became clear in other themes, such as how judges prepare cases, and how they reach their decision. Most of the interviewed judges thought diversity and inclusivity within their organization could and should be improved. Some judges remarked that improving diversity and inclusivity could lead to better decision-making, since these improvements should lead to more diverse perspectives and a safe environment to discuss these. This study finds that there are several areas of potential influences on judicial decision-making that should be researched further. These insights therefore provide the building blocks of a bridge between research and practice, where future research can be based on influences acknowledged by judges and include the judicial perspective on decision-making.

KEYWORDS

judicial decision-making, judicial perspective, influences on decision-making, criminal law

DECEPTION DETECTION

POSTER PRESENTATIONS | DECEPTION DETECTION

TITLE **Unmasking Deception: How do Consumers Determine the Veracity of Online User Reviews?**

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ABSTRACT

To influence consumers to buy products of lower quality, criminals produce fake online consumer reviews, which in health and safety related products can not only lead to financial and emotional but also physical harm. Understanding how people make judgements about review veracity presents an opportunity to examine how people make deception judgments in a naturalistic setting, when there are direct personal consequences for the decisions they make.

The objective of this research is to develop a grounded theory of how consumers determine the veracity of online user reviews, within the context of online shopping behavior, with a longer term objective to develop interventions to strengthen consumer resilience.

Study 1 comprised 25 interviews with Dutch and German consumers analyzed through grounded theory. In study 2, we used a think-aloud method where participants described their thought processes while they decided whether or not they would like to buy 7 different products.

Study 1 showed that deception judgments only occurred late in the review process, after usefulness, credibility, and trustworthiness were evaluated. Furthermore, when deception judgments are made, they encompassed a wide range of cues, including evaluation of the reviewer, seller and platform and corroboration with external information as well as the content of the review itself. We expect that the second study will refine our developed theory by addressing the key limitation of our first study, which is that it is based upon recollections of purchasing behavior rather than capturing live decision making processes.

Theoretically, our research demonstrates how deception decisions are embedded within wider decision-making contexts. Practically, our research indicates that deception training interventions will have to be multifaceted and would likely include increasing the perceived legitimacy of genuine products and sellers as well as facilitating recognition of reliable cues to deception for individual users.

KEYWORDS Fake reviews, deception detection, consumer-perspective

TITLE **How to interview a MOCKing bird. Deception detection in face-to-face and online settings**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Most of the research addressing investigative interviewing to date has been conducted in classic, face-to-face settings, but with the emergence of new technologies and the ever-increasing shift towards the online medium, the question of their potential implications for interviewing policies is more relevant than ever. Despite this, the literature comparing classic (face-to-face) and online interviewing settings is still emerging.

Objectives: Our ongoing study focuses on the potential differences between these two interviewing mediums and their effects on deception detection, with emphasis on the verbal cues of deception.

Method: Using a video of a mock crime involving a theft as basis for the interview, we asked participants to assume the perpetrator's perspective and provide truthful and deceitful statements for the incident depicted in the video. The interviews, which are conducted both face-to-face and online, include a free recall component, as well as a temporal segmentation phase, aimed at enabling the participants to provide detailed statements.

Expected results: Our preliminary analyses will address both quantitative and qualitative measures for the potential differences in 1) the amount and type of details provided in face-to-face versus online settings 2) effects of the interviewing phases on the quality of the statement and on the memory of the event.

Conclusions: These preliminary findings are aimed at encouraging further research that includes both face-to-face and online conditions in interviewing settings.

KEYWORDS

deception detection, investigative interviewing, verbal cues, online interviewing

MISCELLANEA

POSTER PRESENTATIONS | MISCELLANEA

TITLE Social Networks: use and risk during adolescent

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ABSTRACT

Background/Aim: In recent years, the progress of new technologies has meant a change in people's lives, especially during adolescence. In particular, previous studies have warned that the time spent using social networks is excessive and their use entails various risks. Thus, literature has focused on investigating digital literacy in childhood and adolescence. Nevertheless, there is a little literature on this subject. Method: The present research focuses on examining variables related to the use of social networks and digital literacy in a sample of 167 adolescents (49.10% females and 50.90% males), with an age range between 14 and 18 years ($M = 15.47$; $SD = 1.07$), who completed the measurement instruments. Results: The results showed that the mean age of first accessing a Social Network was 11.53 years ($SD = 1.76$) and the most used platforms were Instagram (40.00%) and Whatsapp (36.40%). With regard to the above requesting information before using Social Networks, the results indicated that 66.70% requested information before using them, compared to 33.30% who did not inquire about it. In relation to digital literacy, results showed significant differences according to gender, with boys obtaining higher scores than girls, with the exception of the variable "I know how to compare different sources to decide if the information is true" in which girls obtained a higher score. Discussion: Bearing in mind the limitations of our study, the results are discussed and future lines of research are proposed, linked to the implementation of intervention programmes on digital security within the framework of police prevention.

KEYWORDS Internet, Adolescents, Digital literacy

TITLE**From Bias to Verdict: Investigating the Influence of Racial Bias and Individual Characteristics on Mock Jury Deliberations and the Implementation of Bias Reduction Interventions**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Despite the extensive body of literature addressing racial biases, cognitive biases, and their impact on jury decision-making, gaps persist in our understanding of how these biases interact and influence each other. There is limited research exploring the interplay between biases, personality traits, and the efficacy of intervention or verdict decision strategies to counteract biases. This study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How do pre-existing biases manifest within mock jury discussions?
2. How do juror attitudes, characteristics, and biases impact on the effectiveness of intervention strategies?
3. Are intervention strategies effective in the long-term and what is their relationship to juror bias and personality?

Methodology: An online questionnaire is used to collect qualitative and quantitative data in a mixed methods design. Participants answer a set of questionnaires evaluating their personality type as defined by the HEXACO personality inventory, as well as potential biases due to racial bias, legal attitudes, political identity, and participant's internal and external motivation to respond without prejudice. Participants then answer a set of vignettes that detail a grievous bodily harm case committed by either a white or black offender. A randomised subset will also receive a bias reduction intervention and are then tested on another case vignette.

Expected Results: Provisional results will be presented. It is expected that there will be a racial bias present in the verdict decisions, mediated by the participants motivation to appear less prejudiced. It is also expected that the bias reduction strategy will be effective in reducing biased decision-making. Relationships between other biases and personality will be evaluated.

Conclusion: This study aims to develop our current understanding of bias in the courtroom and the methods in which we can ensure a fair and unbiased trial is reached.

KEYWORDS Bias, Intervention, Courtroom, Decision-Making

TITLE Expert endorsement and political opinion: do constitutions possess psychological power?

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ABSTRACT

Theoretical work suggests constitutions have a role in shaping citizen opinion and behaviour. Previous focus-group work on this project suggests that when participants are presented with an issue of “constitutional” importance, they tend to defer to expert views. This work seeks to test if the branding of an issue as constitutional is an effective way of increasing participants’ deference to expert opinion, hence giving constitutions an avenue to shape political opinion.

We will investigate these objectives with online between-participant experimental designs. We will employ fictitious newspaper like stimuli introducing participants to a realistic policy problem. Participants will be told that there is newly proposed legislation to address this problem. We will compare how participants’ approval of the legislation varies depending on the approval of and reasons presented by experts.

In Study 1 participants will be informed that there is expert approval or disapproval of the legislation for constitutional reasons. The sample size will be determined by pilot testing.

Study 1 will test the impact of expert constitutional support for the intervention – support, criticism or no mention of experts. We will test these factors with between participant T-tests.

We expect that participants will be sensitive to expert opinion on matters of policy and hope ultimately to show that branding some issues as “constitutional” is an effective way of increasing deference to expert opinion.

The broader project aims to examine the reason for support e.g., constitutional, legal, or moral norms, the expert’s position e.g., judicial, academic or political and the policy problem identified e.g., immigration, electoral rules or parliamentary conventions. The project seeks to provide an experimental basis for a theorised impact of the constitution on citizens’ views and behaviours and to inform additional investigations into this under-investigated overlap between psychology and law.

KEYWORDS Constitutional Law, Expert Authority, Political Opinion

TITLE **What is just? The effect of perspective and victim sensitivity on people's stances towards Article 103, Sentence 3 in the German Constitution**

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ABSTRACT

Article 103, Sentence 3 in the German Constitution states that an acquitted person may not be charged again for the same offense, even if new facts or evidence are available, which was recently affirmed by the German Federal Constitutional Court. We investigate whether people's justice perceptions and trust in the legal system depend on how the Article's implications are framed. 1) From a Type-1-error perspective: preventing false positives, thus protecting (correctly) acquitted innocent suspects; or 2) from a Type-2 error perspective: enabling false negatives, thus protecting (falsely) acquitted guilty offenders. In an online study (N = 560), we examined the impact of perspective on the Article's perceived justice and trust in the legal system, including a control condition with unspecified perspective. We hypothesized that emphasizing the prevention of false positives would lead to greater perceived justice and higher trust in the legal system than focusing on enabling false negatives or having no specified perspective. Additionally, we tested the moderating role of dispositional justice sensitivity from the victim's perspective to investigate if victim sensitive individuals show even larger differences. Results indicate heightened perceived justice when emphasizing the prevention of false positives compared to the enabling of false negatives, as expected, with the unspecified perspective in between. However, trust in the legal system did not differ between the two manipulated perspectives. No interaction effects with victim sensitivity were observed. The results demonstrate the malleability of people's justice perceptions and expand our understanding of how laypeople perceive rulings that weigh Type-1 versus Type-2 errors.

KEYWORDS **Justice, Trust, Perspective, Victim Sensitivity**

TITLE **The effects of memory distrust toward commission and omission on recollection-belief correspondence and memory errors**

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ABSTRACT

Our appraisals and beliefs about our memory functioning shape how we reconstruct and report specific memory episodes. Research has shown that people differ in the extent to which they are sceptical about their memories, which is termed memory distrust. In general, memory distrust has two aspects: distrust over forgetting (i.e., making omission errors) and distrust over falsely recollecting events that did not happen (i.e., making commission errors). Although these two aspects of memory distrust have been studied, how they are associated with memory validation (e.g., the formation of autobiographical belief) and reporting remains unclear. In the present study, we plan to examine the effect of metacognitive appraisals on the memory validation process as well as the commission and omission errors in memory reporting. Specifically, participants will first complete a memory task where they either receive inaccurate feedback regarding making commission errors or making omission errors, or they receive no feedback. Then, they will complete another new recognition task. We expect that compared to the control group with no feedback, participants receiving feedback on their errors will show larger belief-recollection divergence (i.e., smaller correlations between ratings). Further, people who receive feedback indicating a tendency to make commission errors in the first memory task will make more omission errors in the second task and show a shift toward a more conservative response criterion. Conversely, individuals who receive feedback suggesting a tendency to make omission errors will show an increase in commission errors during the second task, demonstrating a shift toward a more liberal response criterion.

KEYWORDS

Memory distrust, memory validation, response criterion, commission errors, omission errors

TITLE **Blind Implantation of False Autobiographical Memories**

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to replicate and expand upon the research conducted by Otgaar et al., (2022) by investigating the effectiveness of a new method for implanting false autobiographical memories. In particular, we ought to examine whether false autobiographical memories could be successfully implanted by using this paradigm, and to explore the impact of event frequency on the formation of false memories. Participants will be presented a list of 20 autobiographical events including a critical false event (e.g. lost in a shopping mall), and they will be asked to indicate whether they have experienced these events. After one week, individuals who have not experienced the critical event will receive a second survey, which will suggest that they indicated to have experienced the false event. One group of them will be told that the false event happened only once (Single Group), and the other will be told that the event happened repeatedly (Repeated Group). Participants will provide recollection and belief ratings, and details related to the event. We expect that false autobiographical memories will be successfully implanted with the new paradigm and that participants in the Single Group will be more prone to form false memories for the critical event compared to the ones in the Repeated Group. Furthermore, we anticipate that the participants in the Single Group will provide more details regarding the false event. In conclusion, this study will give us a better understanding of the malleability of memory and its implication in legal contexts, where false memories may impact the reliability of testimonies.

KEYWORDS **false memory, implantation, event frequency**
